

**Understanding the meaning in activities and interactions for
people with advanced dementia in a Scottish care home:
An action research study**

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of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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Declaration

I, Angela Carter, hereby certify that this thesis has been written by me and has not been submitted for any other comparable academic award.

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Date: 31st July 2025

Abstract

'Meaningful activities' is a term often used in dementia practice in relation to enhanced wellbeing and quality of life, yet what makes activities and interactions meaningful for people in the advanced stages is unknown. This can risk unintentional exclusion from occupational, relational and social opportunities or the selection of inappropriate activities, potentially invalidating the person's preferences and/or existence. Research actively involving this population is rare because of complex ethical processes, assumptions about the person's ability to participate, and inflexible, inappropriate methods. Thus, an under-representation and/or exclusion of the voices of people with advanced dementia (PwAD) has occurred.

The aim of this study was to understand meaning in activities and interactions in collaboration with PwAD, their family members and staff in a care home setting. Using a qualitative, Action Research methodology and creative methods, audio-visual data was collected over a six-month period during three phases of Action Research. The study took place in one Scottish care home with four PwAD, four family members, and six care home staff. Creative methods included using images and objects during family member interviews and staff focus groups, co-created activities with PwAD (e.g. walking, drumming, dancing), and a workshop with family/staff.

Data was analysed using methods by Stringer and Aragon (2021) to create themes for each phase, from which four key findings were developed. Finding One presents components of meaning, Finding Two highlights how the ordinariness of meaning can be inadvertently understated, or overlooked by others, Finding Three discusses potential signs of meaning, and Finding Four describes synchronising with PwAD during joint activities. This research contributes to the field by providing insights into what meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD can represent, how it can be recognised, and how this understanding of meaning can be used to enhance their participation in everyday life.

Conferences, public engagement & awards resulting from this research

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Glossary of key terms

Action Research: a collaborative approach to research that facilitates learning and change through continual cycles of looking, thinking and doing. Participants are active, equal agents in the process

Advanced dementia: a progressive condition which affects how a person functions in everyday life, requiring increasing levels of support to complete daily tasks. Depending on the type of dementia, the individual, and their underlying health, the person's cognitive, emotional, physical, sensory and spiritual health may be severely affected

Agency: purposeful action which is self-initiated and/or completed with others in the context of the everyday

(A)synchronicity: a space through which bodies, emotions, objects and environments (mis)align and (un)attune during activities/interactions to (co)create (un)meaning. (A)synchronicity may be missed, delayed, interrupted, revisited or fluctuate

Care home: a specialist home offering respite, short-term or long-term care for adults over 18 years of age, with nursing support, depending on the person and the home

Chaining: a technique which supports a person to actively participate in a task when another person provides practical support and/or prompting

Co-creation/co-creativity: a creative, relational and collaborative process which offers opportunities for freedom, exploration and change with no expected outcome. All collaborators are equal and interdependent, and all contributions are welcomed

Curiosity: a need or desire to know about and/or interest in others, objects and the social and physical environment. Curiosity is linked to motivation and satisfaction

Everyday creativity: a form of creativity which everyone can access. Everyday creativity encompasses flexibility, adaptability and change in response to the context and environment in a way that celebrates different ways of being, doing and knowing

Inscape: a reference group of expert members set up specifically for this study to inform and guide each stage

Interactions: a way of being with others which changes according to time and space. This dynamic process enables meaning to be negotiated and co-created

Inter-corporeality: a process of collaborative action and participation where bodies and selves are negotiated, shared and exchanged in a way that validates their co-existence

Embodiment: the emulation of the self through the constantly changing and evolving body in response to the social, cultural and physical environment

Glossary of key terms - continued

Inter-embodiment: a cyclical and transactional process of meaning-making between bodies

Meaningful activity: acts of human 'doing' which add meaning and purpose to our lives and enhance health and wellbeing. These can include essential daily activities, such as housework and self-care, and leisure activities

Meaning in activity: meaning (co)created through the process of doing an activity

Meaning-making: an interactive process through which meaning is co-created

Occupational Science: a discipline concerned with how humans spend their time and structure their lives in the social and physical environment to create meaning and purpose, and how this impacts their health and wellbeing

Post-verbal: a form of communication and/or relating to others and objects which embraces the body and voice and may or may not include words

Abbreviations

AR: Action Research

NR: Nearest Relative

Person: Person living with advanced dementia

PwAD: People with advanced dementia

PwD: People with dementia

WA: Welfare Attorney

WG: Welfare Guardian

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Chapter 1 : Introduction and Background

1.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the background and context for this Action Research (AR) study. It begins with a brief narration of the impetus for the research and my interest in the topic. The prevalence and stages of dementia from international, national, and Scottish perspectives are presented, followed by a definition of advanced dementia. Next, the Advanced Dementia Practice Model (Kinnaird, 2015) is briefly discussed, and human rights, stigma and inequality are described. Meaningful activity is explored generally, then described in relation to care homes and people with advanced dementia (PwAD), after which the term, 'meaning *in* activities' is introduced. 'Interactions' are then defined in the context of this study. Since the concept of meaning is vast and complex with diverse literature, it is explored and critiqued separately in Chapters Two and Three.

1.2 The roots of this study

Prior to my involvement, this study was initiated using a qualitative case study approach by Brown (2016), who researched quality of life and people with severe dementia, recommending an investigation into meaningful activity with PwAD using personal objects and the senses. Brown's (2016) work underpinned a Ketso workshop in 2017, facilitated by Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) to explore ideas for further research with people with dementia and care home staff. Ketso is an evidence-based portable workshop which uses practical methods to enhance participation and encourage diverse views (Ketso Ltd, no date). During the workshop, meaningful activity with PwAD was highlighted as an important research topic. The AR approach to this study was influenced by these outcomes alongside key learning from a sensory, participatory eating and drinking project called, 'Food for Thought' (Brown *et al.*, 2014; McWhinnie and Brown, 2016).

Prior to commencing this research, I was working as a Health and Care Professions Council (HCPC) registered occupational therapist in a hospice in England. As an occupational therapist, I had worked with people with differing types and stages of dementia, in community and in-patient settings. During this time, I observed how PwAD were often inadvertently excluded and stigmatised from social and occupational opportunities (Ashworth, 2020), and how this negatively impacted on their wellbeing (Fletcher, 2021). This led to an interest in researching with this population to promote learning and change.

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Prevalence of dementia

Worldwide, more than 55 million people are estimated to live with dementia (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2023), 982,000 of whom live in the UK (Alzheimer's Society and Carnall Farrar, 2024). The prevalence in Scotland is inconsistently reported. For example, in 2019, Wittenberg *et al.* estimated 46,800 people were diagnosed, whereas McLeish (2019) reported this to be 90,000; in 2021, the Alzheimer's Society (2021) estimated this figure to be 66,000. With the ageing population increasing, 1.4 million people are expected to live with dementia by 2040 (Alzheimer's Society and Carnell Farrar, 2024), making dementia a public health crisis with worldwide impact on individuals, families, societies and economies (WHO, 2017). Despite the scale of the issue, dementia research remains under-funded, particularly when compared with other health conditions (Luengo-Fernandez and Landeiro, in preparation; Alzheimer's Research UK, 2017).

Although there are over 100 types of dementia (Alzheimer Scotland, 2025a), Alzheimer's Disease is the most common form in the UK (Alzheimer's Society, 2025a). Each type of dementia affects a person differently, and the individual experience is equally diverse (Brown, Tolson and Ritchie, 2020). The person's whole life is profoundly affected and depending on the type of dementia, they can experience difficulties with cognition, behaviour and functioning (Byrne *et al.*, 2008). These difficulties may cause sensory, perceptual and emotional changes (Houston and Christie, 2018), and create challenges with verbal language, memory and planning (McLeish, 2019; Brown, Tolson and Ritchie, 2020). As the condition progresses, PwAD may experience Behavioural and Psychological Symptoms of Dementia (BPSD), such as agitation and aggression, which are often inappropriately treated with antipsychotic medication despite this being discouraged (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2018). BPSD is also known as 'stress and distress' (NHS Highland, 2023) and is the preferred term in this thesis.

Care for PwAD includes day care (Rokstad *et al.*, 2019), sheltered housing (Smith *et al.*, 2021) and home care (Alzheimer Scotland, 2024), although, care homes are often the main providers for the Long-term Care (LTC) of PwAD (Scottish Government, 2021; Alzheimer Scotland, 2024). Thus, a care home was the selected setting for this study. Care homes provide specialist respite, short-term rehabilitation or long-term 24-hour care to vulnerable adults over the age of 18 (Public Health Scotland, 2024), with or without nursing support, depending on the type of home and needs of the person (Watson *et al.*, 2020). In the UK, almost 40% of PwD aged over 65 reside in a care home, amounting to 69% of the care home population (Prince *et al.* 2014). According to

the Care Home Census for Adults in Scotland (Public Health Scotland, 2024), over 30,000 older people lived in care homes long-term in March 2024, of which 63% were estimated to be diagnosed, or suspected to be living with dementia. However, identifying PwD in care homes remains a challenge (OECD, 2018) and there do not appear to be any statistics on PwAD living in care homes.

1.3.2 Stages of dementia

Dementia is usually categorised into different stages, and often described as mild/early, moderate/mid, severe/late/advanced (Alzheimer's Society, 2025c). Although the complexities of advanced dementia are acknowledged in the literature, a preoccupation with cognitive symptoms does not reflect the diversity or depth of symptoms (Byrne *et al.*, 2008; McLeish, 2019), for instance, increasing difficulty with everyday tasks such as washing and dressing, eating and drinking, mobility and continence care, constituting: “*a progressive array of nursing needs, physical, psychological, social, spiritual and existential*” (Tolson and Brown, 2019, p.10). Yet a consistent definition of advanced dementia does not exist (Hanson *et al.*, 2019; Eisenmann *et al.*, 2020) and those that do often exclude important contextual information such as relationships and the physical and social environment (Byrne *et al.*, 2008). Further, since PwAD may live for up to ten years before reaching end-of-life (Holmerova *et al.*, 2016), there may be missed opportunities for occupational and social engagement. An example is palliative approaches which can enhance quality of life, encourage family involvement, maintain function and provide comfort, however they are ill-defined and often seen as inapplicable to this population (van der Steen *et al.*, 2014; 2016).

1.3.2.1 A definition of advanced dementia

The White Paper by van der Steen *et al.* (2014) provided the first definition of palliative care for PwAD, consisting of 11 core domains, including psychosocial and spiritual needs, person-centredness and physical comfort. This was used in combination with the perspectives of PwD and family/professional carers to create Dementia Palliare, a specialist, biopsychosocial-spiritual, palliative approach to advanced dementia practice (Holmerova *et al.*, 2016). A definition of advanced dementia and accompanying best practice statement was created by Holmerova *et al.* (2016) and Hanson *et al.* (2019) using the Dementia Palliare approach. This definition offers a refreshing break from medical perspectives and was the definition used in the Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN) 168 (Healthcare Improvement Scotland, 2023). Dementia Palliare was selected to define advanced dementia in this AR study because its holistic approach aligns with the study's real-world, human-rights based perspective. An edited version of the definition is provided below.

“Advanced dementia will be unique to each individual and dependent on factors relating to underlying health, personality, biography and social context... As dementia progresses, living well requires increasing levels of support and care. Loss of autonomy, declining physical health, increasing vulnerability and frailty usually signal progression... healthcare needs must be addressed in tandem with other psychosocial and spiritual needs and careful attention must be paid to the living environment and family caring.” (Holmerova et al., 2016, p.4).

1.3.3 Advanced Dementia Practice Model

Alzheimer Scotland’s Advanced Dementia Practice Model (Kinnaird, 2015) offers guidance and recommendations to manage the complex and changing needs of PwAD. Consisting of eight pillars of support, including therapeutic, personalised, environmental and community factors, a strength of the model lies in its acknowledgement for adapted communication and activities, for instance, gestures, touch and momentary interactions to connect with the person (Kinnaird, 2015). However, some methodological information is deficient, for example, the consultation process lacks clarity, and details such as the consultees’ stage(s) of dementia and the specific skills/background of contributing practitioners are omitted.

1.4 Human rights

The human rights of PwAD are often denied in care homes (WHO, 2017). Therefore, this study advocates a human-rights-based approach and is informed by the European Convention on Human Rights (1950), the Human Rights Act 1998, the Charter of Rights (Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer’s, 2009), Participation, Accountability, Non-discrimination/equality, Empowerment and Legality (PANEL) (Scottish Human Rights Commission, 2025) (SHRC), and the Scottish Convention on the rights of residents in care homes for adults and older people (Scottish Care, 2016). This is important to promote the dignity of PwAD, and their choices, control, equality, inclusion, and participation in everyday life (Life Changes Trust, 2020) and research (Diaz-Gil et al., 2023).

1.5 Stigma and inequality

PwAD and their family/informal carers may experience stigma, which may invalidate the person (Sabat, 2003; 2006) and their social citizenship (Bartlett and O’Connor, 2010). Stigma refers to people categorised by society as having a trait or disability that separates them from the majority

(Goffman, 1963). Different types of stigma have been identified in the literature, including, self-stigma, public stigma and courtesy stigma (Werner, 2014). *Self-stigma* is the internal process which occurs when individuals experience stigma (Larson and Corrigan, 2008; Werner, 2014), which can lower the self-esteem of PwD, causing them to hide symptoms or delay seeking support (Ashworth, 2020). *Public stigma* refers to societal reactions towards ostracised people (Larson and Corrigan, 2008; Werner, 2014), which can breed stereotypes and discrimination (Nguyen and Li, 2020), such as PwD being considered subhuman, useless, or having ‘lost’ themselves (Sabat, 2003; Behuniak, 2011). *Courtesy stigma* is the feelings or beliefs experienced by those supporting or working with stigmatised individuals (Larson and Corrigan, 2008; Werner, 2014), which can reduce opportunities for informal carers of PwD to access social support (Werner and AboJabel, 2020). Additionally, epidemic injustice is a form of stigma resulting from power imbalances that harms stigmatised people through their awareness of the stigma (Fricker, 2007), potentially causing others to consider PwD to be unreliable and untrustworthy, and PwD to withdraw from others as a result (Young *et al.*, 2019).

Additionally, PwD are more likely to experience unequal access to health services and higher costs than those with other advancing conditions (McLeish, 2019), a situation that was amplified during the COVID-19 pandemic when this study took place. During this time, care home residents, family members and staff faced a disproportionate risk of infection and death than any other setting (Comas-Herrera *et al.*, 2020; Social Care Institute for Excellence, 2022) and residents experienced unequal social and occupational restrictions, impacting negatively on cognitive decline, quality of life, and wellbeing (Giebel *et al.*, 2021; Dawson *et al.*, 2023). Hence, stigma is an important consideration for this study because how PwAD are perceived by others may impact opportunities for understanding meaning in activities and interactions; this is explored further in Chapters Two and Three.

1.6 Meaningful activity

‘Meaningful activity’ is a frequently used term in Health and Social Care, often applied interchangeably with the term ‘occupation’. Definitions of these terms are constantly debated and differ according to the country and cultural and historical context (Salles and Matsukura, 2016). Despite this lack of clarity, it is internationally agreed that engaging in meaningful activities/occupations can enhance health, well-being (Salles and Matsukura, 2016), identity, and create opportunities for self-actualisation, connection, belonging and security across diverse cultures (Leufstadius, Nilsson and Hovbrandt, 2024). Meaningful activity is the term used in this

study because it is arguably more consistently used in care homes than 'occupation', which has a wide range of definitions including military connotations, paid employment, and human behaviours (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015).

Meaningful activity is integral to occupational science, which provides the theory and knowledgebase for occupational therapy (Salles and Matsukura, 2016). Occupational science studies how people structure, orchestrate and fulfil their everyday lives using activities, roles and routines, and how these impact health and wellbeing (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015). The focus of occupational science lies in the purpose and meaning of engaging in activities and their connected human and environmental experiences (Hocking and Wright-St Clair, 2011). Meaningful activities can also contribute to general meaning in life (Eakman, 2013) and include a broad array of activities including Activities of Daily Living (ADLs), i.e. the fundamental activities humans need to survive, such as eating, sleeping and continence care, leisure occupations and work/productivity (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015). However, meaningful activities can appear deceptively simplistic and therefore suffer neglect from scientific inquiry (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015).

Related concepts to meaningful activity include, "*doing, being, belonging, and becoming*" (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015, p. 134). 'Doing' refers to collective and individual action, 'being' to reflection, contemplation and relaxation, 'belonging' is a sense of connectedness which arises through meaningful activity, and 'becoming' represents a continual process of development and transformation experienced individually, communally and societally (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015). These terms can be likened to self-actualisation (Maslow, 1943), which Ventegodt, Merrick and Andersen (2003) define as the essence of meaning, created in 'the moment' to enhance quality of life. However, self-actualisation in PwAD can be overlooked in institutions such as hospitals because of a preoccupation with safety and risk-management (Scerri, Scerri and Innes, 2020), a scenario which is transferable to care homes.

1.6.1 Meaningful activity, care homes and people with advanced dementia

Meaningful activities are integral to the wellbeing of all, including PwD (Kitwood, 1997a; 1997b; Wenborn, 2017), and are recommended for care home residents to promote enjoyment, pleasure, health and wellbeing (Care Inspectorate, 2017; National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2018; Healthcare Improvement Scotland, 2023). Meaningful activities can also be used as non-pharmacological interventions to reduce stress and distress in PwAD and address unmet needs

(Cohen-Mansfield, 2018), for example, complementary therapies (Mitchell *et al.*, 2020), multisensory stimulation and individualised music sessions (Sánchez *et al.*, 2016).

In care homes, meaningful activities can be defined as: “*activities that provide emotional, creative, intellectual and spiritual stimulation*” (Drew, 2015, p. 2), and care home residents have highlighted how participating in meaningful activities can enhance their independence and quality of life (Cahill and Diaz-Ponce, 2011; Nygaard *et al.*, 2020). Despite this, various studies have reported a lack of meaningful activity in care homes, with PwD considered to be spending two thirds of their waking day unoccupied (Bowie and Mountain, 1993; Ice, 2002; Morgan-Brown *et al.*, 2011). As a result, boredom and loneliness have been noted (Wood, Womack and Hooper, 2009; Mjorud *et al.*, 2017), particularly for PwAD for whom self-initiating activities and social interactions becomes more difficult (Boyd *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, care homes often over-rely on structured group activities when individual activities are often more appropriate for PwAD (Perrin, May and Anderson, 2008; Brown *et al.*, 2020a). To address these issues, various initiatives, toolkits and social media campaigns have been created, for example, ‘Make Every Moment Count’ (Care Inspectorate, 2013) and ‘Living Well through activity in Care Homes: the Toolkit’ (Drew, 2015); however, what makes these meaningful is unclear and/or assumed.

In part, this may be explained by what others consider to be a) an activity and b) meaningful. For example, care home staff may view ADLs as a task to complete ‘to’ PwAD rather than an activity to co-create meaning ‘with’ PwAD (du Toit and Buchanan, 2018). Likewise, leisure activities may be perceived as additional, non-essential tasks (Bowes *et al.*, 2022), resulting in a lack of occupational opportunities for PwAD (Brown *et al.*, 2020a). This may be linked with organisational cultures, such as values, routines and practices, which are entwined with and directly impact quality of care, placing responsibility on those in specific roles such as Activity Co-ordinators (Killett *et al.*, 2016) and occupational therapists as opposed to a whole team approach (Wenborn, 2017).

Meaningful activities for PwAD are not satisfactorily reflected in many relevant policies. For instance, although the recent Scottish Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2023a) addressed meaningful activities for PwAD, information specifically regarding the advanced stages of dementia mainly focussed on prevalence, care, and communication. Meaningful activity was briefly discussed in terms of formal, structured interventions such as Validation Therapy and Reminiscence Therapy, yet enhancing meaning in everyday life was not addressed. This implies

that only formal activities requiring specialist skills and resources may be meaningful, perhaps creating missed opportunities for meaning-making.

Although meaningful activities for PwAD have been researched from various perspectives, these are mainly regarding interventions rather than the concept of meaning. These include sensory stimulation (Spaull, Leach and Frampton, 1998), doll therapy (Tamura *et al.*, 2001), and Snoezelen (Baillon *et al.*, 2016). Research has also been completed to analyse the effects of interventions and activities on behaviours and participation of PwAD (Brooker *et al.*, 1997; Kovach and Magliocco, 1998; Orsulic-Jeras, Judge and Camp, 2000; Ballard *et al.*, 2002; Belgrave and Belgrave, 2009; Esker and Ashton, 2013; Stacpoole *et al.*, 2014), and their levels of alertness, communication and responses (Whall *et al.*, 1997; Takayanagi, Kirita and Shibata, 2014). Other research has focussed on evaluation, outcomes, or effects of meaningful activities (Athlin and Norberg, 1998; Spaull, Leach and Frampton, 1998; Hoerster, Hickey and Bourgeois, 2001; Stacpoole *et al.*, 2017; Wilks *et al.*, 2019).

Few researchers have explored the meaning in activities and interactions with PwD. Those that have, have mainly focussed on people with mild to moderate dementia using interpretive phenomenology (Phinney, 2006; Phinney, Chaudhury and O'Connor, 2007) and ethnography in a community setting (Harding *et al.*, 2023). Canning (2020) researched emotional and social engagement with PwAD in a care home setting using focussed ethnography and recommended further research using innovative methods to analyse everyday occurrences. None of these studies explored the meaning *in* activities with PwAD. This gap is important to explore because without understanding what is meaningful for PwAD, it seems impossible to enhance meaning in activities and interactions.

1.6.2 Meaning *in* activities

What makes activities meaningful has been largely overlooked by the occupational therapy literature (Reed, Smyth and Hocking, 2011). Furthermore, goal-focussed outcomes are often prioritised and valued at the expense of overlooking processes of 'doing', where the essence of meaning may be found and created (Hasselkus and Dickie, 2021). The gap in understanding meaning in 'meaningful activity' is widened in advanced dementia practice where the term seems to be used with little understanding of what makes activities meaningful because of a belief that PwAD no longer have the skills to participate (Smith *et al.*, 2018), a protective instinct towards PwAD (Carter and Brown, 2023) and a need for further training (Wenborn, 2017).

1.7 Interactions and people with dementia

As dementia advances, PwAD become progressively reliant upon others to continue participating in meaningful activities (Giebel *et al.*, 2019; Carter and Brown, 2023), highlighting the need to explore interactions with PwAD. There are different perspectives of social interactions, however these are mostly from a cognitive or behavioural view and are often passive, individualistic, or one-dimensional (Fuchs and De Jaegher, 2009). As these perspectives focus on the potential difficulties of PwAD rather than strengths, they are an unsuitable lens for this study. As such, this research uses the definition of interaction by Fuchs and De Jaegher (2009), where meaning is co-created, negotiated and changed through a dynamic process of action and fluctuating synchronisation in time and space. This definition is slightly adapted in this study to include triads rather than dyads because of the emphasis on relations between PwAD, family members and care home staff described in the literature. This definition also embraces post-verbal communication i.e. embodied ways of relating to others and objects which may or may not include words (Quinn, Blandon and Batson, 2021). Interactions and their relation to meaning are explored further in Chapter Three.

1.8 Summary

This chapter has provided an overview of the impact of advanced dementia on individuals, their family members and professional carers within the wider social and cultural context, and key terms have been defined and explored. Issues around human rights, stigma and inequality have highlighted how PwAD may be negatively perceived, potentially affecting opportunities for participating in meaningful activities and interactions. This is particularly important given the apparent need for a relational approach.

Key learning from this chapter is the emerging picture that both PwAD and meaningful activities are poorly understood in advanced dementia practice, possibly creating inequalities in accessing meaningful activities and interactions. This has exposed a neglected area of research which seems to have negatively impacted PwAD and widened these disparities. This study therefore contributes to two gaps in the literature: 1) actively and directly researching with PwAD, their family members and care home staff; and 2) exploring the *meaning in activities*. My response to these issues is presented in the following chapters. Chapter Two offers a multi-disciplinary integrative literature review to understand why and how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD is perceived and applied in practice, and Chapter Three offers a theoretical and philosophical view of meaning; reasons for their separation are described within the chapters.

Chapter Four explores the AR methodology, pragmatist ontology and a social constructionist epistemology, and Chapter Five provides a reflexive account of what happened when these were applied in the field. Chapters Six, Seven and Eight present the findings of each of the three phases of the AR cycle and Chapter Nine offers a discussion of four key findings. Additionally, strengths and limitations and implications and recommendations for education, research, policy and care home practice are provided in the final chapter.

Chapter 2 : Exploring meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia: An integrative literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents an integrative review of the literature to explore how meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia (PwAD) has been interpreted, and why and in what ways it was considered meaningful. This review follows the framework of Whitemore and Knafl (2005) to include diverse methodologies using a robust and systematic approach. It aimed to understand real-world, multidisciplinary applications of meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia (PwAD) and gather methodological insights to inform the methodology of this study (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005). The review included qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods literature published up to 18th August 2020. Relevant literature after this date is critically discussed in Chapter Nine. This chapter firstly explains the literature review methodology, then provides an overview of the selected literature and review findings.

2.2 Literature review methodology

This integrative review followed the five stages outlined by Whitemore and Knafl (2005): 1) problem identification; 2) literature search; 3) data evaluation; 4) data analysis (data reduction; data display; data comparison; conclusion drawing and verification); and 5) presentation. An integrative literature review uses a comprehensive search strategy to answer a clear question (Noble and Smith, 2018) to inform, develop and contribute to policy, practice and/or research (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005). Although an integrative literature review can include theoretical and empirical literature (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005), theoretical literature in this thesis was not included because it was often not specific to PwAD and therefore did not meet the eligibility criteria. However, to understand the foundations of meaning and how the concept applied to PwAD, it was important to review the literature on meaning more generally. Thus, a theoretical and philosophical discussion of meaning can be found in Chapter Three.

Other literature review methodologies were considered, including a scoping review and a systematic review. However, a preliminary search of the literature revealed a lack of empirical and grey literature on the topic, revealing that a scoping review would not be appropriate because

the breadth of the literature would likely be inadequate (Munn *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, it would not have gleaned the standardised results expected for systematic reviews (Powell and Koelemay, 2022). Thus, an integrative review which includes diverse methodologies from empirical and grey literature offered a useful framework to explore meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD and extract valuable data for practice (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005).

Various integrative review methodologies exist which differ in terms of addressing issues of quality and rigour (for example, Whittemore and Knafl, 2005; de Souza, da Silva and de Carvalho, 2010; Torraco, 2016). The methodology of Whittemore and Knafl (2005) was selected for this review because it claimed to address concerns of rigour, particularly during analysis. Whittemore and Knafl (2005) suggest complementing their methodology with criteria to assess the quality of selected papers matched to individual methodologies, therefore three critical appraisal tools (CAT's) from the Joanna Briggs Institute (n.d.) were chosen to examine the selected literature according to their methodology (Barker *et al.*, 2023). Whittemore and Knafl (2005, p.551) further advise: *“Creativity and critical analysis of data and data displays are key elements in data comparison and the identification of important and accurate patterns and themes”*. Therefore, the review methodology was adapted to enhance my strengths as a neurodiverse researcher by using visual and practical ways of analysing the data (Grant and Kara, 2021). Examples include using mind-maps to create the search strategy, paperchains to identify relationships and tensions, and word collages to extract and reduce data. The collages enabled an immersive, felt experience (Culshaw, 2019), which was important to enhance my understanding of the data. This process is outlined in Table 2.1 and supplemented with images in Appendix 1.

Table 2.1 Stages of the literature review (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005)

Problem identification	Little known about meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD resulting in the unintentional exclusion of PwAD from potentially everyday meaningful experiences. The aim of this review was to understand a real-world, multidisciplinary application of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.
Literature search	Search completed with a specific focus on meaning, activities, interactions and advanced dementia. Mind-maps used to create a search strategy. From 54 potentially relevant sources, 18 were selected for review.
Data evaluation	The final sample consisted of qualitative and quantitative sources, one of which was an empirical report. Sources used a wide variety of methodologies which were assessed for quality using the most appropriate JBI tool. No literature was excluded based on their score but literature with a lower score contributed less to the analysis and findings. Literature was initially divided by methodology. Analytic notes and mind-maps were created to provide an overview of each study.
Data analysis	Data was extracted and displayed in a matrix in Microsoft Excel. Type of data extracted included study design, methodology, theoretical framework, demographics of participants, methods, how meaning was interpreted, and why activities and interactions were considered meaningful for PwAD. Paperchains were used to identify relationships and tensions. Data about meaning, activities and interactions was coded in the matrix, then printed to create moveable collages where codes were iteratively arranged into subgroups. Codes were compared, contrasted and abstracted, and physically (re)moved as part of this process to identify relationships and themes. Mind-maps were used alongside moveable collages to isolate and develop themes. Throughout, data was iteratively reviewed alongside the original source to check and verify the interpretation of abstracted data.
Presentation	The themes were then written to synthesise and integrate the data, with the aid of mind-maps. Review questions were partly answered, identifying further gaps which justify the purpose of this study.

2.2.1 Limitations of the review methodology

Integrating different methodologies was a challenge (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005), mainly because it was difficult to find a suitable CAT which scored different research designs in a consistent and fair manner. On reflection, a tool like the Quality Assessment Tool for Studies with Diverse Designs (QATSDD) (Sirriyeh *et al.*, 2012) or the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) (Hong *et al.*, 2018) may be more suitable for this type of literature review to provide consistency during the appraisal process, although this is unlikely to have affected the findings (Sirriyeh *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, in their attempt at clarifying the analytic processes in an integrative review, Whittemore and Knafl (2005) over-complicated them; these difficulties were overcome using the visual methods described earlier.

2.3 The Literature review

2.3.1 Literature review questions

There is little published literature that explores what makes activities meaningful for PwAD, therefore this review aimed to understand a real-world, multidisciplinary application of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. The review questions were as follows:

1. How is meaning in activities and interactions interpreted in the literature?
2. Why and in what ways are the activities and interactions considered meaningful for the PwAD?

2.3.2 Search strategies

2.3.2.1 Preliminary searches

Preliminary searches of primary peer-reviewed research were completed between 25th March and 27th May 2020, using CINHALL and socINDEX to define parameters using the search terms presented in Figure 2.1 (Conn *et al.*, 2003). This process identified the type and extent of literature available, in relation to the review questions, which in turn helped to refine a search strategy (Conn *et al.*, 2003; Grant and Booth, 2009; Atkinson and Cipriani, 2018).

Figure 2.1 Sample of the preliminary search strategy

Meaning* AND (Activit* OR Occupation*) OR non-pharm* OR (Interact* OR relationship*) OR (Strengths-based* OR person-centred*) AND (“Advanced dement**” OR "severe dement**” OR “late-stage dement**” OR “late stage dement**” OR “later stage* dement**” OR “late-stage Alzheimer*” OR “late stage Alzheimer**” OR “severe Alzheimer**”)

2.3.2.2 Refined search strategy

The refined search strategy used the guidance of Whitemore and Knafl (2005) to systematically search peer-reviewed research and empirical reports and evaluations between 28th May and 18th August 2020. To develop the search strategy, further guidance was sought from Salvador-Olivan, Marco-Cuenca and Arquero-Aviles (2019) since information about search errors was not provided by Whitemore and Knafl (2005).

2.3.3 Empirical research

Peer-reviewed literature was searched using the following databases in EBSCO host: APA PsycArticles, CINAHL, Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition, MEDLINE, Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Collection, and SocINDEX with Full Text. To reduce the limitations of searching computerised databases (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005), other approaches were also employed, including searching references from relevant literature, directly contacting pertinent authors, and creating Google Alerts.

2.3.4 Reports and evaluations

Reports and evaluations were sourced by searching the following websites: Arts Council England, Google Scholar, Health Management Online, INVOLVE, National Elf Service, National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), Public Health Scotland, Trip medical database, and The King's Fund Library service. Ancestry searching of references from relevant literature was performed, alongside directly contacting pertinent authors/health services.

2.3.5 Search terms

The search terms used are presented in Table 2.2. They were used with Boolean operators such as 'AND' and 'OR' and truncations like '*' within the Title (TI) and Abstract (AB) fields. Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms were used to increase the effectiveness of the database searches for empirical literature (Richter and Austin, 2012).

Table 2.2 Search terms used in the literature review

Search Topic	Search	Search Terms
Meaning AND	1	Meaning*
Activity AND	2	Exploded MeSH terms: ADL OR "Activities, Daily Living" OR "Chronic Limitation of Activity" OR "Limitation of Activity, Chronic" OR Non-MeSH terms: PADL OR DADL OR IADL OR Activit* OR Occupation*
	3	non-pharmacological* OR nonpharmacological* OR intervention* OR Montessori* OR sensory* OR psycho-social OR psychosocial
Interaction OR	4	Interaction* OR relation* OR relationships OR interrelationships
	5	OR agential OR validation
	6	Communicat*
Approach OR	7	Approach*
	8	OR personcentred* OR person-centred* OR strengths-based* OR "positive practice"
Dementia AND	9	Exploded MeSH terms: "Alzheimer Disease" OR "Alzheimer Dementia" OR "Frontotemporal Lobar Degeneration+" OR "Frontotemporal Dementia" OR "Huntington Disease" OR "Lewy Body Disease" OR "Pick Disease of the Brain" OR "Prion Diseases" OR Non-MeSH terms: "Advanced dementia*" OR "advanced stage of dementia*" OR "severe dementia*" OR "late-stage dementia*" OR "late- stage dementia" OR "later stages of dementia" OR "severe Alzheimer's" OR "significant dementia" OR "severely demented"

2.3.6 Inclusion criteria

Literature that clearly defined the stage of dementia as 'severe', 'late-stage', 'advanced', or 'moderately severe' was included. To maintain the focus on the review questions, literature that involved people with different stages of dementia was only included if advanced dementia was a major emphasis and/or they were reported separately in the findings. Only literature that focussed on activities and interactions perceived as meaningful for PwAD was included. Literature that discussed specific interventions was only included if it focussed on meaning in activities and interactions rather than on the evaluation/outcomes of interventions/measures. Literature from any country written in English was included. The preliminary search found potentially relevant literature dated pre-2000, therefore a date limit was not set.

2.3.7 Exclusion criteria

Literature involving children with dementia, and literature written in a language other than English was excluded. Literature was also excluded if it concentrated on interventions, evaluation, and outcome measures rather than meaning, activities/interactions and PwAD. Some studies were excluded because they combined people with different stages of dementia in the analysis and results, making the meaning for PwAD indecipherable (for example, Harmer and Orrell, 2008; Jarrott and Gigliotti, 2010; Cruz *et al.*, 2011; George and Houser, 2014; Swinnen and de Medeiros, 2017; Canning, Gaetz and Blakeborough, 2020).

2.4 Search results

Searches for peer-reviewed research identified 18,750 literature sources. Searches for reports and evaluations identified 1,490 literature sources. Duplicates (n=7684) were removed. The remaining 12,556 were screened by title and abstract, and 12,502 were removed. Fifty-four papers were further assessed for eligibility, of which thirty-six were excluded. Eighteen literature sources, dating from 1999 to 2019 were selected for inclusion. See the PRISMA diagram in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2 PRISMA flow diagram

Figure 5 – PRISMA

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

2.5 Quality appraisal

Quantitative peer reviewed research was assessed using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Quasi-experimental Studies (Tufanaru *et al.*, 2020) and the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Analytical Cross Sectional studies (Moola *et al.*, 2020). Quantitative literature was scored out of eight or nine, depending on the tool. Qualitative peer reviewed research and the empirical report/evaluation were appraised using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research (Lockwood, Munn and Porritt, 2015) and scored out of ten. See Tables 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5 for an overview.

Table 2.3 Overview of quantitative peer reviewed research

Author(s), date etc., discipline/ school	Aim(s) of study	Research design, data collection & analysis	Relevant participants & setting	Key findings	JBI score
Cohen et al. (2009) Aging, Health and Humanities	To examine the effect of a bespoke game on mood, satisfaction and interaction during family visits	Single group, within-participants design. Observed Emotion Rating Scale 1-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), repeated measures design	PwAD (n=33); family members (n=33) Nursing homes (n = not stated) Country: not stated	Pleasure and interest in PwAD was highly significant. Family interest was significant. Agitation in the PwAD significantly increased (family scoring).	8/9
Ellis and Astell (2017) Psychology, Neuroscience, Mental Health	To examine the usefulness of Adaptive Interaction as a communication tool with people with severe dementia	Experimental design (AB Multiple Baseline); direct observation of each person Microanalytic and behavioural coding	People living with severe dementia (n=5) Nursing home (n = 1) Scotland	PwAD spent 68.6% of their time in 'neutral' e.g. sleeping. Most social interaction during ADL's. Each person had unique communication style. Adaptive Interaction can provide meaningful engagement for participant group.	7/8
Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin (2017) Nursing	To examine the range of and characteristics of activities prescribed by occupational therapists for people living with mild, moderate and severe dementia.	Correlational study (Bivarial). Activity Theory of Aging Secondary data analysis of 158 activity prescriptions Pearson product-moment two-tailed correlation coefficient analysis	Families (n=56), including people with severe dementia (n=22); carers (numbers not stated) Own homes USA	People living with severe dementia were more likely to be prescribed activities like music/entertainment, manipulation/sorting/sensory activities and repetitive, physical exercises, lasting 13-17 mins. Required regular prompting and redirecting during activities. Required support to initiate activities 50% of the time	8/8

Table 2.4 Overview of qualitative peer reviewed research

Author(s), date etc., discipline/school	Aim(s) of study	Research design, data collection & analysis	Relevant participants & setting	Key findings	JBI score
Hansebo And Kilhgren (2002) Neuroscience, Occupational Therapy, Caring Sciences	To understand interactions between carers and people living with severe dementia using video. To note any changes because of study	Phenomenology (Hermeneutic) Part of larger study Video-recorded interactions (n=24) Ricoeur's analysis	People living with severe dementia (n=9); carers (n=4) Nursing home (n=1) Sweden	Positive and negative caring interactions were observed. Positive = collaborative, person-centred, strengths-based approach. Negative = person ignored, objectified, not validated. Task-focussed. Power imbalance. Doing to, not with. Meaning was found when person was validated. Reflections, supervision and discussions supported nurses to develop validating techniques. Mutual and respectful relationships provided foundation for equality in interactions and activities	10/10
Hillier and Stokes (2012) Dementia Care	To understand if PwAD living in a care home benefitted from short, personalised interactions	Qualitative Focus group with care staff (n = 1) Observations using Dementia Care Mapping (Bradford Dementia Group, 1997) Analysis method not stated	PwAD (n=25-30); care staff (n = not stated) Nursing home (n=1) England	Six interactions were required to see an observable improvement in the mood of the PwAD, after which it was easier to stimulate a more positive mood. Meaning appeared related to family visits, personalised activities and interactions involving other residents whilst doing activities.	6/10
Holst, Edberg and Hallberg (1999) Caring Sciences	To explore nurses' narratives about caring for people living with severe dementia and to identify meaning for the person	Phenomenology, Hermeneutic approach Researcher notes Norberg and Lindseth's analytical approach	People with severe dementia (n=7); Ward-based nurses (n=39); mental health nurses (n=2)	Relationships between people living with severe dementia and nurses was delicate, complex and inter-connected, requiring skill, sensitivity, empathy and interpretation. Mutual acknowledgement helped create meaning-making through validation.	9/10

			Psychogeriatric clinic Sweden	People living with severe dementia required others to facilitate meaning-making and maintain 'the self'. Perceptions of the person affected meaning-making opportunities	
Kuosa, Elstad and Normann (2015)	To understand the meaning of activities in relation to a person's life narrative within the context of advanced dementia	Qualitative data informed by Leontyev's Activity Theory Interviews (n=11) Thematic narrative analysis	Close relatives of PwAD (n=11) Range of settings Norway	Past, present, and future activities were considered important for PwAD. Creative approaches helped to adapt activities to suit current strengths. Place of residence reduced or enhanced opportunities for meaningful activity. Advancement of dementia reduced meaningful opportunities	8/10
Nursing and Health Sciences					
Litchke and Hodges (2014)	To explore the meaning of multisensory chair yoga with people with dementia	Qualitative data from mixed-methods design. Grounded theory 10 weeks of a multisensory chair yoga programme Grounded theory analysis	Residents (n=39), including PwAD (n=10) Community assisted homes (n=3) Texas, USA	Stage of dementia affected person's experience of yoga, with PwAD requiring tactile/visual prompting and close interaction to actively participate. Multisensory approaches enabled others to see the strengths of the person	9/10
Health and Human Performance					
McNiel and Westphal (2018)	To explore how residents, families and carers experienced a Namaste Care Program	Interviews (n=15) Thematic analysis	Staff members (n=14) (nursing assistants, registered nurses, clergy, and therapists). Family member (n=1) was removed from analysis Long-term care facility (n=1) USA	Multisensory approach created relaxation, calm, comfort and enjoyment. Namaste offered the person purposeful, bespoke activity and provided staff with tools to facilitate interactions. Staff observed person's body language/expressions and responses to gauge motivation to participate. Staff satisfaction increased. Flexible approach required.	8/10
Nursing					
Perkins et al. (2015)	To understand what is meaningful to residents, family and staff.	Semi-structured interviews (n=18) Thematic analysis	People living with moderately-severe dementia (n=6); family members (n=5); staff (unit	Relationships were reciprocal and complex. Facilitation from others was essential for retaining meaning.	8/10

Ageing and Spirituality, Medicine	To explore spiritual practice within the home		manager, charge nurse, activities-therapist, caregivers) (n=7) Two secure units, New Zealand	Personality and identity of individuals with dementia were important. The progression of the condition affected relationships with the self and others, and ability to engage in usual activities. Meaning was created in the moment through love, care and connection.	
Pollanen and Hirsimaki (2014)	To investigate the positive effects of using crafts-based memory triggers with women with severe dementia who previously enjoyed craft occupations	Case study approach Hermeneutic circle	Women living with severe dementia (n=3)	Meaning was created through sensory interaction with personalised objects. Sensing and touching objects stimulated pleasure and calmness. Objects supported conversations, recall, aesthetic appreciation, and own crafting experiences.	8/10
Educational Science, Health Care		Reminiscence sessions using craft items made/owned by the women (n=3) Content analysis	Enhanced sheltered housing (n=1) Finland	Familiar, previously used objects with a clear purpose stimulated procedural memory and evidenced skills. 'Doing' e.g. knitting provided opportunities to contribute to conversations.	
Roland and Chappell (2015)	To understand how carers perceived the meaning of leisure activities outside of the home for people living with different stages of dementia	Qualitative. Part of a larger study (interviews). Thematic content analysis	Family carers (n=906) (11.6% representing a person with severe dementia) Individual homes British Columbia, Canada	Meaning connected to social esteem and social participation. 91% of carers believed activity to be beneficial for PwAD, although they were considered less likely to feel meaning and self-worth through activity participation. Activities at home were considered more appropriate. Activities were more meaningful if they reduced the person's boredom, improved mood and offered carer respite	6/10
Schneider et al. (2019)	To explore meaning-making with one PwAD during visual art appreciation and to explore if video sufficiently captured this	Exploratory. Case study. Theories of selfhood Filmed interactions	PwAD (n=1); art gallery staff (n=2)] Art gallery (n=1) UK	Person needed others to facilitate and manage interactions. Person was active contributor and co-constructor of meaning through non-verbal interactions. The natural conversation style acknowledged the person's social citizenship	9/10
Sociology, Education, Media					

Psychiatry and Psychology		Video analysis & modified conversation analysis			
Treadway et al. (2019)	To understand how the compassionate design of bespoke objects can enhance wellbeing, pleasure and mood	Action Research, grounded practical theory; participatory, compassionate co-design	PwAD (n=6); family members; workshop participants (n=20)	Bespoke, co-designed objects stimulated curiosity, offered comfort and pleasure, supported communication, and facilitated 1:1 activities and interactions. Bespoke objects also evoked memories, stimulated the senses and encouraged haptic skills. Personalised approaches were recommended since each person reacted differently to the objects	8/10
Creative Practice		Paper reports on research process of LAUGH project	Care homes (n=2) Wales		
		Life histories; workshop (n=1); comparative case studies			
		Narrative, thematic and text analysis			
Walmsley and McCormack (2017)	To interpret expressions of awareness from people living with severe dementia, and the associated family understanding and responses	Phenomenology, critical realism, social interactionism	Family groups (n= 5) consisting of fourteen individuals (people living with severe dementia, n=5)	People living with severe dementia retained complex levels of awareness, which supported relationships. Restrictive, authoritative, invalidating approaches reduced meaningful communication. Flexible, sensitive, validating, playful and open approaches enhanced meaning and reciprocity. Sharing significant memories stimulated deeper conversations	9/10
Psychology		Observations of family visits (n= 2 x 15 minute visits per family group)	Care homes (n=4) Australia		
		Thematic Analysis			
Watson (2019)	To critically analyse supporting factors for embodied and inter-embodied interactions. To understand how this could be enhanced through the Senses Framework	Ethnography, case studies. Theories of selfhood. SENSES Framework	PwAD (n=20); care staff (n=33)	'Body work' formed the core of care. Carers focussed on making connections with the person at this time. Observing subtle changes helped to understand the person's communication style. Listening to the person actively involved the person in activities/interactions. Emotions could be mirrored. Not recognising a person's strengths could undermine them. 'Doing with' the person was mutually rewarding. Inter-embodiment supported relationships.	8/10
Nursing		195 observational hours & supporting staff during ADL's. Interviews with care staff (n=24)	Care home (n=1) Scotland		
		Examination of care plans/care notes			

		Embodied and inter-embodied selfhood framework analysis			
Wood (2019)	To see if a musical lens could capture a care experience	Art-based ethnography, musical methodology. Preverbal theories	Care home resident (n=1); care staff (n=1)	Meaning can be co-created during everyday interactions between care staff and PwAD when a musical lens is applied.	
Music Therapy		Audio tracks capturing personal care, mealtimes and interactions (n=18)	Care homes (n=3) London UK	Personhood can be heard through the tone, pitch, rhythm, and emotion of the voice of a person living with dementia. Procedural and embodied vocal skills can be retained, enabling agency and reciprocity. Verbal and musical meaning	9/10
		Musical analysis			

Table 2.5 Overview of empirical report / evaluation

Author(s), date etc., discipline/ school	Aim(s) of study	Research design, data collection & analysis	Relevant participants & setting	Key findings	JBI score
Tolson et al. (2015) Nursing, Health, Social Sciences	To pilot an enhanced day care model for PwAD using sensory-based and collaborative approaches	States mixed methods but qualitative. Pilot study report Semi-structured interviews (n=7) and quality of life questionnaires (family) Group interviews (n=2) and self-efficacy questionnaires (staff and volunteers) Brief feedback interviews (family, staff and volunteers) Observational log and documentary photography Thematic analysis, T-test analysis	PwAD (n=6). Complete data gathered for four people; family carers (n=5 enhanced day care, n=8 standard day care) Staff and volunteers (n=8-16) Day care (n=1) Scotland	Families valued both standard and enhanced day care. Quality of life was enhanced for three out of the four PwAD and lower for one person, all attending enhanced day care. Improved communication with the person reflected improved quality of life, which was attributed to 1:1 time. Everyday sensory activities facilitated social connectivity. Staff and volunteers were upskilled in sensory activities. Creative methodological approaches with PwAD warrant further investigation.	7/10

Reasons for downgrading quantitative peer reviewed research included the inapplicability of some questions on the appraisal tool. A tool to critically appraise the study by Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin (2017) was not available at the time of critiquing the literature, therefore this was completed in December 2023 using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Analytical Cross-Sectional studies (Moola *et al.*, 2020). Reasons for downgrading qualitative peer reviewed research and the empirical report/evaluation was mainly due to missing information about ethical approval, philosophical and theoretical underpinnings, and researcher position/influences. This was sometimes because the data discussed in the paper was part of a larger study and may have been described elsewhere, for example, Roland and Chappell (2015). None of the literature was excluded, although papers with a lower score were given less weight in the analysis and findings.

The critical appraisal process appeared less sensitive to older literature, and consequently, this type of literature received a lower score because ethical processes for empirical research were not explicitly reported before the year 2000. Although the JBI tools were a useful guide to assess the quality of the literature, the quantitative tools were vague and are currently being reviewed by the JBI (Barker *et al.*, 2023).

2.6 Overview of included literature

The methodologies of *quantitative* peer reviewed research included a correlational design, a single group within participant design, and an experimental design. The methodologies of the *qualitative* peer reviewed research included general qualitative methodology (n=5), phenomenological (n=3), case studies (n=2), ethnography (n=2), grounded theory (n=1), and Action Research (n=1). The *empirical report/evaluation* by Tolson *et al.* (2015) was described as a mixed methods pilot study, however, there was no mention of integrating the data during analysis (Creswell and Creswell, 2018), thus it was treated as qualitative and assessed using the qualitative tool. Two studies used secondary data (Roland and Chappell, 2015; Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017).

The study settings were varied and included: nursing and care homes (n=9), individuals' homes (n=2), a psychogeriatric clinic (n=1), a secure dementia unit (n=1), a community assisted home (n=1), enhanced sheltered housing (n=1), an art gallery (n=1), Enhanced Sensory Day Care (n=1), and a range of settings (n=1). The literature represented a range of disciplines including health, social sciences, creative practice, music therapy, education and spirituality.

Most studies used small samples bar two (Roland and Chappell, 2015; Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017). Numbers of participants ranged from one (Schneider *et al.*, 2019) to 906 (Roland and Chappell, 2015). Participants mainly included PwAD, informal family members, and staff and volunteers. The level of the inclusion of PwAD varied from observational methods (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Watson, 2019) to active inclusion (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Wood, 2019; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019).

2.7 Methodological insights

Some literature shared methodological learning when researching with PwAD. This included consulting family members to clarify interpretations of embodied communication (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017) and to support the person's participation in meaningful activities (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015). Wood (2019) felt a musical methodology enabled the power between PwAD and carers to be shared. He also discovered that this approach revealed a creative perspective of dementia practice and captured the mood of PwAD, atmosphere and context of interactions (Wood, 2019).

Nine of the eighteen studies used audio-visual methods, including video, (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019), documentary photography (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and a mixture of video, drawing, sketching and photography (Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Where provided, reasons for selecting audio-visual methods included accommodating non-verbal communication (Perkins *et al.* 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017) and simultaneously capturing the context (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Audio-visual methods were thought to enhance reliability (Cohen *et al.*, 2009) and illustrate activities and interactions (Tolson *et al.*, 2015). For example, Schneider *et al.* (2019) used video stills to demonstrate their findings. This was helpful from the perspective of a reader because the subtle, non-verbal and embodied communication of PwAD could be seen, inviting the reader to assess rigour (Schneider *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, changes and challenges in dementia practice could be physically seen, offering insights audio data cannot provide (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). Perkins *et al.* (2015) switched to audio-visual methods after audio-recorded interviews with PwAD were found unhelpful for non-verbal, embodied communication.

Video and photography were perceived to create richer data than other methods (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002), and to illuminate the responses, mood, participation (Tolson *et al.*, 2015) and strengths of PwAD (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Video and photography were useful for re-watching/reviewing the responses of PwAD and for capturing detail, increasing rigour and understanding (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Schneider *et al.*, 2019).

Some limitations of using audio-visual methods were described. These included participants declining to be filmed (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999), and the labour-intensiveness of this method (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). There was some initial concern that audio-visual methods would increase participant self-consciousness, however this issue was either not observed (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), or briefly observed (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002).

2.8 How the literature identified PwAD

The methods used to identify PwAD varied and included informal approaches, such as staff identification, specialist knowledge, and the person's presentation, or formal approaches using standardised measures. See Table 2.6 for an overview.

Table 2.6 Overview of how PwAD were identified in the literature

Authors/date	Measures/methods used to identify PwAD
Holst, Edberg and Hallberg (1999) Pöllänen and Hirsimäki (2014) Roland and Chappell (2015)	Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE)
Cohen <i>et al.</i> (2009)	MMSE and Global Deterioration Scale
Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin (2017)	MMSE, Allen Cognitive Level Screen-5, Dementia Rating Scale
Walmsley and McCormack (2017)	Clinical Dementia Rating Scale
Hansebo and Kihlgren (2002)	Cognitive Performance Scale in Resident Assessment Instrument
Tolson <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Functional Assessment Staging Test (FAST) and Pool Activity Level (PAL)
Perkins <i>et al.</i> (2015)	FAST
Ellis and Astell (2017)	Nursing home manager identified residents with diagnosis or probable diagnosis of dementia with little/no verbal communication skills
Hillier and Stokes (2012)	Facility specialised in PwAD
Kuosa, Elstad and Normann (2015)	Staff identified PwAD
Litchke and Hodges (2014)	PwAD lived in a specialist house
McNiel and Westphal (2018)	Participants were required to work with residents accessing a pre-existing Namaste programme, including PwAD
Schneider <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Person mobilised in a wheelchair and did not communicate verbally
Treadaway <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Staff identified PwAD
Watson (2019)	All residents lacked capacity to consent
Wood (2019)	Staff identified PwAD

The guidelines for using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) (Folstein, Folstein and McHugh, 1975), differed between countries, resulting in inconsistencies in identifying PwAD (Nieuwenhuis-Mark, 2010). For example, a score lower than twelve in Finland indicated advanced dementia (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014), whereas this translated to a score less than ten in Sweden (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999). Although this fluidity of scoring can be viewed as an advantage of the measure (Folstein and Folstein, 2010), it further highlights difficulties in identifying this research population (Holmerova *et al.*, 2016).

2.9 How meaning in activities and interactions was defined and understood

No clear, explicit definition of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD was provided in any of the literature. The focus on meaning was variable according to the study, and the reasons for an activity or interactions being meaningful were often overlooked or assumed. Only seven of the selected studies gave sufficient attention to meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD i.e. they described what made activities/interactions meaningful and/or why. Two of these gathered data from family members (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015), one from nurses (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999), and four directly involved PwAD (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Wood, 2019). One gathered information from people with early, moderate and advanced dementia (Roland and Chappell, 2015), and although the data was described according to stage, only the sections discussing PwAD were analysed in this review to preserve clarity. This limited the data available for extraction. Some studies described how the meaning differed for PwAD, family members and staff (Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015), highlighting the importance of involving a range of stakeholders in research to gain different perspectives.

The term meaning-making only appeared in one study in the reviewed literature (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), where it was defined as an interactional 'doing' process through which meaning was actively co-created. This process was thought to be affected by context and acknowledged through (non)verbal communication (Schneider *et al.*, 2019). Meaning-making as described here is a useful term for this current study because it implies a practical, corporeal aspect to meaning in activities and interactions which is likely to align with the strengths of PwAD. It will therefore be used hereafter where appropriate.

Meaning was sometimes perceived as socially co-constructed, with reference to creating a sense of connection and belonging (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019; Wood, 2019). This was thought to be created through reciprocal, mutually beneficial interactions, for instance by establishing a shared language, through co-production/co-creation (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; McNeil and Westphal, 2018; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Wood, 2019), and making a contribution or feeling useful (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015;

Roland and Chappell, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). Relational intricacies were also described as meaningful, such as love and mutual appreciation (Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; McNeil and Westphal, 2018; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019).

Individual benefits for PwAD when experiencing meaning in activities and interactions were also described, however these were not completed alone as others were required to facilitate and maintain activities (Watson, 2019). Benefits included a sense of achievement, comfort, pleasure and/or enjoyment (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Other perceived benefits included stimulation, motivation and the reinforcement of selfhood and identity, which was thought to be enhanced through personalisation (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019).

For a minority of papers, meaning in activities and interactions was not always positive, and could be hindered or enabled through non(confirmatory) and (non)affirmative interactions during everyday life (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999). Some activities were thought to have negative effects on the person, causing anxiety (Roland and Chappell, 2015), and the progression of dementia hindered engagement in meaningful activities (Roland and Chappell, 2015; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Perkins *et al.*, 2015).

Some studies specifically attributed meaning to philosophical and theoretical frameworks, movements, or concepts, including psychological perspectives and Symbolic Interactionism (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), Activity Theory (Kuosu, Elstad and Normann, 2015), developmental theories (Ellis and Astell, 2017), and theories of ageing (Cohen *et al.*, 2009). Other studies used art theories (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), art-based/musical methodology (Wood, 2019), craft literature (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014) and spirituality (Perkins *et al.*, 2015).

When stated, further research recommendations included exploring meaning in activities with people living with different stages of dementia (Roland and Chappell, 2015), and researching purpose in PwAD (Perkins *et al.*, 2015). Other literature offered guidance for practice, such as using multisensory (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015), creative (Wood, 2019), and strengths-based approaches (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014).

2.10 Findings

Four inter-related components of meaning in activities and interactions were identified: 'Ways of Being: relationships with PwAD', 'Ways of Doing', 'Ways of Communicating', and 'Ways of Knowing'. Briefly, 'Ways of Being: relationships with PwAD' explores the complexities of relationships during meaning-making, 'Ways of Doing' describes practical elements of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, 'Ways of Communicating' reports the need for others to adapt to diverse communication styles, and 'Ways of Knowing' describes how PwAD may express meaning. See Appendix 2 for mind-maps illustrating how these themes were developed.

2.10.1 Ways of Being: relationships with people with advanced dementia

This component of meaning describes the intricacies and complexities of relationships, and how meaning in activities and interactions can be enhanced or diluted depending on how PwAD are perceived by others. It also encapsulates the form and function of relationships, the role of emotions, relational power and diverse approaches to connecting with PwAD.

PwAD were mostly considered reliant upon others to initiate and maintain activities and interactions on their behalf, therefore relationships were integral to the person's access to meaningful experiences (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019). Maintaining meaning through activities and interactions was important to retain the identity of PwAD (Perkins *et al.*, 2015), validate their selfhood (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002), reinforce citizenship (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), and improve their quality of life (Cohen *et al.*, 2009).

Relationships and interactions were described in the literature as various forms of dyads (Wood, 2019), or triads (Watson, 2019). Relationships were reported between PwAD, family members, staff members, and other residents, and often involved interactions with physical objects (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Family relationships offered PwAD familiarity and pleasure (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015), whereas staff facilitated engagement in activities and interactions (Schneider *et al.*, 2019) and were essential for fundamental care (Watson, 2019). Other residents could provide romance and friendship (Perkins *et al.*, 2015). In one study, relationships between PwAD and deceased family members continued because

PwAD could not remember the person had died, which appeared to maintain this relationship and provide comfort to PwAD (Perkins *et al.*, 2015).

Relationships could be mutually (in)validating and (non)confirmatory (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). Validating and confirmatory activities and interactions were believed to mutually reinforce the identities of PwAD and their activity partners (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Watson, 2019; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019), and create a shared experience (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Invalidating and non-confirmatory activities and interactions could compromise personal and professional identity, reducing wellbeing for all involved (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Watson, 2019).

In some studies, the role of relationships included a responsibility for others to maintain the social identity of PwAD. This appeared to be a direct result of how the person was viewed by others, which in turn, could enhance or dilute meaning. For instance, when carers observed a PwAD doing something they were assumed incapable of, such as multisensory yoga (Litchke and Hodges, 2014), or verbally communicating (Treadaway *et al.*, 2019), staff and family member views of the person changed from seeing them as passive, to being an active participant (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019).

PwAD could be seen to exist in their “*own world*”, a negative view which made it difficult for family members to connect with the person (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015, p. 214; Roland and Chappell, 2015, p. 563). Although there was a discord among these realities, connections between these worlds were still possible. There were many examples of how this connection could occur, including the merging of realities (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999), attempting to keep the person in the “*real world*” to maintain the person’s social status and citizenship (Roland and Chappell, 2015, p. 563), or when attempting to meet the person in their world (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). Merging realities were thought to enhance empathy (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999). However, shared experiences were not always mutually beneficial (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), because they could simulate insights into the traumatic experiences of PwAD, causing staff to avoid encounters with the person (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999). Viewing PwAD as an embodied, experienced being reduced the likelihood of a ‘social death’ and enhanced meaning-making possibilities (Watson, 2019). Watson (2019) cited Kontos (2004; 2005) to define embodiment as the ‘self’ which resides in the entire body, unrestricted by cognition. Watson (2019) also cited Glaser and Strauss (1965), Sudnow (1967), Froggatt

(2001), and Brannelly (2011) to define social death as the point where others no longer see the person as agential or influential in their own lives. When PwAD were objectified, activities and interactions were approached and completed without considering the meaning for the person, creating an imbalance of power (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019).

The way others perceived PwAD could change the meaning but not necessarily prevent interactions from being meaningful. Holst, Edberg and Hallberg (1999) described how stories informed by the person's past and present experiences could be created by staff, unintentionally flattening their view of the person. However, this did not always negatively affect meaning as it required staff to bring themselves into the narrative as an activity partner, which could enhance empathy (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999).

Several studies suggested emotions and empathy could support or impede meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Emotions experienced by PwAD and others were diverse and often blended and mirrored one another (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Watson, 2019). Much of this was unspoken and mutual, for instance care staff attuning to the person's emotions and unique communication style, awareness, and an ability to sense emotions (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Watson, 2019). This mutual absorption of feelings could be calming for those involved (Watson, 2019), elicit expressions of love, care and pleasure (Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019), and had the potential to balance relational power (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002).

Balancing power seemed to be directly linked with meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). Power referred to opportunities for PwAD to be autonomous, for example through active involvement in self-care and daily life, involving the person in decisions, or participating in activities (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). Power was also used to describe situations where PwAD were perceived to feel powerless, for example when control was lost because of difficulties with memory or communication (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Conversely, power was also related to PwAD retaining power and control, such as withdrawing from a situation (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Power and control could feature in familial relationships, specifically reciprocal sarcasm which created difficult dynamics (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Meaning in activities and interactions appeared linked to autonomy, balanced dynamics, and an ability to sense one

another, highlighting potential importance for others to reflect on their encounters with PwAD and adapt themselves according to the person and context (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Watson, 2019).

Some families explored different ways of 'being' with the PwAD, for example through Namaste (McNiel and Westphal, 2018), however maintaining these connections became more difficult as the person's dementia progressed (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015). In two studies, families felt that their loved one was no longer present, and reduced their visits (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). This unintentionally isolated the person and situated them in a liminal space (Roland and Chappell, 2015; Wood, 2019), causing them to withdraw, and seem distant and lost (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Ellis and Astell, 2017). Likewise, meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD was not always consistent and could be interrupted by tensions and pressures, for example when balancing essential care needs with the person's wishes (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Watson, 2019). This implies meaning is fluid and changeable depending on the context.

Different approaches to engage and connect with PwAD were described in the literature and connecting with PwAD was considered important for meaning-making. Approaches included task-focussed, person-centred, strengths-based/asset-based, relationship-centred, and slow approaches. Task-focussed approaches empowered staff (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002) but risked ignoring the PwAD because they were about doing 'to' or 'for' the person, rather than 'with' (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019). Activities and interactions between PwAD and staff often centred around self-care, therefore effort was required to maintain connections as the focus could easily switch to the task rather than remaining on the person and the meaning (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Watson, 2019), particularly if PwAD communicated non-verbally (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Watson, 2019) and were considered "*unreachable*" (Ellis and Astell, 2017, p. 18;). Task-focussed approaches could also cause the person to become withdrawn and detached (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), retiring their remaining skills, and reducing opportunities for meaning-making (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Watson, 2019).

Person-centred approaches were reported in over half of the literature sources, and described as seeing the person not the task, by tailoring and personalising communication, activities and interactions to the person's interests and preferences (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017;

McNiel and Westphal, 2018; Watson, 2019; Wood, 2019; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). This was not surprising given the influences of Kitwood (1997a) in health and social care. Person-centred approaches were seen as meaningful because they were believed to empower PwAD (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), reinforce their identity and personhood (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015), provide responsive support (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and create a shared, familiar language (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Wood, 2019). However, the meaningfulness of person-centred approaches was affected by how others perceived the PwAD (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), and by institutional rules and routines (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019).

Strengths-focussed approaches were similar to person-centredness but specifically focussed on recognising and using the person's previous interests and current skills to create opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). For example, using humour and play to provide opportunities for expression and interaction without the need for verbal exchange, offer opportunities for laughter and mutual enjoyment, and distract the PwAD from upset (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). For the carer, this approach increased job satisfaction and provided a way to connect with the PwAD (Treadaway *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, an asset-based approach illuminated what was going well for the person, which could be used to enhance wellbeing (Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). This approach actively combined the preserved skills of PwAD with those of staff and family members to increase participation in activity (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002). Combining skills could also reinforce the person's selfhood (Watson, 2019) and offer a chance for the PwAD to use their preserved skills, experience satisfaction and enhance mood (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). An example includes the other person moving close to PwAD during multisensory yoga, enabling the PwAD to see and mirror the pose (Litchke and Hodge, 2014).

A relationship-centred/relational approaches appeared to develop strengths-based and asset-based approaches by drawing on the embodied knowledge of PwAD (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Watson, 2019). For instance, Watson (2019) adapted the 'Senses Framework' (Nolan *et al.*, 2004; Nolan *et al.*, 2006) specifically to the needs of people with dementia (PwD) rather than older people. The 'Senses Framework' is a model which aims to enhance meaningful relationships in health and social care through the six senses: security, continuity, belonging, purpose, fulfilment, and significance (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Nolan *et al.*,

2004). Informed by observing and engaging in fundamental care activities with PwAD and care staff, Watson (2019) added sensory, personalised, and embodied/inter-embodied perspectives to the framework and suggested that meaning occurred when PwAD were acknowledged as an active and joint partner in their own care. Watson (2019) cited Zeiler (2013) to define inter-embodiment as a partnership through which a person and their skills are validated.

Alternatively, Walmsley and McCormack (2017) studied familial relationships and established the term, 'Relational Social Engagement' (RSE) to describe an array of negative and positive interactions and emotions between PwAD and their family members. Positive interactions were defined as being 'in-step' i.e. where family members thoughtfully and sensitively approached the person and were attentive to their needs. Negative interactions occurred when interactions were 'out-of-step' i.e. when PwAD were ignored or undermined by family members, or when the expectations of family members were too high. Interestingly, meaning was implied in positive and negative interactions because of the embedded family bond (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017).

Lastly, a relaxed, peaceful and slow approach was encouraged in two papers to allow time and space to be with PwAD, satisfying all involved (Tolson *et al.*, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018). Relaxation was noticeable in some PwAD during and/or after Namaste (McNiel and Westphal, 2018) and during sensory day care (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), suggesting that the pacing of activities and interactions is important for meaning.

This theme focussed on the impact of relationships on meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, revealing the intricacies and complexities of such relationships.

2.10.2 Ways of Doing

The following component of meaning describes the practical elements of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. It highlights the types of activities and interactions and their perceived purpose, the use of physical objects, adapting activities and the environment, and time/timing.

Various activities and interactions for PwAD were described in the literature, although these were not always explicitly related to meaning. These included planned and spontaneous one-to-one activities and group activities. One-to-one activities often had a sensory element (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018; Treadaway *et*

al., 2019), for example using nail painting to stimulate smell, sight and touch, and using picture books to rouse the visual system (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Tolson *et al.*, 2015). Other one-to-one activities included storytelling, dancing (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), music and singing (Perkins *et al.*, 2015), sorting beads, simple physical exercises (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017), and self-care (Watson, 2019). Group activities also involved the senses, such as multisensory yoga (Litchke and Hodges, 2014), Namaste (McNiel and Westphal, 2018), and reminiscence (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Although group activities were believed to offer psychosocial benefits and create opportunities for reciprocity and connection (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), they were not always offered. One study found family, social and reminiscence activities to be prescribed less often for PwAD by occupational therapists than those living with early or moderate dementia (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017), but the reasons for this were not explained.

The purpose of activities and interactions for PwAD varied. Activities and interactions were thought to provide opportunities for relaxation and spirituality (Perkins *et al.*, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018), reconnect with ‘the self’ (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015), provide stimulation and enjoyment (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019), and explore, navigate and interact with the world (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Co-creating activities and interactions with PwAD could enhance a mutual sense of achievement and purpose (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and increase reciprocal wellbeing, quality of life and participation. For family carers, activities for PwAD could offer respite (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015), although the effect of respite was seen as less effective as the dementia advanced (Roland and Chappell, 2015). However, activities and interactions were not always considered positive (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002) and could be “*the cause of anxiety and/or the solution*”, particularly if activities were too difficult for PwAD (Roland and Chappell, 2015, p. 567). This suggests that activities need to be closely matched with the person’s current skills to create meaning.

Objects were sometimes used as an activity themselves, or as part of an activity to encourage expression and provide shared opportunities (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Personalised objects were believed to generate wellbeing and quality of life (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019), and initiate curiosity and interest, even if the person had no memory of previously using them (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Objects representing activities from the person’s life history offered opportunities for PwAD to

showcase and use their haptic knowledge and embodied skills, for example textile items and crafting tools encouraged PwAD to perform crochet and knitting activities (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Furthermore, touching/stroking animals and inanimate objects were perceived to enhance communication and reciprocity (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; McNeil and Westphal, 2018).

Other personalised objects included a bespoke therapeutic game (Cohen *et al.*, 2009), personal photographs (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015), co-designed and playful objects (Treadaway *et al.*, 2019), dolls, soft toys, fabrics, flowers (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and gallery artwork (Schneider *et al.*, 2019). The therapeutic game was thought to provide comfort for family members during visits by offering a structured, focussed activity (Cohen *et al.*, 2009). Leaving objects, items and unfinished activities within reach of PwAD could encourage and attract PwAD to engage in purposeful activities and provide them with opportunities to use embodied and haptic skills (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015). This suggests that (personalised) objects may invite PwAD to participate in activities and interactions and/or facilitate family visits.

Personalising and tailoring activities and interactions were believed to enhance meaning for the PwAD in over half of the literature sources (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019). Personalisation involved gathering an occupational history of the person's preferences and interests and considering them alongside the person's current mobility, nutrition, continence care, washing and dressing. Information about the person's ethnicity (Perkins *et al.*, 2015) and native language was sometimes integrated into activities and interactions to provide familiarity, comfort and maintain the person's identity (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Activities related to the person's past were considered meaningful for similar reasons (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). However, relying purely on previously enjoyed activities could result in missed opportunities and experiences (Tolson *et al.*, 2015).

Two studies specifically focussed on providing individually tailored support through services for PwAD. One analysed secondary data from Tailored Activity Programmes (TAP) for people with mild, moderate and severe dementia, and described TAP as an activity-based programme to enhance the participation of PwD by tailoring activities according to the person's skills, needs and environment (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017). TAP enabled people living with

all stages of dementia to participate in activities, although the meaning in these activities was not discussed (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017). Similarly, Enhanced Sensory Daycare was described as an environment tailored to the needs of PwAD through sensory-based activities and one-to-one interactions (Tolson *et al.*, 2015). This service was perceived by family members to be stimulating and engaging for PwAD, however, transport and the progression of dementia were potential barriers (Tolson *et al.*, 2015). Although 'meaningful activities' were fundamental to the sensory focus of the pilot study, the meaning in the activities was not clearly identified.

A sensory and embodied perspective also offered a meaningful way to adapt, facilitate and support activities and interactions with PwAD (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; McNeil and Westphal, 2018; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). For example, exploring the properties of objects i.e. their materials, aesthetics, textures, colours, and being able to: "*touch, smooth, pat, jiggle, stretch and straighten*" items, provided opportunities for PwAD to experience play and feelings of pleasure, comfort and calmness (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014, p. 421; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019) whilst enhancing satisfaction for staff and volunteers (Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, touch could reinforce experiential knowledge and skills, for example, during multisensory chair yoga. This form of yoga was adapted to emphasise the senses, for instance, using touch to physically prompt PwAD, sounds and songs to provide auditory stimulation, and modelling poses to provide visual information (Litchke and Hodges, 2014). Furthermore, purposeful movement could increase focus and participation (Litchke and Hodges, 2014), provide purpose (Tolson *et al.*, 2015) and create personal meaning (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017).

Other ways of adapting activities and interactions were described in the literature. These included finding alternative ways to present information (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017), for example, using images (Cohen *et al.*, 2009) and visual cues (Litchke and Hodges, 2014), and encouraging social connections through music, dancing and singing (Perkins *et al.* 2015). Additionally, small acts like ensuring PwAD were wearing their glasses or hearing aids could enhance communication, reciprocity and participation in interactions with family members (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017).

Adjusting the time required for PwAD to participate in or complete activities and interactions was thought to maximise their abilities. Perspectives on the duration of activities for PwD differed according to the stage of dementia and the study. For example, one study found that occupational therapists recommended 45.50 mins (mean rank score) for activities for people with early dementia, and eleven minutes for PwAD (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017),

whereas another study facilitated reminiscence sessions lasting between 55-65 minutes (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014). The reasons for the duration of these activities in either research were not specified. Litchke and Hodges (2014) took a graded approach to multisensory chair yoga, starting with 30 minute per session, building up to 55 minutes over a ten-week period, while Kuosa, Elstad and Normann (2015) recommended the duration of activities to be adapted to suit individuals. Alternatively, a slow pace of delivery and high ratio of staff was suggested to enable the tailoring of one-to-one interactions (Tolson *et al.*, 2015). These examples suggest the duration of activities and interactions with PwAD may impact meaning, although, the reasons for this remain unclear.

The timing of activities and interactions could also enhance meaning, with momentary activities and interactions considered meaningful in nine of the selected papers (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; McNiel and Westphal, 2018; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019;). Momentary activities could be spontaneous or planned, last seconds or minutes, and be used at any time of day, during any task (Hillier and Stokes, 2012). 'In the moment' topical conversations could be co-created and developed into meaningful interactions (Wood, 2019). These approaches promoted flexibility (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019) and reduced cognitive demand for PwAD (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019). However, meaning was not always instantly visible and could require six attempts of momentary activities before positive effects on the person's mood were noted (Hillier and Stokes, 2012). Examples of meaningful moments included complimenting PwAD, asking their opinion, responding to the news, using reminiscence, or personalising interactions (Hillier and Stokes, 2012).

Spontaneous moments promoted humour, play, fun, enjoyment (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019) and offered mutual opportunities for expression, relaxation (McNiel and Westphal, 2018), decision-making (Perkins *et al.*, 2015), acceptance, and connectivity (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018). Conversely, Cohen *et al.* (2009) found mutual pleasure and wellbeing was enhanced for PwAD when family visits and activities were structured and organised, whereas unstructured visits increased stress for PwAD and family members. Alternatively, Perkins *et al.* (2015) reported PwAD having difficulty with planned, structured activities because the inflexibility of these activities were incompatible with the person's fluctuating mood and interests.

Some studies considered adapting and personalising the physical and social environment to enhance meaning for PwAD. For instance, personal belongings in a dementia unit could create meaning by creating a familiar, private space (Perkins *et al.*, 2015) and personhood could be reinforced if the social environment was responsive to the communication styles of PwAD (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Wood, 2019). However, the person's anxiety could increase if new activities were attempted with the person (Roland and Chappell, 2015), and changes in approaches to care could enhance or disrupt the person's ability to engage in activities and interactions (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; McNiel and Westphal, 2018).

The perception of meaning in activities and interactions appeared changeable depending on the participant group and whether activities occurred indoors or outdoors. For instance, two studies described how family members felt at-home activities for PwAD were important for relieving boredom and enhancing the person's mood (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015), but opinions about outdoor activities differed. In one study, outdoor activities were considered beneficial for the person's physical and psychological health but were difficult to organise once the person moved into a care home (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015). Another study found activities outside of the home were only perceived to be important by 4% of family members caring for PwAD compared to 59% of those caring for people living with early dementia (Roland and Chappell, 2015). This appeared to be because of the progression of dementia, particularly if the PwAD was incontinent or fatigued (Roland and Chappell, 2015). From the perspectives of PwAD and staff, connections to nature and the outdoors were thought to be spiritually meaningful for some PwAD because they provided opportunities for enjoyment (Perkins *et al.*, 2015). In this case, spirituality was not related to religion, rather the term was used to reflect how individuals in a dementia unit connect to the world (Perkins *et al.*, 2015). These examples suggest opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions are affected by access to/interaction with the physical environment, practicalities and the perceived importance of the activity.

Non-clinical environments were considered meaningful for some studies, including an Enhanced Sensory Day Care and an art gallery. Day care was perceived as meaningful by carers because it offered PwAD a place of safety and trust (Tolson *et al.*, 2015). The art gallery was considered meaningful because it reflected the person's previous interests, encouraged interaction, and facilitated a collaborative and socially equal exploration of meaning (Schneider *et al.*, 2019). The layout of the gallery also encouraged time and space to pause, reflect, consider and engage with the artwork (Schneider *et al.*, 2019). These examples imply

meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD is somewhat affected by the physical and social environment and how they relate to the narratives of PwAD.

This theme identified how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may alter according to the type and purpose of activities and how meaning could be enhanced by adapting activities and interactions.

2.10.3 Ways of Communicating

This component of meaning portrays the diverse communication styles of PwAD and how alternative approaches and responses from others were required to create meaning. It includes reciprocity and a need for others to adapt 'the self'.

Adapting and responding to the diverse and unique communication styles of PwAD was a consistent thread in the literature. Although some PwAD communicated verbally, paying attention to post-verbal, embodied communication was important because it offered insights into the person's mood (Watson, 2019; Wood, 2019). Wood (2019) used the term, 'post-verbal' to define PwAD who were no longer able to use coherent speech but could still use their voices to communicate their emotions and convey their personhood, with or without the use of words. Post-verbal was not used in any other literature, but since most studies referred to PwAD as 'non-verbal' to characterise a variety of communication styles that may or may not involve words, post-verbal is used throughout to avoid confusion. Post-verbal communication included how the person used their body (Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Watson, 2019), and their voice, for example through the tone, pitch, rhythm and speed (Wood, 2019), using limited words, and when singing or vocalising high-pitched/speech-like sounds (Ellis and Astell, 2017).

Listening and responding to post-verbal, embodied communication was key to meaning-making, and numerous examples were provided in the literature. These included communicating through activities requiring touch, such as hair brushing and massage (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and different types of touch, such as sensitive and appropriate touch (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002), purposeful touch (Litchke and Hodges, 2014) and personal touch (McNiel and Westphal, 2018). Other ways of responding involved simulating typical reciprocal conversations by respecting natural pauses (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), imitating the person's communication style to provide acknowledgement and validation (Ellis and Astell, 2017), gesturing to music (Litchke and Hodges, 2014), or attending to emotional and musical tones in the voice rather than focussing the content (Wood, 2019). Additionally, it was important to

observe the person's facial expressions and posture, and to note any signs of agitation or distress (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Watson, 2019). Bespoke and unique ways of communicating were also observed between families through love, gestures, facial expressions, movement, dance, play and storytelling, which appeared to create meaning through reciprocity and familiarity (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Although the meaning in these texts was related to shared experiences, the meaning itself was not unravelled, making it difficult to understand why it was meaningful.

Responding to the person required others to be mindful of their own approach and adapt themselves according to the person's way of communicating. This involved using auditory and tactile cues to prompt the person and maintain their interest (Regier, Hodgson and Gitlin, 2017), asking questions that did not require the person to remember the content, asking one question at a time, and keeping to the topic (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017). Ellis and Astell (2017) proposed using closed questions when interacting with PwAD to allow space for non-verbal communication, rather than open questions which required verbal skills. Overvaluing verbal communication and memory and not recognising alternative communicative acts appeared to limit opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Wood, 2019).

Reciprocity helped to create meaning (Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019) by acknowledging the person and their need for affection, love and care (Perkins *et al.*, 2015). Different ways of giving and receiving were illustrated in the literature, including embodiment and inter-embodiment and Adaptive Interaction. Watson (2019) described how embodiment and inter-embodiment could be used as a dialogue with PwAD during self-care activities to maximise the person's agency, validate them, and provide physical and emotional comfort if adequate time was provided. This approach required authenticity from others, and an ability to notice and respond to subtle forms of communication (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019). Adaptive Interaction acknowledged and validated PwAD through an iterative process of observing and mirroring to co-create and reciprocate a bespoke, mutually satisfying interaction (Ellis and Astell, 2017). It seems that reciprocal acts appear to co-create meaning through shared, validating experiences.

This theme examined how attending and responding to the diverse communication styles of PwAD could enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. It also emphasised the importance of others adapting to PwAD.

2.10.4 Ways of Knowing

This component describes how the literature identified when meaning had occurred. Although some literature stated it was impossible to know if activities and interactions were meaningful to PwAD, many studies described looking for 'clues', for example in the person's mood, behaviour, levels of engagement, and body language.

Displaying positive emotions during activities and interactions was seen as meaningful in many literature sources. Positive emotions included self-worth, enjoyment, joy, satisfaction, happiness, and pleasure (Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015). These emotions seemed to be meaningful because they created a sense of normality (Cohen *et al.*, 2009), motivated the person (Kuosa, Elstad and Normann, 2015), enhanced self-esteem (Roland and Chappell, 2015), and stimulated relaxation (McNiel and Westphal, 2018). Positive emotions were noted during a range of activities, including listening to music (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), during Namaste (McNiel and Westphal, 2018), and when eating (Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Watson, 2019). Some papers also described negative emotions in both PwAD and others when engaging in activities and interactions (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), including distress, overwhelm, anxiety, boredom (Roland and Chappell, 2015), depression and sadness (Cohen *et al.*, 2009).

Various behaviours were thought to evidence meaning, for example, increased engagement (Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Treadaway *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019), being motivated to attend an activity (Tolson *et al.*, 2015), and reduced agitation (Cohen *et al.*, 2009). Refusal and disinterest were thought to signify a lack of/reduced meaning in activities and interactions (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Roland and Chappell, 2015).

Watching how PwAD used their bodies could also guide the meaningfulness of activities and interactions, for example through body language, facial expressions and reactions. Giving eye contact, actively looking at another person/activity/object, higher levels of awareness or alertness, and increased attention, concentration and focus were viewed as evidence for meaning-making, as were deliberate and purposeful movements such as clapping or tapping (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; McNiel and Westphal, 2018; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, a variety of reactions signalled meaning, including animated expressions, changes in posture, attempts at making speech sounds, smiling, laughter, mirroring, reaching out/touching others, and expressions of love or affection (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Hillier and Stokes, 2012; Litchke and

Hodges, 2014; Pöllänen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Tolson *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; McNeil and Westphal, 2018; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). These examples demonstrated a repertoire of communication methods used by PwAD, however they may be subtle and easily missed or overlooked by others (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019).

Establishing whether activities and interactions were meaningful to PwAD was difficult, particularly if the person communicated post-verbally (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019). This difficulty was assigned to the progression of the dementia and associated deteriorating verbal skills, which reduced social and occupational opportunities (Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Roland and Chappell, 2015). Facilitating opportunities which nurtured diverse communication could help to maintain the person's participation (Walmsley and McCormack, 2017), such as using a musical and emotional perspective (Wood, 2019). Staff could be supported to do this through reflective activities e.g. supervision in a dedicated space and with organisational support (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Watson, 2019).

2.11 Summary

This integrative review aimed to understand a real-world application of meaning in everyday activities and interactions with PwAD from diverse perspectives. It sought to provide insight into how meaning in activities and interactions was interpreted in the literature and why and in what ways the activities and interactions were considered meaningful for PwAD. However the focus on meaning varied between studies, and the reasons for an activity or interaction being considered or interpreted as meaningful were often overlooked, assumed or lacked detail, hence literature review questions were not wholly answered, highlighting an empirical gap about how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD are understood.

Key learning from the findings suggests meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD are difficult to define and identify. This suggests that close attention to the embodied and post-verbal communication of PwAD is required to observe the presence and co-creation of meaning. Relational, inter-embodied, personalised and empathic approaches and/or the use of physical objects may enhance meaning, however opportunities for activities and interactions using these approaches appear to depend on how others perceive PwAD and what others consider to be a meaningful activity. If PwAD are perceived by others to be incapable of participating in activities and interactions, power imbalances may occur, risking PwAD being objectified and invalidated. Hence there appears to be a need for others to sense

and feel the reactions of PwAD and appropriately acknowledge PwAD for meaning to be (co)created. Meaning in this context seems to have the potential to provide sensory stimulation, enjoyment, comfort and calm for PwAD, their family members, and staff. The literature also provided some methodological insights, for example, a need to focus on learning and change, and a collaborative approach which actively includes PwAD, their family members and staff. Additional insights include selecting methods which can sensitively and effectively capture post-verbal, embodied communication and movement. This suggests that participatory, action-orientated research designs and creative, flexible, audio-visual methods are required to explore meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

This review did not include theoretical and philosophical literature. This was because this extensive body of work was not specific to PwAD and would have gone beyond the realms of the criteria. It was therefore decided to treat this literature separately in the form of a critical discussion to understand diverse theoretical and philosophical conceptualisations of meaning; this viewpoint is offered in the next chapter.

Chapter 3 : A theoretical and philosophical exploration of meaning

3.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to provide a critical exploration of diverse theoretical and philosophical conceptualisations of meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia (PwAD) outside of the integrative review criteria. Since most of this literature is not specific to people with dementia (PwD) or PwAD, its potential relevance and application to this population will be considered and discussed. Rather than providing a summary at the end, the relevance to PwAD is woven into each section of this chapter to assess its suitability in context.

Literature about meaning is vast and the concept has been explored from diverse perspectives over centuries (Machielse, 2024). As such, a non-systematic, purposive approach was used to allow flexibility and an in-depth exploration of the literature based on my knowledge of the field. Literature was identified by hand searching reference lists when reading in and around the subject and during conversations with scholars in the field. This provided an understanding of the conceptual perspectives of meaning which were used to develop the study design and inform the methods.

This discussion is structured through a theoretical and philosophical discussion of 'the self' and selves (Goffman, 1969) because literature about meaning focussed on various aspects of the human body. Firstly, literature describing a mind/body divide will be critically discussed, followed by dialogues exploring the mind, the body, 'bodies with and between other bodies', and 'beyond the body'.

3.2 The mind/body divide

This section discusses literature that views meaning and identity as being contained within the mind, dislocating the mind from the body.

Descartes (1892) metaphorically deconstructed the mind and the body, describing the mind as a unit consisting of memory, intellect, imagination and reasoning, and the body being composed through form and movement. While the work of Descartes has since been revisited, and his contribution to psychology acknowledged (Brown and Key, 2020), a disconnected view of humanity prevails. This disconnect led to the dominance of biomedical models and the belief that 'the self' resided in the mind, contributing to the stigma of PwD (Walrath and Lawlor, 2019).

Stigma can dehumanise PwAD (Behuniak, 2011) and indirectly impede the person's ability to (co)create meaning (Zeiler, 2014). Thus, the mind-body divide appears to close opportunities for understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD by emphasising likely areas of difficulty.

Although Locke (1997) developed the theory of dualism by connecting the senses, the body, and the brain, identity was still restricted to memory. This implies that the 'self' and identity only exist in memories, awareness and other cognitive functions (Kontos, 2004; Hughes, 2013), creating legal, philosophical and ethical conflicts for PwAD (Hughes, 2001). Furthermore, dualistic perspectives impose criteria for persons to qualify as human (Zeiler, 2014), dismissing or neglecting other ways of being, and disembodiment and dehumanising PwAD, which can alienate them from society (Behuniak, 2010).

3.3 The mind

This section discusses literature that describes meaning from psychological and narrative (language and communication) perspectives.

3.3.1 Psychological perspectives

Psychological perspectives of meaning focus on how people make sense of their lives, themselves, others and their surroundings (Wong, 2012). These positions include existential psychology, positive psychology, the dual-systems model (Wong, 2012), scientific psychology (Klinger, 1977), social psychology (Baumeister, 1991), and humanism (Derkx, 2013).

The four fundamental human concerns in existential psychology, namely death, freedom, isolation and meaninglessness (Yalom, 1980) focus on the bleakness of living (Wong, 2012). Although there may be aspects of this which may relate to meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, for example, enhancing freedom and reducing isolation, this view may emphasise stigma by focussing on illbeing. However, it is equally important not to completely dismiss Yalom's (1980) contribution, since this integrative review highlighted that meaning in interactions and activities with PwAD could be created through positive *and* negative emotions and experiences. In contrast, positive psychology encompasses positivity, such as hope, pleasure and creativity, shifting the focus from survival to growth, development and transformation (Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Perhaps an approach which regards meaning as multifaceted and inclusive of all emotions is worth considering to avoid invalidating or simplifying the experience of living with advanced dementia. For example, the dual-systems model consists of desires and goals, fears/overcoming them, and making sense of human

experience, recognising meaning in a multitude of emotions (Wong, 2012). As such, the latter view is perhaps more validating to the experiences of living with advanced dementia.

Klinger's (1977) scientific psychological approach examines meaning in terms of thoughts and feelings and how these affect an individual's motivation and capacity to carry out their goals. To a certain degree, this perspective may be useful when understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, for example, the relationship between meaning and the thoughts and feelings of PwAD during an activity/interaction. However, identifying meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD through a cognitive lens would be difficult since cognitive approaches are unlikely to match the skills of PwAD. Furthermore, PwAD are rarely directly included in research (Collins *et al.*, 2023), therefore it is unclear how meaning is experienced for this population.

From a social psychological perspective, Baumeister (1991) described meaning as a sense-making process which occurs through the act of doing, and that a lack of meaning may be a motivator to seek meaning. He identified four needs of meaning: purpose, value, efficacy and self-worth (Baumeister, 1991). 'Purpose' encompasses present and future possibilities for fulfilment through the process of pursuing goals (Baumeister, 1991). It is important to note that the *opportunity* for possibility creates meaning rather than whether the goal is achieved (Baumeister, 1991). This suggests that opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may be meaningful in and of themselves, regardless of the outcome.

'Value' refers to personal, societal and cultural values, while 'efficacy' is a self-belief that a goal is achievable because it is the 'right' level of difficulty for those concerned (Baumeister, 1991). 'Efficacy' also relates to control and choice in life, either by adapting the physical and social environment or by adapting the self (Baumeister, 1991; Derkx, 2013). Finally, 'self-worth' is positive high regard for 'the self', and the need to feel worthy, which may overlap or conflict with the 'value' need (Baumeister, 1991; Derkx, 2013). Baumeister (1991) suggested that to experience meaning, all four needs must be satisfied. However, while each of these needs may somewhat apply to PwAD it may be unlikely that anyone, with or without dementia would achieve all these needs. Nevertheless, Baumeister's (1991) four needs raise important and complex questions for PwAD. For example, PwD may experience reduced opportunities for personal and social growth upon diagnosis and/or moving to a care home because their main motivator may be to avoid a 'living death' (Cohen, 1988, p 25). This may result in a grieving process for PwAD and their family members (Wearing, 2023), and the needs described by Baumeister (1991) may go unsatisfied or be non-meaningful. This suggests that the stigma of dementia may directly impact meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD.

Baumeister's (1991) model was critiqued and developed by Derkx (2013) along with colleagues Mooren (1998) and Smaling and Alma (2010), as cited in Derkx (2013; 2020). This revised model acknowledged gaps in Baumeister's needs, leading to the addition of three more: comprehensibility, connectedness and transcendence. *Comprehensibility* is the desire to make sense of the world, *connectedness* is a need for social contact, love, friendship and citizenship, and *transcendence* is the experience of curiosity and wonder when exploring new possibilities outside of the self (Derkx, 2013). Derkx *et al.* (2020) later applied and analysed the seven needs to older people from an interdisciplinary perspective. This created new insights, including the potential to view meaning in terms of past, present and future and whether meaning earlier in life could be relevant/reapplied in later life (Derkx *et al.*, 2020). This suggests that meaning is fluid, iterative and connected to temporal aspects of life. These ideas by Derkx *et al.* (2020) may be helpful for understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because it considers the person as continually evolving rather than stagnant and fixed, potentially extending possibilities for meaning-making.

During his search for meaning as a prisoner in an Auschwitz concentration camp, Frankl (2004, p.75) contemplated potential relationships between meaning and "*spiritual freedom*" – a personal feeling of control over how to act in a situation to protect self-dignity. He concluded that even in times of great distress and adversity, meaning could be achieved by considering other perspectives which opened opportunities for choice, nourishment and imagination (Frankl, 2004). This implies that dignity, freedom and control may be interlinked with meaning, which is relevant to PwAD, their human rights and ethics (Heggestad, Nortvedt, and Slettebø, 2013). Furthermore, there appear to be links between dignity, stigma, and how others perceive older people and PwAD (Heggestad, Nortvedt, and Slettebø, 2013; Banerjee *et al.*, 2021) – factors which also seem significant in meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Frankl (2004) also identified how meaning could be achieved through 'doing' activities and connecting with others, for example when prisoners forfeited food rations for opportunities to participate in creative pursuits, such as singing and poetry. This suggests that some aspects of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may be more important than others, and that this may alter depending on the context. A creative view of meaning is explored in Section 3.4.4.

A side-step away from the dualistic views of meaning combines psychological views with hermeneutic realism, as represented by Slife and Christensen (2013). Their interpretation places context, changeability and possibility at the heart of meaning, acknowledging how individuals are affected and altered by social experiences (Slife and Christensen, 2013). This highlights the fluctuating and dynamic nature of meaning and potential opportunities for growth

(Slife and Christensen, 2013) in a similar way to how psychiatrist and philosopher, Julian Hughes (2013) related meaning for PwD to context, history and culture, as discussed in Section 3.4.2.

3.3.2 Narrative (language and communication)

Narrative perspectives of meaning include semiotics, language and communication (Ogden and Richards, 1960; Bruner, 1990). Ogden and Richards (1960) theorised about meaning in semiotics and how meaning was disrupted by thoughts and emotions. They concluded that meaning is created through the transaction of words and symbols, and weakened or strengthened by (mis)understandings between the speaker and listener (Ogden and Richards, 1960). Their focus on words is unhelpful in the context of advanced dementia because PwAD often lose the ability to communicate verbally (McLeish, 2019), and society's preoccupation with linguistic skills has created a damaging, toxic and flawed understanding of dementia (Jenkins, 2013; Quinn and Blandon, 2017; Kontos *et al.*, 2021). Nonetheless, Ogden and Richards' (1960) argument that meaning can be intended and interpreted differently depending on the person's prior experiences may be a useful consideration for this study, particularly since the perspectives of PwAD, family members and staff are invited.

Bruner (1990) argued that to create meaning, a person needs a foundational ability to both decipher language and use it appropriately according to the context. Whilst he did not specifically relate this to the formation of words, Bruner (1990) focussed on child development rather than dementia. Given that the PwAD in this study are adults who have likely acquired language skills during their lives, it is reasonable to suggest prelinguistic skills may be retained in post-verbal communication. This indicates that language can be adapted to co-create shared meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, as suggested in the literature review. In addition to the language aspects of narrative, Bruner (1990) combined psychology and anthropology to suggest meaning was socially constructed (Bruner, 1990), as discussed in Section 3.5.3.

3.4 The body

This section explores literature that focusses on various aspects of meaning related to the body, including phenomenology, embodiment, human agency, creativity and selfhood/personhood.

3.4.1 Phenomenology

Meaning through a phenomenological lens depends on the perspective of the theorist. Husserl (1970) founded phenomenology to separate from dualistic and psychological perspectives of meaning and instead focus on living experiences through doing (Vagle *et al.* 2024). Husserl (1970) described how meaning could be understood through the processes of human-object experiences and interactions. He defined objects as abstract thoughts/images as well as physical items and places, believing that the essence of meaning could be separated from the act, whilst remaining contradictorily inseparable (Husserl, 1970). Although the focus on the experience rather than the mind is more helpful for the context of this study, Husserl's (1970) ulterior view of subjective-objective interactions suggests a removal of oneself is required to appreciate a true meaning of an experience. This is unhelpful for this current study because PwAD are often prejudiced and considered 'lost' to themselves (Katz and Leibing, 2023), and Husserl's (1970) view may exacerbate this.

Conversely, Heidegger (1962) related meaning to simply existing, by which he meant participating in and being part of everyday life to create an inseparable 'whole' (Vagle *et al.* 2024). This perspective is more useful to understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because PwAD, their experiences and what they do, are acknowledged in connection with others, things and places. This perspective may validate the existence of PwAD who are perhaps unseen by others.

Merleau-Ponty (1964; 1968; 2002) attributed meaning to how the body actively perceives, feels, senses and experiences the world and vice-versa. He explored relationships between 'seeing' and acknowledging the visibility of others as well as deepening understandings of the self and the world (Merleau-Ponty, 1964; 1968). Merleau-Ponty (1968) described how this process created opportunities for (inter)connectedness through which a constantly renewed and updated reality occurred. Although criticised for not adapting his theories to the disabled body (Thanem and Knights, 2019), the theories of Merleau-Ponty (1964; 1968; 2002) are somewhat useful for understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. For instance, his work about implicit bodily knowing is useful for PwAD who may express meaning post-verbally through their bodies (Kontos, 2004).

3.4.2 Embodiment

Embodiment is the expression of identity and 'the self' through the body (Thanem and Knights, 2019). The expressions and actions of the body are shaped by evolving physical, social and cultural environments which are interconnected and inter-dependent with the body, feelings, senses and thoughts (Johnson, 2017). Meaning is created through the choreography of bodies

interacting with these environments, suggesting meaning itself is embodied (Johnson, 2017). Framing the body and its relationship with environments as an absorber, processor and exhibitor of meaning provides more accessible opportunities to explore an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Kontos has written extensively about embodiment and dementia (2004; 2005; Kontos and Naglie, 2009; 2011; 2012b; Kontos and Martin, 2013), progressing this field by combining the work of Merleau-Ponty (1968; 2002) and Bourdieu (1990) to coin the phrase, “*embodied selfhood*” (Kontos, 2004, p.832; 2005, p. 556). Embodied selfhood establishes the body as an active expressor of meaning and narrator of ‘the self’, created from personal, social and cultural experiences (Kontos, 2004; 2005). Kontos (2004) describes how people with moderate and advanced dementia in a long-term care facility demonstrated meaning through embodied selfhood by means of their appearance, movement, interactions and gestures. This is particularly important for this study because observing and ‘doing’ with PwAD may offer insights into how meaning in activities and interactions is portrayed and created.

Similarly, Hughes (2013) describes how in the absence of verbal language, meaning can be established through feeling, sensing and bodily know-how (Wittgenstein, 1968; Merleau-Ponty, 2002), for example through the Situated Embodied Agent (SEA) View (Hughes, 2001). The SEA View presents PwAD as embodied beings capable of purposeful action (Hughes, 2001). Through this lens, meaning is constituted in and shown through the body to reflect personal, familial, cultural and historical narratives (Hughes, 2001). This perspective is useful for this study because it reinstates PwAD as purposeful, useful and valid social citizens.

3.4.3 Human agency

Agency has been explored from diverse angles and perspectives, for example, from a psychological view of selfhood (Harré, 1998), an archaeological viewpoint (Dobres and Robb, 2000), and through a post-humanist lens (Caronia and Mortari, 2015). Since agency is a term that can apply to individuals and social groups (Baars and Phillipson, 2014), it is discussed here and in Section 3.5.1.3.

Considered to be a core part of personhood, agency is commonly associated with the ability to purposefully ‘act’ to initiate change (Zeilig *et al.*, 2019), and the very act of striving for meaning is itself agential (Brockmeier, 2009). From a selfhood perspective, agency requires the ability to initiate and perform actions independently, and to control, review and achieve personal goals (Harre, 1998). This view has some merit in that it may empower PwAD as agential beings, however, the focus on independence may dislocate PwAD from essential

relationships. Furthermore, this view places responsibility on individual PwAD and may dismiss the impact of the physical and social environment (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010).

Other perspectives of agency are more inclusive. According to Gubrium and Holstein (1995), agency is meaningful because it is co-created and embedded in the everyday through the individual self, social selves, the environment and material objects (Gubrium and Holstein, 1995). This ordinary view implies agency is fluid and continually created and renewed rather than something that is acquired and/or lost (Gubrium and Holstein, 1995). This perception of agency seems more helpful for understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because of its adaptability and applicability to the everyday lives of PwAD. Moreover, it does not appear exclusive or reliant on particular skills, opening opportunities for creativity.

3.4.4 Creativity

According to Csikszentmihalyi (1996), creativity is the essence of meaning. Meaning in creativity is related to opportunities for self-expression, joy, excitement, satisfaction, fulfilment and producing something that will leave a legacy (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996). Creativity is often assumed to be a complicated process requiring great skill, talent and imagination, complex thought and/or action (Richards, 2007), through which opportunities for self-actualisation and wellbeing occur (Kaufman, 2018). However, Camic *et al.* (2018) argued this perspective of creativity is elitist and ignores quieter, more everyday forms, particularly for PwAD whose voices are underrepresented.

By contrast, everyday creativity is integral to being human, and is applicable and accessible to everyone (Richards, 2007; Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009). Rather than restricting creativity to the mind, everyday creativity provides: “*a pervasive and dynamic way of being and knowing, and of encountering the world*” (Richards, 2007, p.48). Embodied creativity can offer everyday opportunities for learning, expression and imaginative acts, potentially providing a sense of purpose, wellbeing and enjoyment (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015; Hasselkus and Dickie, 2021). Examples of everyday creativity include adapting to an environment, improvisation (Richard, 2007), helping others, or repairing/altering a physical object (Kaufman, 2018). This form of creativity appears useful in contributing to the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because its ordinariness seems accessible and applicable to their everyday lives and does not require specialist skills/equipment.

3.4.5 Selfhood, personhood and person-centredness

Selfhood and personhood have historically been used to categorise traits regarded necessary to qualify as a person (McIntosh, 2018). Although they are often used interchangeably, they have distinctive roles (Collins and Fletcher, 2024). Harré (1998) defined selfhood as a position from which individuals sense, experience, navigate and (inter)act with the world and which he divided into three intertwining constructs. 'Self One' refers to embodied human attributes and values, 'Self Two' combines the experience of feeling and doing, and 'Self Three' is how humans see other humans (Harré, 1998). When combined, the three selves define personhood as a continuous thread in human life (Harré, 1998).

In Harre's earlier work with Sabat, the loss of self was explored in people with Alzheimer's Disease (Sabat and Harré, 1992) who ascertained two types of self, a personal identity and a social identity, which they relate to Goffman's work (1969). From this viewpoint, the person's social identity, which is socially constructed, is threatened upon receiving a dementia diagnosis (Sabat and Harré, 1992). Therefore 'selves' can be de-constructed and re-constructed to form a different narrative when others change their view of the person (Sabat and Harre, 1992). As a result, others may alter how they act towards the person, altering meaning according to the context and the narrator (Sabat and Harré, 1992). This is an important consideration for this study because meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may be influenced by stigma.

Personhood in dementia practice can also be interpreted as acknowledging each person as unique with their own preferences, skills and values rather than defining them by their diagnosis (Kitwood, 1994; 1997a; 2007). Communicative acts are considered a source of meaning in personhood, particularly if the person is consistently validated through reciprocity (Kitwood, 1993; 1994). However, Kitwood's (1993; 1994) work has been criticised for being hyper-individualistic because person-centred approaches unintentionally enhance the mind/body divide, exacerbating stigma (Zeiler, 2014) and social inequalities (Tieu *et al.* 2021). This implies that meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may include individual, relational and social features.

3.5 Bodies with and between other bodies

This section investigates how literature has related meaning to bodies interacting through and between other bodies, such as relational, social, and narrative (cultural) perspectives.

3.5.1 Relational

Unlike dualistic views of reality, relational ontologies can (inter)link, connect and equalise people, things, societies and cultures because “*meanings themselves are relationships*” (Slife, 2004, p.165). Thus, examining meaning without acknowledging these connections may lose or misrepresent important details (Slife, 2004). This infers that meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD is linked to, and affected by, other residents, family members, staff, physical items and the care home environment, and that multiple perspectives of meaning are required to gather a rich understanding.

3.5.1.1 Inter-corporeality

Inter-corporeal perspectives broaden opportunities for participation in everyday life by enhancing collaborative interaction (Zeiler, 2014). Zeiler (2014) explored different perspectives of inter-corporeality, including the intra-actional and interactional experience of touch (Merleau-Ponty, 1968), and the perception and negotiation of (non)human bodies during interactional exchanges (Weiss, 2013). Zeiler (2014, p.137) proposed an alternative view of inter-corporeality, “*primordial intercorporeality*” in which the sharing of selves during interactions with others informs the self and (co)existence. Similarly, “*mutual incorporation*” is reciprocal and purposeful (inter)action between mutually inter-dependent bodies who attune with one another to co-create meaning (Fuch and De Jaegher, 2009, p.474). The latter two examples suggest that meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD requires self-awareness from others so that the sharing of selves can be facilitated and the visibility of PwAD reinforced. This is important because these approaches have potential to empower PwAD and counteract the unequal power dynamics that person-centred approaches have inadvertently created (Behuniak, 2010; Jenkins, 2013).

3.5.1.2 Inter-embodiment

Likewise, the “*inter-embodied self*” combines the work of Merleau-Ponty (1968, 2002) and Kontos (2005) to stimulate meaning between PwD and others through a dynamic, transactional process (Jenkins, 2013, p.9). The continual cycle of action and change (Blumer, 1969) during inter-embodiment renews and co-creates ‘selves’, offsetting the individual ‘loss’ of self often referred to in PwD (Jenkins, 2013). This view is helpful to the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because the strengths and skills of PwAD and others appear to combine, which may jointly enhance the participation of PwAD in activities and interactions.

Also drawing on the work of Merleau-Ponty (1962), Fuchs and De Jaegher (2009) describe interactions as ‘enactive intersubjectivity’, which can be unidirectional or mutual (Fuchs and

De Jaegher, 2009). *Unidirectional* refers to: a) interactions between (non)humans, for example between a PwAD and a hairbrush, which becomes incorporated with the body through interaction, or b) interactions sensed between humans, for instance, people-watching or activities initiated and led by another (Fuchs and De Jaegher, 2009). *Mutual interactions* are human-to-human, for example when two people echo, mirror and empathise with one another through activity, or where embodied skills and prior experiences can anticipate action, whether or not the action is completed (Fuchs and De Jaegher, 2009). These views of interaction open possibilities for understanding meaning with PwAD because they align with the potential communication styles of PwAD previously outlined.

3.5.1.3 Relational citizenship

Kontos, Miller and Kontos (2017) created the Relational Citizenship model to redirect and resituate embodied selfhood. Relational citizenship extends social citizenship to promote the participation and agency of PwD by mutually enhancing the skills, senses and tacit knowledge of PwD and those interacting with them (Kontos, Miller and Kontos, 2017). Although a clear definition of this term was not provided, it offers some insight into how creative acts can support meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, potentially enhancing their agency.

3.5.2 Social

3.5.2.1 Social citizenship

Social citizenship was initially described by Marshall (1950) in terms of social structure, status, (in)equality, rights and (in)justice through the industrial, economic and political lens of post-war Britain. Correspondingly, Faulks (1998) outlined three overlapping forms of social citizenship: legal, philosophical, and socio-political to highlight social duties, behaviour and status. Although the aspects of fairness and welfare rights persist as important features of social citizenship (Dwyer, 2004), these definitions appear too rigid to contribute to understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

In terms of dementia, social citizenship is a term which is not well understood or explained (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010). Bartlett and O'Connor (2010, p.37) offer a working definition, suggesting that social citizenship for PwD is "*a relationship, practice or status*" which promotes human rights and challenges stigma, creating opportunities for personal and social growth and participation. This definition is more attuned to the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD developing through this thesis.

3.5.2.2 Other social perspectives of meaning

Weber (1947, 1962) related social meaning to purposeful actions, and perceived passive or involuntary action as non-meaningful. This can be likened to symbolic interactionism and non-symbolic interactionism, as discussed by Blumer (1969) in response to Mead's (1934) work. In symbolic interactionism, meaning is sought through iterative interaction with the self, others and/or (in)tangible objects (Blumer, 1969). This is a process which is continually evolving in response to the interpretation of interactions, whereas in non-symbolic interaction, gestural acts occur without interpretation (Blumer, 1969). This suggests that a goal and level of autonomy is required to create meaning and raises questions about how meaning can be recognised in PwAD.

One of the terms used by Weber (1947) when exploring meaning was 'Verstehen', or 'understanding', which is defined as an empathetic act aiming to understand a person, their actions and the context. This suggests that 'doing with' PwAD may provide valuable insights into the experience of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD whilst amplifying their voices.

Alternatively, Bourdieu's (1984) perspective of meaning relates to a term called 'habitus' - the interplay between individuals and social, economic and cultural structures. According to Bourdieu (1984), meaning is created through this network to initiate change and learning within the boundaries of structural rules and standards. This suggests that meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD cannot be separated from the context of the person and their life histories, their relationships with others and the care home routines and regulations.

Moving to a social gerontological perspective, Gubrium and Holstein (2000) assert links between meaning and aging through the thoughts, emotions and actions of older people. From this perspective, everyday experiences are the essence of meaning-making, which are experienced and shaped by older people themselves (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000). Within this complexity lies various layers of meaning, including personal and social meanings and the changing, subjective body which can only be understood qualitatively (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000). In the context of a nursing home, meaning centres around the bodies of older people, which become public property through constant surveillance (Gubrium and Holstein, 1999). Meaning then becomes shaped by institutions and the wider culture through stories, interactions and institutional principles, with signs of meaning being recognised through lucidity, responses and the body (Gubrium and Holstein, 1999). This work is important for this study because it implies that meaning in activities with PwAD may be socially constructed through the way bodies are perceived and highlights the urgency of gaining the voices of PwAD.

3.5.3 Narrative (social and cultural)

Narrative can be thought of as a continuum, ranging from self and identity to selves in social and cultural contexts (Smith and Sparkes, 2008). On the identity end of the continuum, although social and cultural narratives are present, 'the self' is the more dominant narrative (Smith and Sparkes, 2008). An example is represented by Bruner (1990) who viewed narrative as language formed in the mind and shaped by living and working with others. It was through these shared social processes that Bruner (1990) believed meaning was created. This understanding of meaning has less to offer this study than the more socially and culturally informed narrative because of the dualist inference.

At the other end of the continuum, selves are socially and culturally constructed with varying degrees of the single 'self' remaining (Smith and Sparkes, 2008). Dialogical perspectives of narrative are positioned more towards the social end of the continuum (Smith and Sparkes, 2008), representing socially created identities that fleetingly empathise, disagree or cooperate with other social selves (Hermans, 2001). In this respect, the self can be embodied and assembled from collective voices embedded in culture and shifting power relations, and cultures are complex voices expressed through shared stories (Hermans, 2001; Smith and Sparkes, 2008). Meaning is therefore a constellation of amorphous, fluid, unfinished and emerging selves and cultures rather than a fixed, singular identity (Hermans, 2001; Smith and Sparkes, 2008; Brockmeier, 2009).

Performative views of narrative are at the very end of the social continuum where selves are formed as an outcome of social and relational processes from which they are inseparable (Smith and Sparkes, 2008). Through this lens, the individual self as a cause of action is diminished (Smith and Sparkes, 2008). Selves are viewed in terms of action permeated through sounds, gestures and expressions entwined with the physical and social context (Gergen, 2023). Meaning is co-created through social and relational processes and associated actions and responses (Gergen, 2023).

Dialogical and performative narratives offer promising contributions to the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. They suggest a freedom from the fixed view of the person imposed by others, reducing expectations for the person to remain static. They also frame meaning-making around social and cultural processes rather than individuals, potentially emphasising social responsibility for creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

3.6 Beyond the body

This section acknowledges a growing body of literature from post-qualitative inquiry to outline how it may contribute to future understandings of meaning in the context of this study.

Post-qualitative inquiry is beyond the scope of this study because it is a complex philosophical inquiry with its own 'language' which cannot be adequately represented in this chapter (St Pierre, 2021). However, it is important to acknowledge the potentially valuable contribution the post-qualitative movement could offer in understanding meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. For instance, the unconventional nature of post-qualitative inquiry potentially offers exciting, fresh perspectives for health sciences (Beggan, 2024). Potential frameworks include post-structuralist theorists such as Deleuze and Guattari (1988), Barad (2003) or Braidotti (2019).

3.7 Summary

This chapter critically discussed disparate theoretical and philosophical literature, much of which was not specific to PwAD. Engaging in this literature helped to understand which of these perspectives might be applicable to meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, particularly those concerning the body and 'bodies with and between other bodies'.

Key learning has created sufficient understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD to inform the research design for this study. Meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD appears to be a fluid, continually emerging and evolving concept. It seems to be a sense of (co)existing, feeling, being, doing and relating to the self/selves, others, objects and the physical and social environment. Meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD appears to be post-verbally (co)created and inseparable from past, present or future self/selves and context. Meaning may be enhanced when skills and selves are shared, relationships are empathic and equal, and opportunities for everyday creativity and curiosity are nurtured and (co)created. A research design which is flexible, creative, sensitive, inclusive to PwAD and which explores views from different participant groups is therefore required.

Meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD seems to be accessed through opportunities for PwAD to participate in everyday life through the medium of the body/bodies and the social and physical environment. This heavy bodily focus suggests that approaches which celebrate movement, action, (inter)embodiment, inter-corporeality and (co)creativity are required. Therefore, a qualitative Action Research methodology combined with creative, flexible, multi-modal methods may enable collaboration, participation and change within a care home setting.

Furthermore, meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD is possibly simultaneously experienced on individual, relational, social and cultural levels, suggesting a pragmatist ontology is required to embrace different realities. Additionally, meaning in this context may be affected by how others view PwAD and how PwAD sense themselves in the social and physical environment. This relationship between meaning, the self/selves and socially constructed narratives about PwAD is compatible with a social constructionist epistemology. The methodology, epistemology and ontology are explored, discussed and justified in the proceeding chapter.

Chapter 4 : Methodological, philosophical and theoretical perspectives

4.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to explain and justify the research design and theoretical underpinnings. It begins with a critical discussion of the selected qualitative Action Research (AR) methodology (Stringer and Aragon, 2021), creative methods, ontology and epistemology. Subsequently, the approach to this study is outlined and researcher positionality in AR is considered, followed by the study aim, objectives, and research question. Ethical processes and concerns in AR are later described, with special attention given to people with advanced dementia (PwAD) and audio-visual methods. Participants are briefly introduced at this stage to situate them in this study (Hughes, 2013), and data collection methods for each of the three phases of the AR cycle will be described. Lastly, the selected analytical methods will be explored, and rigour and quality within AR will be addressed.

4.2 Research Design

4.2.1 Overview

This study used a qualitative, AR methodology and creative methods to enable the active inclusion of PwAD (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Webb *et al.*, 2020). AR was selected for three reasons. Firstly, as stated in Chapter One, meaningful activity for PwAD was identified by care home staff and people with dementia (PwD) as an area requiring improvement. Secondly, decades of literature illustrate boredom and poor quality of life experienced by PwAD as a direct lack of appropriate meaningful activities in care home settings (Bowie and Mountain, 1993; Harmer and Orrell, 2008; Wood, Womack and Hooper, 2009; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Brown *et al.*, 2020a; Scerri, Scerri and Innes, 2020). Lastly, PwAD have a human right to be included in issues which directly affect them (Cross-Party Group on Alzheimer's, 2009; World Health Organisation, 2015; Diaz-Gil *et al.*, 2023). AR was therefore selected to stimulate change and empower participants through active inclusion (Reason and Bradbury, 2008; McNiff, 2017; Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Methods based on everyday 'doing', action and transaction (Dewey, 1976; Jenkins, 2013; Bellass *et al.*, 2019) were chosen to amplify the post-verbal, (inter)embodied voices of PwAD (Hughes, 2001; Jenkins, 2013; Quinn, Blandon and Batson, 2019).

4.2.2 Other considered methodologies

Participatory Action Research (PAR), ethnography and phenomenology were also considered. PAR was unsuitable because the literature reviewed in Chapter Two implied PwAD would participate in subtle ways, requiring a more sensitive and nuanced approach. This indicated that collaboration, participation and co-learning would be 'quieter' than PAR could allow, particularly given the extra demands on all participant groups resulting from the pandemic. To accommodate this, a combination of AR and creative methods was selected to sensitively enable subtle participation. 'Subtle participation' is a term used in this thesis to define potentially understated, hidden, post-verbal and embodied ways PwAD may actively take part in the research. In their paper exploring the limitations and learning during a PAR study with PwAD, family members and staff, Smith and Phillips (2020) described their difficulties in engaging PwAD in meaningful ways. Despite their expertise in PAR, Smith and Phillips (2020) identified the need for partnership work to enable PwAD to participate through sensory and creative methods. This current study therefore used AR rather than PAR to accommodate the subtle participation of PwAD.

Although ethnography would have enabled an intimate and in-depth perspective of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD in a care home setting (Denscombe, 2010, p.84), its main concern lies in social behaviours and cultures (Creswell and Creswell, 2018) rather than meaning, action and change. Similarly, phenomenology could have provided insight into the lived experience of PwAD, their family members and staff, yet its descriptive nature (Creswell and Creswell, 2018) and predominant use of interviews (Englander, 2012) would not have addressed the current issues in dementia practice.

4.2.3 Action Research: the process

The AR process is iterative and uses continual cycles of looking, thinking and acting to facilitate learning and change (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Drawing on Dewey (2000), AR explores how lived experience can be explored and sensed through embodied action and changing realities. AR situates participants as autonomous agents who create meaning by 'doing' i.e. using their body and feeling through it to experience the world (Dewey, 2000; Hughes, 2001; Merleau-Ponty, 2002).

AR has been described as having: "*twenty-seven flavours*" (Chandler and Torbert, 2003, p. 133) and "*a family of approaches*" (Reason and Bradbury, 2008, p.7). The AR approach by Stringer and Aragon (2021) was selected for this study because they detail practical guides

for AR cycles and illustrate methods of data analysis, enabling a rigorous approach to action, learning and change throughout the study. One cycle of AR was used in this research, in combination with micro-level cycles to allow moment-by-moment adaptation (Dick, 2015; Stringer and Aragon, 2021), as represented in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Microlevel cycles of Action Research

4.2.4 Terminology in AR: co-creation, co-design and co-production

In AR, distinct terms are often used interchangeably, such as co-creation, co-design, and co-production (Banks, Herrington and Carter, 2017; Vargas *et al.*, 2022). Although these terms share similarities, for example, the collaboration and active involvement of participants to influence change, there are differences depending on the level and stage(s) of involvement (Brandsen and Honingh, 2018). Definitions also differ depending on the discipline, for instance, the term co-creativity has mainly been more prevalent in the public sector or design field and is still evolving (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). From a public management perspective, co-creation is an umbrella term referring to how services are influenced at a strategic level by those using them (Brandsen and Honingh, 2018), and co-design is a branch of co-creation through which people using services influence how they are delivered (Voorberg, Bekkers and Tummers, 2015). Co-production specifically refers to collaborating with stakeholders during the implementation stages (Brandsen and Honingh, 2018).

From a sports, exercise and health perspective, Smith *et al.*, (2023, p.159) describe three forms of co-production: 'Citizens' Contributions to Public Services', 'Integrated Knowledge Translation' and 'Equitable and Experientially-informed Research'; this study best relates to the latter two. For example, 'integrated knowledge translation' is an academic-practitioner collaboration where diverse skills are shared and woven into the research process (Graham, Kothari and McCutcheon, 2018). It is evidenced in this study by seeking the opinions of people with dementia (PwD) and carers when creating resources, and by involving members of a

purposely established reference group, 'Inscape' in the research design, as described in Section 4.12.2. 'Equitable and experientially-informed research' includes people with lived experience to challenge positions of power and enhance equality and inclusivity (Smith *et al.*, 2023). This was partially achieved by viewing PwAD as essential collaborators and adapting the study to promote their active inclusion. However, the term co-production is too ambitious for this study because the anticipated subtleties of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD are unlikely to be captured.

A more apt approach for this study is described by Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams (2018) who addressed inconsistencies with definitions of co-creativity through an arts/dementia lens. Four components of co-creativity were developed: improvisation, structure, leadership and equality (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). *Improvisation* is the freedom to play and explore, *structure* is negotiated, flexible and changeable, *leadership* is shared amongst everyone involved, including PwD, and *equality* is co-dependency and a recognition of all contributions being equal to the creative process (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). This understanding of co-creation is process-led rather than task-orientated, therefore there is no expected product or outcome, rather it exists of its own accord in a space and time within, and through, relational and mutual processes (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). Although somewhat dependent on collaboration and participation, co-creativity extends these terms and recognises perceived inaction and inactivity as a contribution (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). This definition of co-creativity will be used hereonin because of its compatibility with meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

4.2.5 Using creative methods

Creative methods are consonant with both AR and PwAD. The flexibility and adaptability of creative methods (Rose, 2016) can validate PwD, (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2010; Carter and Brown, 2023) and offer opportunities for agency, equality and inclusion (Zeilig *et al.*, 2019). This is particularly important for PwAD who are often dehumanised (Behuniak, 2011).

In this study, the term 'creative methods' represents two different approaches, 'mini-c' and 'little-c' creativity (Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009). 'Mini-c' creativity refers to both my own personal journey of learning during the AR study (Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009), and the learning produced by visual and sensory approaches to research (Kara, 2020). 'Little-c' creativity, or 'everyday creativity' encompasses a form of creativity that is accessible to all (Richards, 2007; Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009), as previously described.

Everyday creativity is about instinctively responding, adapting and changing 'selves' in response to the context, circumstances and environment, lending itself to artistic expression (Richards, 2007). In this thesis, everyday creativity is used to embrace, capture and celebrate the sensory, (inter)embodied qualities of PwAD during activities and interactions (Bellass *et al.*, 2019), and to invite PwAD to co-create their lives through spontaneous action (Kontos, Miller and Kontos, 2017).

Creativity literature is often written from psychological/cognitive perspectives which can lead to the selection of research approaches and methods which are inaccessible to PwAD (Camic *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the creative methods used in this study were multimodal i.e. they were selected according to the purpose, participants, and/or context (Kara, 2020). Creative methods in this study were used twofold, firstly as a form of documentation, reflection and learning, and secondly as a data collection tool with PwAD, family members and staff. The latter are described in Section 4.12.6.

4.2.6 Creative methods for documentation, reflection and learning

Creative methods for decision-making, reflection and learning consisted of sensing and crafting with a range of materials, in line with 'mini-c' creative acts (Kaufmann and Beghetto, 2009). For example, I created a sculpture called 'The Thing' (Stake, 2010) from wire, fabric, and found/bought materials to represent my continual learning as the study evolved (see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2 The Thing

The Thing evolved with me, and was continually developing and shaped by my learning, echoing the AR cycles and pragmatist ontology (Rosiek, 2013; Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Change was represented by, and communicated through, different materials as fabrics and other medium were selected based on their unique properties (von Kürthy *et al.*, 2023). For example, thin, flexible wire was manipulated to match my changing positionality (Chandler and Torbert, 2003), and hand-dyed fabrics illustrated how my own experience influenced the study. In another example, paint was applied to large paper using a combination of my hands and paint brushes to literally grasp and shape the AR process/study, see Figures 4.3 and 4.4. Applying paint with my hands intensified the tactile experience, enabling me to 'feel', absorb, and embody the methodology, creating a unique sensorial and corporeal experience, connecting myself and the research (Douglas and Carless, 2021; Carless, 2023). Paint offered a unique space to spiritually and emotionally connect with the everyday lives of PwAD by seeing the concept, potential participants, and place differently, taking a side-step from the prevailing text (Balmer, 2020). This experience was physical and visceral; it spotlighted action and the corporeal (Balmer, 2020), and helped me to prepare for ethical processes and fieldwork.

Figure 4.3 Painting the AR cycles

Figure 4.4 Close-up of painting the Action Research cycles

Small toy figures were used to enact how the study design could work with different participant groups to explore complexities and formulate plans in meaningful and authentic ways (McCusker, 2019; Gripton and Vincent, 2020). For example, they enabled participants to be sensed before recruitment (Douglas and Carless, 2021). Additionally, they assisted me to understand how the research might affect potential care home visitors before I had access to the field. See Figures 4.5 and 4.6.

Figure 4.5 Visualising the participants

Figure 4.6 Visualising visitors in the field

Furthermore, 'mini-c' creativity offered a form of non-verbal communication (Kontos *et al.*, 2017; McCusker, 2019; Gripton and Vincent, 2020) more attuned to my neurodiversity. However, these approaches are often misunderstood, belittled or dismissed in academia where words dominate (Burge *et al.*, 2016; Judge, 2018), potentially exacerbating disability, exclusion (Goffman, 1963) and internalised shame (Ashworth, 2020). I am therefore inviting the reader to critically embrace this creative approach and to consider neuro-difference as an asset in academia (Judge, 2018; Grant and Kara, 2021).

4.3 Underpinning Assumptions: Pragmatism and Social Constructionism

This research was underpinned by a pragmatist ontology and a social constructionist epistemology. A pragmatist ontology is a worldview which embraces constant change and celebrates the present and future as iterative and interdependent concepts rather than distinct notions (Rosiek, 2013). A pragmatist ontology complements AR by embracing a multitude of lived experiences of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD without the constraints of specific realities or set methods (Rosiek, 2013). The freedom in a pragmatist ontology allows methods to be selected according to the inquiry and participants, matching the flexible, creative approach of this study (Rosiek, 2013). This was especially helpful during the pandemic because it enabled methods to be adapted according to continually changing circumstances and available resources (Lévi-Strauss, 1966). Furthermore, a pragmatist ontology is consistent with AR (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) because of the crossover between learning and doing and the focus on exploring 'real world' problems as they arise (Patton, 2015).

Social constructionism theorises that knowledge and understanding of the world is created through social interaction and participation (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Gergen, 2023), embracing the fluidity and diversity of meaning-making (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000). Social constructionism explores meaning-making as a process rather than studying meanings in general, aligning with this study because of the focus on action and change (Gergen, 2023). This perspective is important when researching meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD because it provides opportunities for meaning to be co-created using a multitude of realities (Gergen, 2023), potentially enhancing the agency and participation of PwAD. This is significant because the participants and the field and are continually evolving (Gergen, 2014).

It is also important to note my assumptions about the research design and how these may influence the research findings (Lincoln, 2010). When designing this study, I assumed the realities of participants and the meaning of activities and interactions would change between and according to participant groups and the context (Sparkes and Smith, 2009; Rosiek, 2013), and that knowledge would be made through action (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). I also assumed diverse realities and knowledge would be formed from participants' past and present experiences and that new learning would influence future activities and interactions (Rosiek, 2013). It will be important consider these points when reading the findings because the field and the participants have already changed and are constantly changing (Gergen, 2014).

4.4 My approach to this study

Traditionally, academia has been dominated by Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic (WEIRD) perspectives, at the expense of excluding other groups (Henrich, Heine and Norenzayan, 2010). I identify as a white, working-class, bisexual woman from a Northern English background with late-diagnosed autism spectrum condition (ASC) and Attention-deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), or AuDHD when combined. Thus, while the purpose of this thesis aligns with academic expectations, such as to undertake and communicate independent research and offer an original contribution to knowledge in textual form (Gould, 2016), it also incorporates visual, arts-based information, going beyond what is seen to encompass what is felt and sensed (Sou and Hall, 2023), an approach that is integral to being an autistic artist. Appropriate literature is used to support and explain any deviations from the traditional approach. The readers of this thesis are invited to embrace, explore and celebrate neuro-difference as a potential asset to academia (Judge, 2018; Grant and Kara, 2021) by viewing visual, arts-based and sensory methods as legitimate forms of communication that are not 'less-than-academic' i.e. inferior to textual reporting.

4.5 Researcher positionality

My positionality also changed in the field, moving from outsider to insider and vice-versa depending on the phase of AR, the participants, the context and my familiarity to the setting (Anderson and Jones, 2000; Herr and Anderson, 2005). For example, during the preparation stage, I entered the setting as an 'outsider in collaboration with insiders', but I was treated as an insider by residents, family members and staff (Herr and Anderson, 2005). As I became more familiar with the setting, I felt more like an 'insider in collaboration with other insiders',

particularly when interacting with PwAD (Herr and Anderson, 2005), perhaps because of previous clinical experience with PwAD.

I also felt a connection with PwAD because our neurodifferences may have led to societal imbalances and stigma (Brown and Leigh, 2020). Although I do not claim my experiences to be the same as PwAD, there are some similarities (Orulv, 2023). For instance, I feel disabled, excluded and flawed by Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic (WEIRD) academia, and society in general (Goffman, 1963). I experience social marginalisation, misunderstanding and stigma, exposing me as less-than-human (Turnock, Langley and Jones 2022; Heney, 2023), connecting me to similar discrimination PwAD may experience (Sabat, 2006; Behuniak, 2011).

4.6 Aim, Research Question and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to understand the meaning in activities and interactions in collaboration with PwAD, their family members and staff in a care home setting using a qualitative, AR approach and creative methods. The research question for this study was as follows: *How can we understand the meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD to collaboratively enhance their everyday experience within a care home setting?* The study consisted of one cycle of AR with three phases. The objective(s) for each phase are outlined below.

4.6.1 Phase One objectives

1. To develop a shared understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD with family members and staff.
2. To prepare for Phase Two by learning about the life histories, preferences and communication styles of PwAD.

4.6.2 Phase Two objectives

1. To explore how everyday experiences of meaning in activities and interactions were created with PwAD, their family members, and staff.
2. To include the post-verbal voice of PwAD using embodied, flexible and creative methods.

4.6.3 Phase Three objective

1. To review and apply a new understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, family members and staff based on the learning from the study.

4.6.4 Phase Three revised objectives

The objectives for Phase Three were revised in the field because of pandemic restrictions, time constraints and family and staff holiday/leave, as follows:

1. To collaboratively and actively review, deepen and develop an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, family members and staff.
2. To amalgamate and share learning resulting from the study.

4.7 Ethical considerations

4.7.1 Overview

Under Scottish law, PwAD are unable to provide valid informed consent (Scottish Government, 2008), therefore ethical approval was gained from Scotland A Research Ethics Committee (AREC) - the body responsible for reviewing studies involving Adults with Incapacity (Scottish Government, 2008) (REC reference 21/SS/0056; IRAS project ID: 277401) (See Appendix 3). This lengthy process was further complicated when AREC experienced a three-month delay in processing applications due to the pandemic. Combined with the time restrictions of the PhD, this made it unfeasible to apply for ethics approval in the preferred manner i.e. before each phase of AR to enhance co-creation (Webb *et al.*, 2020), hence one application was made for the entire study.

4.7.2 The process of applying for ethics

This involved completing an application using the Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) version 5.20, writing a study protocol, and producing various documents, including a Data Management Plan, risk assessment, Participant Information Sheets (PIS), consent/proxy consent forms, and an Aide Memoire. The Aide Memoire was an A6 leaflet about the study to assist the House Manager (HM) during recruitment; a copy of these documents can be seen in Appendix 4. Additionally, a letter from the Director of Care from the care home was provided evidencing consent to access the home for the purposes of the study (see Appendix 5). My experience of the ethical process is reported in Section 5.5.

4.7.3 Identification of and access to the study site

Access to care homes was difficult during the pandemic, resulting in some researchers being unable to complete studies because digital alternatives could not capture visceral, sensorial and embodied experiences (Douglas, 2021). To enhance the possibility of accessing a home, a decision was taken to recruit a care home with multiple sites where relationships were pre-established. Online discussions took place between myself, my Lead Supervisor and a Director of Care to determine which care home(s) would be recruited and how to adapt the study in adherence with governmental restrictions. To avoid the risk of spreading COVID-19 between homes, we agreed the study would commence in one dementia-specific care home. See Figure 4.7 for site map.

Figure 4.7 Site map of the care home

4.7.4 The Inclusion of PwAD

PwAD are often excluded from research because of inappropriate research methods, complex ethical processes (Mann and Hung, 2018; Alzheimer Europe, 2019; Webb *et al.*, 2020) and/or

misguided perceptions of the ability of PwAD to participate (Diaz-Gil *et al.*, 2023). Thus, experiences of PwAD are often sought from others, such as healthcare staff (Isene *et al.*, 2021a) or family members (Greenwood, 2020), which excludes the voice of PwAD. In this study, PwAD were vital as experts-by-experience who could offer essential and invaluable contributions to the future of health and care services (The Kings Fund, 2014; Alzheimer Europe, 2019; Shepherd, 2020).

Various processes were established during this study to honour and respect the person's autonomy, dignity, personhood, and right to choose (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013; Mann and Hung, 2018; Shepherd, 2020). In addition to the legally required proxy consent from the person's Welfare Guardian (WG), Welfare Attorney (WA), or Nearest Relative (NR) (Mann and Hung, 2018; Scottish Government, 2008), I individually met with PwAD to ensure all practicable attempts were made to meaningfully support the person to assent or dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010). Assent seeks to establish each person's understanding and indication of the study and their choice to participate, while dissent involves understanding if a PwAD is unable to or does not wish to participate (Black *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, to explain the study to PwAD, I created a short, pictorial document with limited large print text and contrasting colours (see Appendix 6) (The UK Network of Dementia Voices, 2020; Collins *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, I used a decision tree for respecting dissent and seeking assent (Black *et al.*, 2010) and process consent for all participant groups to ensure consent was not assumed or used as an isolated event (Dewing, 2008). All PwAD assented, as described in Section 5.7.

4.7.5 Audio-visual data

The choice to use audio-visual data was carefully considered in terms of supporting ethical research in this study. Audio-visual data can amplify the post-verbal voices of PwAD (Cook, 2002; Puurveen *et al.*, 2015) and promote the inclusion of disabled people in research (Capstick, 2012), as demonstrated by Canning (2020) and Keady *et al.* (2020). However, because people and places can be more easily identified with audio-visual data, extra thought is required to ensure anonymity and confidentiality (Rose, 2023; Mannay, 2016). This calls for enhanced researcher reflexivity and sensitive management, particularly when including PwAD (Puurveen *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, various processes were implemented to protect anonymity and confidentiality, for example, covering the camera lens when necessary to protect non-participants and gaining informed (proxy) consent from participants to use selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data for academic purposes.

The care home was digitally well-developed with iPads, telephones and tablets being used daily with residents, when for instance, documenting participation in activities. The HM informed me that the Power of Attorney (POA) for each resident routinely signed a consent form for these purposes, which was reviewed every six months. This provided some reassurance that residents may be comfortable with audio-visual methods, however assent and dissent for using these methods was sought during each interaction with PwAD (Black *et al.*, 2010) alongside process consent for all participants (Dewing, 2008).

4.8 Sampling

4.8.1 Sampling technique

Purposive sampling was selected to recruit the care home and all participant groups (Denscombe, 2010) in order to collect rich, diverse data from relevant, experienced and knowledgeable participants (Robichaud *et al.*, 2006). Recruiting care homes in research can be complex and time-intensive, requiring repeat visits to sensitively build relationships and understand the needs and strengths of potential participants (McKeown *et al.*, 2010; McKeown, 2019; Webb *et al.* 2020). At the time of this study, accessing care homes was additionally challenging because of the pandemic, even for family members (Giebel *et al.*, 2022) who were initially only permitted to see relatives through windows or in care home gardens (Giebel *et al.*, 2022; Burton *et al.*, 2023; Haslam-Larmer *et al.*, 2023). A purposive sampling approach helped to navigate these issues by providing access through existing partnerships (Webb *et al.*, 2020; Smith *et al.*, 2023), helping to select participants who were most compatible with the methodology (Alzheimer Europe, 2019).

The sample for this study included PwAD, family members and staff to embrace diverse realities (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000; Rosiek, 2013) and avoid eliminating essential data (Smith *et al.*, 2023). The HM was the gatekeeper to all participant groups because an 'insider' with in-depth knowledge was required for ethical good practice (McKeown, 2019). One limitation of this sampling technique was that the population were white Scottish people, therefore the diversity of voices relied upon the different participant groups rather than ethnic diversity (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

4.8.2 Sample size

The sample size was tailored to this study, aiming to gain sufficient data to answer the research question (Levitt *et al.*, 2017), hence participant numbers changed according to the

objectives of each phase (Vasileiou *et al.*, 2018). The sample size was informed by literature, clinical experience, and discussion with expert qualitative researchers in the supervisory team. With these factors in mind, a total of fourteen participants from three participant groups were included, comprising four PwAD, four family members and six care home staff. Smaller numbers of PwAD were required to accommodate complex post-verbal communication and multi-modal methods. A larger staff ratio was required to capture a variety of roles and to accommodate staffing levels, training and sickness.

4.9 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

4.9.1 People with Advanced Dementia

People over 65 years of age with a diagnosis of any advanced stage of dementia were included in the study, identified as such by a score of 6d (moderately severe dementia) to 7e (severe dementia) on the Functional Assessment Staging (FAST) (Reisberg, 1988). To identify potential participants, the HM completed the FAST for each resident. Additionally, PwAD had an active certificate of incapacity (Section 47 of the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act (2000)) (Scottish Government, 2008). PwAD had lived in the care home for at least three months to allow a settling in period and had a family member who was familiar with their life before living in the care home. The family member was required to know the PwAD well and to be actively involved in their care, as indicated through weekly or fortnightly visits/contact. The PwAD was required to have a WG, WA, or NR who was able to provide proxy consent.

PwAD were excluded if they were end-of-life, i.e. if a Supportive and Palliative Action Register (SPAR) (NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde Care Home Collaborative Standard Operating Procedure, n.d.) was maintained. They were also excluded if they experienced acute, distressing pain or acute physical/mental illness, if they had an anticipatory/advanced care plan, directive or statement affirming a preference not to be included in research or known to dislike partaking in research/being observed. This information was obtained from family members and/or staff prior to inclusion. In the case of a disagreement between family members/friends regarding the inclusion of PwAD, the WG/WA/NR had the final decision. This was in place to protect the PwAD if there were disagreements within the family network, however this did not happen. Additionally, people living with young onset dementia were excluded because of potentially different needs from PwAD aged over 65 (O'Malley *et al.*, 2022).

4.9.2 Family members

Family members were included in this study if they were a WG/WA/NR aged over 18 and visited/contacted the PwAD on a regular basis i.e. weekly or fortnightly. It was essential family members were familiar with the life of the PwAD before living in a care home and were actively involved in the person's care, interests and preferences.

4.9.3 Staff

Care home staff were included if they were aged over 18, had worked in the care home for at least three months before the start of the study, and worked with PwAD on a regular basis i.e. at least twice per week to ensure their knowledge of PwAD was sufficient. To avoid burdening volunteers and agency staff, only paid, permanent employees were recruited. I was unable to provide an interpreter, therefore, all participants needed to be English-speaking although it was not necessary for English to be their first language.

4.10 Recruitment processes

4.10.1 Overview

The recruitment period lasted between 8th December 2021 – 25th February 2022, with a three-week break during Christmas. As previously stated, the HM was the gatekeeper to all potential participant groups. See figure 4.8 for an overview of the recruitment and data collection process.

Figure 4.8 Recruitment and data collection processes

4.10.2 People with Advanced Dementia

Potential PwAD were identified using a combination of the HM's clinical experience and the previously mentioned FAST score (Reisberg, 1988) prior to any contact with families. The FAST was chosen because it is one of the most widely used dementia severity scales sensitive enough to differentiate the advanced stages (Byrne *et al.*, 2008).

Other considered tools included the Pool Activity Level (PAL) (Pool, 2012), Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) (Folstein, Folstein and McHugh, 1975), and the Global Deterioration Scale (GDS) (Reisberg *et al.*, 1982). The PAL initially seemed appropriate because of the sensory, strengths-based and person-centred focus (Pool, Copley and Dickinson, 2023), however, its purpose is to match cognitive ability to appropriate meaningful activity rather than identify the stage of dementia (Pool, Copley and Dickinson, 2023). The MMSE is not sensitive enough to detect subtleties in advanced dementia (Monroe and Carter, 2012) and PwAD would likely receive a low score (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011), potentially causing unnecessary stress. In the GDS, dementia is identified using a seven-point scale, ranging from stage one (no cognitive decline) to stage seven (severe dementia) (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011), whereas the FAST is more detailed and identifies stages on a sixteen-point scale, from Stage One (no cognitive decline) to Stage Seven F (person has lost the ability to hold up/move head) (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011).

The HM completed the FAST for each care home resident to identify potential participants. Once identified, the HM contacted the person's WG/WA/NR to introduce the study. I then contacted any interested WG/WA/NR by telephone or email according to their preference to discuss the study and arrange an in-person meeting. Family members were offered the choice of meeting at the care home or in their own home, and all chose the care home.

4.10.3 Family members

Potential family members were approached by the HM to identify interest in the study, and at the HM's request, I recorded a presentation for family members. In total, seven family members expressed an interest, three of whom were related to one PwAD who sadly died before I contacted the WG/WA/NR, therefore they were excluded from the study. I then contacted the remaining four using the process previously described for PwAD.

4.10.4 Staff

The HM preferred to approach staff herself but asked me to record a presentation for staff. I was aware of the potential for coercion if the HM approached staff and I was careful to emphasise the personal choice of any participant. Six staff members initially agreed for me to contact them via email or through the care home intranet. I met with all six individually provide further information and answer questions.

4.11 Consent

4.11.1 People with Advanced Dementia

PwAD were unlikely to have the capacity to formally consent to the research (Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act, (2000)), therefore proxy consent was gained from their WG/WA/NR. I met with the person's WG/WA/NR in a private room within the care home to describe the study, provide a PIS and proxy consent form, and answer questions. The latter asked the WG/WA/NR if the PwAD had previously expressed any wishes or interests regarding their participation in research (The UK Network of Dementia Voices, 2020), for example in an anticipatory/advanced care plan, directive or statement such as the document, 'Getting to Know Me' (Alzheimer Scotland and Scottish Government, 2023). Signs of stress or distress in PwAD were established to guide assent/dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010) and process consent (Dewing, 2008), for example, changes in body language or facial expressions. The WG/WA/NR was assured an activity would be paused/stopped if such signs were observed, and that assistance from a relevant staff/family member who knew the person well would be sought immediately. If the person showed signs of stress or distress as a direct result of the study on more than three occasions, they were to be withdrawn, however this did not happen.

Additionally, I met with each PwAD to seek assent or dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010) and process consent (Dewing, 2008) to actively and meaningfully include them in the recruitment process. This was important because it respected the person's autonomy (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013) and enhanced the ethical integrity of the study by recognising PwAD as integral and valued participants (Smith *et al.*, 2023). It also enabled me to 'sense' if the person was comfortable in my presence (Canning, 2020). PwAD were included in the study if proxy consent was provided, the GP did not request exclusion, and assent was sought for spending time with PwAD. Four PwAD were recruited.

4.11.2 Family members

All family members were presumed to have capacity to provide informed consent to participate in this study (Scottish Government, 2008). I met with interested family members in a private room within the care home to discuss the study, provide a PIS and consent form, and answer questions. Family members were asked to return the consent form within seven days if they were interested in participating. If a response was not received within this timeframe, they were contacted again and allocated a further seven days; one family member required more time, as reported in Section 5.7.2. If after the second attempt, a reply had not been received, they would have been excluded from the study, but this was not required. Four family members were recruited.

4.11.3 Staff

All staff members were presumed to have capacity to provide informed consent to participate in this study (Scottish Government, 2008). Staff who had indicated an interest to the HM were contacted to arrange a meeting in a private room within the care home discuss the study, provide a PIS and consent form, and answer questions. Staff members were provided with the same conditions as family members to return the consent forms, and all were returned within the allocated timeframe. Six staff members were recruited to the study although more showed an interest.

4.12 Process of Inquiry: Pre-research activities, the setting, the participants, preparation period and data collection and post-research activities

4.12.1 Overview

Various activities and processes guided and informed this study to prepare for the field and complete data collection. See Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Overview of activities and processes

Phase of study	People involved	Purpose	Data Collection methods	Data contribution (in hours)
Pre-research activities	Carers of people with dementia (n=5)	To provide feedback about an abstract and language used	N/A	N/A
Pre-research activities	People with dementia (n=4)	To provide feedback on a vlog outlining the study design and purpose	N/A	N/A
Pre-research activities	Inscape group (n=10)	To examine and guide research decisions e.g. World Café and pilot interviews	N/A	N/A
Pre-research activities	Peers (n=3)	To refine skills in facilitating focus groups	N/A	N/A
Preparation period	House Manager, Depute, general care home staff, residents and their families	To introduce the research and prepare for recruitment	N/A	N/A
Phase One of AR	Family members (n=4) Care home staff (n=6)	Create shared understanding of meaning	Individual interviews (n=4) Focus groups (n=2)	7 hours 26 mins
Phase Two of AR	PwAD (n=4) Family members (n=4) Care home staff (n=6)	Gather everyday experiences of meaning	Family visits (n=4) Observed staff activities (n=8) Activities with researcher (n=8)	17 hours, 23 minutes
Phase Three of AR	PwAD (n=3) Family members (n=4) Care home staff (n=6)	Reflect on and develop understanding of meaning	Workshop (n=1) micro conversations/ interactions (n=6)	5 hours, 24 minutes
Post-research activities	All participants	To thank participants	N/A	N/A
Post-research activities	Peers (n=2)	To create a visual representation of findings	N/A Workshop	N/A

4.12.2 Pre-research activities

I completed a range of activities to inform and develop the study before entering the field. These included establishing the 'Inscape' reference group, completing pilot interviews and a pilot focus group, consultations with family carers, and feedback from PwD. Inscap was established to develop and shape the study using guidance from experts (Moore, Noble-Carr and McArthur, 2015) to ensure the study was considered from a 'real world' perspective (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Inscap consisted of nine people from Canada, Scotland and England with diverse experience/skills, including dementia research/practice, lived experience, and the arts. Activities involved two individual pilot interviews to refine my research skills (Creswell, 2016), specialist advice, and an online World Café to explore potential creative research methods (Steier, Brown and Mesquita da Silva, 2015; Monforte, Netherway and Smith 2023).

Other pre-research activities included a pilot focus group with peers to explore different modes of delivery (Braun and Clarke, 2013). For example, object-elicitation to explore and facilitate discussion (Iltanen and Topo, 2015), and a creative toolkit to support participation and stimulate the senses (Zino *et al.*, 2021). The creative toolkit comprised of diverse materials and physical objects, including Post-it notes, pens, textures/fabrics, words, and snacks. This experience highlighted the importance of justifying the use of creative methods (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023).

Other activities included consultations with family carers about dementia-friendly language and a critique from Scottish Dementia Working Group (SDWG) members in response to a vlog I created to explain the study. This helped to shape the research design and develop my communication style.

4.12.3 The setting

The study was set in a forty-bedded dementia-specialist Scottish care home with four separate Houses. The purpose-built site was a single storey unit within a rural area which provided 24/7 nursing care for either permanent residence or respite. The Care Inspectorate reports were consistently positive.

4.12.4 The participants

This study included three participant groups: four PwAD, four family members and six care home staff. All three groups were required to provide a real-world view (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) and diverse perspectives (Robichaud *et al.*, 2006). First name pseudonyms are used throughout this thesis to protect the identity of participants. All drawings in this thesis were created by myself and are not a true representation of the participants. A visual of the participant dyads and triads can be seen in figure 4.9, supplemented by a synopsis of the life histories of PwAD in Section 5.10.2, to respect and celebrate their personhood (Kitwood, 1997a).

Figure 4.9 The participants

4.12.5 Preparation period

Before data collection, I completed a preparation period in the care home to familiarise myself with the setting, residents, routines and COVID-19 procedures. This involved visiting the home over ten visits between November and December 2021 to spend time with staff and residents, meet with the HM and/or depute and attend an online family member meeting.

During this period, I also observed and participated in activities, such as a Lunch Club and Sonas. The Lunch Club was a social dining experience, and Sonas was a multisensory communication-focused activity for people with moderate-to-severe dementia (Strom, Saltyte Benth and Engedal, 2018). Multisensory activities included a welcome song, moving to music, smelling and tasting food/drinks, and a proverb activity (Strom, Saltyte Benth and Engedal, 2018).

To further immerse myself in the setting, I created sensescapes using video, photography and text (Halloy and Servais, 2014). Sensescapes have previously been used in research to explore various settings, including tourist destinations (Buzova *et al.*, 2021) and natural environments (Kou *et al.*, 2024). They were used in this study to document the intangible experiences of being in the care home, rather than employed as a data collection method (Dowling, Lloyd and Suchet-Pearson, 2018).

4.12.6 Data collection

Everyday creative methods were used during data collection (Kaufmann and Beghetto, 2009), and adapted according to participant groups, individual abilities/interests and the availability of resources and spaces (Lévi-Strauss, 1966), for instance drinking tea. Audio-visual data was used in the form of an 11 inch, 3rd Generation iPad Pro, a GoPro Hero 7 wearable camera, and an Olympus Digital Voice Recorder DM-670. These were chosen to provide opportunities for empathic and inter-embodied encounters with PwAD (Jenkins, 2013; Puurveen *et al.*, 2015; Sawchuk and Moorhouse, 2016; Dowling, Lloyd and Suchet-Pearson, 2018) and to capture the sensory and corporeal experiences of PwAD (Dowling, Lloyd and Suchet-Pearson, 2018; Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023). Fieldnotes were regularly completed to capture observations, thoughts and insights during data collection (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

Data collection methods were multi-modal, and selected according to the participants, environment and phase of AR (Kara, 2020); see Table 4.2 for an overview.

Table 4.2 An overview of data collection methods used and duration

Phase of AR cycle	Method	Duration	Total duration
Phase 1: Shared understanding of meaning in activities and interactions	1) 1 x interview with family member/friend (n = 4 x family members/friends)	Between 1 hour 2 mins and 1 hour 13 mins	7 hours, 26 mins
	2) 2 x focus groups with care home staff (n = 3 x staff members per focus group)	1 hour 32 mins and 1 hour 34 mins	
Phase 2: Explore everyday experiences of meaning in activities and interactions and include post-verbal voice of PwAD	1) Audio-visual participant observation periods with PwAD during different activities/interactions with either family members or care home staff. Discussions were woven into observations to capture meaning in activity and interaction as it arose. (n= 3 observations/discussions per person)	<i>Family visits:</i> between 40 mins and 27 secs and 55 mins and 59 secs <i>PwAD and staff:</i> between 14 mins 25 secs and 47 mins 27 secs	17 hours, 23 mins
	2) Audio-visual direct activities with PwAD. (n = 2 interactions per person)	Between 8 mins 56 secs and 1 hour 31 mins	
Phase 3: Reflect on understanding of meaning and identify learning	1) 1 x workshop with care home staff and family members to explore data, findings and identify key learning (n = 4 x staff members and 4 x family members)	1.5 hours	5 hours, 24 mins
	2) Individual reflections with PwAD, family members and staff (n = 3 x PwAD, 1 x family member, 3 x staff members)	Reflections with staff: between 46 secs (GoPro independently stopped recording) and 36 minutes 2 secs Reflections with PwAD: between 10 mins and 9 secs and 35 mins and 20 secs Reflection with family member and PwAD not recorded	

4.13 Phase One of AR

4.13.1 Overview

This phase spanned seven and a half weeks between January and March 2022 and used four object-elicitation interviews (Iltaanen and Topo, 2015) with four family members, and two focus groups with six staff, (three staff members in each). Ideally, focus groups would have been completed with family and staff members together to diversify the shared understanding of

meaning (Denscombe, 2010) and support learning and change (Braun and Clarke, 2013), however pandemic restrictions prohibited this. PwAD were not included in this phase to enable me to gather information to support their participation, for example, their life histories, preferences and communication styles (Kitwood, 1997b; Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Dewing, 2007; Carter and Brown, 2023). This was obtained from family members and staff during interviews and focus groups.

An iPad and Digital Voice Recorder were used to collect audio-visual data. The iPad captured the visual aspects of interviews and focus groups and the voice recorder was used as a back-up.

4.13.2 Interviews

Semi-structured interviews provided a flexible framework to ask questions whilst providing opportunities for family members to contribute (Braun and Clarke, 2013) (see Appendix 7 for interview schedule). Interviews took place in a private room within the care home, enabling family members to participate around visits. Family members were invited to bring a physical object of significance to the PwAD to facilitate a reflective and compassionate dialogue (O'Brien and Charura, 2023) and provide insight into their lives (Kara, 2020). Personal objects can be intertwined with the embodied personhood of the owner (Twigg and Buse, 2013), hence I also hoped this would maintain the focus on meaning.

The 'Visual Enquiry Tool' (My Home Life, 2022a) and Emotional Touchpoint word cards (My Home Life, 2022b) were also used to facilitate discussion. Family members chose up to five images which represented meaning in their visits with PwAD, with an option to use the Emotional Touchpoint words if the images did not resonate. Three family members chose images and one person used words. Family members were aware they could pause/stop the interview at any point, and although some family members became visibly upset, they chose to continue, as discussed in Section 5.12.1.

4.13.3 Focus groups

In-person focus groups were chosen to facilitate in-depth, diverse discussions (Braun and Clarke, 2013) (see Appendix 8 for focus group schedule). Focus groups commenced in a private room within the Houses, allowing staff to participate during working hours, as approved and arranged by the HM. Focus groups needed to be completed in the care home after routine medications and lunches and were contained to 1 hour 30 minutes each to reduce burden on all staff.

The same picture cards/words used in the interviews were implemented during focus groups. Staff were asked to choose up to three pictures which best represented the word 'meaning/meaningful', and all staff selected images. The previously described creative toolkit (Zino *et al.*, 2021) was available should the images and words be insufficient, however, this resource was not required.

4.14 Phase Two of AR

4.14.1 Overview

This phase spanned five weeks between March and April 2022 and involved four PwAD, four family members, and six staff. Data collection comprised of four observations of visits between PwAD and their family member, eight observed activities between PwAD and staff, and eight direct activities between PwAD and myself. Two activities per PwAD were completed for PwAD/staff observations and direct activities. Observations included 'micro-reflections', which were mini dialogues to explore the meaning in activities and interactions as they occurred (see Appendix 9 for observation/interaction guide).

4.14.2 Types of activities/interactions

All methods in Phase Two reflected the everyday life of PwAD, inviting them to participate rather than imposing the research (Bellass *et al.* 2019). This multi-modal approach added flexibility and created rich data, enabling methods to be shaped with PwAD (Kara, 2020). To maintain the person's dignity and privacy, intimate care activities were excluded from this study.

Activities were selected and adapted according to the routine of PwAD, and their previous/current interests and preferences. PwAD were also invited to participate in new activities to open opportunities for meaning-making based in the present rather than the past (Rosiek, 2013; Canning, 2020) Activities initiated by PwAD were also explored. To enhance comfort for all participants and to reduce instances of activities being uncharacteristically used, activities were consistent with the person's routine and environment. For example, observational activities took place in social, public spaces or in the bedroom of PwAD, according to where they naturally occurred and/or where the PwAD seemed comfortable. The types of activities completed/attempted are detailed in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Type of activities and interactions completed with PwAD during Phase Two

Person with advanced dementia	Activities/interactions during family visits	Activities/interactions with staff	Direct activities/interactions
Donald	Watching DVD of photographs with music; jigsaw puzzle; eating	Face shaving; talking; looking at football cards; trainset; walking; looking at flowers	Boules; walking; sharing food/drink
Morag	Sharing food/drink; hand massage; nail painting; looking at photograph album; talking	Talking in garden; looking at photograph album; listening to music	Sharing food/drink; talking; bubble blowing; drumming
Hamish	Talking; looking at photographs and videos; dancing; looking out of the window; playing 'catch'	Dancing (Ceilidh); sharing a drink; looking at a newspaper	Dancing (Tea Dance); attending Lunch Club
Fraser	Sharing food/drink; trying on slippers; cutting nails; talking	Interactive table; looking at paintings; walking; eating/drinking	Sensory eating/drinking; talking; word activity; therapy cat

4.15 Phase Three of AR

4.15.1 Overview

This phase spanned two weeks in May and June 2022 and included one workshop with four family members and four staff, and seven reflective conversations/interactions, of which three were with PwAD, one included a PwAD and their family member, and three involved staff. Only three PwAD participated in the reflections because one PwAD was unavailable. The reflection involving a PwAD and their family member was not recorded, so fieldnotes were completed immediately afterwards.

During the workshop, the iPad, GoPro and digital voice recorder were used to collect audio-visual data, as previously described to capture conversations in different parts of the room. The GoPro was used to capture reflective conversations.

4.15.2 The workshop

All family and staff participants were invited to the workshop and eight out of ten attended. Two staff members attended on their day off, demonstrating high interest in and commitment to the study (see Appendix 10 for workshop schedule).

Discussion prompts were created from an initial analysis of Phase One and Phase Two data to use in the workshop. These consisted of five A0 sheets of paper, each headed with one of the codes outlined in Section 4.18.2. The codes were the result of early findings from Phases One and Two and accompanied by raw data quotes, related drawings and comic-strips to illustrate the voice of PwAD and humanise the data (Roth, 2021). Each sheet was displayed in the activity space with space for contributions from participants. As previously described, a creative toolkit (Zino *et al.*, 2021) was also provided. The experience of the workshop is described in Section 5.14.1.

4.15.3 Reflective conversations/interactions

Reflections were chosen as a research method to provide opportunities for inner thought and joint discussion (Kordys, 2022), to clarify complexities, deepen understanding of meaning in activities and interactions, and identify learning (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). They were designed to fit with the everyday lives of PwAD, family members and staff by remaining flexible around visiting, work and care home routines. Reflections with each participant group differed, as described in Section 5.14.2.

4.15.4 Other considered data collection methods

A range of data collection methods were considered for this study, including Photovoice (Wang and Burris, 1994; 1997), modified diary method (Bartlett, 2012) and the adaptation of routine care notes. Photovoice aims to empower people with lived experience, enhance perceived control and identify areas for social change (Wang, 1997; Liebenberg, 2018). Photovoice was considered for this study, for example, to analyse meaning in photographs of activities and interactions documented on Workplace (Meta, 2024), a virtual platform used during the pandemic to document residents' involvement in everyday activities for family member viewing. Photovoice was not chosen because the voices of PwAD may not have been adequately represented (Evans-Agnew and Rosemberg, 2016). Additionally, I strongly felt a need to complete activities/interactions in person with PwAD so I could feel and sense their experiences (Dewey, 2000; Douglas, 2021).

Modified diary method involves participants recording their actions, thoughts and feelings for the purpose of research, for example by using words, drawings, audio and/or photography (Bartlett, 2012; Herron *et al.*, 2019). This method was considered for family members and staff and was Inscape's most popular choice, however this type of data collection can place great burden on participants (Braun and Clarke, 2013) and heighten negative experiences (Bartlett, 2012). Given the complex demands of caring for PwAD (Herron *et al.*, 2019) combined with the pandemic, I felt this would be too demanding on participants with time constraints and infection control being other factors in this decision.

I also considered adapting the format of the care notes staff completed to include questions about meaning in activities and interactions. However, care home management reported that these changes would impact all care homes within the charity, not just the one home I was working with, therefore this was not considered appropriate.

4.16 Post-research activities

After data collection, I created bespoke paintings for PwAD and cards for family members/staff. These were given to participants in July 2022 to thank them for their participation, as described in Section 5.15.

4.17 The management of data and transcription

A Data Management Plan was completed before data collection using tools from DMPonline (2024) to decide how the data would be treated, organised and stored (UK Data Service, 2024a). The plan outlined copyright issues, Intellectual Property, and required resources (DMPonline, 2024). Data was treated in accordance with data protection legislation to ensure confidentiality and security (GDPR.EU, 2025; Data Protection Act, 2018).

Three different data types were collected: 1) data for analysis; 2) routinely collected data; and 3) sensory-based data. Each data type was treated according to its purpose (Stake, 1995). Data for analysis included transcripts, observation records and a matrix derived from interviews, focus groups, observations, direct activities with PwAD, the workshop and reflective activities. Routinely collected data included Activity Plans, images of objects, site maps, fieldnotes and reflections; this data was not analysed but used for reference. Sensory-based data included soundscapes, sensescapes, drawings, and photographs to enhance my understanding of the lived experience and sensitise me to the field (Dowling, Lloyd and

Suchet-Pearson, 2018). This data was not analysed but used to re-immense myself in the field during data analysis (Pink, 2012).

Data was organised according to best practice and ease of use, for instance alphabetically and logically logging the data in a Microsoft Word document (UK Data Service, 2024b). Interviews and focus groups from Phase One, Key experiences from Phase Two, and the workshop from Phase Three were transcribed verbatim using Microsoft Word. In Phase Two, activities, interactions, objects and the environment were described moment-by-moment, in-keeping with the analytic method (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Vast amounts of data were collected during Phase Two (Stringer and Aragon, 2021), therefore attending to and interpreting all data equally was impossible in the allocated time. However, not all data is equal, requiring deep immersion to select key experiences (Stake, 1995), hence, upon re(watching) audio-visual data, findings from Chapters Two and Three were used as a guide to select key experiences. An example includes observing PwAD for changes in facial expressions and bodily expression/movement to identify meaning in activities and interactions. Additionally, transcripts from all data sources were checked against the original data to attune to their content and enhance rigour (Stringer and Aragon, 2021).

Analytic memos were written to create an ongoing narrative between the data, participants and meaning (Saldana, 2016) and an audit trail was created using Microsoft Excel to enhance rigour (Johnson, Adkins and Chauvin, 2020). I also used a reflexive approach during transcription and analysis which involved discussion with supervisors (Birks, Chapman and Francis, 2008) and corporeal methods to help process and absorb the data, for instance, listening to data whilst walking or painting and sewing in response to audio-visual data (Lembo, 2015; Thanem and Knights, 2019). This stimulated a dialogue between myself, the data and the analytic process, and provided space to reconnect with participants and the setting (Powell, 2010), creating a tangible, visual reference during analysis (van der Walt, 2020). See Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10 Example of sewn data

4.18 Data analysis: 'Coding and Categorising' and 'Key Experiences'

4.18.1 Overview

As previously described, the data was analysed using two different methods to match the phase of AR and the data type. The method, 'Coding and Categorising' was used to analyse data from Phases One and Three, and 'Analysing Key Experiences, Epiphanic Events or Critical Incidents' (referred to in this thesis as 'key experiences') was used to analyse data collected in Phase Two (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Given the everyday focus of this study and the post-verbal communication of PwAD, the latter method was adapted to include subtle moments of engagement, participation and autonomy rather than the 'ah-ha' moments recommended by Stringer and Aragon (2021).

The analytic process used in Phases One and Three, 'Coding and Categorising' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) employed the following six stages: 1) reviewing the data; 2) unitising the data; 3) categorising and coding; 4) identifying themes; 5) organising a category system; and 6)

developing a report framework. The analytic process used in Phase Two, 'Key Experiences' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) applied the following six stages: 1) review the data; 2) identify key experiences; 3) identify main features of each experience; 4) identify the elements associated with each experience; 5) identify themes; and 6) write an account. All data was analysed using a mixture of computer software e.g. Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, and paper-based activities to enhance clarity and deepen understanding (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). These processes are described further in the following sections.

Although these methods share similarities with reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2019), Stringer and Aragon's (2021) methods were chosen because of their specific applicability to AR and because the audio-visual data was 'in action'. Audio-visual data was used to facilitate detailed data analysis (Hindmarsh and Tutt, 2012; Ritchie *et al.*, 2023) by capturing nuances which could be re-watched as required (Pink, 2012; Schneider *et al.*, 2019).

4.18.2 Initial analysis during data collection to prepare for Phase Three

To facilitate action, an initial analysis of Phase One and Phase Two data was completed over a four-week period for use in Phase Three. For this purpose, data from Phase One was analysed up to stage four of the 'Coding and Categorising' method, and data from Phase Two was analysed up to stage two of 'Key Experiences' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021), using mind-maps to visually condense the data (Torraco, 2016; van de Walt, 2020). This allowed an informed discussion in the workshop, using the codes: 'Safety and Comfort'; 'Curiosity and Creativity'; 'Sensing and Feeling'; 'Time'; and 'Differing Worlds' (See example in Figure 4.11).

Figure 4.11 Example of analytic code: Sensing and Feeling

4.18.3 Phase One data analysis

The analytic method, 'Coding and Categorising' was used to analyse six transcripts from four interviews and two focus groups, totalling 7 hours 26 minutes, using a mixture of computer software and paper-based methods (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Computer software was used up to stage two of the analytic process and included Microsoft Word to identify and colour code units from the transcripts, Microsoft Excel to extract and organise data into a matrix, and Inspiration 10 IE to create mind-maps. Paper-based methods were then used from stages three to six and included colour-coded units, analysed to form codes and categories, from which themes were developed (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) (see Appendix 11).

The final themes developed in Phase One are: 1) Components of meaning; 2) Still curious; 3) Maintaining and building meaningful, trusting relationships; and 4) Adapting to an alternative reality: progressing through the fog and finding the key.

4.18.4 Phase Two data analysis

The analytic method, 'Key Experiences' was used for Phase Two to analyse activities and interactions and identify the associated components and features that created their meaning (Stringer and Aragon, 2021).

Data from Phase Two consisted of 239 key moments from four family visits, eight activities/interactions between PwAD and staff, and eight direct activities/interactions between PwAD and myself. In total, there were 77 videos, totalling 17 hours and 23 mins of data. More videos than occurrences of activities/interactions were created because the GoPro automatically started a new recording after 17 minutes 40 seconds of data. Data was analysed using computer software and paper-based methods (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Computer software was used up to stage four of the analytic process and included Microsoft Word to list and organise key experiences, and Microsoft Excel to organise these into a matrix. The matrix displayed each key moment and their related features and elements. Features provided a macro view of the key experience, for example planning and preparation, and elements provided detailed and sensory information, such as activity components and mood of participants (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Paper-based methods were used from stages five to six and included printing and cutting out features and elements from individual PwAD and systematically organising these into groups. Large sheets of paper were then used to identify commonalities across the data sets, from which themes were created (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Inspiration 10 IE was also used to create mind-maps to identify themes (see Appendix 12).

Vignettes were created to represent the content of the themes. The vignettes were written from verbatim transcriptions and moment-to-moment descriptions of audio-visual data and further informed by fieldnotes. Video stills accompany the vignettes to visually and textually reflect the experience of co-creating meaning with PwAD (Capstick *et al.*, 2021). Vignettes were selected because they best represented the post-verbal, embodied communication and movement of PwAD and demonstrate how meaning can be understood through the bodies of PwAD as they felt, experienced and negotiated the care home environment (Dewey, 2000; Merleau-Ponty, 2002). The intention of the vignettes is to amplify the voices of PwAD (Ely *et al.*, 1997; Jenkins, Keyes and Strange, 2016; Jenkins, Ritchie and Quinn, 2020) and preserve the complexity of the care home environment. These portrayals are also inkeeping with the setting, methodology and use of audio-visual methods.

Vignettes in research are often used to discuss fictional scenarios in qualitative interviews (Jenkins *et al.* 2010; Sampson and Johannessen, 2020), however the vignettes presented in this thesis are 'real-life' excerpts (Sampson and Johannessen, 2020) which feature the participants and myself to represent the findings (Ely *et al.*, 1997). Additionally, the findings in this phase are enriched with anonymised drawings, video stills and photographs created by myself to illustrate the perceived lived experience of PwAD (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023) and enhance the visibility of PwAD (Wiles *et al.*, 2012). The final themes

developed in Phase Two are: 1) 'Curiosity and purpose (seeking and exploring)'; 2) '(A)synchronicity (feeling and sensing)'; 3) 'Enhancing participation and visibility (seeing, adapting and doing)'; and 4) 'Embodying and identifying meaning (feeling, looking and listening)'.

4.18.5 Phase Three data analysis

The analytic process, 'Coding and Categorising' was selected to gather different perspectives and identify learning from PwAD, family members and staff (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) using nine transcripts from one workshop and eight reflections. In total, there were twelve videos from the GoPro and iPad combined, totalling 5 hours 24 minutes. There were more videos than transcripts because participants sometimes contributed more after a recording had stopped, so a new recording commenced. Data was analysed using similar techniques to Phase One. Computer software and paper-based methods were used to analyse the data (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Computer-based methods were used up to stage two of the analytic process and included Microsoft Word to complete an observation form for the workshop (Creswell, 2016), and to organise a table from the reflections. The observation form included transcribed audio data and accompanying thoughts and reflections (Creswell, 2016), while the table contained transcribed audio data, the contents of each code, and the timestamp. Microsoft Excel was then used to transfer this data into a matrix to identify units. Paper-based methods were used from stages three to six and included printing and cutting the units, organising them into participant groups, identifying codes and categories and grouping them into themes (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) (see Appendix 13).

The final themes developed in Phase Three are: 1) 'Making sense of living with advanced dementia'; 2) 'Seeing the person as an active agent'; 3) 'Reframing meaning in activities and interactions'; and 4) 'Moving forward'.

4.18.6 Other considered methods of data analysis

Other considered analytic methods included conversational analysis to examine the interaction of human engagement (Schegloff, Jefferson and Sacks, 1977) and arts-based data analysis (Kara, 2020). Although Conversational analysis fitted with the focus on action (Peräkylä and Ruusuvuori, 2018) and can be used to analyse post-verbal communication (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), it is limited to interactions between humans (Peräkylä and Ruusuvuori, 2018), potentially eliminating interactions between PwAD and themselves (Jenkins, 2013) and PwAD and objects (Treadaway, 2019). Arts-based data analysis

encompasses a multitude of creative approaches (Kara, 2020) including the analysis of collages (Culshaw, 2019) and comics (Galman, 2022). Although arts-based methods interested me as a researcher and artist, they were not best placed to answer the research question (Kara, 2020).

4.19 Quality Criteria: assessing rigour in Action Research

In recent years, assessing the quality of qualitative research has been heavily debated (Morse, 2015; Cypress, 2017; Smith and McGannon, 2018). This has initiated researchers to explore quality markers aside from Lincoln and Guba's (1985) trustworthy criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability (Tracy, 2010; Smith and McGannon, 2018). Examples include reflective pragmatism (Gergen 2014), and addressing the worthiness of the topic, sincerity, resonance, contribution, ethics, and cohesiveness (Tracy, 2010).

Although some specific criteria for assessing quality in AR exist, for instance, twenty guiding questions by Waterman *et al.* (2001) and Herr and Anderson's (2005) quality criteria, these appear too rigid to use with PwAD in a care home setting. Alternatively, a relativist approach embraces the possibility of change and flexibility as opposed to following a fixed, pre-established criteria (Sparkes and Smith, 2009), judging quality according to each unique inquiry (Smith and McGannon, 2018) alongside the context of the whole research process rather than at completion (Cypress, 2017). This approach seems more suited to the phenomenon being researched, the participant groups and setting, hence, the relativist approach used in community research by Schinke, Smith and McGannon (2013) will be used to explore rigour.

Schinke, Smith and McGannon (2013) offer 'characterising traits' to guide researchers in judging the quality of their work according to the said inquiry and study context. These traits are not intended to be prescriptive or exclusive, hence researchers are encouraged to adapt, expand or edit traits to suit individual studies (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). The following characterising traits were used to assess the quality of this study: community-driven research; localising research practices/methods; community capacity building; and project deliverables (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

'Community-driven research' means the research topic stems from the interests of participants rather than researchers (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). This study was community driven in various ways, including the topic being chosen by care home staff/residents during the previously described Ketso workshop before my involvement, guidance from Inscape and feedback from family carers/SDWG (Smith and McGannon, 2018). During data collection, further collaboration with family and staff participants was encouraged, although this proved

challenging, as described in Section 5.14.1. Additionally, member reflections in Phase Three invited participants to critique and discuss initial findings (Tracy, 2010).

'Localising research practices/methods' is when research methods and analysis are tailored to the everyday lives and values of participants (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). This was achieved by using multi-modal methods to fit all participant groups (Kara, 2020), critical reflection with participants in Phase Three, consultations with Inscape, the richness of data (Smith and McGannon, 2018), and my ability to recognise and reflect upon tensions in the research (Johnson, Adkins and Chauvin, 2020), as demonstrated throughout Chapter Five. One objective of this study was to include the post-verbal voice of PwAD. Although I genuinely attempted to reflect the voices of PwAD by interpreting embodied, post-verbal communication (Quinn, Blandon and Batson, 2019), the experience of PwAD will always be understood through my own reality (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Smith and McGannon, 2018). However, by merely attempting, I endeavoured to see and feel the perspectives of PwAD through my own experiences (Buber, 1970), therefore, rigour in this study cannot be judged on the accuracy of this interpretation, rather it needs to be assessed according to *how* the study was adapted to include these diverse realities (Smith and McGannon, 2018).

'Community capacity building' relates to skill-sharing, learning and research legacy (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). This complements AR because quality goes beyond the generation of knowledge to evidencing action, change and learning (Herr and Anderson, 2005; McNiff, 2013), therefore I decided not to complete a formal evaluation, but to establish learning and change in the field through reflection and discussion with participants (Wallas, 1926; Morris, 2020). A formal evaluation could have been harmful to participants, particularly since care home staff across Scotland felt scrutinised by the government during the pandemic and had concerns of being arrested for acting for the benefit of residents when government guidelines were incompatible with the needs of PwAD (Grimes and Wood, 2021; Burton *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, outcome measures can be one-dimensional, unreliable and unhelpful when measuring meaningfulness, hence quality in dementia research is best assessed through the wider social context and involvement of diverse stakeholders (de Medeiros and Basting, 2014). Achieving community capacity building is demonstrated by the change and learning identified in Phase Three findings in Chapter Eight, and by receipt of an email from a family participant who reported how her participation changed her perception of her dad and her approach towards him.

'Project deliverables' refers to how findings are disseminated (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). This was explored with family members and staff during the workshop, however little

input was gained, therefore no commitments were established. The reasons for this are unknown.

4.20 Summary

This chapter has provided an in-depth discussion of the selected methodology, ontology and epistemology in relation to PwAD, offering insight and transparency as well as demonstrating quality and rigour. My own assumptions of applying the research design within the context of this study have been acknowledged and the autistic experience has been included where relevant. All decisions have been explained and justified, emphasising the need for the active inclusion of PwAD using methods that genuinely invite them to participate in research.

Key learning from this chapter includes the need to adapt research methodologies and methods to include PwAD and celebrate diverse realities. This goes beyond data collection and continues throughout the research process, including how PwAD are represented in this thesis. 'Doing with' PwAD in this study has provided a unique contribution to the field because their voices were captured through post-verbal communication and my own experiences as a participant-observer. Furthermore, my creative approaches to decision-making, reflection, learning and data analysis offer insights into alternative ways of exploring academia. This learning is expanded in following chapter which presents a complementary reflexive view of the study, demonstrating what happened when the methodology was applied by 'doing, looking and thinking' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) with PwAD, their family members and staff.

Chapter 5 : Research methods: the realities of doing, looking and thinking

5.1 Overview

This chapter makes an original contribution to knowledge by sharing the learning and insights from completing this study with people with advanced dementia (PwAD), family members and staff. The following aspects are interwoven and entwined. Firstly, it reveals what happened when the methodology and methods were applied and co-created in the field to understand what 'doing, looking and thinking' in Action Research (AR) can look like with PwAD (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). Secondly, it offers a reflexive understanding by exploring how I perceived and interacted with the participants and environment (Finlay and Ballinger, 2006). Lastly, this chapter examines how participants taught me to identify meaning in activities and interactions using different approaches to communication (Sawchuk and Moorhouse, 2016; Quinn and Blandon, 2017).

To continue the dialogue between this and the preceding chapter, it extends the research design to demonstrate *how* this was applied and co-created in the field. This begins with setting the scene of the cultural and political landscape at the time of the study to explain the impact of COVID-19, followed by reflexive accounts of key stages of the research, such as, the experience of applying an AR methodology with PwAD in a care home, ethical considerations, recruitment and consent. Thereafter, the successes and challenges of using creative, multi-modal methods during each of the three phases of the study will be discussed in reference to the 'characterising traits' of quality markers (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). Post-research activities and leaving the field will also be considered. As previously described, I am an autistic woman, thus relevant literature will be included.

5.2 Setting the scene: the impact of the pandemic

Before reading this chapter, it is important to understand the landscape at the time of data collection and how COVID-19 greatly impacted this study. This research began in August 2019 and shortly afterwards, in December 2019 the pandemic was announced followed by numerous lockdowns, causing general feelings of panic, anxiety and uncertainty which were as contagious as the virus (Carless, 2022).

Combined with the disruption of risk-focussed governmental decisions and restrictions, the wellbeing, social and occupational needs of PwAD at this time were severely neglected

(Amnesty International, 2020; Grenier and Phillipson, 2023). Access to care homes was limited, with family members having contact through a window or online platforms, which had a detrimental effect on the psychological, emotional and social health of residents (Giebel *et al.*, 2022; Burton *et al.*, 2023; Haslam-Larmer *et al.*, 2023). This study is therefore privileged as it concentrated on meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD at a time when this type of research, and researching with PwAD in general, was limited and rare.

Governmental restrictions during COVID-19 further medicalised and marginalised PwAD living in care homes (Grenier and Phillipson, 2023), and care home residents, family members and staff faced a disproportionate risk of infection and death than any other setting (Zimmerman *et al.*, 2021; Deber *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, guidance from national bodies frequently changed, adding further pressure on staff (Burton *et al.*, 2023). These conditions made it difficult to complete research in care homes, particularly since COVID-focussed studies were initially prioritised over social research (Grenier and Phillipson, 2023).

My access to the care home was also reliant on several conditions. The study site required me to be fully immunised against COVID-19. Prior to each visit, I consulted the Care Inspectorate's COVID-19 guidelines and undertook a rapid lateral flow test (LFT). Upon arriving at the care home, the infection control procedures were extraordinary. As soon as I entered the building an automated message was replayed: "*please wear a mask, please wear a mask*" whilst I washed my hands, put on a mask and signed a declaration to confirm my negative LFT. Wearing a mask was uncomfortable and hot, adding another sensory dimension to an already sensorially overloaded environment, and although residents were not required to wear masks, some PwAD found it difficult to hear others, asking me to: "*speak English*". To reflect upon these experiences, I sewed masks into the sculpture, 'The Thing' as described in Section 4.2.6, which helped me express, process and integrate unusual circumstances (Carless, 2022).

The routines of the participating care home changed during the study and staff repeatedly shared how activities were reduced and perceived as less meaningful because of pandemic restrictions. Staff roles also expanded to fit COVID-19 regulations, requiring even more flexibility and patience when collecting data.

Family members were required to meet PwAD in the person's bedroom, or in a heated gazebo in the garden. Family members and PwAD were unable to share food and drinks using the care home crockery, so some brought flasks and snacks during visits to 'normalise' interactions. Family members were forbidden to speak with other residents, reducing social contact for those without visitors.

During data collection, one House was locked down because of COVID-19, meaning a ten-day restriction on visits which restarted if another resident tested positive. During this time, I was unable to collect data with one PwAD and needed to postpone a family member interview when they contracted the virus.

This chaotic landscape meant continual uncertainty for this study, and required back-up plans, extra thought and planning. For example, if access to the care home had not been possible, data collection would have been adapted to online or telephone, and resources would have been sent through the post. If the workshop was unable to proceed, an asynchronous workshop would have been completed using a mobile station that adhered to strict infection control procedures. With this lens, I now invite the reader to join me on a reflexive journey to explore what happened in the field.

5.3 Applying Action Research in the field

This study used creative methods to implement one cycle of AR with three phases. AR provided a useful approach for this study. The focus on change and learning (Reason and Bradbury, 2008; McNiff, 2017; Stringer and Aragon, 2021) and the use of creative, multi-modal methods was paramount when working with diverse realities because it enabled the study to be adapted and responsive to different participant skills (Rosiek, 2013). However, AR demands substantial energy to maintain active partnerships, creating significant activity and data (Stringer and Aragon, 2021), particularly when combined with the complexities of a dementia-specific setting (Webb *et al.*, 2020) and a pandemic. Within this landscape, the AR process was ever-shifting (Cook, 2009), particularly so during COVID-19 (Podar, 2024). Although uncomfortable, this state of messiness can be seen as a sign of rigour and is essential for change to emerge (Cook, 2021; Podar, 2024).

5.3.1 Co-creativity with people with advanced dementia

This uncomfortable space appeared to offer opportunities for meaning-making with PwAD. In this space, meaning had to be sensed and felt rather than fitting typologies, such as those categorised by Smith *et al.* (2023), which lacked the sensitivity to recognise and acknowledge subtle and/or post-verbal communication and realted co-creativity (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018).

Although uncomfortable, this indefinable space was also beautiful and magical. It required continual adjustment of my positionality according to the participant group, methods and how the study unfolded in the field (Chandler and Torbert, 2003), creating freedom to shape and

co-create meaning in activities and interactions with participants moment-by-moment (Zeilig, West and van der Byl Williams, 2018). This space offered opportunities for new communication to be learnt through inter-embodiment (Jenkins, 2013), where the body itself was a source of meaning (Kontos 2004, 2005; Fuchs, 2020). Through the medium of the body and the emotions, PwAD indirectly defined co-creativity as an authentic, mutual, learning partnership embedded in experiences of change through 'being' and 'doing' together, in a similar way to the Care Empathia pedagogy formed through the head, heart and hands of learning (University of the West of Scotland and Alzheimer Scotland, 2021). In this space, I felt an affinity with PwAD, partly because my own experiences of stigma helped me to absorb the diverse lived experiences of participants. Also, being a body in this space with the bodies of PwAD taught me how to co-create meaning and share control within the negotiation of everyday life (Haraway, 1998).

5.4 Researcher positionality

Research in the care home required positionalities which shifted according to the participants and context. This changeability was also partly related to the third space (Sigurdardottir and Puroila, 2020; Hawley and Potter, 2022) and dual identity (Hay-Smith *et al.*, 2016). The 'third space' posits that many spaces can exist at once (Hawley and Potter, 2022), creating liminality and an array of emotions and tensions (Sigurdardottir and Puroila, 2020). When applied to this study, the 'third space' is where the home and identities of PwAD met academia to become a shared research space with possibilities for co-creativity and change (Hawley and Potter, 2022).

My positionality was fluid in this third space. For example, during an observed family visit between Fraser (PwAD) and his wife, Sorcha (family) in Phase Two of the study, I had intended to maintain an observer positionality. However, the third space provided opportunities for negotiation (Hawley and Potter, 2022) when Fraser (PwAD) unexpectedly acknowledged and validated my presence by pointing, smiling and waving at me, to which I responded (Sigurdardottir and Puroila, 2020). All PwAD did this to some degree, indicating that the autonomy and agency of PwAD affected my positionality, shifting me from observer to participant. These acts changed the format and flow of observations, echoing the fluidity of the pragmatist ontology (Rosiek, 2013) whilst demonstrating the action aspects of the AR methodology and social constructionist epistemology (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Stringer and Aragon, 2021). This knowledge is important because positionality appears to be shaped and shifted by/with others in the context of the environment and is not merely in the control of the researcher, an area for consideration during research design, collection and analysis.

My professional identity as an occupational therapist created a dual identity, producing some conflict between my clinical knowledge and the research purpose, causing me some discomfort (Hay-Smith *et al.*, 2016). Although these potential difficulties were considered during the planning stages of the study (Geddis-Regan, Exley and Taylor, 2021), they were difficult to manage at times, particularly at the start of data collection when I was adapting to a researcher role. As an occupational therapist my lens could lead me to perceive actions from a professional rather than research perspective. To help manage this internal confusion i.e. when competing responsibilities clash (Yanos and Ziedonis, 2006), reflexivity and frank discussion with the supervisory team were used to openly acknowledge how my clinical and personal background and assumptions may have shaped my approach to AR, the participants and the data (Finlay and Ballinger, 2006; Geddis-Regan, Exley and Taylor, 2021).

During recruitment, my professional background was clear to family members and staff, although I was not entering the field as an occupational therapist (Geddis-Regan, Exley and Taylor, 2021). This could have risked power imbalances beyond the common perception that researchers are 'experts' (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Arber, 2018). However, I hoped my disclosure would help build rapport with participants by demonstrating transparency (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Geddis-Regan, Exley and Taylor, 2021) and personal and professional integrity (Royal College of Occupational Therapists, 2021). I felt this was particularly important since management had been made aware of my professional background before recruitment. Moreover, I reinforced the shared power in AR (Olsen and Lindo, 2004; McNiff, 2017) by wearing my own clothing to reduce any potential threat a uniform may have created (Richards 2007). There is no easy answer to approaching disclosure (Geddis-Regan, Exley and Taylor, 2021) and disclosures need to be considered and justified as part of the research design to fully consider potential advantages and challenges for participants and the data (Finlay, 2002).

5.5 Applying ethical considerations

5.5.1 Collecting data with people with advanced dementia

Initially, direct activities between PwAD and myself were expected to last up to twenty minutes, the duration of which was informed by the literature review. However, extra time was required for several reasons. PwAD often wanted me to stay longer, which was evidenced by their response, for example, by asking if I was bored when I needed to leave at the end of twenty minutes. Secondly, activities needed to be paced according to the needs of individuals, who often required a slower approach. Although one PwAD required a fast pace, extra time was still required to build rapport and complete a range of short activities to match his diverse interests and need for stimulation. Lastly, group activities often lasted one and a half hours

and it was often necessary to stay for the whole period to understand the context of the activity. These circumstances demonstrated the need for flexibility when researching with PwAD to adapt the research to their needs and interests and allow for co-creativity (Webb *et al.*, 2020), however this created an overwhelmingly large volume of data (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) which was difficult for one person to manage during analysis.

5.5.2 Audio-visual data

Using an iPad and a GoPro to collect audio-visual data required careful consideration, including the practical aspects using audio-visual equipment, assent, dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010), process consent (Dewing, 2008), anonymity and confidentiality.

5.5.2.1 Using the equipment

I trialled the equipment to familiarise myself with its functions before entering the field. This preparation greatly enhanced my experience in the field. There were occasional technical issues such as a short gap in recording on one observation. Here the multiple data collection procedures meant that field notes were available to augment the analysis. I also found that during intense interaction it required conscious awareness of the field of view available to the lens to achieve a full picture.

I originally planned on using the iPad throughout all phases of data collection, however, during Phase Two, I realised the equipment needed to match the activity and the PwAD. Although the iPad had excellent image and sound quality, it did not appropriately capture spontaneous activities involving movement, here, the GoPro provided flexibility. I used each tool according to the activity/person, for instance, the iPad was used for quieter, sedentary activities such as drinking and eating, and the GoPro captured activities such as dancing and walking.

5.5.2.2 Assent, dissent and process consent

To enhance transparency when using audio-visual data, the Participant Information Sheets (PIS) and the (proxy) consent forms explained how this data would be collected and used (Dewing, 2007). Additionally, I demonstrated the equipment to PwAD by placing my hand in front of the lens so they could see how it worked before asking their assent to continue (Black *et al.*, 2010). If the person was unable to communicate verbally, then cues were taken from their behaviour and/or expression of emotions (Black *et al.*, 2010). I continually monitored the person's reactions to guide process consent (Dewing, 2007, 2008).

There are important ethical issues regarding using audio-visual methods with PwAD, interpreting assent/dissent in PwAD, and the importance of appearance and self-identity of PwAD (Ward and Campbell, 2013). On one occasion during an observation between a PwAD

and a staff member, the PwAD looked at the iPad screen and noticed they did not have their teeth in, which displeased her, expressed by the noises she made and the words she chose. I considered whether the observation and/or recording should be stopped, however, because she soon relaxed and her objection appeared to be with her appearance rather than the equipment, I interpreted this as assent (Black *et al.*, 2010). See anonymised Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1 Introducing the iPad to PwAD

5.5.2.3 Anonymity and confidentiality

Using audio-visual research methods increases the risk of exposing the identity of participants, non-participants and places (Clark, 20129; Mannay, 2016). To address this, I initiated discussions with the supervisory team, other researchers, and consulted relevant literature (for example, Clark, 2012; Mannay, 2016; Kara, 2020; Rose, 2023). As well as adhering to strict ethical guidance, I also used various strategies in the field, including lowering the iPad/covering the GoPro or pointing equipment at the wall/floor when non-participants walked past (Canning, 2020).

In addition to seeking assent/dissent and using process consent with all participants, I gained informed (proxy) consent to use selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data for academic purposes (Dewing, 2007, 2008; Black *et al.*, 2010). Anonymising audio-visual, for example, by blurring faces, removed expressions and reduced the portrayal of meaning (Derry *et al.*, 2010), impacting the relationship between meaning, post-verbal and (inter)embodied communication and activities and interactions with PwAD.

Recent literature discusses the purposes of anonymisation, arguing a case for not anonymising data in certain circumstances (Rose, 2023), for instance if anonymisation minimises the control and contribution of participants (Godfrey-Faussett, 2022). Therefore, it may be useful for researchers and participants to collaboratively and carefully consider approaches to anonymising data in AR as part of the co-creative process which are ethically sound and follow data protection legislation (Derry *et al.*, 2010; Godfrey-Faussett, 2022).

5.6 Recruitment

Care home recruitment for research purposes is a two-tiered process requiring consent from care home management and individual participants (Lingler *et al.*, 2009). Recruiting care homes and care home residents is often difficult for various reasons (Lam *et al.*, 2018; Collingridge Moore *et al.*, 2019), including ethical issues, such as capacity and consent (Lingler *et al.*, 2009; Lam *et al.*, 2018), low response rates, staff time constraints, and discomfort with research topics, for instance, end-of-life and death (Collingridge Moore *et al.*, 2019). Despite the intense COVID-19 restrictions, conversely, recruitment for this study was relatively successful. Possible reasons include the low probability of harm to residents because the study was consistent with everyday life (Lingler *et al.*, 2009), and pre-established relationships between the university and care home management. Pre-established relationships enabled trust, clear communication and transparency to be built with the gatekeeper, helping to ensure participants were selected according to the criteria rather than those who were easy to access (Webb *et al.*, 2020).

5.7 Consent

5.7.1 People with advanced dementia

The consent process for recruiting PwAD in this study involved seeking assent or dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010). This approach was supported by a short pictorial document to aid communication and understanding (The UK Network of Dementia Voices, 2020; Collins *et al.*, 2022). This approach proved unsuccessful, causing confusion in the PwAD as their ability to understand the visuals did not seem to enhance the verbal explanations I gave. This implies the assent/dissent process needed to be tailored to individuals and relatable to the present context (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

A key factor in the consent process was to seek assent/dissent to spend time with PwAD before and during each activity/interaction. However, this required extra thought, time and

creativity, for example, when I initially greeted one PwAD, they closed their eyes, which I interpreted as dissent. Being aware of the person's interest in football, I returned later that day with a football and sought assent/dissent for playing a game instead of seeking assent/dissent for the research. His (re)actions, participation and words communicated his assent to the game and reassured me he could participate in the research using process consent (Dewing, 2007, 2008). Involving PwAD in the consent process was an important part of the research because it offered opportunities for learning to enhance their active participation. It also increased my understanding of how to adapt my approach in preparation for data collection (Chatwin, 2014).

5.7.2 Family members

I took a sensitive and empathetic approach when seeking (proxy) consent with family members and ensured they were given time and space to decide whether the study was suitable for them and PwAD. An example was leaving the Patient Information Sheet (PIS) and (proxy) consent forms with family members rather than expecting an immediate signature. Three out of four family members signed the consent forms immediately/shortly afterwards, and one family member required more time. She was unsure whether her dad could meaningfully contribute to the study because she perceived him to spend all day sleeping. We arranged another meeting to discuss this further and ensure any decisions were made for the benefit of PwAD (Scottish Government, 2008). After the meeting, the family member felt comfortable to sign the (proxy) consent forms.

5.7.3 Staff members

More staff members wanted to participate in the study than I could accommodate, perhaps indicating the research was aligned with their experiences and beliefs (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). Although recruitment was managed by the Hospital Management (HM), I also met with interested parties to explain the study, emphasised their participation was voluntary and informed them they could withdraw at any point without question. One staff member who was originally interested declined with no expressed reason, and all others consented. I aimed to fit the research around care home routines and staff schedules to minimise burden (Webb *et al.*, 2020), yet two staff members offered to participate in their own time demonstrating their passion for the research topic and purpose (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

Although there was high interest in the study, staff availability regularly changed which made it difficult to arrange meetings with individual staff, for example, when staff took sick/annual leave, changed their shift patterns, or when group activities over-ran. To compensate, recruitment relied upon the ability to build rapport and required flexible planning and extra time

(Webb *et al.*, 2020), for example, telephoning ahead of arranged visits to confirm potential staff participants were still on duty and rearranging if necessary.

5.8 Pre-research activities

Pre-research activities proved essential to inform and develop the research design and methods using ‘real-world’ perspectives (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) as well as ensuring the research was aligned with the interests and priorities of those with lived and clinical experience (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). An example is the online World Café reported in Section 4.12.2, which took place with four Inscape members (Monforte, Netherway and Smith 2023). After a short introduction, members were asked to vote on the suitability of the following data collection methods: 1) Zines (Piepmeier, 2008; Stanley, 2015); 2) Diary Method (Bartlett, 2012; Herron *et al.*, 2019); 3) sensory mapping and sensescapes (Halloy and Servais, 2014; van der Walt, 2020; Buzova *et al.*, 2021; Kou *et al.*, 2024); and 4) gathering data from an online platform, Workplace (Meta, 2024). This experience highlighted how methods in dementia research needed to appropriately fit participant preferences and skills (Webb *et al.*, 2020) rather than the interests of the researcher (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

5.9 The setting

As previously described, this study took place in a forty-bedded dementia-specialist Scottish care home. Aside from data collection, I routinely collected information about available activities and sensory information (see Section 4.12.5).

5.9.1 Care home activities

The home offered a programme of leisure activities for residents. These were mainly organised and facilitated by Activity Assistants (AA's) or a Speech and Language Therapy Assistant, with support from care staff, and mostly consisted of planned group activities. Each attendance was documented on individual electronic files to capture the type of activity, the environment, and the resident's response. The activity programme was adapted during COVID-19 to accommodate the frequent change in regulations. Staff reported this to be inferior to the pre-pandemic activity programme which included residents and family members in a wide range of activities including outings, concerts, church services, walking groups and adapted cycling.

5.9.2 Sensing the setting

To help orientate myself to the care home environment, I created sensescapes using audio-visual methods, photographs and text (Halloy and Servais, 2014), PwAD and autistic people may experience the sensory world differently from those without these conditions (Houston and Christie, 2018; Judge, 2018), and adopting a sensory perspective helped me to feel and absorb the environment and align myself with the everyday experiences of the care home in a similar way that geographers attune to landscapes (Dowling, Lloyd and Suchet-Pearson, 2018). The sensescapes captured a variety of sensory information including sounds from beeping alarms, ringing telephones, creaking doors, voices and rumbling televisions, and smell which was flattened and desensitised from wearing face masks. Sensescapes also highlighted the oppressive and tiring heat, which was only relieved by the coolness of a residents' hand or slight breeze when a door was intermittently opened.

5.10 The participants

5.10.1 Overview

As previously stated, this study included four PwAD, four family members and six care home staff (see Figure 4.9). This combination of participants offered a more diverse view of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD rather than a snapshot from one participant group (Correia and Caetano, 2023).

5.10.2 Participants with advanced dementia

The four participants with advanced dementia were essential to this study (Smith *et al.*, 2023) because their active participation enabled me to see what may have otherwise been invisible (Correia and Caetano, 2023). Using multi-modal methods enabled PwAD to co-create meaning in activities and interactions through participation, providing opportunities for PwAD to actively participate in research. Through this experiential process, PwAD taught me new ways of communicating that would not have been so apparent through observational methods, for example how teaching does not necessarily require words (Quinn and Blandon, 2017). The PwAD are introduced using the following pseudonyms: Donald, Morag, Hamish and Fraser, using information gathered from family members, staff, and my own interactions.

5.10.2.1 Donald

Donald was an eighty-three-year-old man who had previously worked as a welder on shipyards and power stations around the world. He was divorced and had four adult children, including family participant, Amy. Donald was a kind, sociable, helpful man with a wide range

of previous interests, including playing drums, attending social groups, collecting model trains/cars, boules, football and dancing.

Donald had been living in the care home for eighteen months at the start of the study and lived with mixed dementia: Alzheimer's disease and an unknown dementia. His Functional Assessment Staging Tool (FAST) score was 7a, meaning he lived with severe dementia to the point of having limited speech ability (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011); he also had a diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. Donald was independently mobile, and he was often found walking around the House and gardens. He liked chocolate and eating biscuits with tea.

5.10.2.2 Morag

Morag was the only female participant with advanced dementia. She was ninety-one years old at the start of the study and previously worked for a car company before becoming a cleaner. Morag had two adult children including family participant, Rose. Morag was a warm, friendly and sociable person with a sense of humour who prioritised her family and friends. She previously enjoyed activities like line dancing and bingo at a local 'Over 50's' club, which she founded with friends.

Morag had resided in the care home for eighteen months at the start of the study and lived with vascular dementia with a FAST score of 7d, meaning she lived with severe dementia and was unable to sit up independently (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011). Morag experienced frequent anxiety, often expressing a wish to go home. She was the only participant to mobilise using an attendant wheelchair and was often in the communal lounge drinking tea. She enjoyed having a 'blether'/chat.

5.10.2.3 Hamish

Hamish was ninety-one years old when the study began and previously worked as a salesman. He was a widowed father to three adult children, including family participant Susan. Hamish previously enjoyed socialising, attending church, singing and ballroom dancing and was described as a well-liked, quick-witted man with a sharp sense of humour.

At the start of data collection, Hamish had resided in the House for three months and had settled in well. He had not been formally diagnosed with a dementia because of the pandemic but scored 6e on the FAST, meaning he had moderately severe dementia with faecal incontinence (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011). Although Hamish was able to communicate fluidly using words, the content was often incomprehensible. Hamish mobilised with a stick and was the only participant with advanced dementia observed to attend organised group activities.

5.10.2.4 Fraser

Fraser was eighty-four years old at the start of the study and previously worked as a shorthand typist and retail outlet manager. His wife, Sorcha participated in the study. Sorcha described him as a sociable, careful and methodical man who loved reading books, listening to classical music and brass bands and going on cruise ships. Fraser was a creative cook, loved gardening, and was often hill walking or sitting with his cats. He was actively involved in the community and volunteered at the local church.

Fraser had lived in the care home for twelve months at the start of the study and had a diagnosis of Alzheimer's Disease. Like Hamish, he scored 6e on the FAST (Reisberg *et al.*, 2011). He was independently mobile and spent his time in a care home office collecting items he found interesting or appearing to sleep in the communal lounge. He carried a soft toy in his pocket and had developed a recent liking for sweet foods.

5.10.3 Family members

The four family members in this study are described using the pseudonyms: Amy, Rose, Susan and Sorcha. Family relationships comprised two father-daughter relationships, one mother-daughter kinship, and one husband-wife partnership.

The family members contributed a wider perspective of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, combining historical and present knowledge of the person (Correia and Caetano, 2023). They offered a different view from the embodied communication of PwAD (Correia and Caetano, 2023) and enhanced rigour by broadening understanding, knowledge and perspectives (Flick, 2015).

5.10.4 Staff members

The six staff members in this study are described using the pseudonyms: Anna, Clarissa, Judy, Katie, Harry and Herbert. Roles included one Registered Nurse (RN) with ten years of experience working with PwAD, three Senior Care Assistants (SCA's) with eight, fifteen and twenty-five years of experience, and two AA's who had worked in the setting for seven and eight years. One AA had twenty years' experience of working in a general care home. Staff members were not assigned to specific residents as expected before data collection, they were partnered with PwAD depending on the allocated House during each shift.

Staff participants provided a professional view of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD which iteratively moved from the present to the future (Rosiek, 2013), adding further depth through augmentation of data (Flick, 2015). Their training in dementia and person-centred practice was evident, adding a different flavour to the research than other participants (Correia and Caetano, 2023).

5.11 Preparation period

The preparation period completed prior to data collection consisted of ten visits to the care home between November and December 2021 to build rapport with residents, family members and staff, and orientate myself to the setting and care home routines. Although this has an ethnographic feel which may initially appear inconsistent with the AR methodology, the commitment to relationship-building was part of the AR process and a strength of the study. The rapport built during this period eased the data collection process later in the study because trust was already established, particularly with staff who appeared more supportive of the study as a result (Webb *et al.*, 2020). For example, one staff member felt the time taken to understand the setting demonstrated my interest in their work/PwAD and made them feel valued as a participant. This echoes the work of Cook (2021) who described how relationship-building is key to hearing and including all voices in AR.

During this period of relationship-building in the preparation period, some tensions arose. For example, the HM was keen for me to use care plans as data, and although I explained there was no ethical approval for this, it remained a persistent theme. I had previously considered and excluded this method because my clinical experience had taught me, and evidence suggested that care plans are often inaccurate (Tuinman *et al.*, 2017), unused (Østensen *et al.*, 2020) or not meaningfully applied. I felt uncomfortable and vulnerable communicating this to the HM, particularly because I was not a member of staff.

Termed 'Horse-Assery' by Goffman (1989) and Tracy (2014), the act of being vulnerable in the field can indicate quality research (Tracy, 2014). Although well supported by my supervisory team while in the field, I felt vulnerable at times, and although it was often disconcerting, it could be managed with a sense of humour where appropriate (Tracy, 2014). For instance, during one visit I sat in the activities space waiting for a group to start. The resident next to me had previously been unresponsive to my greetings and smiles, which made me feel uneasy. Whilst we waited, a fire drill occurred, making me jump which caused the resident to look at me with a bemused expression, and resulted in us laughing together. This taught me that being vulnerable myself could offer opportunities to connect with residents and was a feeling to celebrate or explore, not one to fear (Tracy, 2014).

5.12 Phase One

Phase one consisted of four interviews with four family members, and two focus groups with six staff.

5.12.1 Interviews

Interviews with family members were often emotional so after the first interview, I adjusted the order of the questions to ease participants into more specific questions (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Some family members became visibly upset and one reported being concerned they had used the interview like a counselling session. One family member doubted the value of their contribution, and another was surprised they had contributed more than they anticipated. I had identified a list of relevant support organisations such as a 24-hour Freephone Dementia Helpline (Alzheimer Scotland, 2025b), which was provided in the PIS. I also asked family members if they would like to stop or pause the interview, however none did. I often felt responsible when participants became upset, which I managed through reflexive fieldnotes and discussion with the supervisory team.

As previously discussed, the objects family members brought to interviews included photographs, a model train, a tie and a soft toy. Three participants were confident in talking about their selected object(s), and in these situations the objects enhanced and eased conversations, gave family members some control and provided opportunities for reflection (O'Brien and Charura, 2023) and collaboration (Kahlke *et al.*, 2024). The objects also elicited a narrative about PwAD, giving the person a voice when they were not physically present (Abildgaard, 2018).

Conversely, one family member brought an object she had little knowledge of, which limited and stilted the conversation. This challenged my assumptions about how to support object-elicitation, for example, to clarify that family members would select an object they had knowledge of. This highlighted some limitations of object elicitation, suggesting participants may require more choice over elicitation techniques, for example by replacing objects with walking, vignettes or music (Kahlke *et al.*, 2024).

5.12.2 Focus groups

Braun and Clarke (2013) advise three to eight participants per focus group, and even though this study was at the lower end of their recommendation, rich, deep discussion still transpired. Staff in the first focus group consisted of one AA and two SCA's, and the second group involved one AA, one SCA and one RN. The allocation of staff roles in each group was managed by the HM, however there was a good mix of roles, enabling opportunities to explore diverse perspectives (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Although the two focus groups had the same structure, they felt different. For example, the dialogue in the first group flowed, whereas in the second, there were awkward moments where I doubted my ability to maintain flow (Tracy, 2014).

Positive feedback was received from the HM and individual staff participants. Some staff reported enjoying the focus groups, and one reported feeling excited and motivated about the

study. Another reflected on the questions, and shared new insights days afterwards, which suggests the research was relatable and meaningful (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). Staff engagement was perhaps nurtured by the positive relationships built during the preparation period (Webb *et al.*, 2020), increasing my confidence as a researcher (Sigurdardottir and Puroila, 2020).

Ensuring all voices were heard was the main challenge in the focus groups (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Familiarity within the group enabled conversations to flow, however participants often spoke over one another, reducing their capacity to listen which complicated the transcription (Denscombe, 2010; Braun and Clarke, 2013). One participant was quieter than their colleagues (Braun and Clarke, 2013), requiring occasional gentle prompting to ensure their voice was heard.

5.13 Phase Two

This phase consisted of four observed PwAD/family member visits, eight observed activities with PwAD/staff, and eight direct activities between PwAD and myself.

5.13.1 Observations of family visits

All visits took place in the person's bedroom because of pandemic regulations. Observed activities and interactions included hand massage, a jigsaw puzzle, dancing, and looking at photographs. Each visit sensitised me to the participants and setting, offering insights into the lived experience that were not accessible during the interviews, for example, by providing experiential knowledge which I could feel and sense (Merleau-Ponty, 2002).

I met with each family member in a private room before each visit to clarify the purpose of my observations, seek process consent (Dewing, 2008) and discuss how I could minimise any disruption (Webb *et al.*, 2020). On one occasion, a family participant reported being nervous about being filmed, so we spent time exploring this. We discussed the purpose of the audio-visual data, voluntary participation and her ability to ask me to leave at any point, and she was happy to proceed. A signal was established for all family members to use if they wanted me to depart, although none did.

Each visit was a humbling experience, and I felt honoured to share time with PwAD and their family members, particularly during the pandemic when visits were restricted, however I remained alert to the needs of participants. Since I was working with people perceived as vulnerable (Clough, 2017), I approached data collection sensitively. This occasionally created inner tensions, for instance, when finding the 'right' time to initiate the micro-reflections. These tensions arose because I was concerned about intruding or interrupting visits, which perhaps

interfered with exploring the meaning in activities and interactions in more depth (Tracy, 2014). Although I had completed pilot interviews and focus groups before data collection, these did not prepare me for the micro-reflections which required a more nuanced approach, and I could have practiced this approach with people with lived experience before entering the field, for example with Inscape reference group.

I also found it difficult to ask about meaning without excluding PwAD during the micro-reflections, so in collaboration with family and staff participants, I continuously adapted the observations to try to include them. For example, during an activity, I initially asked the PwAD: “*can you show me how do you feel?*” (Basting, 2020) or “*how do you feel?*”, which seemed to confuse some PwAD. Family members and staff revised my efforts using individualised and familiar tones, colloquialisms and dialect when asking the person, “*how are you?*”. Our co-creation partially included PwAD in this dialogue, but I felt this aspect has potential for further development.

5.13.2 Observations of activities between people with advanced dementia and staff

Observations of activities and interactions between PwAD and staff took place in the person’s bedroom, the communal lounge, and the activity space. Observed activities included shaving, walking, dancing and exploring an interactive table.

I met with each staff member in a private room before each observation to discuss the purpose of the observations and seek process consent (Dewing, 2008). I also explored assent and dissent with PwAD (Black *et al.*, 2010). I monitored the person’s reactions and although I would have stopped the observation if signs of stress or distress were noted, this did not happen.

Although I attempted to observe naturally occurring everyday activities and interactions, many sessions were prearranged to match staff availability and care home routines. As a result, some activities felt prescribed which could have affected the meaning in activities and interactions. For example, one staff member approached a PwAD who appeared to be sleeping to see if they wanted a hot drink. This felt uneasy because I worried they were only attempting the activity because of the research, and would not have usually woken a person for a drink (Tracy, 2014). Also, I sometimes felt uncomfortable with how others interacted with PwAD (Tracy, 2014), for example, when staff greeted a PwAD in a wheelchair from behind, or when family or staff seemed to ‘test’ the person’s memory.

5.13.3 Direct activities

Direct activities and interactions between PwAD and myself took place in various parts of the care home, depending on where the person seemed comfortable and/or where they led me. These spaces included the communal lounge, the main activities space, the garden and individual bedrooms. Activities and interactions included walking, using Apps on the iPad, sensory eating and playing drums.

Before meeting each PwAD, I consulted care staff to check if the person was well enough to take part, i.e. not in pain or acutely unwell. If appropriate, I then approached the PwAD to seek their assent/dissent for spending time with me (Black *et al.*, 2010). PwAD mostly assented by using words and/or their bodies, for example by saying “aye” or by smiling. Occasionally, PwAD seemed to dissent, for example by closing their eyes when I approached them, and in these situations, I did not pursue the interaction. I learned ways to engage each person, for example by bringing objects related to potential activities to put them into context, or by approaching the person when they were sat on their own as other residents could actively discourage them from participating. At other times it was difficult to ascertain whether PwAD were sleeping or just closing their eyes, hence, I sought advice from staff who advised whether it was acceptable to approach the person.

Actively involving PwAD using creative approaches amplified their presence in this research and provided a small insight into their daily experiences. Creative, multi-modal methods provided the flexibility, space and opportunities to celebrate inter-embodied, intercorporeal, individual and dialogical interactions (Jenkins, 2013). For instance, listening, communicating and responding through our bodies created the conditions for new and blended narratives (Jenkins, 2013), adding depth and further dimension to the research.

Although autism and dementia are different and should be respected as such, they can both be viewed through a neurodiversity paradigm (Orulv, 2023). It was perhaps for this reason I felt an affinity with PwAD. For instance, during a drumming activity, Morag (PwAD) and I communicated through action and rhythm rather than words which reduced the pressure I often feel when talking. These post-verbal experiences within the ‘third space’ potentially facilitated opportunities for expressive, creative dialogues, enhancing meaning-making through co-creation (Orulv, 2023).

As previously described, co-creating with PwAD also presented learning opportunities for me (Quinn and Blandon, 2017). In the field, PwAD taught me how my own assumptions may impede meaning in activities and interactions, revealing the complexity and multifaceted nature of daily experiences (Quinn and Blandon, 2017). This reinforced the underpinnings of

this study and the diversity and fluidity of realities and truths (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000; Rosiek, 2013).

5.14 Phase Three

This phase consisted of one workshop with four family members and four staff, and seven reflective conversations/interactions with three PwAD, one family member and three staff.

5.14.1 Workshop

The workshop occurred as the pandemic was transitioning to an endemic, marking the first occasion that family members and staff were allowed to meet in the same space during the study. To preserve confidentiality, the space was segregated from the parallel reception area. Overall, the workshop provided invaluable time for family members and staff to share perspectives and narratives, creating an energy which brought the data to life.

The workshop consisted of two different activities, a practical, partnered activity and a group discussion. The aims of the practical activity were firstly for family-staff partnerships to explore early findings using large discussion prompts, and secondly to respond to and develop these by changing and/or editing the discussion prompts and their contents using the Creative Toolkit (Zino *et al.*, 2021). The aim of the group discussion was to critically reflect on the early findings and discuss dissemination (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

The practical activity facilitated skill-sharing and collaborative learning (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). It was intended that the materials provided in the creative toolkit, for example, Post-it notes, pens, textures and fabrics, would encourage participants to think differently (Dowling *et al.*, 2018) and help to visualise thoughts not easily expressed (Pink and Sumartojo, 2018). The toolkit was used sparingly with participants preferring discussion where they did not find the toolkit helpful or necessary. This perhaps reveals my own positive assumptions of creative methods, demonstrating how this way of working is not necessarily accessible to and/or preferred by others (Burge *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, there may have been a communication shortfall where, in my own excitement, I did not fully explain the purpose of the materials (Burge *et al.*, 2016).

Another challenge during the workshop was ensuring my approach encouraged co-creative opportunities. One family participant reported her motivation for attending was to learn about her husband's life in the care home because she needed to know how much he participated in care home life. However, because of my own desire to make the experience positive, I found it difficult to relinquish control during the workshop and incorporate others' views into the aims of the workshop (Cook, 2021). This highlights the complexity and messiness of 'real-world'

research (Stringer and Aragon, 2021; Brockerhoff and Seregina, 2022) and emphasises the importance of shaping the data collection process with participants using the AR approach (Cook, 2021) to enhance collaboration and ensure all aspects of the research are community-driven (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

Maintaining group focus was also difficult during the discussion. At one point, tension was noted between family members and staff which felt uncomfortable, so I gently guided them back to the topic. On reflection, it may have been useful to explore these tensions, reframing them as potential contributions to the research (Mitchell *et al.*, 2018).

At the end of the workshop, participants were asked if they would like to apply the learning with PwAD during my next visit. Perhaps because of a lack of confidence, there was no response. The one hour thirty minutes allocated for the workshop was insufficient, hence a more practical solution would have been to divide the workshop into two parts that could have been completed on separate days.

5.14.2 Reflections

Reflections with PwAD consisted of being with the person, doing a short activity such as drinking tea and thanking them for their invaluable contribution. The reflection with the family member and PwAD involved discussing the study and exploring a piano App together. Reflections with staff comprised exploring learning and change arising from the study and how they were applying this in practice to understand any legacy of the research (Schindler, Smith and McGannon, 2013). The offer to try activities in collaboration with PwAD was not actioned by any family/staff.

I also reflected alone, taking anonymised photographs of objects that had been significant, for example a wet floor sign. This helped me prepare for leaving the field by attending to my body, senses and emotions to acknowledge my experiences of fieldwork (Dewey, 2000; Merleau-Ponty, 2002).

5.15 Post-research activities

These were important to celebrate the end of the study, acknowledge the value of participant contributions and to thank them for their time and support.

5.15.1 Paintings for participants with advanced dementia

I created bespoke paintings for PwAD of the co-creativity that occurred during direct activities. Each painting was A4 size so the PwAD could see it in their field of vision and were produced

whilst (re)watching the audio-visual data. I painted in a sensorial, 'feeling' way using mark-making to visually capture the meaning in our activities and interactions.

5.15.1.1 Donald's painting

Donald's painting captured co-creativity through movement, the brushstrokes are fluid and rhythmical. Pens were used to represent his gait and pace, and the fragmented lines/stitches portray unfinished conversations. The sewing also reinforced my attempts to grasp the ephemeral and transient nature of our interactions. See Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2 A painting for Donald using Stitch and paint on canvas

5.15.2 Morag's painting

Morag's painting captured co-creativity through two opposite forms with colours from each form entering a liminal space. This represents how our personalities and embodied communication was reciprocal and changed the space in and around. The paint was initially applied with brushes, but was later applied with my fingers, allowing me to feel my way around the canvas and the forms to connect with the person. See Figure 5.3

Figure 5.3 A painting for Morag using paint, pencil and pen

5.15.3 Hamish's painting

Hamish's painting expresses co-creativity through movement because we spent much of our time dancing. The solid line represents the support from Hamish's family, who were ready to catch him physically and metaphorically should he fall. The colours communicate the range of emotions and embodied communication Hamish expressed whilst dancing and the marks denote his skilled hand and arm movements. See Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4 A painting for Hamish using paint and pencil

5.15.4 Fraser's painting

Fraser's painting demonstrates co-creativity on a sensory level. The textures and imprints represent Fraser's personhood and the hand resembles his curiosity and interest in objects. The colours signify Fraser's attraction to yellow objects, such as the Wet Floor sign in the corridors and daffodils, and the leaf characterises his love of nature and the constantly changing realities within, around and between us (Rosiek, 2013). See Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5 A painting for Fraser using stitch, mixed media and paint

5.15.2 Hand painted/collaged cards for family members and staff

I created individual, hand painted/collaged cards for family members and staff. The painted cards reflected conversations about meaning during the study, for example, an image of an object brought in by a family member and a staff member's values. See Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6 An example of the cards produced for family members and staff

My departure involved creating paintings for PwAD and cards for family members and staff. I wrapped the paintings in brightly coloured tissue paper to provide a sensory experience and arranged a visit to the care home to give the paintings directly to PwAD, with permission from family members and the HM. Each person responded differently to the gifts. Donald reported wanting to open it later and Morag seemed excited about the gift and admired and smoothed out the paper with her hands (Byers, 2011). Hamish was sat opposite two ladies when I arrived, who took a liking to my handbag (Buse and Twigg, 2014). His tone implied a dislike of the painting, however he stroked it and spent time reading the accompanying message before repeatedly folding the tissue paper, which seemed to provide sensory pleasure (Souyave *et*

al., 2019). Fraser's wife, Sorcha was visiting when I arrived, and she invited me into his room. Fraser was too sleepy to fully interact, but he held the painting in its wrapping.

Sorcha reflected on the study and described a shift in her thinking. She explained how she had reframed Fraser's post-verbal communication because of the study, for example how she now believed he was listening and processing information when he closed his eyes rather than wanting her to leave. This illustrates community capacity building, demonstrating how the study created a legacy (Schindler, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

5.17 Summary

This chapter has provided a reflexive account of how the methodology and methods were applied in the field. The experiences of looking, thinking and doing with PwAD, family members and staff have been shared, providing an original contribution by offering insights and guidance for future researchers. Additionally, literature from the autistic community has highlighted occasions when the lived experience of dementia aligned with autism.

Key learning encompassed how actively including PwAD in the research was meaningful in and of itself, how researcher positionality changed according to the responses of PwAD, and how assent and dissent with PwAD needed to be explored on a momentary basis rather than the study. Additional insights included the benefits and challenges of using audio-visual data and the complexities of completing research in a care home environment. This learning is deepened in the subsequent three chapters, which report the findings for each of the three phases of the AR cycle; these are presented separately for clarity.

Chapter 6 : Findings - Phase One

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from Phase One of this Action Research (AR) study. The objective of this phase was to explore a shared understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for people with advanced dementia (PwAD) with their family members and staff from four individual family interviews and two staff focus groups, with three staff members per group. This phase was also used to prepare for the next phase, which actively involved PwAD, for instance by learning about their life histories, preferences and communication styles (Kitwood, 1997a; Nolan et al., 2006; Dewing, 2007; Carter and Brown, 2023).

The purpose of this chapter is to present four inter-related themes to show how family members and care home staff understood meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. These findings are presented using themes which are supported by quotations to portray the richness and depth of the data (Eldh, Arestedt and Bertero). The following themes were identified using the analytic method, 'Coding and Categorising' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021): 1) Components of meaning; 2) Still curious; 3) Maintaining and building meaningful, trusting relationships; and 4) Adapting to an alternative reality: progressing through the fog and finding the key.

6.2 Theme One: Components of meaning

This theme illustrates how attending to the physicality of the body through self-care tasks, noticing and acknowledging emotions, and stimulating the senses appeared to be components of meaning in activities and interactions. These components seemed inter-related and provided a foundation for meaning-making. Self-care in this study refers to essential daily tasks, such as washing and dressing (Royal College of Occupational Therapists, 2025) and self-nurturing activities performed with/by another person, for instance, hand-massage.

This theme examines how activities had the potential to be mutually meaningful when the fundamental physical, emotional and sensory needs of PwAD were met. It also demonstrates how meaning could change depending on how activities were perceived by others. Meaning was recognised by others through knowing the person and closely observing their unique communication style for signs of meaning.

6.2.1 Meaning in activities and interactions: a physical lens

Attending to the person's physical needs was a fundamental part of advanced dementia care. This included self-care activities such as medication management, eating and drinking, and

intimate care activities such as continence care, washing and dressing. Different types of activities for different purposes were discussed within and between participant groups, and staff considered knowing the person to be important to recognise meaning.

Rose and Sorcha were the only family members to describe completing self-care activities with PwAD. Sorcha reported regularly cutting her husband's nails to maintain his preferences and routines. Rose reported how she washed and massaged her mum's hands and painted her nails to maintain physical contact and her caring role. She described this as a new activity that had started since her mum moved into the home, and how meaning was created through enjoyment, the intimacy of touch and caring:

“Just touch and something she loves I like holding her hand... it's just important isn't it...well you're not doing anything else... before I was showering my mum taking her to the toilet doing her feet and doing everything... so doing her nails is a very, very small part of her personal care but everyone else is doing all these other tasks now ((pause)) just want to be near her you know”

Staff described their involvement with different types of self-care activities when compared to family members, for example, eating, drinking, dressing and intimate care. They considered these activities to be a fundamental part of their practice which offered opportunities to build relationships and trust with PwAD. There was consensus among staff that meaning was created in these activities when the person's preferences and choices were respected and when they were physically comfortable and pain-free. Balancing the person's preferences and choices could sometimes clash with the physical needs of PwAD and conflict with a duty of care, particularly if an outcome was required, for example, when a PwAD needed a pad change or medicine but did not understand the necessity. Staff described adopting a different role or emphasising their actual role, as described in Section 6.5.

Two family members described the importance of knowing the PwAD was physically safe. Sorcha (family) related safety to familiarity for Fraser (PwAD), and reported feeling relieved that Fraser was now living in a care home because she knew he would be cared for if anything happened to her. Similarly, Amy (family) described safety as reassurance that her dad was no longer at risk of getting lost:

“I didn't want him to go and get lost because that was all you'd be hearing around a certain time is people going missing and then getting found and goodness knows where you know and you're just like no, it can't happen to him... You just want him to be safe”

Maintaining the physical comfort of PwAD also seemed to be meaningful in and of itself but could clash with familial and staff perceptions of meaningful activity. In the excerpt below, Anna and Katie (both staff) described times they were uncertain if an activity or interaction was meaningful to PwAD, and that sometimes it was best not to attempt activities even if staff deemed them to be meaningful. This implies that comfort was either meaningful itself or was conditional to meaning-making. It also suggests that what others perceive to be meaningful may affect opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Anna: *“I put my hands up and say sometimes you just think ‘is it kind of worth it?’ d’you know is it, what are they [PwAD] getting out of this? And they’re getting nothing d’you know I sometimes think they take people up to concerts and they sleep the whole way through”*

Katie: *“Why give them the discomfort of rolling them all the way down there [to a concert] and into an area that’s going to be loud, it’s going to be confusing and they’re lying there... leave them where they are if they’re comfortable, then let them be comfortable”*

(Staff, focus group one)

Harry, Katie and Anna (all staff) believed this type of situation could be a source of tension with families who were often keen for their relative to be involved in care home activities. They felt family members perceived non-participation as exclusion, whereas staff participants viewed this as choice and autonomy. This suggests that meaning may relate to respecting choice and inaction, or alternatively, that these aspects are fundamental aspects of meaning.

Judy, Harry and Anna (all staff) attributed meaning in activities which focussed on the person’s physical needs because they felt this showed the PwAD they were loved and cared for. From Katie’s (staff) perspective, activities involving touch were felt to reinforce the person’s presence in the world. Some staff believed meaning in these self-care activities was dependent on the perspective of the staff member. Clarissa (staff) believed meaning in self-care activities such as brushing hair was often unseen and unconsidered because it was an everyday occurrence, as described in the excerpt below:

“A meaningful activity can be as simple as brushing somebody’s hair and I think that’s where a lot of staff go wrong because they don’t actually see that as a meaningful activity they see that as a basic... I think it’s for staff to be able to engage that step further to make sure that is a meaningful activity so we’ve got a few ladies that absolutely love getting their [hair] done so if you spend five minutes brushing their hair and then chatting to them then you know that can be really meaningful for them as opposed to: “right on you go, you’re out for breakfast”...”

Clarissa, Herbert and Judy (all staff) discussed ways meaning in fundamental activities could be more visible to staff, for example through training, education, and participating in research. They also acknowledged the importance of recruiting staff who had empathy, compassion, intuition, initiative and life experience. All staff in both focus groups reported the progression of dementia, paperwork, rules, regulations, legislation and/or time as barriers to creating meaning in everyday interactions.

All staff believed that individual knowledge of PwAD and their unique body language and facial expressions helped staff to understand and respond to the person's needs and identify (dis)comfort. This is represented by Judy and Herbert (both staff) who discussed the potential links between this and meaning in activities and interactions:

Herbert: *“As you get to know them you get to know their trigger points as well if they were to become unhappy, you might know why just by knowing them better...”*

Judy: *“Just somebody soiling themselves can really throw them out of sync so if you deal with the practical side you can deal with the emotional side afterwards, I think that's the thing isn't it?”*

Herbert: *“They [PwAD] may not be able to communicate they need the toilet but they might use hand gestures or their behaviour might become more erratic like and... because you know them so well you know, 'oh they need the toilet' or 'it's such and such' or 'it's a noisy environment' whereas you need to take them into a kind of quieter environment it's just knowing what triggers their behaviour”*

(Staff, focus group two)

6.2.2 Meaning in activities and interactions: an emotional lens

Meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD also seemed related to emotions. This incorporated the ability to feel and show emotions, the presence of emotions, and emotional comfort gained from physical objects. Family members and staff described how meaning could be created by stimulating feelings of safety, security, pleasure and joy, and how emotional comfort could be gained from objects. The presence and expression of emotions were perceived by family members and staff to be a sign of meaning in PwAD which were important to acknowledge.

Family members and staff described how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD could be created through an array of emotions, with different associations being described within and between the different groups. Susan (family) shared how she helped her dad to feel safe by talking to him about familiar places, and how feelings of comfort could be mutual, with meaning being created through reciprocal empathy. However, meaning and the potential associated feelings may change according to context. For instance, Sorcha (family) described

how engaging in religious activities used to bring her husband joy, but she now questioned this because the pandemic restrictions disallowed visits from facilities outside of the care home:

“I wonder if he’s lost that [faith] because there hasn’t been any contact with ministers here or any services because he was the Senior Elder in the church as well which he took very seriously... he hasn’t had that for the last what two and a bit years, he enjoys his church and again it was the social bit afterwards when it’s kind of tea and coffee time and things like that”

Staff considered feeling safe and secure to be a core component of meaning-making and an essential enabler through which PwAD could participate in activities and interactions and that could also be reinforced through appropriate touch. In one focus group, Anna, Harry and Katie (all staff) related feelings of safety and security directly to Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943), suggesting they believed these feelings to be a fundamental aspect of meaning. Judy, Clarissa and Herbert (all staff) described themselves as a symbol of safety, calm and a source of comfort and reassurance for PwAD. This was illustrated by residents gravitating towards them/other staff members:

Judy: *“... Sometimes in here I feel like a light and you know like when the guys are all trying to speak to you when you’re moving through the place and”*

Herbert: *“Yeah absolutely”*

Judy: *“...And that light draws people... the light is a safety thing so it’s a...”*

Clarissa: *“It’s like a magnet”*

Judy: *“It is isn’t it?”*

(Staff, focus group two)

Other emotions were described as meaningful by family members and staff, for example, pleasure and joy, and two staff members described how using the person’s strengths could enhance positive feelings and self-esteem in PwAD. While most family and staff participants described happy emotions as meaningful, Susan (family) reported how noticing sadness and having empathy helped her dad feel acknowledged and validated:

“I don’t want him to not be allowed to be sad... so sometimes I will you know go with it for a while because I think d’you know what you’re allowed to be sad dad it’s end of life and you’re feeling a wee bit... melancholy and low”

This is important because much of the literature relates meaningful activities to wellbeing and positive emotions, hence there may be missed opportunities for meaning-making in activities and interactions with PwAD if other emotions e.g. those not necessarily deemed to be positive are unacknowledged. Additionally, this raises questions about control and whether PwAD are freely able to express all emotions, and whether upon doing so, these are validated.

The ability of PwAD to feel and show emotions during activities and interactions was considered meaningful by some staff because of the *presence* of emotion. Judy (staff) felt meaning was evident if emotions were stimulated, and that the feeling of wellbeing elicited from engaging in an activity lasted longer than the activity itself. Similarly, Anna (staff) believed meaning lay in the pleasure created through participating in activities and interactions rather than the duration or ability to remember it. Judy (staff) believed the ability to feel emotions eventually deteriorated in PwAD, but that touch remained an outlet for the expression of emotions.

All family members and staff described how the person's unique body language, facial expressions and eyes were signifiers of emotions and of meaning having occurred. Movements like feet and hands tapping, and laughter, smiling or tears were considered displays of emotion and meaning, whereas the person walking away or closing their eyes was interpreted as dissent and meaninglessness.

Another considered source of meaning in activities and interactions was the emotional and potentially sensory comfort gained when PwAD interacted with personal, tangible objects. This is difficult to define because it seemed related to a feeling that was evoked when seeing, touching, or being touched. In this way, it seemed that comfort could be both meaningful and an activity in and of itself and potentially facilitated through an object. Various new and historical objects were described by family members. For example, Sorcha (family) reported how she had recently bought her husband a bolster pillow to aid his sleep - something he could cuddle into which would cover his front/back. Susan (family) explained how a soft toy, Berty (pseudonym) provided mutual comfort for her dad and the wider family. Berty was seen as part of the family unit, providing comfort to all. Amy (family) did not discuss objects in this way, suggesting that she did not consider objects to have these qualities, or did not disclose this.

Anna, Katie and Harry (all staff) believed items such as handbags, furniture and ornaments could provide meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD by providing comfort and familiarity. Katie (staff) felt the physical environment of the care home was a barrier to creating meaning because it was too uniform to enable PwAD to bring in larger objects, depersonalising the space. Harry (staff) felt the single beds in the care home could cause emotional discomfort,

particularly if the PwAD previously slept in the same bed as their partner. These perspectives highlight potential links between meaning and the person's interactions with their personal belongings, and potential loss of meaning if PwAD are separated from significant objects upon moving into a care home.

6.2.3 Meaning in activities and interactions: a sensory lens

Stimulating the senses appeared to be another component of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD. Family members and staff described how sensory activities could be a meaningful way of connecting with PwAD, albeit differently between the two participant groups, with family members appearing to use the senses instinctively and staff applying them as an intervention. Various sensory activities and interactions were described, including activities involving touch, smell, taste, vision and sound. The physical and social environment was also a consideration for staff when using the senses as an intervention.

For Rose and Susan (both family), activities involving touch seemed to create meaning with PwAD by facilitating an (in)direct emotional and physical connection which could remain despite the person's changing needs. Rose (family) reported how the relationship with her mum had changed since her dementia advanced, for example, how they previously napped together on her mum's sofa when her mum lived alone, but how this was now hindered by the room layout and her mum's wheelchair. Touching her mum's hand using massage and nail painting enabled their close bond to be maintained. Susan (family) did not use touch in the same way because her dad was not 'a hugger', however she used indirect touch for similar reasons to Rose (family). In the excerpt below, and in Section 6.3, Susan (family) described stroking soft toy, Berty to maintain the connection with her dad.

"Berty is comfort for me and also because in some ways if Berty's with me and my dad is seeing that Berty is part of me and sitting with me... I'm leaving part of me with my dad, Berty does that job for me because I can't be there all the time... because he's [Berty] interacting with us all the time that we're there, and in the room the first thing I look for is Berty... because then I connect with Berty and through Berty I'm connecting with my dad so that when Berty's left that little ((pause)) just continues".

All staff described using human touch as a tool for co-creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. For instance, Judy (staff) perceived touch as a way PwAD could express their emotions and purposely used touch during activities and interactions to enhance the person's physical, emotional and sensory comfort, provide physical warmth, stimulate emotions and memories, and express love. Clarissa (staff) used touch to communicate to PwAD they were not alone, Anna (staff) believed touch showed the person they were appreciated, and Harry (staff) thought touch helped the person feel safe and accepted.

Judy and Clarissa (both staff) described how they used different types of touch depending on the activity and interaction. For instance, they used soft touch to reassure and comfort the person, and a gentle, mindful, purposeful touch during Namaste. Clarissa (staff) described how only the fingertips were used during this activity to enhance the person's senses. This suggests touch can be a meaningful form of communication with PwAD and that different types of touch are a tool for meaning-making. It also infers that touch can be a meaningful activity with PwAD through which meaning, empathy and mutual connection can be co-created.

Touch was not always considered suitable for all PwAD, particularly if unexpected or if the person had experienced previous trauma. Judy, Clarissa and Herbert (all staff) acknowledged that touch needed to be appropriate and tailored to the person, while Harry and Anna (both staff) reported time to be a barrier to using touch as a sensory activity.

Other senses were used by family members and staff to enhance meaning during activities and interactions with PwAD. Family members described listening and dancing to music, looking at photographs and eating food and drink to engage with the person or keep them awake, whereas staff described formal multisensory interventions, such as Namaste, Sonas and an interactive table. These activities relied upon changing the social and physical environment, for example, by facilitating activities in groups or one-to-one, and/or by using ambient lighting/muted colours, and animated images, such as a fish tank. Food and drinks were reported to be offered during Sonas and Namaste, providing opportunities for PwAD to explore different tastes and textures, and bubbles and smells added extra sensory experiences. Judy (staff) believed sensory activities were meaningful because the senses, emotions and memories were stimulated, enabling PwAD to participate:

“People forget that smell is really important...well if you’ve had a terrible experience accompanied by the smell that relates to that terrible experience you’re always going to bring back that memory to yourself if you’ve had a lovely experience like your granny’s Bell Air hairspray from donkey’s years ago or your daddy’s aftershave when you felt safe and comfortable so that immediately evokes that emotion so it’s just nice smell, good emotions, bad smell you know and it’s just a simple thing like even when you’re talking about the bad smell somebody soiling themselves ((sniffs)) smelling themselves that’s not going to go down well is it to that person, but the smell of their mother’s perfume or their husband’s aftershave or something like that, so that’s why we use all the senses for meaningful engagement with anything”

This theme has presented three different components of meaning in activities and interactions. It has also highlighted times when formal activities may be non-meaningful to PwAD, with comfort and safety being important components of meaning and meaningful in their own right.

Although deconstructed into themes for clarity, the components appear to be connected, intertwined and interdependent.

6.3 Theme Two: Still curious

This theme reflects how meaning in activities and interactions seemed related to the PwAD's existential need for a purpose, how purpose was sought and found and why this was considered meaningful. The need for purpose was recognised by family members and staff through the person's curiosity and motivation to self-initiate and/or participate in activities and interactions, and in the achievement of small goals. A perceived outcome was enjoyment and improved wellbeing and quality of life. Inaction and disinterest was also discussed by both groups of participants and tensions between participant groups were noted.

Family members and staff described how PwAD demonstrated their need for a sense of purpose through curiosity and awareness. Showing an interest in activities and interactions was considered meaningful by family members and staff for similar reasons, and all family members shared examples of this. For example, when the PwAD responded to and enquired about sounds and voices, by asking questions about people in photographs, or when initiating a leader role during a football stadium trip. Sorcha (family) shared how her husband demonstrated his need for purpose by creating a role for himself and collecting items in the care home:

“He doesn't like jigsaws he doesn't like colouring in, I think he just enjoys being in the office? And bless them [staff] they're really good at putting up with him going in there and needing everything that's on the wall and going round and telling them what's on the computer, whose to get their tablets and things... He likes to carry things about with him, at the moment it's the wet floor sign... Now I don't know whether that's because you're carrying something ((pause)) like, could be a briefcase? There isn't a TV in his room now because he tried to carry that about”.

All family members and staff (in)directly described goals as important for providing a sense of purpose for PwAD. Susan (family) described how achieving a goal during a game of catch was important for her dad to challenge and motivate him and provide enjoyment. In the excerpt below, Susan (family) described how she and her brothers watched her dad's response for signs of stimulation, skill and interest, and adapted the activity accordingly.

“I was with my brother one day and he started saying, “right you've got to throw the little cat... and then transfer Berty [soft toy] to actually make it more difficult for my dad... we'd have never of done it if he'd become upset or “I can't do it”... no he enjoys the challenge... his response to it [shows us he's enjoying it] smiling, laughing

and we'll intensively say to him "now you're doing so well with that what we think we're going to do is we're going to change direction" now what's interesting is initially he finds it very difficult to change direction so I've to really pause and say... "you're holding cat so where's cat going to go now?"... you can see by his facial expressions that he is enjoying the challenge of having to work out the direction of flow... and slowly but surely that's developing to where he gets in the rhythm of it and he's enjoying it and we're counting".

Family members also described times PwAD were able to find their own purpose and achieve a goal by doing so, with the meaning being described differently between family members. For example, Amy (family) explained how her dad's response to her husband when he kicked a football towards him initiated a short game of football. She felt this was meaningful because it normalised her dad's experience:

"All the toys were out in the garden and the football was out...so [Amy's husband] started kicking the ball to him [Amy's dad]... And then the ball went in the net or something my dad went over to the net and got the ball out and then he started kicking it to [Amy's husband] and the two of them, and he was running after the ball and everything with his like wee fancy kicks you know what I mean...just like so good he was like running about after this ball ((laughs))...he did like football... I think it was [meaningful to him] just I don't know I think maybe ((pause)) kind of normal? Back to you know he wasn't somebody with dementia?"

Staff added a different perspective and described how activities could be adapted to suit the person's interests. Katie, Harry and Anna (all staff) believed having a goal could increase a person's motivation and offer variety and direction in life, without which they felt life would be meaningless. Herbert, Clarissa and Judy (all staff) felt goals for PwAD needed to be adapted so they were simple, small, manageable and immediate, for example, by limiting options to enhance choice.

All staff described how key information about PwAD and their previous interests could assist in setting them small goals. This knowledge was obtained through a variety of sources, including spending time with the person, consulting with family members and reviewing the individuals' Care Plan. However, Harry and Anna (all staff) believed these sources were not always dependable because the information was often exaggerated or no longer represented the person's current abilities or interests. They felt that family members in general did not understand dementia, individual needs, choices and preferences of PwAD, which could cause tension in family-staff relationships and be non-meaningful to PwAD:

Anna: *"I think the family or some of the families are unrealistic as to what"*

Katie: *"Unrealistic what they could do"*

Harry: *I think that it's just - the guilt comes into it... and they just can't comprehend they don't want"*

Anna: *"I think jealousy comes into it as well they see other residents who are getting ((pause)) but they don't realise my relative wouldn't benefit from that... if 'oh she's getting' it, he should be getting it as well' ((pause)) kind of thing"*

Katie: *"And why don't they go on a barge ((pause)) I could never get a bucket chair on a barge"*

(Staff, focus group one)

Different approaches to stimulating the curiosity of PwAD were described between participant groups. All family members appeared to have a fixed routine during visits. During the observed visits, Sorcha and Amy (both family) pursued activities PwAD previously enjoyed, for example reading, and completing 500-piece jigsaw puzzles. When the person was unable to participate in these activities, the family members believed it was caused by a lack of concentration or demotivation. Some family members integrated new activities into their routines during visiting times, for instance by incorporating new songs into a playlist of familiar songs. All staff used flexible, (un)structured and spontaneous approaches and felt a trial-and-error approach was required because of the person's rapidly fluctuating interests and abilities. These perspectives are important for two reasons. Firstly, if activities solely based on a person's previous interests are pursued, opportunities to create meaning may be restricted, and secondly, there appears to be a need for family members and staff to collaborate with PwAD to create a new occupational narrative to enhance meaning-making opportunities. However, Clarissa (staff) reported how flexible approaches were not always possible:

"I could be rolling with somebody, engaging and then an emergency buzzer goes and somebody's fallen... you know, there's no contest there I need to respond to that... so although we're saying yeah, you need to go with in the minute, depending on at that time, whether you actually really can always it's not always possible"

Disinterest in activities and interactions was also described by some family members and staff. Amy (family) described how her dad would walk away when he lost interest in an activity/interaction, and Sorcha (family) felt her husband would close his eyes to communicate his disinterest in the other person. In the extract below, Katie (staff) expanded on this:

"Not showing any interest we see that a lot... There'll always be that one that's just ((pause)) [holds head and eyes still] sitting like that and you know they're not enjoying it... but you will go and talk to them and you will hold their hand you will try, so it's really not meaning anything for that person"

Three family members and all staff described how as the dementia progressed, it became more difficult to understand if an activity or interaction was meaningful to the person because of communication differences and/or sensory impairment. Although they adapted activities to accommodate, this resulted in some family and staff not knowing if meaning had been created with PwAD. This discussion prompted two family members to question who was benefitting from the activity/interaction and three staff members to believe meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD was created for family members rather than the person. These examples suggest that meaning changed according to the perspective of the participant, the interpreted communication style of PwAD, and the intended purpose of activities and interactions. This is represented by Sorcha and Susan (both family):

Sorcha: *“I mean there’s no conversation anyway because his words are all jumbled up but yeah sometimes even very early in the visit, he’ll sit down with his eyes closed and that’s why I think you know does he not want me to visit? Is that a sign? He can’t be bothered?... Or am I doing the visit just for me?”*

Susan: *“Now what I’m dealing with as I’m discussing that with you...perhaps ((pause)) I wonder if Berty’s [soft toy] more for us than for my dad?”*

This theme illustrated how PwAD seemed to have an existential need for a sense of purpose and how this was understood by family and staff. It described how curiosity, (dis)interest and small goals can create a sense of purpose for PwAD, and how meaning appears fluid and dependent on perspective and interpretation.

6.4 Theme Three: Maintaining and building meaningful, trusting relationships

This theme explores how meaning could be enhanced when relationships between PwAD and their family members and staff were reciprocal, validating and equal. It examines how relationships between PwAD and their family members could be maintained to preserve, sustain or rebuild meaning, and how PwAD and staff could build and maintain trusting relationships to co-create meaning. It also demonstrates the role of objects and creative forms of communication within these processes. Relationships between family members and staff are also explored, demonstrating interdependency, complexities and tensions and potential impact on meaning-making. Additionally, the physical and social environment is discussed in terms of other residents potentially impeding or interrupting meaning-making opportunities with PwAD.

Maintaining relationships between PwAD and family members was complex, particularly since the study took place during a global pandemic when interactions within the care home were severely restricted, as discussed in previous chapters. All family members described different activities which supported them to maintain their relationships with PwAD, for example, dancing and looking at photographs. Sorcha (family) described how her husband was able to fulfil a need for companionship and calm by spending time with a robotic cat or when touching a soft toy dog. Rose (family) described how two mugs represented the close familial bond with her mum, and how they would drink tea from the mugs during visits, suggesting that significant objects could enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD:

“She [mum] used to always say to me “love you” and I’d say “I love you more” and now when I say to her “love you” she says that back so we’ve got mugs as well in her room? One’s ‘love you’ and one’s ‘loved you more’, so that’s us”

Susan (family) also described how objects and activities supported and facilitated visits with her dad. These objects/activities seemed to ‘hold’ the space and provide a focus, enabling her family to maintain a relationship with her dad and co-create meaning:

“So when we [family] go in [to the care home] that’s part of the things we do is throw the [toy] cat and see how many times we can catch the cat... it’s something that has brought something to our lives it’s a simple little ball because when it falls he laughs when he throws it short he apologises... we’ve found a real form of communication through a little ball”

“If I play Sweet Sixteen or something [he] sometimes gets a wee bit tearful and then I’ll go for an upbeat one [song] and he’s on his feet dancing it’s marvellous, music is our communication now that’s how we communicate through music, undoubtedly, yeah”

All staff shared how they personalised activities and interactions to build trust and meaning with PwAD. Harry (staff) described using his knowledge of the person’s preferences, life history, and social, physical and psychological needs to build relationships with PwAD, and obtained this information from family members if the person was post-verbal. Harry and Judy (staff) described nurturing relationships with PwAD by showing them they were loved, wanted and cared for, as illustrated by Katie (all staff):

“You can open a door in here and a resident... will go like that right away [opens arms wide]... what’s the harm give them a cuddle ((pause)) give them a cuddle”

Described as a large, extended family by Harry (staff), all staff expressed how they built reciprocal relationships with PwAD by building trust. They recalled using their instincts, empathy, and knowledge of the person to emulate feelings of safety and comfort and reported feeling satisfied and/or motivated when this was achieved. An element of this was to learn how PwAD communicated, as represented by Judy, Herbert and Clarissa (staff):

Judy: *“I think it’s all boiling down to the empathy that they [staff] have with the situation that they’re [PwAD] in and just that instinct...”*

Herbert: *“To know what to do at the right moment”*

Clarissa: *...“And it’s about taking opportunities isn’t it?”*

Herbert: *“Absolutely”*

Clarissa: *“In the moment”*

Herbert: *“Because their behaviours can be erratic like extremely erratic and... we’ve got a man the now that’s very very challenging... I walked with him because I was trying to give him his medication and he wouldn’t take the medication off other people and he eventually took it off me, I was just using my instinct I know this sounds like really silly but he was saying kind of gobbledegook and so was I, I was making stuff up just to make him feel like safe... to make him feel more comfortable”*

(Staff, focus group two)

Relationships and dynamics between PwAD, family members and staff could also be a source of tension. This complexity seemed to place some staff in an uncomfortable position because staff described family members in general as wanting the person to participate in previously enjoyed activities, whereas staff felt it was important to respect the person’s choice not to participate:

Katie (staff): *“... but we will get families coming in they’re saying, “well why isn’t my mum at this concert? or “why isn’t my dad getting taken?”... and then we have to then say the reason why they’re not getting it and then I feel guilty because ((pause)) I feel as if well ‘I know your mum better than you know your mum now’... so you’ve got to take all that into consideration as well but I think the family want more”*

(Focus group one)

Judy (staff): *“People can still make choices and they do and you give them the opportunity to make choices, even people with advanced dementia but their way of talking or letting you know when they like it or not, they’ve not got so many ways to tell you... but the fact that they liked scrambled egg all their life is not going to mean it- so they’ll spit it out and then we’ll say, “oh maybe she doesn’t like that anymore” but they can still change tastes can change”*

Herbert (staff): *“They change it’s the freedom of change and if they don’t like what their choice isn’t it”*

Judy: *“So they still are able to let us know until they get to that very final stage... so we have to be always alert to the fact that people have the right to change their mind or to like new things”*

Clarissa (staff): *“But I think that’s one of the biggies is that... it doesn’t matter how advanced the dementia is we still need to give them choices”*

(Focus group two)

Furthermore, relationships between family members and staff were interdependent and reciprocal, feeding-forward and back. Put differently, family members appeared to depend on staff for information about PwAD to remain connected to the person, and staff seemed to rely on information from family members to use when building trust with PwAD. For example, Amy (family) reported seeking information from staff about her dad’s participation in activities, and Clarissa (staff) described how staff relied on family members completing a ‘Getting to Know You’ form to provide key information about PwAD. However, Herbert (staff) described how this information needed to be used cautiously because it was sometimes hyperbolic.

This interdependency is important because meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD appears to rely somewhat on the effectiveness of family-staff relationships, yet these relationships may also experience tension, which has the potential to stall or prevent meaning-making opportunities. For instance, Harry, Anna and Katie (all staff) discussed how family dynamics could alter the meaning in interactions between family members and PwAD if they themselves had a difficult relationship, or if there were tensions between family members.

The physical and social environment was also reported as complex, with all staff members describing how meaning-making could be interrupted, disrupted or ceased as a result. Anna (staff) reflected on the unusually high number of people that lived in a small space, which she and Harry (staff) believed could cause confusion and tension between residents, for instance, some residents questioned why there were so many people in their living room, and others believed they lived in a hotel. Additionally, Herbert (staff) described how it was difficult for all residents to like one another, and Judy (staff) felt some residents’ responses could affect meaning-making with PwAD:

“And jealousy has come in as well you know if you spend too much time I mean especially with the men I think with women because I know sometimes one of our resident’s quite angry if somebody’s paid me too much attention but he thinks I ((inaudible)) his wife or something... so it is other factors... External factors can affect how meaningful something is to somebody and it can even be something as simple as another resident shouting and bawling beside you”

This theme explored the meaningfulness of the complex, relational dyads/triads between PwAD, their family members and staff, and how these could support, interrupt or impede meaning-making opportunities. The social and physical environment have also been examined in this context.

6.5 Theme Four: Adapting to an alternative reality: progressing through the fog and finding the key

This theme investigates how family and staff perspectives of PwAD could alter meaning-making processes, and how opportunities for meaning-making could be improved when others adapted themselves to match the interests of PwAD in the moment. It also describes how PwAD were viewed as living in a different reality, and how family members and staff made sense of living with advanced dementia. Listening and responding to the unique communication style of PwAD appeared to help others understand whether they had successfully entered the person's reality and co-created meaning as a result. The idea of 'visibility' is also discussed in this theme i.e. mutual validation to situate PwAD in the world and confirm their existence.

All family members and staff described PwAD as living in a different world, by directly using these words or by implication. For example, Amy (family) described how her dad became "*wakened*" when he responded to family by blowing kisses when saying goodbye. Sorcha (family) described her husband as living in an almost unreachable, intangible and isolating reality and Susan (family) illustrated a confusing and discombobulating world pervading her dad, which she desperately wanted to save him from. Similarly, Rose (family) described the anxiety that enveloped her mum when she became confused and disoriented:

"Just about every visit my mum will have not a panic attack per say but she'll get into a little bit of a panic and be saying: "where am I? Where is- where have I to go?...Where have I- what have I to do today?"

Staff also viewed the PwAD's reality to be liminal, uneasy and enigmatic. This is represented by Judy (staff) who described the person's world as a frightening and fearful space, which seemed to separate PwAD from others, resulting from the dementia progressing and reduced opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD:

"If there's nothing there that means something to you then you will shut down and that's what happens to our residents lack of stimulation they shut down especially

with an advanced dementia so it is there's that fog but eventually it's just, it's the disease cells the brain cells die off yeah they shut off it's like a big barrier there and it's trying to chip through that barrier"

Some staff members contemplated possible reasons for these differing realities. These included a lack of purpose, meaning and activities, or an unmet need, for example PwAD feeling unsafe, insecure or needing comfort.

Connecting with PwAD perceived to be living in a different reality appeared to require a quality from others that was undefinable, visceral and sensed. Different approaches towards the person were described among family members and staff. Sorcha (family) expressed how she had tried an array of activities to find a meaningful hobby for her husband:

"We've tried Dominoes and cards... And I brought a notebook up and a pen thinking if he wants to write but... he didn't want to do that I mean I feel sorry that when I get the pictures of things that are happening [in the care home], the people enjoying doing a, whether it's jigsaws or board games or whatever... I mean he used to play chess! So he's not stupid you know but I would just like to get the key to unlock a door, I've thought about gardening because he loved his garden"

Susan's (family) experience was different, in that rather than seeking a way to access her dad's reality, she attempted to keep her dad in her family's world. Susan acknowledged how this was getting harder as his dementia progressed:

"As he slips further into his own world knowing that he's harder to reach is harder and trying to pull him and keep him in our world but knowing that that's becoming increasingly difficult to do that... And he doesn't have an awful lot of understanding now about what's going on around him... He's kind of lost connections as to who people are... it's losing his ability to understand who we are and who we represent in his life... That's what it feels like as if I'm trying to keep him where he still has that understanding which he did for a long time? But that's slipping and he's becoming less aware of those who love him."

Conversely, Clarissa and Judy (staff) explained how others needed to enter the world of PwAD rather than trying to keep them in the perceived reality of others. This was connected to spontaneity and flexibility rather than working to a plan:

Judy: *"You have to live in their world not them living in our world we've got to live in theirs"*

Clarissa: *"And I think that's the thing about 'in the moment'"*

Judy: *"That's it"*

Clarissa: *“We can’t do our work with saying, “oh right I’ll come back to you in ten minutes because I’ve got to do this”, it has to be in that moment because other than that you’ve lost it... So if that means you need to stop something to engage or do something with a specific resident then that’s what has to happen and that’s where I think a lot of staff struggle.”*

(Staff, focus group two)

A different perspective was offered by Katie, Harry and Anna (all staff) who viewed the person as being ‘new’, having left their old life behind to begin a new one when they moved into the care home. This perspective appeared to enable staff to see the person as a dynamic being rather than a static entity’, potentially opening opportunities for meaning-making by acknowledging the person’s narrative but not being anchored them to it:

Katie: *“... It’s not the person they were it’s a new person we get... So we don’t know anything like that so we take it as ((inaudible))”*

Harry: *“Fresh”*

Anna: *“We’ve got to take it as a fresh page really haven’t we?”*

Katie: *“A new relationship”*

(Staff, focus group one)

However, two staff members described how this could be affected by the person’s narrative. Harry and Anna disclosed that if PwAD had committed a violent crime, they would find it difficult to see them as a new person. Katie (also staff) disagreed and questioned whether this type of information should even be available. This highlighted how meaning may be affected by what is known about a PwAD, and how meaning in activities and interactions could change as a result. This suggests that knowledge of the person may affect the approach used by staff, and have a consequential effect on meaning-making.

Family members and staff used a variety of approaches to adapt to the perceived differing realities of PwAD. As previously discussed, all family members described using routines and specific activities during visits, and although these were structured and planned, they also required an element of flexibility and spontaneity to meet the person’s changing interests and needs. The extent of this adaptable approach appeared to rely on the awareness and skill of family members. For instance, Amy (family) seemed to approach activities and interactions with rigidity, clashing with her dad’s spontaneous approach to activities and interactions while Susan (family) reported changing her approach towards her dad to match his current pace and lessen his confusion by being reflective, mindful and slow in her interactions.

All staff described adapting their approach to match the person's experiences and needs, guided by their reaction. For example, Judy (staff) reported how she and other staff mentally stored information about the person's preferences, interests and comforts, which were collated during everyday activities and interactions. She explained how staff referred to this archived knowledge and combined it with the present time to attempt to recreate and/or stimulate happiness when the person's dementia advanced. This approach seemed to combine the skills and realities of PwAD and staff, co-creating meaning by formulating a legacy to safeguard future meaning-making with PwAD.

Clarissa (staff) described an approach which encompassed everyday creativity, where she responded to the needs of PwAD without the restrictions and boundaries of time. Everyday creativity in these Phase One findings is when family members and staff adapted activities and interactions to suit PwAD by being flexible and not rigidly following plans or routines. Clarissa recalled a recent nightshift when a PwAD requested a shower at two o'clock in the morning, and how she supported him to achieve this. Other staff members in the focus group agreed with this approach, describing it as meaningful because it matched the person's needs at that time, although they also acknowledged that not all staff would have responded in such a person-centred way.

All family members and staff described approaches using everyday creativity, although staff appeared more skilled at this, potentially because of experience, knowledge and training. For example, everyday creativity was applied when Sorcha (family) described how she had been seeking a vintage typewriter like the one her husband previously used to see if he found it meaningful, and Amy (family) shared how she would organise visits to her dad at times when her sister in Canada could attend virtually in the care home garden marquee. Clarissa, Herbert and Judy (all staff) used spontaneous, performative and playful approaches, for instance by metaphorically changing their roles. This involved taking on different personas, and figuratively shape-shifting and altering their personalities, for example by matching the person's accent, speaking a different language, or becoming a police officer. This was described as an enjoyable, fun and satisfying experience which seemed meaningful because realities merged, creating connections with PwAD.

Judy: *"I can be somebody's wife girlfriend mother... you are to them what they want you to be to them... So he could be somebody's son, you could be somebody's daughter or I could be somebody's wife ((laughs))"*

Herbert: *"I was a security guard one night because of my height and size... that probably made them feel safer"*

Judy: *"That's what makes it interesting though isn't it... You actually are a different person all the time"*

Herbert: *“You feel as if you’ve got twenty-eight different personalities in a film you know what I mean?”*

Judy replied genuinely and enthusiastically: *“Ooh it’s great”*

Clarissa: *“Every day’s a”*

Judy: *“Every day’s a”*

Clarissa and Judy in unison: *“school day absolutely!”*

(Staff, focus group two)

Similarly, Katie, Harry and Anna (all staff) described a time when dolls were introduced into the care home and how some PwAD responded as if the dolls were live babies. Katie (staff) described a need to educate herself when she first started working in the care home because she did not see the potential meaning dolls offered PwAD. She reported how seeing the activity from the perspective of the person helped her appreciate the possible happiness the dolls could offer PwAD. Anna (staff) remembered a time she did not see this activity from the person’s perspective, misaligning with the person’s reality. She explained how she did not treat the doll like a baby when bathing it with a PwAD, and how the person became distressed because they believed the baby was drowning. This is important because it suggests that meaning may be co-created when others embody the reality of PwAD during activities and interactions.

When realities merged, reciprocity and mutual empathy appeared to be created between PwAD, family members, and staff. This seemed to enhance meaning for family members by reinforcing love and familial bonds. For instance, Susan (family) recalled feeling sad during a visit to her dad, and although she tried to hide this from him, he noticed, recognised and acknowledged her sadness. She explained how this was evidenced by him becoming tearful in response, demonstrating empathy through his body rather than words. A different experience was described by Amy (family) who reported her dad occasionally being able to reciprocate, for example, by blowing kisses to Amy’s sister, creating meaning through reigniting connections, happiness and love.

Staff also described similar moments, fuelling their motivation to continue working with PwAD because of the variety, continual learning and potential for future connection. Judy (staff) felt that during these times, the barriers enforced by dementia were lifted, creating heartfelt, magical experiences in which the person became more alert, situated and engaged. In the excerpt below, Judy and Herbert (staff) discuss this experience:

Judy: *“You actually see this...blossoming thing that’s happening in front of you and they’re starting to waken up and their eyes are, and they’re sitting in and then suddenly you’re singing all their Sunday school songs and in that moment ((pause)) they’re totally engaged with you you’ve got them! You see when you’ve got them you want a keep them for a wee while”*

Herbert: *“Aye and that gives meaning for them, it gives meaning for them”*

Judy: *“Aww, it is though, it’s brilliant!”*

(Staff, focus group two)

The merging of realities could raise ethical dilemmas amongst staff. Anna, Katie and Harry (all staff) described differences in opinion among colleagues regarding truth-telling or telling ‘therapeutic lies’. Therapeutic lies are common practice in dementia care, defined by the telling of lies to support the wellbeing of people with dementia (PwD) as opposed to a non-therapeutic lie which is for the benefit of others to control the PwD (Canone et al., 2019). An example is when a PwAD asks for their deceased relative and staff report they have gone to the shops rather than continually telling the person their relative is dead. The staff members felt therapeutic lies were a more compassionate and caring approach that generally comforted PwAD, rather than distressing or re-traumatising the person by telling the truth. This was considered meaningful because it aligned with the person’s reality, enabling staff to stimulate happiness and avoid distress for PwAD.

Merging realities with PwAD could also feel uneasy and uncomfortable for some staff. Different perspectives are portrayed in the excerpt below about the multisensory group Sonas. In the extract, staff discuss their experiences of the group.

Anna: *“See Sonas? I mean I know they get a lot from Sonas but I just can’t get my head round Sonas I find it dead infantile... see that singing [starts singing] ‘Hello such and such, how are you doing”*

Harry: *“Yeah it reminds me of nursery a wee bit”*

Anna: *“It makes me cringe”*

Katie: *“It does doesn’t it, it does”*

Anna: *“But I know I mean they’ve come back and I’ve watched them doing it”*

Harry: *“Aye and it is engaging”*

Anna: *“And it’s engaging and they all join in and it’s just a personal thing for me”*

Katie: *“See I’m bored, I’m bored with it, if they’re happy I’m happy...see if it makes them happy doesn’t matter what I think it’s what they want... see if they’re enjoying themselves I’ll dance with them or if you go to talk to somebody and he tells me he’s*

been to the moon well I'll go to the moon with him... You know what I mean it it's all about them it's what's important to them"

(Staff, focus group one)

Some staff and family members described difficulty knowing when activities and interactions were meaningful to PwAD, particularly because the signs of meaning were considered less obvious in the advanced stages. For instance, Susan (family) described often not understanding the content of her dad's speech, but how she still used typical, reciprocal social communication skills and cues to acknowledge and affirm his contribution. She believed her response was not always aligned with her dad's expected reply, which could inadvertently confuse him. All staff resonated with this view, reporting some PwAD not showing a reaction at all, making it difficult to understand if meaning had been created during activities and interactions. Despite this, Katie, Harry and Anna (all staff) described the importance of letting PwAD know they were not alone, offering their time and company to create meaningful interactions.

As reported in other themes, family members and staff described observing PwAD for signs of enjoyment, connection or change, with an array of corporeal and embodied responses being reported. This information seemed to indicate the presence of meaning and the temporary alignment of different worlds. All family members described how emotions could be represented in a person's eyes, or how laughter, singing, clapping, or walking away could provide signs of meaning in activities or interactions. All staff reported observing the person and combining this with their knowledge of the person to establish their mood and interest levels. Some staff considered any reaction at all to be a sign of meaning and described subtle communication, for example, if the person followed something with their eyes, or if their eyes 'lit up'. Ascertaining the presence of meaning and whether the 'fog' had been lifted or a door unlocked therefore seemed to require an alternative way of listening and an ability to perceive subtle and obvious differences in facial expressions and body language.

All staff described using the senses as a form of mutual, non-verbal communication which was translatable across realities, with touch being especially powerful. For example, in the excerpt below, Harry (staff) felt touch could facilitate a connection with PwAD and communicate care, whereas Katie (staff) felt touch could validate PwAD by confirming they were alive whilst communicating a mutual appreciation. She strongly believed touch from another person could prove to PwAD that they were visible to others and still meaningfully existed in the world:

Harry: “They’re touching things [in Namaste] stimulating all the senses for them I think they get a lot more engagement for that because likes of that maybe it’s just the touch of somebody because that’s all they really have now...”

Katie: “Because they know they’re there [moves hands from head to space in front of them in a circular movement]”

Harry: “Maybe somebody massaging them they just feel like a motherly kind of or a fatherly kind of they’re being loved they’re being nourished you know and that’s maybe what they’re getting”

Katie: “They’re not locked in that wee corner you know what I mean...they’re aware of you...they know they’re there”

Harry: “... Aye so that that brings in a sense of meaning for them because then they know somebody’s actually looked at me and is caring for me you know they’re not I’m not just like that stuck in a corner I’m just left to, they’ll come over now and again with a drink and-”

(Staff, focus group one)

This suggests a potential consequence of living with advanced dementia is a disconnect from what others perceive to be reality, potentially causing PwAD to feel non-existent, withdrawn and/or isolated. Touch may be one way to connect with the person and co-create meaning in activities and interactions.

This theme explored how family members and staff perceived PwAD as living in a different reality, and how activities, interactions and communication were adapted accordingly to connect with the person and co-create meaning. As a result, the visibility of PwAD seemed to be enhanced and their existence confirmed.

6.6 Summary and key learning

This chapter explored a shared understanding of meaning in interactions with PwAD from the perspective of family members and staff. Additionally, the chapter provided important opportunities to learn about the life histories, preferences and communication styles of PwAD which was used to prepare for the next phase of the study, which actively involved PwAD.

Key learning from the data suggests there are inter-related and co-created components of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Physical, emotional and sensory components in addition to sub-components, such as comfort and safety, seem to be important and perhaps conditional to a person’s participation in perceived meaningful activities. Comfort, safety, love and care may be meaningful in and of themselves to validate and confirm the

person and their existence. Meaning appears somewhat dependant on family and staff perspectives of the past, present and future PwAD and what family and staff perceive meaningful activity to look like. Meaning appears to potentially be (in)directly (co)created, enhanced, interrupted or lost, which may be impacted by a number of factors including advancing dementia, interactions with other residents, family-family relationships, family-staff relationships, physical objects and the physical and social environment.

Additionally, learning from this chapter suggests PwAD may have an existential need for a purpose, as shown through their curiosity towards others, physical objects and/or the environment at any point in time. This may be stimulated and enhanced by an everyday creative approach which may include: a) others adapting themselves, for example by using performance, matching the person's accent, or using appropriate touch b) adapting activities by using small, simple, immediate goals, offering refined choices or trying new activities and c) adjusting the environment by reducing noise levels or softening lighting. However, family/staff may have intended meanings informed by the person's past and present narrative which may not align with PwAD in that moment. This suggest that equal, flexible, inter-embodied partnerships with PwAD are required to co-create meaning in the present and future. Communication with PwAD therefore needs to be sensitive and responsive to potential subtle communication styles which may indicate the alignment of differing realities, signify the presence of meaning or be meaningful in and of itself.

These findings offer several new contributions to the field, mainly more tangible insights about what meaning in activities and interactions may look like for PwAD and how meaning-making opportunities may be impacted by family and staff perceptions of both PwAD and meaningful activities. The findings also offer understanding of everyday creative ways of co-creating meaning and how meaning may be recognised in PwAD. Similarities between these findings and the previously reviewed literature include identifying meaning through the body of PwAD, co-creating meaning between bodies, the presence of opportunities for meaning in everyday life, and meaning being affected by cultural and social narratives. The findings from this phase offer more depth, richness and clarity specific to PwAD than the insights identified in the literature. This learning is important to take forward into Phase Two because it offers guidance and preparation for the active inclusion of PwAD and suggests ways of exploring and co-creating meaning in activities and interactions directly with PwAD.

Chapter 7 : Findings - Phase Two

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from Phase Two of this Action Research (AR) study. The objectives of Phase Two were to firstly explore how everyday experiences of meaning in activities and interactions could be created with people with advanced dementia (PwAD), their family members and staff, and secondly to include the voices of PwAD using embodied, flexible and creative methods. This AR phase applied the learning from Phase One to introduce multi-modal methods so all participants could be invited to contribute to the study, including PwAD and myself as a participant observer (Creswell, 2016) (see Section 5.4).

These findings are presented using themes and vignettes. Themes are appropriate to the selected method of data analysis (Stringer and Aragon, 2021) and 'real-life' vignettes (Sampson and Johannessen, 2020) were chosen to amplify the voices of PwAD and preserve and resemble the complexity of the care home environment (Ely et al., 1997; Jenkins, Keyes and Strange, 2016; Jenkins, Ritchie and Quinn, 2020). Anonymised drawings and video stills are used to illustrate the perceived lived experience of PwAD (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023) and enhance the visibility of PwAD (Wiles *et al.*, 2012).

The purpose of this chapter is to present four themes to demonstrate how meaning was (co)created with PwAD, their family members, staff and myself. The following themes were identified using the analytic method, 'key experiences' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021): 1) 'Curiosity and purpose (seeking and exploring)'; 2) '(A)synchronicity (feeling and sensing)'; 3) 'Enhancing participation and visibility (seeing, adapting and doing)'; and 4) 'Embodying and identifying meaning (feeling, looking and listening)'.

7.2 Theme One: Curiosity and Purpose (seeking and exploring)

This theme represents how meaning in activities and interactions appeared related to opportunities for PwAD to explore their curiosity and find purpose in their everyday lives. Curiosity is defined in this thesis by a motivation and desire 'to know', and demonstrated by taking an interest in others, objects, and/or the environment for personal satisfaction (Pekrun, 2019). Purpose is used to represent the meaning created when possibilities were identified and sought, even if they were not achieved (Baumeister, 1991). Purpose may be recognised by an intention, goal, fulfilment (Baumeister, 1991) or curiosity and associated with wellbeing (Reker, Peacock and Wong, 1987).

This theme is firstly presented by exploring how PwAD showed interest in others and secondly by how PwAD engaged with both everyday objects and novel items by looking, seeking, touching and exploring. All examples demonstrate how PwAD used (inter)embodiment to show curiosity and purpose.

7.2.1 How people with advanced dementia expressed an interest in others

All PwAD demonstrated a general interest and curiosity in others to varying degrees. Donald and Fraser (PwAD) seemed to 'people watch' when they purposely turned their heads and followed people with their eyes as they walked past or made a noise. This seemed more than a reflex response because they continued to watch others for longer than the initial sound or movement, suggesting this was purposeful and satisfied their curiosity. Hamish (PwAD) appeared to connect with others through humour and by trying to catch other people's attention through performance, and Morag (PwAD) asked questions about others, using her body to show her interest in them. An example can be seen in Figure 7.1 when Morag tried turning herself in her wheelchair towards the direction of voices. These examples appeared meaningful because PwAD showed they wanted to be in(directly) socially involved and were able to use a repertoire of communication skills and agency.

Figure 7.1 Vignette illustrating Morag's interest in other residents

"I like to see"

It was fairly quiet in the communal lounge aside from a few voices and the intermittent beeping of the alarm. Morag and I sat opposite one another with Morag in her wheelchair. We were experimenting with the piano app on the iPad when Morag played a few notes in succession. When she had finished, she looked at me, smiling and giggling, and seemed surprised at herself because she briefly raised her eyebrows, pointed at me and smiled. I asked if she liked it and she replied, "that's good... ((inaudible)) you get a tune (from it)". I confirmed: "yes exactly, you get a tune", and Morag continued playing, humming some of the notes as her fingers hit the keys. We were playing with different octaves when Morag suddenly stopped with a puzzled look on her face. Morag asked who I was and when I told her, she complimented me by telling me I had a "nice name".

Another female resident who was sat behind Morag asked me: "where am I to go now?". I reassured her, telling her she could stay if she wanted and Morag became curious, trying to move her body around to see her. Morag then asked me: "who's that, that you're talking to?". I introduced them, and asked Morag if she would like me to move her so she could see, and Morag agreed: "((inaudible)) turn round, I like to see". Once Morag was facing the two residents, I said: "Morag just wanted to know whose voice it was". The other resident replied: "and whose voice was it?", to which I stated, "yours!".

All PwAD expressed a curiosity towards me, spotlighting their presence and mine. This was expressed in many ways, including asking who I was and repeating my name, actively including me in conversations using words and smiles, or referring to my English accent or 'twang'. Curiosity in this context seemed to create meaning when the interest of PwAD was acknowledged, validated and satisfied through reciprocity. This is represented in Figure 7.2 when Fraser (PwAD) asked his wife, Sorcha (family) who I was, and used pointing to show his curiosity.

Figure 7.2 Vignette illustrating Fraser's interest in me

7.2.2 How people with advanced dementia expressed an interest in objects

All PwAD demonstrated an interest in (non)personal everyday objects and/or novel items, to differing levels. As previously reported, Fraser (PwAD) was known to collect and borrow items found around the home, such as a wet floor sign. I observed an example of his interest during an interaction between him and Judy (staff) as they walked through the automatic fire doors in the care home. Figure 7.3 illustrates how Fraser studied a sticker on the door and how he expressed his appreciation of the item using his facial expressions and actions, accentuating the sticker as an aesthetically pleasing object. The meaning appeared related to a moment of pleasure and having the opportunity to explore the item, which occurred because Judy noticed and responded to his curiosity and autonomy, creating a partnership. If Judy had missed or disregarded Fraser's interest and continued to walk, his choices and freedom could have been undermined and his interest belittled.

Figure 7.3 Vignette illustrating Fraser showing his interest in an everyday item

'The Fire Door Sticker'

Judy and Fraser linked arms as they walked down the corridor of the care home, when a sticker reading: 'automatic fire door' caught Fraser's attention. He looked at the sticker and intensely focused on the small blue and white sign, squinting his eyes. Lifting his hand, he slowed down and touched the sign, causing Judy to turn around towards him. Judy paused, giving him time to explore the sticker.

Fraser touched the sign for a few seconds then removed his hand with a little purposeful, satisfied flick of his fingers, still intensely looking at the sign. Judy acknowledged his interest and read the writing on the sign to Fraser, then she gently started walking towards the House. Fraser continued looking at the sign for a moment, then followed Judy whilst saying: "automatic, ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh-ooh" with his lips pursed.

Donald (PwAD) sometimes demonstrated an interest in objects, but at a faster pace than Fraser (PwAD). On a few occasions, I observed Donald walking around the care home, opening doors that were closed and peering around them, or closing doors that were already open. Although these examples were momentary and sometimes during another activity, Donald's actions seemed meaningful because he used purposeful movements to explore his surroundings. These expressions of curiosity seemed to be an activity in their own right. It could be argued that he was agitated and looking for an exit, however when I had previously observed him in an agitated state, he would bang on doors frantically until someone let him in or he departed. The activities described here were different and seemed to create meaning by stimulating curiosity, providing purpose, and relieving boredom.

Hamish (PwAD) used objects differently from Fraser and Donald (PwAD). Hamish creatively and performatively engaged with objects on numerous occasions when he repurposed items into 'props', showcasing his embodied social skills and his adaptability. These included using a sachet of sugar as a percussion instrument and his walking stick to emphasise performative movements. He often used props to perform comedy sketches, cleverly animating a silent narrative through an array of facial expressions, in a similar way to mime artists. This is illustrated in Figure 7.4 when Hamish pretended the butter knife was a razor for shaving his face. Meaning appeared to be created through a sense of belonging, purpose and satisfaction achieved when Hamish entertained others.

Figure 7.4 Vignette illustrating Hamish miming shaving at Lunch Club

Morag (PwAD) mainly seemed interested in personal objects, particularly her family photograph album. Morag's daughter and a staff member both used the album to engage her in activity during the observations. Morag showed curiosity by asking questions about the people in the photographs, touching the images and pointing at those she was enquiring about. Interacting with another person during activities seemed important to Morag who often sought reassurance and support to make sense of the present. Meaning appeared to be created when Morag's life and those she cared about was animated and co-created through the photographs, as emulated through her vocalisations of delight and surprise and engagement with others.

All PwAD demonstrated an interest in novel objects, for example, the GoPro and iPad used to collect data. This curiosity was evident when PwAD asked questions about the equipment and/or reached for/pointed at it. I used this engagement as an opportunity for activity and interaction, and everyone responded differently. Donald (PwAD) noticed the iPad each time we met, and on one occasion he saw himself on the screen and responded with a big smile. On a different occasion when Donald was conversing with Herbert (staff), Herbert commented how they were like celebrities being filmed; he then waved and asked if Donald would like to wave at the camera. They both looked directly at the iPad and waved, and once they had stopped, Donald continued to look at the equipment and a slight smile momentarily showed in his eyes. Morag (PwAD) showed her interest in the equipment by enquiring about the tiny flashing red light on the GoPro, commenting that it was eye-catching, and Hamish (PwAD) intently looked at the GoPro, peered around it, and asked me questions about it. During an activity, Fraser (PwAD) looked straight at the camera, said it was 'lovely', and reached his hand out to touch it while squinting and concentrating. These reactions demonstrated curiosity in the equipment, changing it from a functional object to an interactive tool through which collaboration was facilitated. In this regard, the technology had a role in co-creating an interaction, and meaning appeared to be created in PwAD having the opportunity to explore and satisfy their curiosity.

7.3 Theme Two: (A)synchronicity (feeling and sensing)

This theme represents how meaning in activities and interactions appeared to be co-created through synchronous or 'in sync' moments. In this thesis, synchronous is defined as emotionally attuned, rhythmic, temporal connections between PwAD, others and/or objects/environments during activities/interactions (Schirmer, Meck and Penney, 2016). It also characterises how meaning in activities and interactions between PwAD and others could be asynchronistic or 'out of sync' i.e. missed, delayed or interrupted, or alternatively where 'in

sync' and 'out of sync' activities fluctuated. 'In sync' and 'out of sync' activities and interactions were identified through embodied and postverbal interactions between PwAD and other participants and objects. These findings suggest meaning may be co-created through activities and interactions with PwAD when others are in-sync with PwAD, and how synchronicity may fluctuate throughout the same activity/interaction. This is important because it suggests co-creating meaning with PwAD in this context may require an adapted, flexible and mindful approach from others, which has implications for how activities and interactions are facilitated in care homes with PwAD.

7.3.1 'In sync' activities and interactions

This section will explore activities and interactions that appeared 'in sync' with PwAD. This will firstly be presented by describing activities and interactions involving PwAD and their family members using music and dancing, and through empathy and laughter. Next, examples will be presented to show synchronicity between PwAD and staff, initially through music and then through humour. Thirdly, examples will be presented which illustrate synchronicity between PwAD and myself through walking and dancing. Finally, an example will be presented between PwAD and others during a group activity.

7.3.1.1 People with advanced dementia and their family members

For one PwAD and their family member, synchronicity appeared to take place when they communicated through music. During his life, Hamish (PwAD) entered dancing competitions with his late wife and music and dancing remained part of his life in the care home. On one occasion, Susan (family) comforted Hamish because he became visibly upset when looking at photographs of his great-granddaughter, and to try and improve his mood, she played some music. Through movement, Hamish, Susan and the music seemed to synchronise, opening opportunities for reciprocal embodied communication and expression. Meaning in this activity and interaction appeared to be created through the expression of emotions and touch which were observed in Hamish's movements. His purposeful, accentuated, fluid repertoire of movements and his singing also appeared to provide a freedom of expression he no longer achieved in spoken language.

Emotional expression and touch appeared to create synchronicity for Morag (PwAD) and Rose (family) whilst they spoke about a friend during a hand massage activity, even though this seemed to create doubt for Morag when she could not remember. Morag and Rose's mutual attention and caring touch is illustrated in Figure 7.5 where meaning seemed to be co-created through synchronicity and empathy.

Figure 7.5 Vignette illustrating Morag and Rose sharing how they feel

"I forget a lot"

Morag and her daughter, Rose were sat opposite one another in Morag's bedroom with music playing in the background. Rose massaged Morag's hands on a small table and Rose chatted about someone they both knew, but Morag was unable to remember. The conversation changed and Rose joked with Morag. After the banter, Morag suddenly appeared lower in mood and, looking directly at her daughter, said in a sad tone of voice: "I forget a lot". Rose looked at her mum, stopped the massage, held her mum's hands, and replied: "I know, do you know what, I forget". Morag leaned in closer to her daughter. Rose continued: "I always need to write a list", and continuing to look at each other whilst holding hands, Morag said: "oh-aye". Her daughter added: "I write a list every day, my 'to-do' list". Morag leaned in, signalling she did not hear by slightly raising her head, so Rose repeated her comment. They looked at each other with sincere expressions, making eye contact and the moment felt poignant.

Rose reminisced about her mum's habit of writing lists, which often featured food and sweaters. Morag continued to look at her daughter whilst Rose massaged her hands and continued talking. Morag acknowledged Rose and reciprocated with a frequent, "ah-huh", smiling when her daughter chuckled. At one point, Morag leant back slightly, seeming to communicate she could not remember liking "custard pots", and Rose reassured her that she'd probably not had them for a while. Yet, Morag's concerns about her memory persisted: "I forget, hmm", so her daughter talked about an upcoming family wedding, presumably to distract her mum, and when she seemed to recognise a name, Morag joined in the conversation.

For two PwAD and their family members, laughter appeared to have a role in creating synchronicity. For example, Hamish (PwAD) and Susan (family) were talking near his bedroom window when Hamish pointed to the sky and commented on the birds. Susan responded by asking Hamish if the bird was his friend, resulting in them both laughing, with Hamish shaking his head humorously as Susan playfully pushed him on the shoulder. The meaning in this interaction seemed related to a father-daughter bond and in the recognition that her father seemed to find her comment surprising. Similarly, Fraser (PwAD) and his wife, Sorcha (family) laughed many times during their visit, but it was not always obvious why. Sorcha described meaning as being in the *sound* of their laughter because before Fraser moved into the care home, their relationship was fraught and laughter was absent. Sorcha felt the marriage was 'saved' because of the care home and described appreciating the presence of laughter and sharing such moments with Fraser. These examples suggest meaning can be amorphous, precarious and ephemeral, and represented in a range of emotions and their accompanying sounds.

7.3.1.2 People with advanced dementia and staff

Synchronous activities and interactions were also observed between PwAD and staff, facilitated through music. For example, Hamish (PwAD) and Anna (staff) sat next to one another during a live music event in the care home and Hamish appeared sad. Anna responded to him using movement rather than words, clapping her hands in his line of sight. Hamish looked at Anna's hands, apparently studying the tempo before waiting for the beat and starting to clap in time to the music, and Hamish, Anna and the music seemed to synchronise through the rhythm. This appeared meaningful because participation was co-created using a form of communication synchronised to Hamish's strengths. In a micro-reflection with Hamish and Anna, Anna believed the activity's significance lay in Hamish's ability to connect with others and his freedom to express himself.

Synchronicity also seemed achievable through humour between PwAD and staff, as illustrated in Figure 7.6. In this vignette, Fraser (PwAD) used his agency to initiate a joke during a conversation about a mural with Judy (staff). Even though the content of the joke was not clear, the act of telling it was expressed through Fraser's body, facial expressions, and tone of voice. Judy responded playfully to his humour, and the two appeared to align and synchronise through laughter. Meaning appeared to be co-created through play, which was facilitated by their interaction with each other and the physical environment.

Figure 7.6 Vignette illustrating Fraser joking with Judy

“You would Make It”

Walking arm-in-arm towards Fraser’s House, Judy pointed at one of the large paintings on the wall and spoke to Fraser about a boat, which featured in the picture: “The [boat name], look the [boat]”, running her fingers across it. Fraser instantly turned to look whilst Judy continued talking: “I know you’ve been on the [boat] haven’t you?”, and Fraser agreed, “aye”.

Judy narrated the painting, pointing to different parts as Fraser rubbed his face, appearing tired. Judy described some of the image: “that’s [name] rock as well, Fraser”. Without looking, Fraser replied: “yeah” and rubbed his face, appearing disinterested. However, as they continued walking, Fraser moved his hand out in front of his body, looked at Judy and said: “o-over the-”, moving his hand, appearing to gesture going over the rock. A smile came on his face, and Judy, who was looking at Fraser asked: “over the other side of the water was it, yeah?”. Fraser pointed at her and said: “you could, you would, you wo-”, then shook his finger close to her face, and with a serious but playful expression, joked: “you would make it”. He turned his head in a playful manner, closed his lips and moved them slightly to the side of his face. Fraser and I laughed and Judy responded jovially: “I would! ((Inaudible)) would make it, I’d make anything me ((inaudible))” and we all laughed together.

7.3.1.3 People with advanced dementia and myself

Despite only knowing limited information about each PwAD, synchronicity seemed to occur between PwAD and myself. On occasions, the information I received about PwAD from family members and staff did not fit my own understanding, requiring me to be led by instinct and *the way* PwAD used their bodies. For example, I was advised that Donald (PwAD) was disinterested if he walked away during an interaction, yet Figure 7.7 demonstrates how his verbal and embodied communication indicated a different meaning. This process required me to seek assent and dissent based on ‘feeling’ the situation, through which, Donald and I became ‘in sync’. The meaning in the activities and interactions which followed seemed multifaceted and appeared to be co-created when typical social rules were redefined. For Donald, meaning seemed related to self-initiating a role and a purpose, and in a social connection and shared experience.

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Figure 7.7 Vignette illustrating Donald inviting me on a walk

“Hold On”

Donald and I walked through the communal lounge and down the corridor, past bedrooms, magnolia walls and pictures of cityscapes and cars. Donald walked quickly and with purpose, breathing heavily as a result, requiring me to keep up with him.

During a short rest on the sofa at the end of the corridor, I was mid-sentence when Donald stood up and started walking towards the communal dining area. Although he had walked away, it did not feel like he was ending our interaction, so I asked: “d’you want me to come?”. He decisively and quickly replied, “aye”, so I walked beside him and he instructed me to “hold on”, whilst glancing down at our arms. Surprised, I enquired: “pardon?”, and he repeated: “hold on”, continuing to look at our arms. I realised this was an invitation to join him, so I accepted, linked arms with him, and thanked him as we strolled. He then led me on a tour of the care home and the gardens.

Feeling' the situation also seemed to support synchronicity with other PwAD. For instance, Hamish (PwAD) and I synchronised by listening and responding to one another as we danced to music at a tea dance. Rhythm and touch became a facilitator for expression and communication, requiring me to relinquish control over the movements so I could feel his agency and emotion through dance. Hamish expressed his feelings (non)verbally, for example by disclosing that he did not feel as skilled at dancing as he used to be, and by showing excitement about the next dance by rigorously moving our arms as we held hands and urging the music to hurry. Being in-sync appeared meaningful in and of itself and seemed to provide opportunities for further meaning through co-creativity, building trust and reciprocity.

7.3.1.4 People with advanced dementia and others

Hamish (PwAD) was the only PwAD observed to attend group activities and events. These activities appeared to offer opportunities for connection and synchronicity, for instance, during Lunch Club when Hamish began nodding his head in time to the beat of the background song. His actions encouraged others at the table to sing, and when I began dancing, Hamish mirrored me, and he moved his hands and arms gracefully to the music and sang. Initially he seemed uncertain as he echoed the words, but as the song progressed, his singing voice became louder, and he appeared more confident as everyone's voices and bodies merged with the music. Meaning appeared to be created through mutual synchronisation, connecting through movement, sound and music.

7.3.2 'Out of sync' activities and interactions

This section will explore activities and interactions that appeared 'out of sync' or asynchronous with PwAD, which seemed to alter and/or dilute meaning-making opportunities. This will firstly be described using examples involving PwAD and their family members through a jigsaw puzzle, and self-care. Next, asynchronous examples when eating and drinking will be described between PwAD and staff, followed by PwAD and myself. Lastly, an example will be presented during a group activity.

7.3.2.1 People with advanced dementia and their family members

'Out of sync' activities and interactions sometimes seemed to occur when family members failed to recognise that PwAD could change their preferences and interests, which could be further impacted by difficulties with communication. This was observed in Figure 7.8 when Amy (family) encouraged Donald (PwAD) to do a preloved jigsaw puzzle with her, but Donald dissented. Each jigsaw piece was small and similar in colour, making them hard to differentiate, hence this activity may have been asynchronous with Donald's current skills and

interests. The meaning in this activity and interaction seemed twofold. Firstly, Donald's choices did not seem to be acknowledged, and secondly, Donald's desires and his daughter's expectations appeared asynchronous, potentially highlighting an intended meaning and an implied meaning. Intended meanings were meanings that seemed to be pre-planned from the perspectives of family members, staff or myself and implied meanings appeared to be (co)created in the moment.

Figure 7.8 Vignette illustrating Donald showing disinterest in a jigsaw puzzle

“Dunno what you're saying!”

Donald and his daughter, Amy spent time together in his bedroom with the television on in the background. She sat next to him and commented: “you didn't do any more of the puzzle yesterday”. Donald turned his head to look at her but did not answer so she repeated herself twice and pointed in the direction of the puzzle. Donald looked towards the puzzle, with his tongue poking out and a confused facial expression. Amy asked, “no?”, but Donald looked at her and replied: “dunno what you're saying!”. She pulled her mask down, leant nearer to her dad, and repeated the question. He said “oh” whilst lifting his head and raising his eyebrows, followed by: “puzzle”, still looking at his daughter and giving eye contact.

Amy asked: “could you not be bothered doing it? Eh? Did you not want to do it?”, and maintaining eye contact, Donald replied: “aye”, his eyebrows raised. Amy invited Donald join her: “do you want to do it just now?” ((pause)) “do you want to do it?”, and Donald repeated: “aye”, raising his eyebrows and maintaining eye contact. Amy picked up the puzzle and sat back down next to her dad whilst telling me in a soft voice, “he started it yesterday well he did help me look out for wee bits but then he got fed up so, I just did it”, followed by a chuckle. She continued: “this used to be one of his favourite things to do but now he just forgets how to do them you know but he'll say he wants to do it... but then I bring it up and I end up doing them myself”.

Donald, who had been looking at himself in the iPad immediately diverted his eyes to the puzzle pieces when Amy emptied them onto the lid. Amy placed the pieces in front of Donald and asked: “right will we start with the green bits? Eh for the grass?” Donald started to take his hand from his pocket but stopped and looked at Amy. Amy asked him again, moving the pieces around in the box. Donald's eyes looked down at the jig-saw puzzle and his daughter pursued: “what d'you think?”. Donald did not answer so his daughter asked: “you gonna help me?”, and when he didn't answer again, she gently prodded him on his stomach and repeated the question. Donald replied “no” and Amy, said: “what?”, and he repeated “no”, so she asked why not. It was difficult to hear Donald's answer. Amy tried to clarify, and Donald looked at her and replied: “I'll leave it to you”. Amy confirmed, jokingly: “you're leaving it to me are you?” and started laughing, before adding: “well you're supposed to be helping me so you are ((pause)) will we leave your puzzle just now then if you don't want to do it eh?”. Donald looked down at the puzzle. His daughter asked again: “what do you want to do? Huh dad?”. Donald closed his eyes. His daughter turned to me, nodding, and whispered: “go to sleep”.

Inadvertently undermining a person's dignity and independence also seemed to create asynchronous activities/interactions. For example, during a visit from her daughter, Morag (PwAD) needed a tissue to wipe her nose so Rose (family) attempted to wipe Morag's nose for her. Morag demonstrated her agency by tilting her head away from Rose, stating that she could do it herself, and by reaching for the tissue. The meaning in this self-care activity and familial interaction appeared to be different for Morag and Rose. For Morag, the meaning seemed to be in maintaining her dignity and establishing her independence, whereas for Rose, the meaning seemed to be in caring for her mother. This suggests that meaning is complex and that both an intended meaning and an implied meaning are possible.

7.3.2.2 People with advanced dementia and staff

A similar interaction was observed during a tea-drinking activity with Fraser (PwAD) and Clarissa (staff). Although Fraser had initially reported wanting a drink, his eyes were closed when Clarissa brought the cup to his mouth, so Fraser moved his head away in surprise, suggesting the timing of the activity was asynchronous with Fraser's readiness. Clarissa then attempted to engage Fraser in a conversation by gently touching his arm and using his name, but he continued to close his eyes, so she stopped the interaction. Clarissa believed the meaning in the activity was in listening to Fraser's embodied communication, and in being led by him to maintain his independence. Meaning also appeared to be in acknowledging and respecting choice and in Fraser's freedom to change his mind.

Other asynchronous activities and interactions were observed when the person was inadvertently infantilised. For example, during Lunch Club, everyone at our table had finished their starter except for Hamish (PwAD). Judy (staff) encouraged Hamish to continue eating but instead Hamish pretended to eat the butter from the knife. When Judy acknowledged his actions, Hamish retorted that he did it on purpose because he knew Judy would comment on it. Although delivered with an element of play from both Hamish and Judy, Hamish's contention seemed to create meaning by asserting his autonomy and adulthood. This suggests that co-created meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may require reciprocity and shared control.

7.3.2.3 People with advanced dementia and myself

Asynchronous activities and interactions were also felt and observed between PwAD and myself. This sometimes appeared to happen when I did not understand enough about the person and/or their routine, for example, when I made Donald (PwAD) a cup of tea without providing biscuits. Donald responded by sitting back on the sofa, looking at me and saying: "nothing to eat, no?", gesturing food by lifting his hand towards his mouth. Similarly, Morag frequently asked me where my drink was if I made a cup of tea for her but not myself. Donald and Morag were able to use their agency and embodied skills to communicate the importance

of these simple acts. This suggests that meaning may be diluted when the person's preferences and values are unknown.

7.3.2.4 People with advanced dementia and others

Meaning could easily be missed during activities and interactions with PwAD, which seemed to create out-of-sync experiences. For example, when Hamish (PwAD) did not receive a response when he animatedly sang the phrase, "Get off my barrel" during Lunch Club after some group singing. Susan (family) previously explained how Hamish used to sing that line at the end of songs during her childhood to make her laugh, however, this appeared lost in the context of the care home. This 'out-of-sync' experience is illustrated in Figure 7.9 and demonstrates the importance of the relationship triad i.e. PwAD, family and staff when co-creating meaning. Additionally, it highlights the potential importance of the context during meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Figure 7.9 Vignette illustrating Hamish bringing a past memory to the present

7.3.3 Fluctuating synchronicity

This section will explore how some activities and interactions appeared to fluctuate between being 'in sync' and 'out of sync' with PwAD. This will firstly be presented using examples involving PwAD and their family members through music, and secondly demonstrating examples involving PwAD and staff when looking at a photograph album and engaging with a trainset. Finally, an example will be shared involving PwAD and myself when blowing bubbles.

7.3.3.1 People with advanced dementia and their family members

Meaning and synchronicity did not always seem present at the same time and could fluctuate on a moment-by-moment basis. For example, Figure 7.10, illustrates a scenario when Hamish (PwAD) and Susan (family) were dancing and Hamish's legs appeared tired. After seeming to be in-sync during their dance, Susan and Hamish's goals appeared to diverge, with Susan wanting Hamish to rest and Hamish wanting to continue dancing. Once Susan took the lead from Hamish, they appeared to re-synchronise. Meaning in this activity and interaction appeared to be in Hamish's enjoyment of the music and movement, in his autonomy, freedom and choices, and in his ability to communicate his wishes through his body and actions. This seemed to be supported by Susan who validated his choices with the safety of the chair in proximity.

Figure 7.10 Vignette illustrating Hamish directing Susan how to dance.

"You're supposed to go that side"

Susan encouraged her dad to rest after dancing because his legs seemed tired. She gently guided him back to the chair by holding his hands and dancing slowly backwards. Hamish showed his disinterest in sitting by moving his legs quickly in a shuffling motion whilst Susan patiently touched the chair and kindly gave verbal instructions for Hamish to sit.

Hamish moved towards the chair with the rhythmical guidance of his daughter, but remained standing, so Susan continued: "and if you back up... just a wee bit this way, that's it". Hamish spoke at the same time, asking: "what, what do you get?" with a mischievous look on his face, looking directly at Susan who recognised the humour: "and you sit down, what do you get for, for sitting down? ((Chuckle))". Another song played and Hamish bent his knees, dancing in unison to the beat whilst holding Susan's hands. Susan persevered: "do you want to take a wee seat?". Hamish looked down at the chair in acknowledgement, but continued dancing, so Susan exclaimed: "there's another on-, do you want another one?!". Hamish did not reply verbally, answering instead with his body by continuing to move his arms and bob up and down. Susan acknowledged his preference: "do you want to dance? You can dance if you want?". Looking at Susan briefly, Hamish seemed to say no by slightly shaking his head, quickly followed by pulling a humorous facial expression and quickly moving his feet.

Susan asked for clarification: "would you like to sit down or dance?", and he answered, "no (it's alright)" and turned around slightly, letting go of one of his daughter's hands as if he was about to reach for the arm of the chair. He then turned back to Susan, reached for her hand again and began directing her: "but then the, the thing is-", he advised, touching her shoulder, "you're supposed to go that side". Hamish physically guided Susan around to his other side and she excused herself: "oh right, I beg your pardon". Hamish and Susan then synchronised to the rhythm and one another through their dancing, swaying and moving of their arms whilst holding hands as the light shone through the window.

7.3.3.2 People with advanced dementia and staff

Fluctuating synchronicity was also observed between PwAD and staff. For instance, Morag (PwAD) and Katie (staff) looked at Morag's family photograph album together in Morag's bedroom. Katie attempted to turn the page using her hands and words, whilst Morag kept her finger on a particular photograph, demonstrating her interest, choice, agency and autonomy. In response, Katie slowed her pace, adapting herself by remaining on the image Morag was interested in, exploring it with her. Meaning seemed to be created through synchronicity and flexibility, facilitated by Katie and led by Morag's curiosity and interest.

In another example, Judy (staff) invited Donald (PwAD) to see a working train set after they had spent time together looking at football cards, and he assented by verbally agreeing and walking with her to the corridor where the train was operating. Initially, Donald, Judy and the train set appeared 'in sync' but Figure 7.11 shows how this changed. The meaning in this activity and interaction seemed related to Judy's ability to morph and adapt to Donald's interests in the moment.

Figure 7.11 Vignette illustrating Donald showing and losing interest

“Have you de-railed my train?”

Judy and Donald had been looking at some football photographs together when Judy said: “...I don't know if you're too tired now I've got a trainset out in the corridor there and I managed to get the engine working today it's a big, big trainset, you wanna come and see it?”. Donald turned his head slightly in Judy's direction. He raised his eyebrows and said “ah-huh”. Judy offered Donald assistance to stand and she guided him to the corridor, whilst telling him how good the trainset was.

As soon as we stepped into the corridor, the noise of the tracks could be heard. Donald and Judy walked up to the set, and we lifted the plastic cover of the transparent box as Judy spoke about the set and pointed out features. Donald watched the train intently as it went around the track and lifted his arm in preparation to catch the train as it came nearer. He placed his hand inside the container and held the train, stopping it from moving, and the sound of train slowed down before it stopped. Judy used humour to manage the situation: “I don't- has it stop- ((laughed)) have you de-railed my train? ((Laughed)) let's see if we can get it back on again, there it is”. She pointed to the train, carefully placed it back on the tracks and it continued to go round. Donald watched it intently.

We all stood around the trainset, watching the engine go around the tracks. I picked up a carriage and held it out for Donald who looked at it, took it and placed it down on the fake grass. He manoeuvred it around with his fingers so it faced a different way, then waited for the working engine to pass, and placed the carriage on the track, holding onto it for a while. The train engine came around again and Judy warned: “it's coming down”, and Donald moved his hand. The engine pushed into another carriage that was on the track which pushed the carriage Donald had been holding. All three pieces were now going round the track, driven by the train engine. Myself and Judy started laughing. Donald hovered his hand above the track and watched as the engine and carriages went round; they got half-way and became stuck. He then suddenly turned around and walked away from the trainset, towards reception. Judy asked Donald: “are you away?” and walked after him. Once Judy caught up with Donald, they linked arms and Judy started talking about the chocolate trolley they were approaching.

7.3.3.3 People with advanced dementia and myself

The context of the care home sometimes seemed to fragment meaning, resulting in fluctuating synchronicity, particularly in communal areas where more residents were present. Figure 7.12 illuminates how a one-to-one bubble-blowing activity could be both a facilitator and disruptor of meaning-making and synchronicity. For Morag (PwAD), bubble-blowing appeared to provide opportunities for experiencing positive emotions and employing embodied skills to achieve a small, spontaneous goal. For others, it seemed to have divergent meanings, including risk, discomfort, excitement and enjoyment. As a result, synchronicity seemed to fluctuate, causing meaning to change and (im)balance which created tension between residents.

Figure 7.12 Vignette illustrating Morag and I blowing bubbles

“If that goes in her eyes, they’ll be sore”

I sat opposite Morag in the communal lounge with six other residents. Four residents appeared to be sleeping, one was looking around and the other watched television. I introduced Morag to a bottle of bubbles I had found in the activities cupboard; this caught the attention of another resident who became excited. I asked Morag if she wanted me to blow some bubbles her way, and she waved at me, assenting.

As I prepared the wand by dipping it into the bottle, another resident showed concern using a firm tone: “I think you’d better put that away in case it spill [sic] all over somebody”. I thanked the resident for their consideration and reassured them that the bottle was just bubbles, however this created an unintentional odd dynamic as the excited resident cried: “just bubbles, oh don’t tell her that! (laughs)”. Morag turned her head to see who had spoken. I tried to bring the focus back to Morag by blowing her a bubble and pointing to it, and once spotted, she held out her arms to catch it, demonstrating agency and embodied skills. This continued within the landscape of the room, the undercurrents of different moods creating waves of diverse meanings.

Morag expressed her interest further by rolling her sleeves up, eyes focussed eagerly on the wand, awaiting the next bubble. The concerned resident expressed further apprehensiveness: “if that goes in her eyes, they’ll be sore” which set the excited resident off laughing, covering her mouth. This created a ripple as a further resident said: “shut up you, shut up!”.

The television continued in the background, blending with the intermittent sound of an alarm, amongst the emerging storm. Morag and I continued to blow bubbles whilst the excited resident stuck her tongue out towards the concerned resident, swinging her legs at the same time. This created further tension as the concerned resident retorted: “don’t be so cheeky, don’t put your tongue out at anybody”. The excited resident pointed her finger and retaliated: “don’t tell me”, prompting two staff members to enter the room and referee.

I asked Morag if she would prefer to be in her room, and she dissented so we continued with our conversation as the staff members wheeled the excited resident out of the lounge in her wheelchair. Morag and I continued with the bubble game, with Morag smiling, laughing, and catching the bubbles.

I offered Morag the wand and she reached out for it as the concerned resident stated: “she cannot grip”. Despite this comment and regardless of her arthritic fingers, Morag took the wand from me, put it to her lips and puckered them, but little air came out – she looked at me, appearing a little confused. I encouraged her to blow harder so she lifted her shoulders, took a deep breath, and blew hard into the bubble wand. This time, bubbles came out, I cried “yey!” and we laughed together. With the television mumbling and grumbling, Morag echoed: “give it a big puff” and we laughed again.

7.4 Theme Three: Enhancing participation and visibility (seeing, adapting and doing)

This theme focuses on how family members, staff and myself adapted ourselves, activities, interactions and the environment to match the skills and interests of PwAD to co-create meaning, resulting in the enhanced participation and visibility of PwAD. This theme builds on the previous theme by focussing on the practicalities and action of meaning-making rather than on an intangible phenomenon.

Participation in this thesis is defined as a non-linear and diverse co-creation of activities/interactions (Chilvers and Kearnes, 2020), including subtle engagement of any duration (Smith, Wolverton and Mountain, 2022). Visibility in this thesis is defined as a mutual process of recognition where PwAD and others 'see' and 'are seen', resulting from participation and action (Hatuka, 2022). These findings suggest that participation and visibility appeared interlinked and signified whether meaning in activities and interactions was created. This is important because it implies a cyclical development through which PwAD require acknowledgement and appreciation from others to enhance their participation in activities and interactions, and through participation, their existence is further illuminated, reinforced and validated, co-creating meaning.

This theme will firstly be presented by exploring how a family member adapted their approach to the person using the skills of PwAD. Next, a description of how staff adapted their approach to the person and enhanced the person's participation will be presented, including tailoring activities and interactions, flexible planning and structuring of activities and adapting the environment. Finally, an exploration of how I adapted my approach to the person will be presented, including tailoring activities and interactions, introducing new and old activities, learning with the person, and a technique called chaining. Chaining enables a person having difficulty with a task to actively participate by receiving practical support and/or prompting with parts of the task (McLay et al. 2021).

7.4.1 People with advanced dementia and their family members

Compared to staff, there were less instances of family members adapting themselves, activities and the environment. An approach used by Susan (family) was to use Hamish's (PwAD) retained skills and motivation using music and a game of catch. Susan appeared to have adapted the game, for example by using a soft toy rather than a ball to make it easier for Hamish to catch, by clapping to prompt him to throw the cat, and by counting their successful catches to celebrate achievements. This approach seemed to enhance Hamish's concentration and motivation, as illustrated in Figure 7.13. In this instance, the meaning seemed to be in opportunities for fun, playfulness and the application of embodied skills.

Figure 7.13 Vignette illustrating Hamish and Susan playing cards

"I had trouble with it"

Hamish and his daughter, Susan played catch with a small, soft, toy cat. They were sat opposite each other in Hamish's room and Susan counted each time they caught the cat. If they dropped it, she started again from number one. Hamish was able to throw and catch using one hand, leaning slightly forward with an intense look of concentration on his face, his mouth open. Hamish dropped the cat and pulled a funny face, then shook his finger at it as if playfully blaming it. After a few goes, Hamish mischievously tricked Susan by pretending to throw the cat but he kept hold of it for a few seconds before actually throwing it. She fell for the trick and attempted to catch the cat, and we all laughed. Susan responded: "you had me go over there, and then [moved in the direction she described]", and Hamish replied: "I had trouble with it", joking.

Susan lifted the cat in the air and Hamish prepared himself to catch it by raising his arm, and Susan asked: "right, you ready?"; Hamish signalled his readiness by shaking his hands in front of his torso. Susan threw the cat towards him, and he caught it with his arms. He spanked the cat and said: "I'm waiting for a ((inaudible)) pffft" and punched the air in front of him like a character in a cartoon, his nose slightly screwed up.

7.4.2 People with advanced dementia and staff

All staff participants – particularly the Activity Assistants – adapted activities and interactions by tailoring them to each PwAD, using information about their life history, preferences, interests and current capabilities. Among staff participants, there seemed to be variation in approaches, for example, Judy (staff) reported using information about the person to help her plan activities and maintain the flow during activities and interactions and Harry (staff) described using this information preserve personhood and to stimulate engagement and feelings of joy. Herbert (staff) was observed directly applying key information during an interaction with Donald (PwAD) when he talked about Donald's favourite football team, co-creating a reciprocal dialogue. The meaning in adapting activities and interactions when applying key information seemed to lie in confirming the person and their life history and in actively involving PwAD.

Some staff used key information about PwAD to create a flexible structure through which activities and interactions took place. For example, Katie (staff) had originally planned a colouring-in activity with Morag (PwAD) because Morag had previously enjoyed this activity in a group setting. However, when Katie took the materials into Morag's room, Morag seemed disorientated and anxious. In response, Katie changed the planned activity and played Morag's favourite music, held her hand and spoke to her until she seemed calmer. Katie then invited Morag to look at Morag's photograph album, using her knowledge of Morag to create a shared narrative, as illustrated in Figure 7.14. Katie felt meaning was co-created through mutual validation when Morag and Katie's existence was illuminated, and when Morag was guided through her confusion.

Figure 7.14 Vignette illustrating Morag and Katie sharing memories

“So did I!”

Morag and Katie sat together looking at Morag’s photograph album in Morag’s room. Morag studied one of the photographs, with one finger pointing to the picture and the other hand curled over her lip.

Katie gently tapped Morag’s hand and read out some names, including the name of a company that Morag used to work for. Morag recognised this: “oh. Uh. I worked in there” and Katie replied, “so did I”. Morag turned her head quickly away from the album, towards Katie and said in an amazed tone: “did you?”. Katie continued: “ah huh, but not at the same time. Do you remember what block you worked in?”, and Morag answered: “K-Block”, and Katie exclaimed: “so did I!”. Morag turned towards Katie with her eyebrows raised and Katie continued: “they used to call it [name of block], remember that?”, Morag chuckled and nodded, her finger curled on her lips.

Katie asked: “were you an Inspectress?”, Morag nodded in agreement: “ah-huh [chuckled]”, and Katie remarked: “you’ll never believe it, so was I”. Morag laughed, turned to look at me, then looked back at Katie and said: “oh that is, that’s good”.

Meaning appeared to be co-created when staff skills were combined with the abilities, interests and preferences of PwAD because this partnership seemed to enhance the person's choices and enable participation in activities and interactions. All staff described a need for flexibility when creating meaning in activities and interactions to match the person's fluctuating needs and abilities. For instance, Clarissa (staff) described a 'trial and error' approach to activities and interactions. She also shared how she and other staff would try to evoke a pleasant, enjoyable dining experience by sitting next to a PwAD when assisting them to eat and drink rather than standing over them, and how PwAD would be given plenty of time when dining to match their pace and avoid them feeling rushed. Judy (staff) discussed how she approached activities and interactions with PwAD with an 'open mind' by reducing the expectations placed upon PwAD. She felt that if expectations were too high, the person may not be able to participate and may withdraw. Herbert (staff) reported spending time with the person to understand their experiences, adapting himself accordingly and Katie (staff) described how she adjusted her approach to activities and interactions depending on the type of dementia and the individual. These examples appeared to enhance the participation and visibility of PwAD to co-create meaning.

Two staff members described how they adapted activities and interactions using a technique similar to chaining. Harry (staff) described how he and Morag (PwAD) crafted a conversation together when he started a conversation using a topic Morag was interested in, and how he was then led by Morag to co-create an interaction. Similarly, when interacting with PwAD, Judy (staff) would talk about a topic of interest to the person before asking them a question about the information she had just provided because she felt this offered the person a way of participating. She believed participation created meaning and stimulated positive emotions for PwAD. These examples imply meaning could be co-created through active participation when activities/interactions were adapted to suit the person's interests.

Some staff were observed pacing activities and interactions for PwAD, for example, when activities were slowed down or sped up. Katie (staff) used eye contact, a calming voice and slow touch when Morag (PwAD) was anxious, and Judy (staff) catered for Donald's (PwAD) quickly fluctuating interests by completing three activities in one session. Judy believed the length of an activity was not important for meaning-making, but that stimulation through participation was important to maintain the person's skills for as long as possible. These examples imply meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD need to be tailored to match the person's pace to enhance participation and independence using a mindful, synchronised approach, for which the outcome(s) may be validation and companionship.

Sometimes, participation was subtle and/or socially atypical. For instance, Fraser (PwAD) sat next to Clarissa (staff) appearing to sleep whilst she and I reflected on the eating and drinking activity/interaction. Clarissa felt meaning could have been enhanced if Fraser was more alert, but how it was difficult to achieve because each day was different. At this point, with his eyes remaining shut, Fraser interjected with words and Clarissa explained we were talking about him. Fraser responded by stating he knew he was the topic of the conversation and chuckled. This seemed meaningful for many reasons. Firstly, this scenario offers an alternative perspective to the existing literature which assumes that in this type of situation, PwAD are bored, sleeping or 'doing nothing' (for example, Ellis and Astelle, 2017; Gebhard and Frank, 2024). Secondly, it suggests PwAD may communicate in a socially atypical way, potentially requiring social expectations and rules to be reimaged. Lastly, despite having his eyes closed, Fraser demonstrated a desire to remain socially involved and used agency to enhance his own visibility.

Fraser's (PwAD) visibility was highlighted a second time during an activity with a different staff member. Figure 7.15 captures how a photograph of Fraser sparked an interaction with Judy (staff) and how his participation was facilitated and encouraged when Judy adapted her communication style to match his. Meaning seemed related to re-establishing and validating Fraser's presence and visibility towards himself and to others using humour and animated communication.

Figure 7.15 Vignette illustrating Fraser telling Judy about his teeth

“Teeth”

We stood in the main reception of the care home in front of a display wall which showcased photographs of residents eating a fish supper. Intermittent and intrusive beeping sounds and voices filled the corridor as Judy and Fraser stood side-by-side with Fraser’s arm resting through Judy’s.

Fraser looked off to the side with a smile when Judy announced: “right Fraser”, touching his hand and pointing to a photograph: “have a look”. The moment Fraser heard his name, his eyes lifted until he was looking directly at the photograph. Judy asked: “who’s this?”, still pointing at his image, “is that you there?”.

Fraser lifted his arm, turned towards her, and opened his mouth, saying “my”, his mouth wide as he pointed to his teeth. Judy looked at Fraser, round-eyed and replied, “oh the teeth, is it?” and pointed to her own mouth. Looking directly at Judy, Fraser answered, “aye my tooth ((inaudible))”, and Judy responded: “is it not aha?”, and she pointed to the photograph again. Fraser added: “aye well it’s a, you get, (feel) that”. He placed his finger onto his front teeth and felt them whilst looking at the picture of himself.

Judy looked carefully at Fraser’s teeth whilst he was still touching them, and Fraser responded: “(they’ll be water, water)”, so Judy enquired: “did you have false teeth in there?”. Fraser reacted quickly and clearly: “aye” and blinked purposefully, so Judy asked: “have you lost them?”. After a short pause, Fraser replied: “aye”. Judy joked: “that’s what happens isn’t it? (Laughs)” and Fraser repeated his purposeful eye blink, followed by a turn of his head with his eyes still closed, mouth open. He then opened his eyes wide, appearing to communicate ‘yes’ with humour. Judy jested: “You end up leaving them somewhere or somebody else is wearing them (laughs)”.

On one occasion, enhancing the visibility of PwAD did not elicit a positive response, for example, when Morag did not like the image of herself in the iPad, as described in Section 5.5.2.2. Although Morag (PwAD) reacted in this way, there still appeared to be meaning in the activity and interaction because Morag engaged in a conversation with Katie (staff). It also suggested Morag had pride in her appearance and was aware of how others saw her, potentially reinforcing her visibility. Katie emphasised how participating in activities and interactions confirmed to Morag that she still existed in the world, that she was alive. Katie believed this occurred because Morag was mutually seen and acknowledged and was an active agent in the interaction rather than a passive observer. Katie felt that simply spending time with Morag was meaningful because it communicated to Morag that she was worth spending time with and made Morag feel important, potentially enhancing her sense of self and self-esteem.

Multisensory activities appeared to enhance the participation of PwAD more than unisensory activities. For example, Judy (staff) described how Donald's (PwAD) daughter, Amy had brought in one of his trainsets, but that Donald had not shown any interest because the train was kept in its packaging, restricting the activity to the visual sense. The reasons why the trainset was not taken out of its packaging were not clear. In contrast, Judy felt that all the senses were stimulated when the trainset was in working order and larger in scale, providing an opportunity for Donald to touch and interact with it and create meaning through participation. This suggests that multisensory activities and interactions may offer more opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Some staff members felt that the physical and social environment were important when creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, and this appeared linked to enhancing participation. Harry (staff) believed that talking to Morag (PwAD) in the garden was stimulating and could elicit her wellbeing and Judy (staff) felt that calm and quiet spaces with no interruptions were important to make a connection with and engage PwAD. Katie (staff) believed the environment needed to be matched to the activity and the person's abilities to create meaning and discussed the importance of the atmosphere and one-to-one support to enhance participation. This suggests that the physical and social environment are an important factor when co-creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD to maximise participation.

7.4.3 People with advanced dementia and myself

I adapted activities and interactions to enhance the participation of PwAD and co-create meaning, informed by my learning during the study and underpinned by my clinical background. For example, Donald (PwAD) and I co-created a game of Boules which evolved into a game of football, as illustrated in Figure 7.16. In this instance, I used my limited knowledge of Donald's previous interests in Boules and his current strengths to offer him choices and use embodied skills. Meaning in this activity/interaction appeared related to having fun, participating in an easily accessible game that Donald (PwAD) previously enjoyed, and companionship.

Figure 7.16 Vignette illustrating Donald reinventing a game of Boules

I also introduced new activities with PwAD because in line with my methodology, I did not want to restrict activities to the past or assume PwAD only liked previously enjoyed activities. Figure 7.17 illustrates a drumming activity with Morag (PwAD) and myself. As far as I was aware, Morag had not played drums before, which combined with my own limited experience, meant we were learning together and from each other. Meaning in this activity and interaction appeared to be co-created and linked to mutual encouragement, reciprocity, enjoyment and 'doing' together. Choice also seemed to provide opportunities for participation, which was particularly pertinent because Morag (PwAD) mobilised in an attendant wheelchair and relied on others to move her.

Figure 7.17 Vignette illustrating Morag and I drumming

Pacing an activity and interaction was also a consideration when enhancing participation to enhance opportunities for synchronicity. I became aware of and developed the skill of pacing during the study by observing the actions of PwAD and how family and staff interacted with them, and by watching the recorded data. These processes enabled me to see when I moved/spoke too slow/fast or introduced topics, objects or activities too slowly/quickly. This was particularly pertinent during an eating and drinking activity with Fraser (PwAD) and a walking activity with Donald (PwAD). These activities highlighted how a mindful, reflexive approach enabled me to synchronise with PwAD to enhance their participation. This suggests meaning may be enhanced when others exercise self-awareness to adapt themselves, activities and interactions to match the pace of PwAD.

Adapting activities also seemed to require flexibility of others because the intended meaning did not necessarily match the implied meaning. For example, Fraser's (PwAD) wife informed me he used to enjoy learning new words and reading, so I printed singular words in large, bold, black text on yellow paper, aiming to use his current abilities to enhance his participation. I had intended the words to be distributed around the house and, if Fraser assented, for he and I to find them and talk about them. However, when I invited him to join me, Fraser dissented by staying seated. He then repurposed the activity by independently reading some of the words aloud, from which reciprocal, conversations were co-created. Altering the activity seemed to enhance the meaning because Fraser initiated this change himself, matching the activity to his current interest and preferences which situated him as an active participant.

7.5 Theme Four: Embodying and identifying meaning (feeling, looking, and listening)

This theme specifically focuses on how meaning was embodied, recognised and identified through the bodies, emotions, sounds and sometimes words of PwAD, and how this could be enhanced and reciprocated by others. Although communication has been a common thread in the previous themes, this theme isolates communicative acts to reveal and better understand a repertoire of postverbal and embodied communication that may help to recognise meaning. As a reminder, embodiment is a way of making meaning through bodily expression to communicate and interact with other bodies (Thanem and Knights, 2019), which are performed and negotiated within societies (Goffman, 1959). Post-verbal communication can include embodiment, with a particular focus on how PwAD relate to others and objects without the typical context of words, although some words may still be used (Quinn, Blandon and Batson, 2021).

This theme will firstly be presented by exploring how PwAD communicated with family members using actions, facial expressions and movement. Secondly, this theme will share how staff used observations of PwAD to understand embodied communication in PwAD, and how PwAD and a staff member communicated through an interactive table activity. Lastly, this theme offers examples of embodied communication between PwAD and myself through an interactive robot, drumming, singing, poignant moments, and assumptions and miscommunications.

7.5.1 Communication between people with advanced dementia and their family members

PwAD seemed to express their preferences through embodied and postverbal communication, which appeared to guide family members during visits. For example, Donald (PwAD) was able to show Amy (family) he wanted some chocolate by intensely following her hand with his eyes as she picked up a packet. When Amy offered him a chocolate, Donald responded by moving his mouth with eagerness, removing his hand from his pocket, and popping a chocolate in his mouth. A similar interaction occurred when Sorcha (family) offered Fraser (PwAD) a biscuit. He reacted by quickly holding out his hand and touching the cookie whilst moving his mouth and swallowing in anticipation of eating it. Sorcha asked Fraser if she could halve the cookie, but Fraser appeared reluctant when he held onto the cookie with an indignant facial expression. When the biscuit was halved, Fraser sat upright, raised his eyebrows, tightened his lips, and waddled from side to side in his chair, as if light-heartedly mocking his wife. These scenarios suggest meaning is multi-dimensional. Amy and Sorcha both described using food to stimulate PwAD as an alternative to sleeping, and Sorcha found food to provide an opportunity for sharing something enjoyable with her husband. Additionally, meaning appears to be in the expression of the body to communicate feelings and preferences, potentially amplifying the voices of PwAD and reinstating their autonomy.

Embodied communication could also be expressed through movement and dance, as illustrated in Figure 7.18. The vignette shows how Hamish (PwAD) conveyed his emotions to Susan (family) using his body and words, appearing to co-create meaning through a wide-ranging repertoire of fluid movements. This was suggested through Hamish's purposeful, accentuated movements and his singing, which appeared to provide a platform for expression. This was reciprocated by Susan and they communicated through their bodies to create a shared language.

Figure 7.18 Vignette illustrating Hamish and Susan dancing

"I'm gonna take it heavier"

Susan was visiting her dad, Hamish in his bedroom and they were dancing together to music, as they often did. Susan held her dad's hand up in the air and she danced underneath it, swapping arms to repeat the movement.

Sensing her dad's legs were becoming tired, Susan encouraged him to sit down, guiding him to his chair using familiar dance steps. Despite great efforts and encouragement from her to sit and rest, Hamish refused and continued twirling his hand gracefully in time to the Gaelic music, adding an occasional flick to accentuate particulars. We all started laughing and using his finger to point downwards, Hamish told us: "it's while you're down there and I'm up here getting on", and once Susan had repeated what he said, she explained she was worried his legs were becoming tired. Hamish verbally responded, but it was difficult to understand his words, and he started dancing with his hands.

Susan gave up trying to encourage her dad to sit down, joining in by dancing instead. Hamish invited me to join in, so I accepted by moving my arms, and Susan commented: "beautiful isn't it, we can just all enjoy". Susan removed her supporting hand from her dad's arm so she could freely move to the rhythm, and Hamish continued dancing. With his arms elegantly flowing in a considered manner, he started singing.

The mood of the music suddenly changed. Hamish mirrored and expressed the newly dramatic sounds through words and actions: "I'm going to take it heavier", moving his arm in a circular motion. Susan repeated his words and encouraged him, then observed: "it's like the music's just flowing". When asked about the meaning in the activity, Susan said: "it's beautiful" and Hamish continued dancing.

7.5.2 Understanding embodied communication between people with advanced dementia and staff

Some staff described actively observing the person's body, facial expressions and reactions for signs of meaning during activities and interactions. For example, Katie (staff) reported using her intuition and self-awareness to study Morag's (PwAD) face for signs of meaning, Herbert (staff) 'read' the person's body language for signs of participation and engagement, and Judy (staff) noted Fraser's laughter as a sign of meaning in the moment. Staff members appeared to gain insight into how meaning was expressed and recognised in PwAD by observing and considering the individual's responses. This is important because it is unlikely PwAD will have the verbal skills to state whether an activity and interaction was meaningful, therefore, a nuanced and adapted form of listening appears to be required from others to notice and understand meaning.

This type of listening was observed between Fraser (PwAD) and Judy (staff) during an interactive table activity. Fraser's embodied and postverbal communication seemed to convey disinterest in the interactive table but interest in looking through the window - actions which were mirrored by Judy. Meaning appeared to be co-created when looking through the window was validated as a potentially meaningful activity, and when Fraser's choices and autonomy were acknowledged and respected by Judy.

Although watching the person's body and facial expressions for signs of meaning was important, all PwAD in this study could accompany these acts with words. Sometimes the words did not match the context, but at other times, the words appropriately complemented facial expressions and vice-versa, as represented in an interaction between Donald (PwAD) and Herbert (staff). Donald was a quiet man and his facial expressions were often subtle, possibly because he also lived with Parkinson's Disease. He often used his body to express himself and demonstrate his preferences, for example, by banging on a door to communicate he wanted to come in from the garden. Occasionally, Donald was able to converse using facial expressions and more than a few words. On one occasion, Donald and Herbert engaged in what they termed 'guy chat', as represented in Figure 7.19 which shows how Herbert's observations and responses to Donald's expressions and words, his contribution was acknowledged and meaning appeared to be created through participation, being valued and reciprocity.

Figure 7.19 Vignette illustrating Donald and Herbert chatting

7.5.3 Embodied communication between people with advanced dementia and myself

Fraser's wife had informed me Fraser (PwAD) used to enjoy sitting in his shed with his cats on his lap, which he found calming. The care home had robotic cats, so I invited him to stroke one of them to see how he responded. Figure 7.20 illustrates how Fraser engaged with the cat using embodied and postverbal communication. Fraser's animated and reciprocal responses combined with his look of adoration towards the cat suggested he was enjoying the interaction. The meaning in this activity appeared to be in the ease and comfort of the interactions between Fraser and the cat, perhaps offering him a familiar, enjoyable experience.

Figure 7.20 Vignette illustrating Fraser and the robotic cat

“What a good idea”

Fraser was in the communal lounge when I introduced a robotic cat to him. I asked, “What d’you think, Fraser?”. He looked at the cat and replied: “oh I love them”, so I queried if he would like to hold it. He responded in a happy tone of voice, “it doesn’t matter”. I placed the cat on his knee and stroked its head, then Fraser rested his hand on the cat’s body and said: “what a good idea ((inaudible))”.

The cat meowed in a sad tone, and Fraser responded immediately, looking at me with a mixed expression of surprise, pleasure and adoration, saying: “Oh-oh-oh-a-ee-ee”, and we laughed together.

Fraser became distracted by the television, so I asked: “can you hear it, Fraser?”, gently touching his arm, “it just went ‘meow’”. He looked at me, eyebrows raised and an expression of disbelief; I laughed in response, and he smiled.

The cat twitched its ear, purred, and moved its head. Fraser noticed and quickly looked down to look at the cat, saying: “oh!”, and the cat meowed again.

I asked Fraser how he was and the cat spontaneously miaowed. Fraser looked at me, pointed to the cat, repeatedly shook his finger towards the cat, smiled, then nodded his head once in a purposeful manner.

Other objects could create opportunities for the person to use embodied and postverbal communication. For example, when drumming with Morag (PwAD), I asked if she wanted to continue playing or whether she wanted to finish. Morag did not reply using words, but continued to play, communicating her preference through her actions and perhaps indicating her absorption in the activity. After a short while, she stopped and looked at me with a huge, warm smile. Words were not required as Morag answered my question using her body and agency, which invited me to re-join the activity. Meaning seemed to lie in the non-verbal dialogue we co-created through continual joint action and nuanced listening, facilitated by the sounds of the drum. On other occasions, Morag would sing, *'I like a nice cup of tea in the morning'* with accompanying movements, such as moving her finger in time to the rhythm. Once when I joined in, we incorrectly sang the words, and Morag humorously and verbally insisted: "we need to get it right", displaying her agency, preferences and interpersonal skills.

On some occasions, the person's tone of voice seemed to indicate their feelings about a particular subject, and activities and interactions could offer opportunities for PwAD to share these emotions. For example, during our food-tasting activity, Fraser (PwAD) frowned at one point and his tone of voice saddened as he verbalised various sentences, as shown in Figure 7.21. Although the sentences were fragmented, his tone of voice, sighs, pauses and facial expressions created a reflective moment when he seemed aware he lived with dementia. This was a poignant moment where I found myself feeling his words rather than trying to make sense of the context.

Figure 7.21 Vignette illustrating Fraser seeming sad

“A dementia”

Fraser and I sat together trying different foods and drinks in the communal lounge. The television was on in the background. I had just apologised to Fraser because I had offered him another food item to try when he was still eating something else and he accepted my apology by telling me, “No, no it’s alright” in a sincere tone of voice.

Suddenly, Fraser looked down and appeared sad. The atmosphere changed and felt heavy. He frowned and spoke with a reflective tone in his voice: “you’re quite right I mean I wished I was a, I wish hadn’t had to ((sigh)) ((pause)) and it’s just quite wet”. I reached forward, placed my hand on his and enquired: “it’s just quite?”. Fraser replied, “yes, yeah that’s good, I kinda did it I don’t know if I told you”, and I added, “ok”. He then remarked: “Oh dear”, so I reassured him, and he said: “oh it’s a shame...well it’s a shame, shame, shame, shame, you’ve been trying to make a trying to to have a erh a d-, a d-, a demen-, a dementia oh God knows where”. I asked: “a dementia?” and he repeated: “dementia (inaudible) you see”. I empathised and validated his experience and he chuckled, lifted the cheese he was holding to his mouth and said: “oh sorry”. He pointed to something behind me with his eyebrows raised, so I turned round to look. Fraser added: “yep” and looked directly at me, nodded, then slowly looked to the side with a reflective expression and ate his cheese. There was a long silence.

A similar situation happened during the Tea Dance with Hamish (PwAD) when I asked if he was ok. He too expressed sadness through the flat tone of his voice, staccato, pauses and heavy facial expression. After a short while, he was able to coherently tell me his legs were hurting, so we sought a seat. These examples felt emotional and heartfelt to me as a participant-observer and seemed the case for PwD, as expressed through the emotion in their voices. Meaning appeared to be co-created through the interaction itself, which was reflective expressive and validating, and through shared emotion.

Sometimes embodied and postverbal communication could be misinterpreted. For example, during an interaction between Donald (PwAD) and I, he began yawning. In response, I said I would leave soon but after a few moments, Donald turned to look at me and asked if I was “fed up now”, implying he thought I was bored with his company rather than my intention to acknowledge his fatigue. Similarly, Fraser (PwAD) appeared to be getting sleepy during an interaction, so I gently touched his arm and asked him if he wanted to be alone. He answered,

'no' with a firm tone and serious but sincere facial expression, shook his head slightly, then firmly told me he wanted me to stay. These situations are important because assumptions may reduce or limit meaning-making opportunities between PwAD and their families, and/or staff, particularly if typical societal expectations or assumptions are applied.

7.6 Summary and key learning

This chapter explored how everyday experiences of meaning in activities and interactions could be created with PwAD, their family members and staff. Additionally, it examined how the voices of PwAD could be included in research using embodied, flexible and creative methods.

Key learning from the data suggests meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD can be enhanced through flexible approaches, everyday creativity and opportunities in the social and physical environment. PwAD may make their own opportunities to (co)create meaning in activities and interactions in response to others, objects and/or the environment. Meaning may also be co-created when PwAD are offered choices to participate in (un)structured or (un)planned activities/interactions that match their skills and current interests, however opportunities for meaning may be stalled by the progression of dementia and misfitting or clashing activities, approaches and environments. Participation in activities and interactions by PwAD may be (in)direct, (un)typical, missed or misinterpreted, resulting in meaning also being overlooked. For example, PwAD may close their eyes during a conversation or walk away, but this may not necessarily signify dissent. Instead, this may be a way for the person to remain involved or an invitation for others to join the person in an activity/interaction. Participation may also be more obvious, for instance, through movement, action, touch and facial expressions, however these may still be misinterpreted by others. Therefore, participation, activities/interactions and meaning in activities and interactions may be invisible if typical social rules and expectations are applied. Participation, however subtle or momentary, may provide mutual validation which may enhance and confirm the existence of PwAD to themselves and others, co-creating further meaning.

Other key learning includes meaning appearing to be enhanced and co-created when PwAD, families/staff, activities/interactions, context and the physical and social environment are adapted and/or synchronised. The timing of activities/interactions and the pace at which they are co-created may enhance, interrupt or impede meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD and opportunities for synchronicity.

PwAD may demonstrate curiosity through their body, which also appears to signal the presence of meaning and be meaningful in and of itself. Closely attending and responding to

the movement, in(action), gestures, expression, sounds and perhaps words of PwAD may validate embodied, post-verbal communication and establish a shared language.

These findings provide the field with new insights, highlighting the everyday in a care home setting as being rich with opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, which perhaps requires others to notice and develop an appreciation of the mundane. Additionally, these findings suggest that social communication and expectations need to be collaboratively reimagined so that PwAD, their participation and the activities and interactions they find meaningful are visible. This learning provides the context for the final phase of the study where preliminary findings were actively reviewed and learning and change was established and shared in collaboration with PwAD, family members and staff.

Chapter 8 : Findings - Phase Three

8.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings from Phase Three of the Action Research (AR) cycle. As previously discussed, the objectives were revised to accommodate pandemic restrictions, time constraints and family and staff holiday/leave. This chapter is discussed according to the revised objectives, which were firstly to collaboratively and actively review, deepen and develop an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia (PwAD), family members and staff, and secondly to amalgamate and share learning resulting from the study. Data collection methods included one workshop with four family members and four staff, and one-to-one reflections with three PwAD, one family member and three staff. Since some participants were unavailable during this phase, it is possible that some participant voices are underrepresented in these findings. This phase was the first time family members and staff were able to mix since the onset of COVID-19. This was an important methodological highlight because until this time the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions had not been collaboratively understood, thus learning had been disconnected between participant groups.

This phase focussed on taking early findings back to the participants to inform discussion, critical reflection and identify learning through a workshop and individual reflections. Critical reflection is identified as a stage of learning which produces new knowledge and/or refines what is already known, that is established through enhanced self-awareness and collaboration (Asfeldt, Hvenegaard, Purc-Stephenson, 2018; Morris, 2020). As expected, given the pragmatist ontology of this study, some (dis)agreement, negotiation, tensions and challenges are evident. Learning was recognised by a shift in thinking and/or action regarding the application of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD (Stringer and Aragon, 2021).

These findings are presented using quotations to illustrate the richness and brevity of discussions (Eldh, Arestedt and Bertero, 2020), and vignettes to portray embodied communication and enhance the voices of PwAD, as previously justified. Four themes were identified using the analytic method, 'Coding and Categorising' (Stringer and Aragon, 2021). The themes are as follows: 1) 'Making sense of living with advanced dementia'; 2) 'Seeing the person as an active agent'; 3) 'Reframing meaning in activities and interactions'; and 4) 'Moving forward'.

8.2 Theme One: Making sense of living with advanced dementia

This theme explores the relationship between meaning-making and how family members and staff perceived and empathised with PwAD. It is firstly presented by describing how making sense of individual experiences of living with advanced dementia could offer insights for meaning-making and how empathy, acceptance and change impacted meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Sense-making was recognised in this study when participants seemed to be searching for information to co(create) and assemble a past-present understanding of the PwAD. This appeared to be a process concerned with making and unmaking sense of the experiences of PwAD, drawing upon differing perspectives and contexts to (co)create meaning and organise chaos (Dervin, Foreman-Wernet and Lauterbach, 2003 p.7).

Some staff described how living with dementia affected individuals differently depending on the type of dementia and the stage, suggesting different approaches are required to enhance meaning in activities and interactions. For example, Anna (staff) related the previous findings of PwAD living in a different reality to the type of dementia, describing people with Alzheimer's Disease as living in the past and people with Frontotemporal Dementia having altered behaviour. Harry (staff) believed that Fraser (PwAD) could access his past by imagining he was in his living room or garden rather than the care home, and Katie (staff) reinforced her belief that people living with different stages of dementia required tailored approaches i.e. PwAD requiring one-to-one activities/interactions rather than group alternatives. These examples suggest meaning in activities and interactions may be enhanced if they are tailored to the person, their reality in the moment, and the type and stage of dementia they live with.

The types of dementia symptoms and how these fluctuated were also discussed between family members and staff, which seemed to enhance family members' understanding of the person's experiences of living with dementia. Discussions provided opportunities for staff and family members to share knowledge, and for family members to share/compare experiences with staff and peers; this appeared to facilitate a sense-making exercise. For instance, Clarissa (staff) and Amy (family) described how the memory of PwAD may fluctuate on a momentary or daily basis, establishing that PwAD may never recall certain experiences. Others discussed the difficulty PwAD had in recognising themselves and/or others, and this discourse seemed to lead to an exploration of reality:

Sorcha (family): *"See Fraser doesn't recognise himself in any photographs that's in his room if I say you know- 'no, that's not me'"*

Katie (staff): *"Is it how he looks just now or is it how he was looking when he was young or?"*

Sorcha: *"That's what I don't know"*

Judy (staff): *"If people look in the mirror like they don't recognise themselves at all I mean ((laughs))"*

Katie: *"Yeah they don't know ((inaudible)) because I've held a mirror up before I mean even with your mum [looks at Rose (family)] I've held a mirror up, she's like 'who's that?', 'that's you', 'God I'm old'"*

((General laughter))

Katie: *"You know what I mean but"*

Rose: *"Or that's my mother"*

Judy: *"That's my mother"*

Harry (staff): *"... A lot of the gentleman when you say 'oh who's that?' 'oh that's my father' (you just let it go) ((inaudible))"*

Judy: *"The thing is if they're living in the past then they're remembering themselves being the past ((inaudible))"*

Katie: *"It's when you ask their age 'what age are you?' ((inaudible)) say twenty-nine"*

Sorcha: *"Even if they don't look like one another they'll still ((inaudible)) say"*

Harry: *"Well that's my father', aye honestly if they're not distressed I just let it"*

Judy: *"That's right"*

Harry: *"(That's right) 'that's your father' (I go) 'you look a lot alike, like' there's wee prompts but if they don't then they're just 'oh right, that's fine, that's your dad'"*

Sorcha: *"Why upset somebody?"*

Amy (family): *"My dad always thought there was somebody else who he'd called up, ((inaudible)) some John and he'd sit and talk to them? Like sit on his bed and actually talk to the... Dressing table mirror? And he'd be having a conversation with this guy John and it's himself, I'd go 'but ah dad, dad it's, it's you look it's me, there's me and you' and he'd be like that kind looking and he'd be like that 'no' and then look away and he'd be still talking to this John"*

These discussions revealed different perspectives of, and approaches towards PwAD. Although humour was used, this did not seem intended as derogatory, rather it appeared to ease discussions and create cohesiveness amongst the group. The dialogues between family and staff also seemed to facilitate a sense-making process from which social narratives and shared experiences were co-created.

Opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD appeared to be impacted by the viewpoints of staff and family members because their perspectives seemed to affect their actions towards PwAD. For instance, Katie (staff) and Susan (family) discussed how

Hamish's (PwAD) life had changed since living with dementia, and how Susan would need to be led by him and change with him rather than trying to keep Hamish in Susan's world. During this conversation, they added the following words to the workshop sheet: *"WE have to follow him into his world"*. This implies Katie supported Susan to see the situation differently, highlighting how empathy and acceptance towards PwAD may be developed through relationship dyads and triads. It also suggests that approaches which accept the person's changing reality can enhance meaning-making opportunities. This was discussed further during the workshop, as represented in the excerpt below:

Katie (staff): *"[Referring to one of the data sheets] They're [family/staff] trying to pull him back into our world, it's not our world we have to go into their world, we have to follow them not them trying to stay because they're never going to stay in this world, they're always going to change"*

Sorcha (family): *"They don't understand this world anymore"*

Katie: *"So I took that one, like yourself [referring to Sorcha, family], you want Fraser the way Fraser was which is never going to happen again and it's sad and it's heart-breaking"*

Sorcha: *"No, but it's realistic"*

Katie: *"It's realistic and that's how I started changing the comment, it's their world, it's their world now"*

Mutual empathy and understanding were evident in other discussions between family members and staff, which seemed to change family/staff perspectives of what constituted a meaningful activity/interaction for PwAD. For example, Harry (staff) explained how Fraser (PwAD) potentially remembered doing an activity he previously enjoyed but no longer had the ability to execute. As a result, Sorcha (family) acknowledged Fraser's potential frustration, indicating she was seeing Fraser's perspective. Similarly, Harry reported how the workshop helped him to empathise with PwAD and provided a new perspective on the actions of PwAD. This is important because enhancing family/staff empathy and understanding towards PwAD may offer them new ways of approaching PwAD, which may mutually enrich meaning in activities and interactions.

8.3 Theme Two: Seeing the person as an active agent

This theme describes how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD could be created when the person's agency and their current skills were seen and acknowledged. Meaning appeared to be generated through validation, participation and connecting with others. This theme is firstly presented by exploring how family members and staff acknowledged the

person's agency, followed by perceptions of choice. Lastly, the theme will be presented through a discussion about meaning, validation and visibility, represented by PwAD, family members, staff and myself.

8.3.1 Acknowledging the person's agency

Most family members and staff referred to PwAD as active agents, which indirectly highlighted PwAD as constantly changing. They described PwAD as still being interested, curious and wanting to be involved in activities and interactions, which they felt was shown through the person's (in)actions. Amy (family) offered an example, describing how her dad, Donald (PwAD) used to drive to the shops but now walked constantly in the care home. This led to an interesting discussion about the way Donald walked, which situated him as being 'on a mission' and moving purposefully to express his curiosity. This conversation seemed meaningful because family and staff appeared to be co-creating a new narrative of Donald as a shapeshifter based on the present rather than anchoring him in the past, which potentially opened opportunities for future meaning-making.

Other examples of agency were discussed by family members and friends. This included the PwAD demonstrating empathy and social skills towards other residents by accompanying them on a walk, and in seeking reassurance by asking questions. For example, Susan (family) described how Hamish (PwAD) regularly asked her about the town he grew up in to improve his mood. Susan felt this showed Hamish's cognitive awareness, whereas Katie (staff) believed he was trying to confirm his past and situate himself. This demonstrates different perspectives of agency, with one view suggesting that agency in PwAD dwindles and requires indirect negotiation others, and the latter inferring that the PwAD actively tries to connect with others to reinforce 'the self':

Susan: *"... Every time I come in he wants me to say the word, I know he's waiting for me to say [town in Scotland] because [same town] good feelings, positivity and then he'll look and then he'll say- and he can, he can still so there's still part, it's cognitive awareness because he can still say, 'no, no, no' and I'll say 'well why?' and I can see then he'll, I feel sorry because I do feel as if it's, it, it's slipping, slips forward every time I come in he wants me to pull that back for him to remind him of-"*

Katie: *"I feel as though that's not memory, that's letting him know that he lived that memory because he wants to grasp it"*

Judy (staff): *"But that was his time when he was comfortable, he was well, he was safe and that's the same for all the residents that the past it's ((inaudible))"*

?Family member: *"Nature of the illness isn't it?"*

Agency and participation in PwAD was sometimes described as subtle. For instance, Katie (staff) reported how Fraser (PwAD) did not participate in activities involving music and singing, but that he would respond to one-to-one interactions when the other person provided the time and space to do so. This suggests that active participation of PwAD in activities and interactions somewhat depends on the form/type of the activity, the approach, and the context, highlighting the importance of others adapting themselves, the activity and the environment.

Seeing PwAD represented as an active agent in care home life appeared important to two family members, particularly regarding photographs of residents displayed around the home and the information shared with family members. For family members, knowing that PwAD engaged in meaningful activities and interactions seemed to indicate that PwAD felt included, fulfilled and well-cared for, as represented by Rose (family):

“... If I come in I don't know my mum's been interactive or quiet or had a nap yesterday or was out to- on the barge trip unless see that it's been on Workplace or somebody's told me that's the kind of things that I feel is really missing... and I don't know if she slept through the night?... Am I too noseey?”

Not all family members initially viewed PwAD as active agents, but their opinion seemed to change during the workshop. For instance, Sorcha (family) believed her husband, Fraser (PwAD) spent most of his day sleeping, which did not fit her view of a meaningful life. Through a conversation with Harry (staff), Sorcha changed her perspective as they co-created a new narrative about Fraser which repositioned him as active and autonomous rather than passive and disinterested, adding value to what he appeared to find meaningful. It was interesting that Harry and Sorcha both seemed to need to socially construct this narrative, potentially to piece together and make sense of his actions:

Harry: *“Like I say when he comes to ((inaudible)) he's walking about with the men [other residents] he'll wander about you know... and he'll stop and he'll point to things... and watch a bit of the telly and then wander on... I only really see him sitting down when he's tired you know, like any other time he's wandering about”*

Sorcha: *“And that's just what I see all the time is just sitting down sleeping”*

Harry: *“Him sitting aye... he can be active, he can be up wandering about whether it's down his own corridor in [name of house in care home] or whether it's in [name of different house in care home]”*

Sorcha: *“Like walking about with that [points to picture of 'Wet Floor' sign on data sheet] ((Chuckles))”*

Harry: *“Aye I've seen him walking about... but again to him that's not a 'Wet Floor' sign, that could be anything...”*

Sorcha: *“Do you know I was actually thinking about that, he always carried a briefcase”*

Harry: *“See that could be- and because it’s got the handle like a briefcase he could be thinking that’s my, either his briefcase or...”*

Sorcha: *“Yeah that’s his briefcase...because I believe he enjoys sitting in the staff meetings and things like that ((laughs))”*

There also appeared to be a link between the person’s agency and choice, meaning in activities and interactions, and positive risk-taking. Clarissa (staff) and Amy (family) discussed a balance between keeping Amy’s dad, Donald (PwAD) safe and allowing him freedom to move in a way that emulated his sense of self. In this situation, it was more meaningful to respect Donald’s personhood rather than undermine his agency:

Amy: *“Well that’s right knowing the person’s safe and secure but he still”*

Clarissa: *“It’s difficult because ((pause))”*

Amy: *“You know they’re safe and secure but you still don’t want them to be here you know that way”*

Clarissa: *“Yeah and also you know there’s an element of risk taking? Because as you’ve said with your dad you know he walks about you know his hands in his pocket? So if he falls he’s going”*

Amy: *“He’s going flat on his face”*

Clarissa: *“He’s going flat on his face”*

Amy: *“He is”*

Clarissa: *“And we’re lucky it’s not happened really, that he’s not had a serious injury but you know that’s a potential because ((inaudible))”*

Amy: *“I know that that is a hazard for him”*

Clarissa: *“You know then and for us to continually say ‘Donald, take your hands (out)’ it’s not right”*

Amy: *“((inaudible)) I know”*

Clarissa: *“It’s not right is it”*

Amy: *“I know”*

8.3.2 Perceptions of choice

Meaning in activities and interactions also seemed to involve the right to make choices, which staff believed could be demonstrated by inaction. This caused friction between family members and staff because the two groups seemed to have different opinions about what made activities and interactions meaningful for PwAD. It also highlighted potential challenges

around honouring the choices of PwAD and illuminating their presence in the care home, as represented in the excerpt below.

Judy (staff): *“You [family members] just start to think... why is my mother not there? Why is my father not there?”*

Amy (family): *“That’s me because my dad falls asleep so he doesn’t get pictures put up”*

Judy: *“I think actually appreciate the fact that a) people have choices and b) people say ‘well just don’t listen to what he says, just take them - we can’t.”*

Katie (staff): *“We can’t do that and it’s abuse”*

Judy: *“Pre-pandemic if we had something on and families were there, sometimes a bit of encouragement, you could come down you know... other than that if somebody’s sitting quite happily on the settee half asleep and deciding you know... they’re not going to get up and say ‘right come over and do this’ whatever it doesn’t matter how much we encourage”.*

Issues concerning agency and choice were also raised by two staff members during individual reflections, particularly about PwAD who were immobile. Anna and Katie (staff) recognised how PwAD who were immobile or post-verbal were less likely to have choice in participating in activities and interactions. Anna described how she was led by the person’s cues to understand if the person wanted to participate in an activity or interaction, for example, if a PwAD withdrew their hand when walking and holding hands, she would interpret this as dissent. Anna also questioned if staff ever actually knew whether an immobile PwAD wanted to attend an activity, and she felt many PwAD attended activities without being asked. This is important for meaning-making because if a person’s choices are not recognised or understood, their autonomy may be undervalued. This may result in activities and interactions being meaningless or even harmful. This seems particularly significant for PwAD who are unable to independently mobilise and/or articulate their preferences.

8.3.3 Meaning, validation and visibility

There seemed to be a point in advanced dementia practice where the agency of the person diminished because PwAD were no longer seen by others; this created a powerful link between meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, agency, validation of (co)existence and the visibility of PwAD. Susan (family) and Katie (staff) were the only participants who discussed how this situation could cause PwAD to become withdrawn and question their own existence. In the passage below, they describe how acknowledging PwAD could enhance their visibility. This is significant because it suggests agency in PwAD is co-created and requires

validation of the self and selves to confirm (co)existence, which appears to be both a part of meaning-making and meaningful in and of itself:

Susan: *“How crucial that is as you say, sometimes you see somebody sitting and they’re just [flattens her hand and moves it from the top of her head to chin]”...*

Katie: *“Get in there and cut that [moved hand over face quickly as if breaking something down] cut that up”*

Susan: *“Get in there and say “hello” brings ‘I see you’ they must feel almost as if they have slipped away. Am I, do I exist? [in a quieter voice] Do I exist”*

Katie: *“Because that’s what we’re talking about I’m saying oh right we do groups but I think one-to-one is more important... I think if you’ve got dementia yeah have your group, have your sing-songs, have this, have that because music’s brilliant right... but I think we can then, as a person for anything meaningful it has to be one-to-one you can’t do that in a group... But sometimes I do think they do think it’s just an existence... sometimes when I see likes of [resident]... in the bucket chair I mean that wee woman, that breaks my heart, because... I’m positive in her mind she’s thinking, ‘take me please take me”.*

I took this learning back to PwAD to explicitly acknowledge PwAD and recognise the potentially meaningful small and invisible agential acts. For instance, Fraser (PwAD) and I were talking about the painting I planned to create for him to thank him for participating in the study. Suddenly, the conversation became muddled, but I acknowledged this as a contribution to the conversation to validate his (co)existence. Figure 8.1 demonstrates how Fraser included the environment in our interaction, demonstrating his own agency which highlighted the door/door handle. Together, we co-created meaning in the moment by connecting ourselves to one another and the environment. This added another dimension to our conversation as I continued to learn with and from Fraser.

Figure 8.1 Vignette illustrating Hamish noticing the door

When PwAD were able to use their agency, this seemed to enhance their visibility to other residents. Morag (PwAD) and I encountered this type of experience when we sat in the communal dining area, through which her awareness of herself and others was evident. This situation co-created a cascade of exchanges including waves, vocalisations and giggles, acknowledging and validating all involved. Figure 8.2 illustrates this and suggests mutual awareness could co-create meaning through reciprocal interactions.

Figure 8.2 Vignette illustrating a triad of communication

This theme has discussed how meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may be co-created if they are able to use their agency. Using their agency seems to illuminate the person and their (co)existence, however sometimes others may need to validate the person and recognise subtle participation for this to happen. Additionally, the environment may be part of this process.

8.4 Theme Three: Reframing meaning in activities and interactions

This theme explores how meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD was reframed by family members and staff in the context of the care home. This is presented through discussing what meaning might look like for PwAD and how meaning may be co-created; illustrative examples from individual reflections with PwAD are provided. Situations where meaning may be unmade and/or unmeaningful are also discussed.

8.4.1 What meaning might look like

A variety of activities considered meaningful for PwAD were discussed by family members and staff. Family members shared stories of PwAD gaining pleasure from seemingly simple, everyday activities. For instance, Sorcha (family) reported how Fraser (PwAD) enjoyed watching rabbits from his bedroom window, and Susan (family) shared how Hamish (PwAD)

appreciated looking at photographs and watching a video of a singer. Anna (staff) described how she now saw every task as a potentially meaningful activity with PwAD whereas other staff described activities that were intervention-focussed, for example, reminiscence, therapy dolls, animal therapy, an interactive table and technology. These examples suggest meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD can be (in)formal, mundane, structured or spontaneous.

Some family members and staff collaboratively seemed to reframe how meaning in activities and interactions was perceived. This process involved moving from a rigid perspective of what constitutes an activity to a view that encompassed 'quieter' activities and a sense of being present, as represented by Sorcha (family) and Harry (staff):

Sorcha: *"I don't think he gets involved with, he doesn't do jigsaws or dominoes or anything like that so it's what does he get involved in you know?"*

Harry: *"...well I mean when there's concerts on, I think he would come down and sit for a concert you know... it's hard to say you know if... he would get anything out of it but I have seen him come down and sit for a concert"... "I've noticed as well that when he's in the corridor he'll go up to people's pictures ((inaudible)) their bedrooms and wee memory boxes and he'll stand and just look at them for a bit then he'll move on...like he's taking an interest"*

Some family members and staff described perceived benefits when PwAD participated in activities and interactions deemed meaningful. For example, Susan (family) described how a family member's dog had previously been beneficial for her dad because he loved the animal and was not required to use his memory, and Katie and Judy (staff) believed therapy dolls could provide comfort to PwAD and encourage restless PwAD to sit. However, they also noted how challenges could arise, for example when one PwAD tried to sell the babies. Judy felt reminiscence could be helpful to bring joy and contentment and Anna (staff) believed PwAD gained comfort through touch during activities involving movement or massage, particularly if the person did not receive much physical contact throughout their day. She felt touch could help PwAD feel worthy and deserving of attention from another person. These examples suggest that activities and interactions for PwAD can be meaningful if they stimulate the senses and emotions. They also suggest that meaning can change as the activity/interaction changes, which may impact their meaningfulness.

8.4.2 Approaches to meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia

Three staff members described how 'revisiting the moment' could enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. During the workshop, Katie (staff) disagreed with a comment on one of the discussion prompts which illustrated how meaning could be lost in the

moment; instead, Katie believed that meaning could be revisited using visual cues/probes. She gave an example of a previously observed interaction with Morag (PwAD), and how although Morag did not initially recognise her husband in a photograph, she was able to identify him when the picture was revisited:

Katie (staff): *"In likes of the moment and you [researcher] were saying because you didn't have a football the moment was lost I don't agree with that because... You know what we spoke about and it was your mum [looks at Rose (family)] we were talking about the time when I did my focus group we went through the photo album and when we got to the wedding photo she didn't know your daddy but we left it at that and we continued through, and went through and then the children, you guys came along and ((clicks fingers)) right away she got you and then daddy appeared and she got him right away, then we reverted back to the wedding photo and she went 'that's [Morag's husband] isn't it? I said '[Morag's husband]?' And she went 'That's me and [Morag's husband] so... I think just folding the book shut at that moment would have just, we would have lost everything you know what I mean that's how I ((inaudible)) I'm going to keep going and I'm gonna go through the ages and the stages of it's a life (isn't it) ((inaudible)) it was funny when because you've got a sister haven't you as well aye [looks at Rose] and she rattled the names off ((inaudible))"*

((General laughter))

Sorcha (family): *"... And she recognised him"*

Susan (family): *"Picked the thread up"*

Katie: *" (And then) I said: 'well who's that then?' and she went: 'That's [Morag's husband], that's my wedding day' so the moment might have passed but then you could go back so it's kind like working with people as well it's not just like, 'right that's it, it's not going to work'"*

Anna and Harry (staff) shared similar views, with Harry reporting an occasion where he left a PwAD to obtain a photograph to show them, but upon his return, the person was interested in a different topic. He described keeping the photograph nearby ready to bring into the conversation when appropriate. These examples suggest meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD can deviate and be co-created, (re)created, suspended, changed and/or revisited with PwAD. This is important because it highlights the potential fluidity, flexibility and changeability of meaning, suggesting that these qualities may also require consideration when co-creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

Indirectly inviting PwAD to participate in activities and interactions seemed to be another way of co-creating meaning. Judy and Katie (staff) explained how rather than presenting therapy dolls to residents, they left them in the lounges for them to discover. They reported that this approach worked well, particularly for the male residents who were more interested than the females. The staff members described how one male spent time nursing the dolls, and that they accompanied him to a hospital appointment. This suggests meaning can be indirectly co-created with PwAD in a staggered manner providing there are opportunities for such engagement in the care home environment.

8.4.3 Co-creating activities and interactions

Meaning could be co-created with PwAD through opportunities in the physical and social environment. For example, Morag (PwAD) self-initiated an interaction with a photograph, which she demonstrated by reaching forward towards the photograph and asking questions about it. Although Morag's interest quickly evaporated when she realised the picture was not of a baby as she first thought, demonstrated by her pushing away the photograph, this interaction still seemed meaningful. The presence of the picture stimulated Morag's curiosity, which she signalled through her body, prompting me to pick it up and give it to her. She was then able to explore the item of interest, highlighting her agency and choice, potentially creating meaning. Similarly, whilst Fraser (PwAD) and I explored an app of bird sounds, Fraser showed his interest in a folded piece of paper using his body. The paper appeared to provide him opportunities to explore, satisfying his curiosity, as illustrated in Figure 8.3.

Figure 8.3 Vignette illustrating Frase liking a piece of paper

Donald (PwAD) and I explored a piano app on the iPad. With verbal and physical prompting, Donald played a tune and meaning appeared to be transiently co-created. Although he was not sure if he liked the app, the interaction between us and the facilitation of the iPad offered Donald opportunities and choices. However, meaning may have been suspended when I read his non-verbal communication as dissent when it may have been an invitation. This demonstrates the ‘unknown’ aspects of co-creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, and how embodiment may be (mis)read and shared language misunderstood, as described in Figure 8.4.

Figure 8.4 Vignette of Donald and I playing with the piano App

8.4.4 (Un)making meaning and unmeaningful activities and interactions

Activities and interactions with PwAD appeared to have potential for meaning to be (un)made or unmeaningful. As previously mentioned, Anna (staff) felt PwAD who were immobile were sometimes excluded from potentially meaningful activities, for example haircuts or Barge trips because of inappropriate seating that did not meet their postural needs. Katie (staff) believed the physiotherapy groups in the home were aimed at residents who were able to freely participate and therefore excluded many PwAD. She felt physiotherapy could be adapted for PwAD rather than purely assessing the person for mobility equipment, as was currently the case:

“people in a coma, they all still get physio and things like that, they get that ((inaudible)) they [physiotherapist] come up to valuate [sic] you know if somebody new is coming in or they’re a falls risk and things like that if they need maybe a Zimmer and things like that I mean I physio it’s called exercise, physio exercise on a Monday it’s only your residents that have the ability to join in it wouldn’t be your residents like say anybody that’s in a locked in like [name of resident]? They wouldn’t come down to things like that...whereas you could maybe do a one-to-one in the room?... And it’s not that she’s in a coma but just for slight movement?”

Katie (staff) also considered the garden to be unsuitable for PwAD because of clutter and risk of falls. These points imply there are many missed opportunities for PwAD to engage in activities and interactions which may be meaningful, and that this can inadvertently exclude the person. These examples also suggest that the person, the activity and the social and physical environment all need to be considered and adapted to enable PwAD to participate in and create meaning in activities and interactions. It also suggests inequality and stigma may unmake meaning and/or that the person may be deprived of potentially meaningful activities/interactions because they are not adapted appropriately.

This theme has explored how meaning in activities and interactions could be illuminated and reframed by increasing our understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD using various approaches, including a fluid approach to meaning in the moment and co-creative methods. Situations where meaning may be unmade or activities and interactions unmeaningful were also presented.

8.5 Theme Four: Moving forward

This theme highlights how some family members and staff actioned ways to enhance meaning in activities and interactions. This will be presented by describing how skill-sharing between family members and staff may support the enhancement of meaning-making with PwAD and how learning from the study was applied by staff, who also identified further learning opportunities. Conversely, it shares how one family member felt there was no change, which perhaps related to her expectations of the study.

8.5.1 Sharing skills

Sorcha (family) felt family carers would benefit from the input of care home staff to enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. She and Harry (staff) discussed this alongside her active role in the community and how this could facilitate such information. The excerpt below highlights Sorcha's desire to initiate change through skill-sharing between family members and staff. It seems that this collaboration could open opportunities for meaning-making with PwAD and consequently reduce distress to PwAD in everyday life, which suggests meaning in activities and interactions may relate to maintaining a sense of calm and homeostasis:

Sorcha: *"Because I'm involved with [name of group] in [Scottish town] and I'm saying to them 'why are they [formal carers] not talking to you' for you to tell us, 'oh this small thing would make a difference to stop a situation arising' like I know being out he doesn't like anything taken away from him right so (many) times you bring a plate with a biscuit on it, give him that and then he'll take-"*

Harry: *"I know and then he'll put that down aye"*

Sorcha: *"Why ((inaudible)) know this? You know because in the House that would ((inaudible)) out of his hand"*

Harry: *"Yeah, and then distress him that would, yeah definitely"*

Sorcha: *"You know so we should be getting these"*

Harry: *"All the wee tips, yeah"*

Sorcha: *"Tips down on paper so we can say to carers 'look this might work'"*

Harry: *"Aye they might (see them taken off him) but they're not aware that's actually a really big help yeah"*

Sorcha: *"Exactly yes so I'm trying to get that so-".*

Anna (staff) identified a need for colleagues to receive training about what activities and interactions might look like for PwAD. She spoke about the impact of this study and how it could have reached more staff members. This suggests meaning in activities and interactions

may not be well understood by care home staff, and how opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may be impacted as a result. It also illuminates a potential need for training about meaning in activities rather than meaningful activities:

“I do think that training would probably would help I mean ((inaudible)) you’d picked some of us but...if you’d had time and you’d been able to involve everyone in this then I think it would have opened a lot of people’s eyes I think it would have that: ‘ooh, that is an activity or ‘that is-’ d’you know definitely”.

8.5.2 Putting learning into practice

Two staff members reported that the study had reinforced existing knowledge and/or encouraged them to try new approaches to activities and interactions. Harry (staff) described how the research had refreshed his knowledge and reminded him to question why a PwAD might behave in a particular way. He believed this complemented his current training and reinforced the importance of reflective practice. Anna (staff) felt the study had progressed her thinking and expanded her view of a meaningful activity. She described approaches which were reflective, collaborative, creative, and promoted choice:

“I would say it [care practice] has [changed because of the study] I think about every action that I do now, how to turn it into an activity... I feel as if every action now I’m thinking: ‘oh this is quite a nice wee activity’ you know even if it is just the picking of their clothes in the morning... but no definitely, it has made me think more as to what an activity is”.

8.5.3 Progression/future action

Two staff members reported plans to progress their learning because of their participation in study, demonstrating the continuous process of AR and its ability to stimulate change. In response to reflecting on the use of touch for PwAD, Anna (staff) reported plans to look at courses in massage and essential oils to use with PwAD. It was evident that she had also empathically considered how to adapt this activity to enhance meaning:

“...As I said with the meaningful it kind of made me take a step back and think about that, to make it into something that’s not a question you know or to go through a whole day and nobody’ll touch you and I thought that’s where the massage came in...even it was only a hand, an arm with essential oils or...so I’m going to look at the colleges that do it as a wee, as a kind of night school just see what comes out of it kind of thing but...but even the wee chair she [masseur] had yesterday [when a masseur came into the care home] I thought well normally if I go for a massage it’s a bed and I thought oh that’s not appropriate for them [residents]...but this was like the relaxation chair that ((inaudible)) you can either go down on at your knees or just sit on the chair with your

legs in front or behind or and I thought 'oh most of our residents could manage that wheelchair ones could manage an Indian Head Massage or-'

Similarly, Katie (staff) described exploring how America used technology to stimulate the senses with PwD at end-of-life. Katie described a sense of transcendence arising from her participation in the study which appeared to have the potential to enhance meaning in her future activities and interactions with PwAD and broaden opportunities for meaning-making. She described how she planned to implement and develop her current learning:

"See being involved [in the study] it's kind of opened my mind up ((inaudible)) because... I have been on [the] internet looking for different things to incorporate into my life when working with people because I want to go down likes of the technology... I know singing and dancing is important, I know music's important as well but when they get to that stage where that's not useful to them or they're not getting anything out of that you have to go down a different road to get into that person that's locked in and them pull them back I think the technology needs to then come in... Since working with likes of you and because of being involved in this study I've just decided on looking at different things that I can try and incorporate in here"

Conversely, Amy (family) did not feel anything had changed because her dad was still not present in the care home photographs. She reported hoping the care home would upload videos of her dad engaging in activities to the family website, suggesting that Amy's *perception* of meaning in activities and interactions had remained the same. It also emphasised how subtleties in post-verbal communication and participation may be missed by or invisible to others. By looking for visual evidence that her dad was involved in care home life to signify meaning-making, meaning may be obscured, which clashes with the subtleties of everyday creativity. It also highlights how subtle participation in activities and interactions may be difficult to capture. Amy (family) reported the workshop being helpful because it enabled her to share experiences with other family members. This seemed meaningful to her because it provided a platform to voice and validate her experiences of supporting her dad and an opportunity to socially construct his narrative.

This theme has demonstrated the importance of collaborating with family members and staff to share skills and knowledge, as well as how AR research processes can support learning about, as well as reflection on and implementation of, meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. It also reinforces how others' perceptions of meaningful activity, post-verbal/embodied communication and subtle participation may impact meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

8.6 Summary and key learning

This chapter collaboratively reviewed and developed an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, family members, care home staff and myself. Learning from the study was also identified and shared.

Key learning includes the social construction of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, potential links between sense-making and meaning-making, the (un)making, (re)creation and revisiting of meaning, and the visibility of PwAD, subtle activities and participation. Family members and staff seemed to need to socially construct the narratives of PwAD using shared knowledge from the person's life history and interpretations of what PwAD did in the care home. Socially constructed narratives were not static, rather they changed through discussions – a process with potential to (co)create or unmake meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Socially constructing narratives seemed a way of making sense of the experiences of PwAD, particularly the realities of PwAD, their behaviour, the activities they participated in and the way in which they participated. Sense-making appeared meaningful because it offered different perspectives of PwAD which could reinstate their agency and/or enhance empathy. Meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD may therefore heavily rely on others, their perspectives of PwAD, and how they (in)directly create opportunities for meaning-making with PwAD in the social and physical environment, or not. This suggests the content of socially constructed narratives may have a direct impact on meaning. Additionally, how meaningful activities and participation in such activities are perceived by family members and staff may impact their visibility.

New insights for the field include opportunities to enhance meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD through a heightened awareness of potential connections between socially constructed narratives, sense-making and meaning-making, highlighting the delicate balance between sharing knowledge and the information used to inform that knowledge. Additionally, it highlights a need to review how family members and staff perceive 'meaningful activities'. Further exploration of post-verbal communication, embodiment, subtle participation and everyday creativity may highlight PwAD as active agents and lessen the likelihood for subtleties to be overlooked, missed or invisible.

The following chapter discusses the findings from all three phases of the study and incorporates relevant literature. The limitations of this study and implications for research, practice, education and policy are addressed to conclude this thesis.

Chapter 9 : Discussion, recommendations and conclusion

9.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to present insights from the findings and discuss how the understanding of meaning in activities and interactions has developed in terms of the concept and its relevance to people with advanced dementia (PwAD) and advanced dementia practice. Four key findings are presented and discussed alongside literature from the integrative review in Chapter Two and the theoretical and philosophical literature in Chapter Three to demonstrate this learning. This discussion includes relevant literature published after the literature review. In addition, strengths, limitations, implications and recommendations for practice, policy, education and research are offered as a legacy of the Action Research (AR) process to acknowledge the continuing process of looking, thinking and doing (Stringer and Aragon, 2021).

Similarly to previous chapters, creative approaches were used to adapt the writing process to accommodate neurodiversity. This involved physically 'making' each key finding and using these as a visual prompt to write this chapter. Different materials/mediums were used to communicate their unique content, including self-drying clay, moveable collages, and water. Photographs of these representations are presented at the end of each key finding, alongside a brief explanation of their content.

9.2 Overview

The aim for this study was to address a gap in the literature by understanding the meaning *in* activities and interactions, in collaboration with PwAD, their family members and staff in a care home setting using a qualitative, AR approach and creative methods. The meaning *in* activities and interactions was explored rather than the term, 'meaningful activities' because the latter is frequently used but superficially understood in advanced dementia practice. Inadequate understanding of what makes activities and interactions meaningful for PwAD appears to contribute to reduced opportunities for PwAD to participate in everyday care home life, potentially leading to poorer quality of life and withdrawal from others. Moreover, understanding such a complex term directly with PwAD who are likely to communicate in post-verbal, embodied ways added further complexities. This aim has been addressed through a

deepened understanding of meaning in activities and interactions and what this may look like with PwAD.

This study consisted of one cycle of AR with three phases. The objectives for each phase are outlined in Section 4.6. All objectives were fully met and evidenced in all four key findings. In Phase One, a shared understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD was formed through interviews with family members and focus groups with staff. This information was also used to learn about the life histories, preferences and communication styles of PwAD which offered a fluid guide for data collection with PwAD in Phase Two. The use of multi-modal methods in Phase Two enabled all participant groups to contribute (Kara, 2020) to the exploration of everyday experiences of meaning in activities and interactions and illuminated the post-verbal voice of PwAD. The workshop and reflections in Phase Three provided opportunities to actively review, deepen and develop an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, family members and care home staff. As a result, there was evidence of learning and skill-sharing, and further actions were identified by some participants (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013; Stringer and Aragon, 2021; McCabe *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the following research question was answered: *How can we understand the meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD to collaboratively enhance their everyday experience within a care home setting?* This body of work provided an original contribution to knowledge regarding the concept of meaning and how it can relate to activities and interactions with PwAD, as discussed in the four key findings.

9.3 Key findings

This critical discussion of the four key findings will include relevant studies published since the completion of the integrative review. These include qualitative studies exploring meaning in life for people with severe dementia (Isene *et al.*, 2021a), the experience of meaning-making for people with moderate-to-severe dementia in a specialised dementia ward (Isene *et al.*, 2021b), and understanding the key characteristics of meaningful activities for people with mild to moderate dementia in residential care (Tierney *et al.*, 2023). Other qualitative studies include analysing the meaning in everyday activities for people with mild to moderate Alzheimer's Disease or Posterior cortical atrophy living in the community (Harding *et al.*, 2024) and a study by Haunch, Downs and Oyeboode (2023) to understand meaningful engagement with people living with various stages of dementia. Additionally, a quantitative study by Trudeau, Slotnick and Gately (2024) investigated the impact reading to PwAD had on their

engagement. The emergence of this literature demonstrates an increased interest in this area of practice.

9.3.1 Key finding one

Meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD seems to be a fluid, complex and multifaceted phenomenon with a variety of inter-related and (co)created physical, emotional and sensory components. These include but are not limited to: the person feeling and being safe and secure; the person's physical, emotional and sensory comfort; an existential need for purpose; opportunities to explore curiosity; and responding to the person's continually changing self, as seen in their reactions, realities and interests. These components may be meaningful in and of themselves and perhaps conditional to a person's participation in perceived meaningful activities. They also appear to be affected by the context and the social and physical environment.

This key finding is presented through a theoretical and empirical discussion of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. The components of meaning and how these were applied in a care home setting are also conferred.

The components of meaning resembled physical, emotional and sensory aspects of meaning, such as feeling/being safe and comfortable. Feeling and being safe was expressed in different ways depending on the participant group. PwAD demonstrated a need for safety in an embodied way, for example, in freedom to explore the environment (Donald), in reassuring words and touch when anxious (Morag), reminders of their past (Hamish), and when collecting objects (Fraser). Some family members reported relief in knowing the PwAD was physically safe in the care home, and staff felt they were considered a symbol of safety by being a 'magnet' that PwAD were drawn towards. These examples suggest that being and feeling safe seemed to be about a need for freedom, connection to the self and others, and reassurance.

As identified by the staff in this study, safety and comfort are featured in Maslow's hierarchy of needs (1943; 1970; 1971). Although presented as linear, Maslow (1970) clarified the needs are inter-related and combined, however he still affirmed the importance of some needs over others, depending on individuals and societies. Koltko-Rivera (2006) interpreted Maslow's (1971) updated hierarchy to be read both from the bottom-up i.e. where needs are individualistic, or from the top-down i.e. where needs are altruistic. Either way, a rigidity with the model is still implied. Building on Maslow's (1970) updated hierarchy of needs, this study asserts that the physical, emotional and sensory components were dynamic, intertwined and

interdependent rather than linear. Similarly, Derkx *et al.* (2020) infer that the components of meaning in relation to older people are inter-dependent and often occur simultaneously. However, the findings from this study suggest that for PwAD there are components of meaning which appear to be a spectrum of colours that blend and change according to the PwAD, their interests, the social and physical environment and context. Additionally, there may be conflicting priorities in these components depending on the perspective, for instance when continence care clashes with the person's wishes, as described by staff. This implies there may be further layers to meaning in activities and interactions that may not be relevant to people living without advanced dementia, hence the focus of components may change accordingly, or various components may be present at the same time.

Comfort appeared to be present in all components. Comfort could be physical, for instance, being pain-free, clean and dry. It could be emotional, such as feeling loved, calm and experiencing reciprocal empathy, or it could be sensory, for example, having a hand massage, smelling a scent from the past, or being away from noise. Comfort could also be a mixture of these components, for instance, when Susan (family) stroked the soft toy knowing that her dad would later indirectly 'receive' that touch once she had left when he touched the object. Comfort also appeared to manifest as a tension between family members and staff when family members were perceived by staff to undermine and disregard comfort, in favour of PwAD attending organised activities.

Literature from the fields of dementia and gerontology also describe comfort as being meaningful, among other aspects identified in this current study. These include the physical comfort of older PwAD being integral to palliative care (van der Steen *et al.*, 2014), Kitwood's (1997a; 1997b) five psychological needs, the Senses Framework (Nolan *et al.*, 2004; 2006) and the adapted version by Watson (2019), as reported in Section 2.10.1. Watson's (2019) adaptation is more aligned with this research because it acknowledges subtle communication and the potential for this to be overlooked. Furthermore, Watson's (2019) embodied (Hughes, 2001; Kontos, 2004; 2005; Hughes, 2013) and inter-embodied (Jenkins, 2013) lens also spotlights the body as an important facilitator and signifier of meaning with PwAD. This current study adds to Watson's (2019) research by demonstrating how components of meaning appeared to shift according to a variety of factors. These included the progression of dementia, the interdependency of and tensions in relationships between PwAD, family members and staff, the plethora of realities, current interests of PwAD, and opportunities for meaning in the social and physical environment. Additionally, Watson's (2019) study began with an inquiry about (inter)embodiment and relationships, which identified a need for meaningful interactions and goals, whereas this study focussed on meaning in activities and interactions, with

(inter)embodiment and relationships contributing to the findings. Therefore, this study complements the learning from Watson's study by adding a different perspective. The findings from this current study are also consistent with the summarised understanding of meaning in Chapter Three, which has been enriched by this study through experiential learning with PwAD.

Other studies also found potential interrelated components of meaning in activities and interactions for people with dementia (PwD). However, unlike the frameworks above, they did not identify safety and comfort. The concept analysis of meaningful activity for older people with dementia by Tierney *et al.* (2020) identified characteristics of meaningful activity, concluding that activities were meaningful in this context if they were enjoyable and engaging, matched the person's skills and goals, and confirmed personhood. Similarly, the qualitative exploration of meaningful activity for people with early to advanced dementia by Harmer and Orrell (2008) found enjoyable, stimulating activities that matched the skills, abilities, values and past identities of PwD to be meaningful. Moreover, Harmer and Orrell (2008) found the physical needs of PwAD to be prioritised by staff over other activities, whereas the present study offers a different perspective in that staff participants viewed the physical needs of PwAD to be meaningful in and of themselves and potentially a condition of meaning, although they acknowledged that other staff may not share this opinion. This current study thereby extends this literature by broadening the components of meaning.

Tierney *et al.* (2020, 2023) considered the enjoyability of an activity for PwD to be a conditional characteristic of meaning, which is consistent with Csikszentmihalyi's (1993) understanding of activity from an occupational science perspective. Although this study also found enjoyment to be a potential component of meaning in activities and interactions, *all* emotions were potentially meaningful. This was particularly significant for Hamish (PwAD) who seemed to find meaning in the *expression* of emotions, and in seeking and receiving validation from others. This seemed to give him the opportunity to experience, feel and make sense of his situation using the tone of his voice and words, even if the order of the words were incomprehensible to others. When validated by his daughter, Susan he was then able to further express his emotions through his body in the form of dance. Some staff also described how the *presence* or stimulation of *any* emotion appeared meaningful in PwAD, perhaps because it opened opportunities for validation, empathy and connection. This finding is similar to some of the reviewed literature (Holst, Edberg and Hallberg, 1999; Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Cohen *et al.*, 2009; Roland and Chappell, 2015; Walmsley and McCormack, 2017) who also suggested links with meaning in activities, interactions and varied emotions.

Having a purpose seemed to be another component of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, even if this was momentary, although it may not be easily recognised. For instance, Fraser (PwAD) spending time in the office, Donald (PwAD) leading a walking tour, Morag (PwAD) hosting by making sure everyone had a drink, and Hamish having a 'just right' challenge when catching the toy cat. It seemed that goals needed to be adapted as some staff described making them simple, small, manageable and immediate. Baumeister (1991) and Csikszentmihalyi (1993; 2014) also recognised the importance of matching the complexity of an activity with the skill required to complete it, and in slightly stretching these abilities to open possibilities for fulfilment and transcendence.

Transcendence is referenced in various theories about/infering meaning. These include Maslow (1970), Derkx (2013), and Derkx *et al.* (2020) who described transcendence as a state of being which extends beyond 'the self', occurring when various needs are combined. Flow is a form of transcendence appears to be related to meaning in this current study. Flow is a state of mind involving a loss of self-consciousness which is experienced when a person is fully absorbed in and enjoying an activity with a clear goal, and is optimised when the perceived skills and demands of an activity match (Csikszentmihalyi, 2014). In this present study, Morag's (PwAD) concentrated facial expression when drumming, her continuation of the activity when asked if she wanted to stop, and her commenting that it felt "*great*", suggest she was experiencing flow. During the activity, the goal was implicitly co-created (see Section 4.2.4 for a definition) through movements of our bodies and the sounds, rhythms and beats created when our bodies and the drum merged. This corresponds with a study about severe mental illness and men by Carless and Douglas (2008), who presented two distinct case studies to highlight the potential meanings of sport activities. Although little attention is given to understanding the concept of meaning before applying it to the case studies, Carless and Douglas (2008) usefully demonstrate how meaning can be an *experience* or an *outcome*, depending on the values of the person. In this current study, meaning in activities and interactions appeared to be created through the *experience* of the activity/interaction, perhaps because the outcome was subtle or invisible. This suggests that meaning in activities and interactions may have different forms which may only be visible in particular circumstances. The current study adds depth to this literature by demonstrating how transcendence and flow may be achieved through the *experience* of an activity/interaction with PwAD, particularly when the focus of transcendence highlights daily life in a care home setting rather than specific activities that can be more distinctly recognised.

The needs of connectedness and transcendence are demonstrated when Donald (PwAD) signalled he wanted to link arms with me to show me around the care home. This experience

perhaps provided opportunities for co-creating meaning by providing a purpose, reinforcing self-worth, and connectedness (Derkx, 2013; Derkx *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, Donald had control, choice and agency when he self-initiated and led the activity, suggesting meaning was also stimulated through efficacy and action, helping him to make sense of the reality of care home life and create meaning through comprehensibility (Derkx, 2013; Derkx *et al.*, 2020). Finally, Donald and I perhaps validated one another's existence through touch, acknowledgement and spending time together to explore his interest in the garden, suggesting meaning was co-created through connectedness and transcendence (Derkx, 2013; Derkx *et al.*, 2020). This finding adds value to the literature by Derkx (2013) and Derkx *et al.* (2020) by demonstrating how their model of meaning is somewhat transferable to meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

All PwAD in this study demonstrated curiosity, including curiosity towards themselves, others and/or the physical and social environment. Numerous theorists have also identified curiosity in relation to meaning, for example Derkx (2013), Derkx *et al.* (2020), and Maslow (1970). Derkx (2013) and Derkx *et al.* (2020) discuss curiosity as an emotional response to the extraordinary, such as excitement, wonder and anger, whereas Maslow (1970) describes curiosity in terms of motivation and cognition. This study expands these theories to include curiosity as an embodied, potentially pre-reflexive skill in PwAD.

In this current study, opportunities for satisfying purpose and curiosity, and experiencing the associated meaning appeared more difficult for those reliant upon others to mobilise them. Morag (PwAD) was the only participant to mobilise in an attendant wheelchair and this seemed to restrict her choices and freedom. For instance, Morag's photograph album seemed potent with meaning, as suggested by the attention she gave to people in the images when she studied and touched them, however, she was unable to independently access this, suggesting that opportunities for Morag to experience meaning through the album relied on the availability and awareness of others. This is important because opportunities for experiencing meaning in activities and interactions may be linked the visibility of PwAD, particularly if that person is not independently mobile and/or able to verbalise preferences. This offers an original contribution because it identified a subpopulation who may be more at risk of occupational deprivation i.e. reduced access to a range of activities or lacking activities which directly impacts wellbeing (Wilcock and Hocking, 2015 p.285).

9.3.1.1 Visual representation

Figure 9.1 depicts a visual representation of this finding. Air drying clay and dog hair were used to create two asymmetrical forms to signify the multifaceted, complex non-linear nature of meaning. Wire was used to connect these forms to represent the interrelated components of meaning. The thick wet paint is still drying and alongside the beads and imprints communicate the changeability of the components within the context. The watch face characterises the person's continually changing self within their time and reality. The paint and drawn lines bleed into the forms and the paper to show how the components, and the social and physical environments connect.

Figure 9.1 Visual representation of key findings

9.3.2 Key finding two

PwAD may appreciate and find meaning in the everyday. Flexible, adaptable, everyday creative approaches may enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. However, the ordinariness of the everyday, combined with others' perceptions of PwAD

and their views of meaningful activity may disguise meaning in this context. As a result, meaning in activities and interactions may be inadvertently missed, understated, misinterpreted, or overlooked by others. For others to recognise meaning activities and interactions with PwAD, it may be necessary for them to develop an awareness of, sensitivity to and skills in everyday creativity. Noticing, sharing, and reciprocating the person's appreciation of the everyday could illuminate their visibility and (co)existence to themselves and others, which may enhance meaning and/or be meaningful in and of itself.

This key finding is presented through a discussion of meaning in relation to everyday creativity in the form of subtle activities and interactions between PwAD, family members, staff, myself and objects, and the adaptability of family members and staff. How everyday activity appeared to enhance mutual visibility is discussed as a thread throughout this key finding.

Everyday creativity was observed throughout this study during activities and interactions with PwAD, family members and staff. The definition of everyday creativity here is similar to Richards (2007) and Kaufman and Beghetto (2009), as described in Chapter Three, except it varied according to participant groups. For PwAD, it seemed to be a form of navigating, exploring and connecting to the social, physical and sensory aspects of the care home in a way that provided stimulation and fulfilled curiosity. For family members, everyday creativity appeared to normalise visits and provide the person with stimulation and connection, while staff seemed to use everyday creativity to enhance the person's choice whilst ensuring their needs were met.

PwAD appeared more attuned to everyday aesthetics than family, staff or myself, and this seemed to illuminate potential meaning by enhancing the visibility and existence of PwAD and everyday items. In turn, the act of *noticing* the person and the object seemed to open opportunities for others to experience and learn about beauty in the everyday, offering a mutually validating experience. An example is when all PwAD pointed at and/or asked questions about the red flashing light on the GoPro, which created openings for interaction, exploration and reciprocity and brought attention to the PwAD, the GoPro and potential meaning in noticing. Again, these micro-interactions would not necessarily be immediately recognisable as a meaningful activity, nor as opportunities to satisfy curiosities or connect to the self, others, or the physical and social environment. Alongside demonstrating everyday creativity, these instances suggest that the agency and participation of PwAD may be initiated and supported through everyday objects. This key finding suggests that mundane objects may initiate, facilitate meaningful (micro)activities and interactions with PwAD and others.

Objects could be intangible, for instance, the senses, humour and the atmosphere, or they could be tangible, such as cups, furnishings, fixtures and fittings (Blumer, 1969). Objects could be new or old, sentimental or ordinary, and could become an activity and co-create meaning through interaction or exploration, for example, when admiring a piece of paper, stroking a photograph, opening a door and peering around it, or looking through a window.

Similarly, Souyave *et al.* (2019) suggested folding everyday items such as cloth and paper were a potentially meaningful activity for people with moderate to advanced dementia. This finding is relatable to other studies, for instance, how handbags, clothing and dress can reinforce the self and selves of PwD (Twigg and Buse, 2013; Buse and Twigg, 2014a). Also how dress can create a metaphoric space for PwD upon moving to a care home (Buse and Twigg, 2014b) and how the meaning of home can be generated upon moving into a care home through a cyclical process of interaction between older people and new, as well as personal items such as furniture and smoking pipes (Lovatt, 2018). Lovatt (2018) found that meaning could be generated in the way objects were used and what they signified rather than being used according to their primary function. Conversely, in an ethnographic study exploring everyday life with PwD living in residential care, Lee and Bartlett (2021) found that mundane functional objects could enhance the participation and independence of PwD in self-care and domestic tasks. They therefore advocate the right for PwD to access these functional objects to enhance these skills, which they termed, 'material citizenship' (Lee and Bartlett, 2021, p.1481). The current study supports and extends this literature by identifying how objects may be used by PwAD in an everyday creative way. The present research also expands the term, 'material citizenship' to include the right for PwAD to creatively (and safely) explore everyday objects, whether this is for functional purposes or not.

The way in which PwAD used everyday objects varied and this appeared to create different meanings depending on the PwAD. For instance, when Hamish (PwAD) turned functional objects like a butter knife into a performance prop, this seemed to be a way to connect with others by making them laugh and appeared to connect the present with his past roles as a salesman and entertainer. Other examples include when Donald (PwAD) finished the game of Boules by turning the Boule into a football to practice his kicks, and when Fraser (PwAD) carried the 'Wet Floor' sign around the care home as he may have done with a briefcase in his office job. Creatively using everyday objects potentially required perceptiveness, imagination and innovation from PwAD (Hughes, 2014), resonant of the Situated Embodied Agent (Hughes, 2013) described in Chapter Three. Alternatively, the creativity demonstrated by PwAD may be symbolic of a lack of meaningful activity, in that any stimulation experienced by PwD is eagerly received, whether it is meaningful or not (Hughes, 2014), or that PwAD

sought meaning because they lacked meaning (Baumeister, 1991). This did not appear to be the case in this present study because offers to engage in activities/interactions were not always accepted, and staff identified how they enhanced choice in activities/interactions with PwAD. However, the possibility that any activity may be welcomed by PwAD, whether it is meaningful or not, raises important considerations for practice and suggests how meaning may be co-created and 'un-created'.

PwAD were observed to engage in other subtle activities such as 'people-watching', which perhaps offered PwAD an indirect way of maintaining social relationships and activity. 'People-watching' is an everyday pastime consisting of observing others in public spaces to satisfy curiosities about social life (Jayne, 2022; 2023). Completed individually or amongst small groups, people-watching can help to obliquely orchestrate social connections (Quadflieg and Penton-Voak, 2017; Jayne, 2023), provide pleasure, and offer opportunities to 'see-and-be-seen' (Stevens, 2007). In this study, 'people-watching' appeared to be an activity that could provide (in)direct social opportunities. For example, when Morag (PwAD) and I noticed another resident watching us from afar whilst we watched others doing a jig-saw puzzle, the mutual act of 'watching' appeared to reinforce and highlight everyone's visibility. As a result, a ripple of interactions commenced through smiles, waves and laughs, appearing to connect Morag (PwAD) herself and others.

A quieter, indirect form of people-watching was seen in Donald and Fraser (PwAD) who initially appeared disengaged from care home life, but on closer inspection, indirectly participated by following others with their eyes and/or pointing at people. This subtle activity could be easily missed (Pink, 2012; Brown, 2016; Bellass *et al.*, 2019), concealing potential meanings in everyday activities and interaction (Pink, 2012; Neal and Murji, 2015). Subtleties were only observable when spending time with PwAD and when rewatching the audio-visual data. Gubrium (1997) noted similar activities in his study about meaning in everyday nursing home life when he described various 'sitting' activities such as chatting, watching, and sleeping. Gubrium (1997) described how these types of activities were more subtle in PwAD but still present, for example, when a person who was bed-bound watched others through an ajar door. More recently, Tierney *et al.* (2023, p. 319) found people with mild to moderate dementia to engage in "*passive participation*", such as watching others or spending time in communal areas. Harding *et al.* (2024) noted similar activities and although these were still described as potentially passive, they were also considered meaningful for some PwD, and the potential for others to overlook these types of activities was suggested. In this current study, the word 'passive' is challenged since these types of activities appeared to be a choice of PwAD to remain indirectly socially engaged, rather than something that was inactive. Thus, the word,

'invisible' is preferred because this type of silent activity appears to rely on others to notice the person's engagement for it to be recognised as an activity, rather than placing responsibility on PwAD.

This finding somewhat supports and develops the work of Temina, Zvonareva and Horstman (2025, p.3) who coined the term, "*invisible participation*". Although their study related to individuals with rare and cancerous diseases rather than PwAD, their overall finding, that everyday participation was unseen because of its spontaneity or mundanity, bears relevance to this current study. Whereas Temina, Zvonareva and Horstman (2025) found everyday participation to be unseen by participants, researchers and policymakers, this study also found that (in)visibility seem to shift. In this current study, the participation of PwAD in activities and interactions may have initially been unseen, however their interests and curiosity, as shown through their bodies, highlighted their participation to themselves and others. Through this illumination, PwAD appeared to reframe the meaning of 'meaningful activities', extending its inference beyond jig-saw puzzles and Activities of Daily Living (ADLs) and turning the everyday into an experience that can be likened to viewing and exploring art in a gallery. This appreciation of the mundane can be seen when revisiting Fraser's (PwAD) interest in the fire door sticker. The way in which Fraser purposefully studied the sticker bore similarities to how one might view a Matisse painting in the Tate Modern, however the mundanity of the sticker, the door and the care home environment elevated prosaic objects and environments as potential aesthetically pleasing experiences and/or spaces for meaning-making. Fraser's interest in the sticker also suggested he was intrinsically motivated to explore the item and took action to achieve this goal in anticipation of an aesthetic reward (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). His satisfied flick of his fingers suggested he had achieved this goal. Furthermore, the act enhanced Fraser's visibility because it was noticed and reciprocated by Judy (staff) and myself, and appeared to co-create meaning by doing so. By responding to Fraser's interest in the sticker, Judy appeared to create further opportunities to reinforce inter-embodied selfhood in a similar way to that described by Jenkins (2013). Everyday creativity in a care home setting therefore seemed to require an ability to notice and sensitise to others, objects and the environment (Bellass *et al.* 2019; Hatton, 2019), in a similar way to how Merleau-Ponty described feeling and sensing the world (1964; 1968).

The findings in this study potentially shift the perspective of what constitutes meaningful activity in PwAD, creating new reflections for care homes and the expectation implied in various literature to always occupy residents (Bowie and Mountain, 1993; Ice, 2002; Morgan-Brown *et al.*, 2011; Ellis and Astell, 2017). Although this concern is valid and relevant because PwAD may be perceived as "*doing nothing*" (Nolan, Grant and Nolan, 1995, p.532; Ellis and

Astell, 2017, p.14), and people with and without dementia living in a care home have themselves reported boredom and a lack of activities (Smith *et al.*, 2018), everyday creativity, subtle, invisible activities/interactions may be overlooked through the lens of 'meaningful activity'. Therefore, meaningful activity for PwAD may be different from what was previously thought. Furthermore, these subtleties may not be recognised by others because of a potential dislocation and tension between the interests of PwAD and socially constructed narratives. This potentially underestimates the role of comfort and safety in meaning-making and risks assuming that only activities that are easily recognisable are meaningful to PwAD. However, this must not be confused with nor endorse unmet needs caused by a lack of meaningful activity (Scholzel-Dorenbos, Meeuwssen and Olde Rikkert, 2010; Smith *et al.*, 2018), which may result in poor quality of life (Wood, Womack, and Hooper, 2009; Boyd *et al.*, 2014; Gebhard and Frank, 2024) and is an abuse of human rights (Steele *et al.*, 2020).

Everyday creativity was also noted in approaches by family members and staff. The approaches used by some family members were adapted to the abilities and perceived interests of PwAD and the continuation of family member roles. By painting Morag's (PwAD) nails and massaging her hands, Rose (family) and Morag co-created a new activity through which they could interact and maintain physical contact, which sustained Rose's caring role. The food used by Sorcha and Amy (both family) was a creative way to keep PwAD awake during visits, and Susan's (family) orchestrated music in response to her dad's mood required her to be intuitively synchronised with his feelings, preferences and responses.

The approaches taken by staff members seemed to encompass practical and performative forms of everyday creativity, both shaped around 'trial and error'. Practical forms of everyday creativity could be seen when staff enhanced the choices of PwAD during mealtimes by physically offering a choice of two different meals, or when staff left therapy dolls around the home to indirectly invite PwAD to interact with them. Other research has described how adapting activities can enhance participation in PwD. Hyden (2014) found that people with early to mid-stage dementia were able to actively participate in joint cooking activities when verbal and tacit prompts were used to support the person. Similarly, Majlesi and Ekstrom (2016) described how a person with moderate dementia co-created cinnamon buns with his wife when visual prompts and (non)verbal instructions were used to compensate for aspects of the activity he was unable to initiate. Likewise, Woodhall and Shaw (2024) found that PwD in long-term care seemed more able to participate in activities when family members adapted activities by providing one-to-one practical support, prompts and encouragement. The current study broadens this literature by including and focussing on PwAD.

Performative forms of everyday creativity emulated from the bodies of staff in their ability to shapeshift according to the needs of PwAD by becoming a police officer, mother or a boss, or change their accent to match the PwAD. Their flexibility was evident when describing how they slid into different personas, with others on standby if their approach did not work. This finding is consistent with that of Kemp *et al.* (2024) who established links between meaningful engagement in dementia practice in assisted living and improvisational theatre skills. Kemp *et al.* (2021; 2024) identified the importance of the following when using improvisation with PwD: continually updating what is known of the person; listening to the way a person uses their body and verbal language; paying attention to ‘the moment’ and adapting ‘the self’ accordingly; and being fully present with the person to maximise opportunities for engagement. This study extends the work of Kemp *et al.* (2021; 2024) by demonstrating similar findings in a different context with a focus on PwAD.

The imagination and intuition required to use everyday creativity to co-create meaning with PwAD in this current study is akin with the philosophical, aesthetic approach to dementia practice by Hughes (2014). Hughes (2014) advocates a multisensory way of relating to and being with PwAD in a shared, attentive and purposeful space to connect with the person, much like the way Katie (staff) sensitively guided Morag (PwAD) on a journey through her photo album. Using touch and her voice with Morag whilst looking at photographs together to co-create Morag’s narrative provided Morag with tactile, audio and visual stimulation that is suggestive of an aesthetic approach. Similarly, Judy stimulated Donald’s (PwAD) curiosity and senses in setting up the trainset to explore with him, which became louder when we got closer leading him to pick up the train and briefly hold it. This type of approach may offer mutual satisfaction and fulfilment. Maslow (1970, pp. 2, 97) described aesthetics as a human need for some individuals, which was indiscernible from cognitive and psychological needs. He defined aesthetic needs as a desire to seek beauty, symmetry and possibly simplicity and how this is expressed through action (Maslow, 1970). This study therefore demonstrates philosophical and theoretical perspectives in practice and shows how aesthetics may be important during meaning-making with some PwAD.

9.3.2.1 Visual representation

Figure 9.2 depicts a visual representation of this finding. Paper, food, objects, images from magazines and paint symbolise the use of everyday creativity by all participant groups. For example, the cookie and the images of cups represent how PwAD and family members often interacted through everyday routines, and the plates of food signify how staff enhanced

opportunities for PwAD to make choices. Sections of the collage were later covered to show how everyday creativity can be missed because of its mundanity.

Figure 9.2 Visual representation of key finding two

9.3.3 Key finding three

To enhance meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD, others may need to understand, acknowledge and validate potential signs of meaning for each person. Meaning in this context may be recognised through the person's awareness and their vocal, physical, sensorial, emotional expression and (in)actions, therefore, close attention must be paid to the person's responses and body to enhance their participation and visibility. This may require collaboration with PwAD, their family members and staff to make sense of living with advanced dementia, co-create a shared language and reframe social rules and expectations.

This key finding is presented through a discussion of how meaning in activities and interactions was recognised, sensed, felt and reciprocated with PwAD. This includes examining how PwAD expressed meaning, how others adapted themselves to post-verbal communication, and how reciprocity, awareness and visibility could both create and obscure meaning in activities and interactions.

Meaning appeared to be expressed through facial expressions, (re)actions, and sometimes words. These were broad in scope and often subtle (Ellis and Astell, 2017), such as mirroring, gentle nods, a purposeful, brief closing of eyes, a tear rolling down the cheek, eye-tracking, smiling with the eyes, and subtle adjustments in posture, such as micro-shrugs or leaning slightly forward/back. Other responses were more obvious like laughter, big smiles, touch, pointing, swaying, dancing, walking away/towards/past, using words, singing, and/or making sounds. This finding was also evident in the literature review (Hansebo and Kihlgren, 2002; Perkins *et al.*, 2015; Ellis and Astell, 2017; Schneider *et al.*, 2019; Watson, 2019), and in recent studies about meaningful engagement with PwAD (Haunch, Downs and Oyebode, 2023; Trudeau, Slotnick and Gately, 2024). Subtle responses in this study were easy to miss and occasions where this happened were evident when repeatedly watching the audio-visual data. Quinn *et al.* (2014) also found that subtleties in post-verbal communication could be easily overlooked, affecting how others interacted with and perceived PwAD, such as when staff reduced attempts to engage the person in activities (Sabat, 2006). The latter was not the case in this study where staff reported consistent attempts to meaningfully engage with PwAD.

It was possible, however for others to incorrectly perceive and interpret meaning in PwAD, which could diminish opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions. For example, when Donald (PwAD) walked away from me, this did not mean he was dissenting as family and staff believed, it meant the opposite. Initially, Donald was not able to verbally ask me to

join him, but he was able to signal this through actions. Upon checking his intentions, it was clear that he was inviting me to accompany him by instructing me to “*hold on*” and emphasising this by offering me his arm. Donald’s daughter, Amy (family) reported times when she ended her visit because care staff believed Donald did not want to return. However, there is a possibility Donald’s actions may have been misinterpreted, that perhaps he was inviting Amy to join him on a walk using the skills available to him at that time, or perhaps he wanted to sit with her in the communal lounge. This is an important finding because opportunities for meaning through social participation may be lost because typical social cues are being applied to PwAD. This suggests that social understandings may require adjustment and reimagination to enhance meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, which may involve others being mindful of and questioning personal assumptions.

Signs of meaning could be seen, sensed and/or emotionally/physically felt through the bodies of PwAD and others. This was highlighted through experiential learning, for instance, when Hamish (PwAD) and I danced, I could feel his emotional responses to the music through his movements. I could feel when he was guiding me, or if he was tired and needed to sit down. This equal ground seemed to enable meaning to be co-created and adjusted with PwAD. This was important because it highlighted the value in experiencing and shaping experiences with PwAD in their everyday context and place (Pipitone and Raghavan, 2017; Morris, 2020). It also suggested that meaning may be synchronised through corporeal, sensorial and movement-based interactions. This finding is consistent with a study by Mittner, Dalby and Gjørnum (2021) who completed an aesthetic analysis of arts interventions with PwD in residential care. The authors described how co-creativity required them to challenge their own assumptions of what constituted a particular activity and instead approach activities and interactions with PwAD with an open mind. This is also resonant in other literature, for example, non-verbal meaning-making in autism research (Delafield-Butt *et al.*, 2020), post-verbal communication with PwAD (Ellis and Astell, 2017; Wood, 2019), and everyday interactions between PwD and care staff (Vrerink *et al.*, 2022).

A similar approach was required when I invited Fraser (PwAD) to interact with the robotic cat. In this shared space in the care home, Fraser responded to the cat using facial expressions and vocalisations, and I (re)adjusted according to the cat and Fraser. This space appeared to open opportunities for meaning to be co-created with no expectations or plans. Multispecies literature has shared similar thoughts, except through human-animal interactions. For instance, Despret (2013, p.51) proposed various possible ways of understanding lived experiences, which he termed, ‘embodied empathy’, when researchers experience and become entangled with the lives of participants by doing, feeling, sensing and thinking with

them rather than cognitively observing (Despret, 2013). Similar thoughts have been shared in research about human-dog interactions (Charles *et al.*, 2024) and human-horse communication (Brandt, 2004, 2006; Dashper, 2019). Thus, this finding affiliates with multispecies literature, emphasising potential areas for cross-disciplinary learning and agrees with the argument presented by Jenkins *et al.* (2021) regarding opportunities for using multispecies perspectives in dementia practice.

Some arts and health literature describe ways of communicating that align with this current study. For example, “*listening with touch*”, is a co-created, inter-corporeal experience used to mutually attend to the self and others during dance performances (Welton, 2010, p.48), and “*aesthetics of care*”, is the sensation of ‘feeling’ amongst humans during theatre performances (Thompson, 2015, p.430; 2020, p.36). More specifically, in their paper presenting two ethnographic studies from hospice and dementia settings, Richardson and Campbell (2024) described the (inter)embodied and material aspects of care, concluding that ‘feeling’, sensing and experiencing the atmosphere played a crucial role in constructing and understanding the lived experience of PwD. From a drama perspective, Hatton (2019) reported on a performance workshop with PwD in residential care, describing the importance of attending to unique post-verbal communication to attune with residents (Kontos, 2004, 2005; Ellis and Astell, 2017). Thus, this current study brings this literature together and asserts that by sensing and feeling PwAD, meaning in activities and interactions can be co-created using authentic approaches to ‘be and do with’ PwAD.

Feeling and sensing in this study involved PwAD and others actively and mutually attuning to all emotions, not just ‘positive’ emotions. ‘Feeling’ another person’s emotions is an inherent human quality (Hughes, 2013) where meaning is created and expressed through the actions of the body (Merleau-Ponty, 1962; Kontos, 2004; 2005) and the rhythm, tone and timbre of the voice (Wood, 2019). Examples include how Hamish (PwAD) empathised with his daughter’s low mood, apparent by a tear in his eye when words were no longer available, and when Fraser (PwAD) said, “*dementia*” amongst other words using a heavy tone and vocalisations which seemed to convey a deep sadness. In keeping with this study, Kontos *et al.* (2017) also highlighted the presence of all emotions in their mixed methods study about people with moderate and severe symptoms of dementia and elder-clowns. The elder-clowns i.e. red-nosed clowns who use improvisation and humour to connect with PwD, observed sadness in subtle actions and responded by ‘being with’ the person and being open to sharing their affect, or they attempted to change the person’s mood. This resonates with how Susan initially acknowledged her dad’s feelings before trying to lift his mood using music, suggesting that meaning can be co-created through listening and responding to the emotions of PwAD.

To enable this to happen, it seems attention to subtleties is needed to notice and validate all emotions. Not attending to feelings of sadness may invalidate PwAD (Feil and Altman, 2004; Feil and Klerk-Rubin, 2012), perhaps resulting in reduced meaning in activities and interactions or withdrawal.

The findings of this current study support previous work that emphasised the importance of authentic approaches to dementia practice, for example, Holstein, Waymack and Parks (2011), Feil and Klerk-Rubin (2012), and Hughes (2019). Holstein, Parks and Waymack (2011, p.128) emphasised the importance of 'authentic caring', an attentive and mindful approach to dementia practice where the person is seen as an active participant in their own care. The Validation Method (Feil and Altman, 2004; Feil and Klerk-Rubin, 2012) is similar in that it attends, responds and adapts to the person's strengths. This method also aims to understand the underlying need of the person, to genuinely see and hear them, orientate to them and seek a common language. In his scoping review, Hughes (2019) linked authenticity in dementia practice to social citizenship, concluding that authentic approaches in dementia practice can maintain the person's 'self' and selves. This current study extends this literature by suggesting that authentic approaches may enhance opportunities to co-create meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

In this study, mutual acknowledgement and reciprocity appeared to create meaning through validation and visibility, or 'seeing and being seen'. For example, on numerous occasions, Katie (staff) linked meaning in activities and interactions to mutual awareness and the ability to know and feel (co)existence. This is important because if opportunities for affirming and validating activities and interactions are limited, the person may no longer feel alive or know that they (co)exist. This resonates with Heidegger's (1962) view of meaning, and Sabat and Harre's (1992) self and selves, as described in Chapter Three. For instance, there were many examples of personal identity in this study because all PwAD expressed themselves using 'I', 'me', 'my' and/or 'myself' (Sabat and Harre, 1992), and/or used gestures such as pointing to themselves or a part of their own body. Examples include Donald's (PwAD) comment: "*in case I forget myself*" in response to my question about why he left his seat to take a brief walk, and when Fraser (PwAD) pointed to and touched his teeth when he saw himself in a photograph. PwAD also showed an awareness of themselves when situated with others (Buber, 1970) by using words such as 'we' and pointing to others during activities and interactions (Sabat and Harre, 1992). Examples include when Morag (PwAD) and I sang the incorrect words to a song and Morag replied, "*we need to get it right*", maintaining her personal values, and when Hamish (PwAD) performed with everyday items to connect with others and to preserve his social identity as an entertainer. These examples suggest the presence of 'ego identity' i.e.

self-awareness of an innate, sensed and visceral quality which remains the same throughout life (Erikson, 1980). They also imply that the self, personal identity, social identity and ego identity are important for (co)creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. However, it would be shortsighted to only view personal identity as 'I and thou' (Buber, 1970), therefore, this current study suggests that the skills, movements and senses within and between bodies are perhaps components or extensions of personal identity (Fuchs, 2020), and that these may change depending on context and the social and physical environment.

The awareness PwAD had of others, objects and the social and physical environment was demonstrated post-verbally in this study and appeared to contribute to meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Awareness can be defined as an implicit or explicit understanding of, or connection to 'the self' and one's surroundings (Clare *et al.*, 2011). In this study, awareness also refers to the person's visibility within the care home setting, other peoples' self-awareness, and their understanding of the PwAD's ability to be aware. For example, Morag (PwAD) demonstrated her awareness of others by attempting to turn her body when she heard other residents' voices and stating she wanted to see who it was, and when Donald and Fraser (PwAD) frequently tracked others with their eyes. These examples could be perceived as reflexive responses; however, the context suggests otherwise. For instance, Fraser (PwAD) sometimes pointed when he tracked others with his eyes, demonstrating a purposeful action which created social connections and showed a desire and a curiosity. If reciprocated, these subtle forms of communication had potential to become an interaction or activity. Sometimes it was not clear how aware PwAD were of others during an activity/interaction, for instance, when Fraser (PwAD) joined in a conversation with Clarissa (staff) and myself with his eyes closed. Fraser made himself visible because we were not aware that he was aware of us. This suggests others' perceptions of the awareness of PwAD could enhance or cloud their visibility and skills.

How PwAD were represented in the care home also seemed to dilute or enhance their existence. For instance, the display of photographs taken by staff of residents during events and activities appeared to carry meaning for family members and have potential to prompt activities and interactions with PwAD. However, if a PwAD was unable/declined to attend, their photograph did not appear on the display which gave the impression that only the residents able to participate in structured activities were visible in the photographs, except for a whole care home event, such as a fish supper. Although individual activities were captured in photographs, they tended to be framed and displayed more permanently around the care home, whereas pictures taken from events were regularly updated and replenished. This made the concept of time seem different for residents who did not attend groups, perhaps

inadvertently signifying and reinforcing the perceptions others had of PwAD (Sabat, 2006; Quinn *et al.*, 2014). In turn, this appeared to affect meaning in activities and interactions because it questioned both the presence of PwAD and assumptions about what was considered an activity worth documenting. Brown (2016) also noted the absence of photographs of people living with similar stages of dementia. Although this was not a key finding, Brown (2016) suggested that family members did not want to formally record this period of the person's life. This was not the case in this study because two family members reported the importance of these photographs to show how PwAD had spent their day. Additionally, the previously described photograph of Fraser (PwAD), which was publicly displayed in the care home offered an opportunity to reinforce his identity and express his opinion whilst initiating an interaction with Judy (staff). Therefore, this study enhances the literature by suggesting the presence of PwAD in the care home through photographs and the like may offer opportunities to (co)create meaning for PwAD and family members, and that although these meanings may differ for each participant group, they may ultimately reinforce the self and selves of PwAD.

Contrary to reports from some family members and staff, awareness of 'the self' was evident in all PwAD, and this appeared meaningful in activities and interactions. For instance, when Donald (PwAD) and Herbert (staff) waved at the iPad, and when Fraser (PwAD) recognised his teeth by pointing to a photograph of himself, then pointing to his mouth and touching his teeth while communicating with Judy (staff) using purposeful blinking, opening and closing his mouth and widening his eyes. However, enhancing the visibility of PwAD was not always positive, illustrated by Morag's (PwAD) response to herself in the iPad. This situation suggests she had the ability to make self-judgements, (Clare, 2010), and that self-esteem and self-image may be meaningful to some PwAD during interactions with others. This is similar to the 'Hair and care Project' (Ward and Campbell, 2013; Ward, Campbell and Keady, 2014; Ward, Campbell and Keady, 2016) in which mixed methods were used to understand the meanings of appearance for people with different stages of dementia. Meaning in haircare activities was found in self-expression, (inter)embodied practices, and in spotlighting the identities of PwD through participation and social citizenship (Ward, Campbell and Keady, 2016). This suggests that identity may be a continuation of the past and present, which is somewhat influenced by how others' perceptions of PwAD (Kitwood, 1997b; Hughes, 2001). This is expanded in this finding which also acknowledged the person in the future, as indicated by some staff members. Conversely, this study also contradicts the idea of continuity as two staff members perceived PwAD as a 'new' person with a new life upon moving into the care home.

9.3.3.1 Visual representation

Figure 9.3 depicts a visual representation of this finding. Magazine pictures, coloured paper and paint were used to demonstrate the importance of the bodies of PwAD to signify meaning and participation in activities and interactions. The repeated outlines and silhouettes communicate movement, expression and (in)visibility.

Figure 9.3 Visual representation of key finding three

9.3.4 Key finding four

Co-occupations i.e. activities performed with the person to combine skills appear to have potential to co-create meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD. Meaning can fluctuate, be (a)synchronous, interrupted, revisited, co-created and/or recreated within this shared space. Opportunities for meaning-making may arise if others, objects, activities and/or the environment are 'in-sync' with PwAD, whereas focussing on tasks, plans, routines, realities or time-related issues like the 'past' may be 'out-of-sync' with PwAD, inhibiting meaning-making opportunities. Several other factors may affect synchronicity with PwAD, including the intended meaning of others, how others and PwAD interpret meaning, socially constructed narratives, unsuitable activities and/or the physical and social environment.

This key finding is presented through a discussion about co-occupations, an exploration of an intended meaning and implied meanings, and (a)synchronisation with PwAD. This involves exploring how others may perceive PwAD, temporality, and adapting the self, the activity and the environment.

Meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD appeared to be co-created through co-occupation. Co-occupation is when two or more people actively participate in the same activity (Pickens and Pizur-Barnekow, 2009; van Nes *et al.*, 2012), as opposed to a shared activity in which people participate alongside others (Pierce, 2003). Pierce (2003) suggests that co-occupation is an interactive, interdependent and synchronous act which does not require a shared goal, meaning or time, but is crafted through a dialogue of 'doing' (Pierce, 2009). In this study, co-occupations were often collaboratively adapted and negotiated with PwAD, through which meaning seemed to be co-created. For instance, when Morag (PwAD) and I played the drums and sang together, we experimented with different rhythms, tempos and sounds to co-create a conversation; sometimes this was 'call and response' i.e. a form of reciprocity when one of us 'replied' to a sound the other had made, using sound. During this activity, we relied on one another and encouraged each other to co-create meaning by participating and learning together, and were physically, emotionally and sensorily entangled (Hyden, 2014; Majlesi and Ekstrom, 2016; Woodhall and Shaw, 2024). This was important because we were both equally new to this activity since I was not attempting to teach Morag how to play drums, rather the drum was brought to Morag to invite her on a mutual exploration of sound, movement and rhythm, and she chose to participate by using words and movement. This type of mutual learning was also found during an evaluation of a music project with PwD, their family/friends and professional musicians and singers (McCabe, Greasley-Adams and Goodson, 2015). An outcome of the evaluation was the equal learning space created through co-occupation, which seemed to equalise the power in relationships through mutually experiencing a new activity (McCabe, Greasley-Adams and Goodson, 2015). This current study extends these outcomes by demonstrating how co-occupation in new activities can provide opportunities to co-create meaning on an everyday level with PwAD as opposed to during structured music sessions.

These findings resonate with literature which explores meaningful engagement with PwD, for example, "*relational presence*" (Kontos *et al.*, 2017, p.2), and "*promoting dialogicality*" (Jenkins, 2013, p.9-10). 'Relational presence' is a way in which PwAD and others can actively engage in a mutual process of 'doing' and 'being' where PwAD are seen as valuable contributors (Kontos *et al.*, 2017), and 'promoting dialogicality' is a space through which PwAD and others can merge, share and transform to create a new narrative. Intercorporeality is an

important concept here, defined as a mutual reliance of bodies to orientate and orchestrate daily life (Ward, Campbell and Keady, 2016). This construct is thought to enhance the participation of PwAD in musical activities by combining and synchronising sensory-motor skills to enable individual expression that would not be achievable alone (Zeiler, 2014). The current study is consistent with this literature.

Co-occupations could also occur when PwAD became the teacher. An example is the game of Boules with Donald (PwAD), which was an activity he had previously enjoyed. The game was adapted for the care home lounge, by bringing the Boules to Donald and inviting him to play, similarly to how the drum was introduced to Morag (PwAD). It seemed important to bring the activity to Donald to enhance his active engagement by providing a visual prompt. This time, rather than equally lacking in knowledge, Donald knew more about this activity than I did, which was evident in his movements and handling of the Boule. Thus, I learnt from Donald by watching the way he used his body to roll the Boule and we synchronised with the Boules, the game and the environment. This demonstrates how PwAD may still be able to pass skills onto others, which may reinforce 'the self' and change socially constructed narratives.

Socially constructed narratives of PwAD appeared to continually change according to information about the person at any given time. There appeared to be to kaleidoscope of meaning-making possibilities which could change according to the (a)synchronicity of interactions between PwAD and others. For instance, Amy (family) and staff generally constructed a narrative of Donald (PwAD) determining that when he walked away during an activity/interaction, he no longer wished to participate. However, there were other possible explanations which did not necessarily mean disengagement. For instance, when Donald did not appear to be able to verbally invite me on a walk, he was able to *show* me that he wanted me to accompany him by lifting his arm for me to link with him. On another occasion when he walked to and from the bathroom mid-conversation, his response indicated that he needed movement to remind himself of his own existence. These examples illuminate the importance of examining socially constructed narratives of PwAD because if the social narratives of PwAD become 'facts', opportunities for meaning-making between PwAD, family members and staff may be diluted or impeded. This finding resonates with some of the empirical and conceptual literature discussed in Chapters Two and Three, particularly the work of Sabat and Harre (1992), Harre (1998), Gubrium and Holstein (1999), Holst, Edberg and Hallberg (1999), Smith and Sparkes (2008) and Brockmeier (2009). Additionally, a study by Bowes *et al.* (2022) which explored movement in care homes from the perspective of residents, family and staff also found links between how others perceived people with cognitive impairment and opportunities for activity. This study extends this literature by showing how socially constructed narratives

can change according to the context, and how opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions can be enhanced if these narratives are fluidly used to co-create meaning with PwAD rather than being applied to all situations.

The social construction of the selves of PwAD was seen during the workshop with family members and staff. For family members, meaning seemed to be co-created when information about PwAD represented their participation and visibility in the care home. For staff, information from family seemed to change how they perceived PwAD. For both groups, meaning appeared to be enhanced through a sense-making process through which information about PwAD was metaphorically collaged. Dervin (2003, p.139) describes sense-making as a fluid, non-linear cognitive, emotive, imaginative act which connects the past, present and future person in time, space and context. Örluv and Hyden (2006) interchangeably used meaning-making and sense-making in their study about confabulation and PwAD. They concluded that sense-making is a process which is co-created with others from information about the person's social and physical environment, their current context and their life history, which is neither true nor false but makes sense given the actions of the person (Örluv and Hyden, 2006). Similarly, in a narratives-in-action study by Tatzler (2019), shared stories were co-created with people with moderate and advanced dementia, family members and staff using words and actions, and seemed meaningful because they maintained the identities of PwD. Sense-making is also described in the models of meaning by Baumeister (1991), Derx (2013) and Derx *et al.* (2020), thus linking theory to practice.

In this current study, socially constructed narratives appeared to inform an intended meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, which were initiated by family members, staff or myself. There also seemed to be an implied meaning, which was (co)created in the moment. Sometimes intended meanings and implied meanings synchronised, and at other times they seemed to be 'out-of-sync' or fluctuating. To illustrate, the intended meaning in the jig-saw puzzle Amy (family) attempted with Donald (PwAD) seemed related to maintaining their relationship and reconnecting Donald with himself through a pre-loved activity. However, Donald appeared uninterested in the jigsaw, which perhaps represented a different period of his life, therefore the implied meaning may have illuminated difficulties that were incongruent with his current skills and interests, resulting in him withdrawing from the activity and Amy. Similar tensions were described in an ethnographic study by Harding *et al.* (2024) between PwD living in the community and their carers, when PwD were encouraged to complete activities that were incongruent with their current abilities. This highlights the importance of others reflecting on the meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD rather than their own motivations. It also suggests the importance of understanding *why* an activity may be/have

been meaningful before attempting to (re)introduce it so that the person's values synchronise with their current skills and preferences; this may enhance opportunities for meaning to be co-created and for synchronicity to occur.

Similarly, a review of meaningful engagement and person-centred care for people with moderate to advanced dementia found that occupational therapists focused on the person's previously enjoyed activities, roles and routines without understanding why the person engaged in them (Du Toit, Shen and McGrath, 2019). This unwittingly neglected the person's opportunities to explore new activities, consequently inhibiting their agency, growth and social citizenship (Du Toit, Shen and McGrath, 2019). Likewise, in a synthesis of qualitative literature about meaningful activity from the perspectives of people with varying stages of dementia, Han *et al.* (2016) found that PwD were less likely to engage in activities if they were not aligned with the core meanings and values of a previously enjoyed hobby, even when the activity was adapted to suit the person's skills. This current study extends this literature by presenting the idea of an intended meaning and implied meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD and linking this to (a)synchronicity.

Being 'in sync' appears to have similarities with the 'attunement' described in various disciplines, including developmental psychology, psychotherapy, health, music (Krøier, McDermott and Ridder, 2022) and art therapy (Kossak, 2023). In terms of dementia, attunement is defined as a mutual and reciprocal process where PwAD and another person metaphorically feel and sense one another to enhance communication and aim for synchronisation (Krøier, McDermott and Ridder, 2022). To achieve synchronisation, the other person must intuitively listen to the post-verbal communication of PwAD and match themselves accordingly (Jost, Neumann and Himmelmann, 2010; Krøier, McDermott and Ridder, 2022). Variations of synchronisation with PwAD was described in a study by Isene *et al.* (2021a) where healthcare professionals attempted to align with the person's realities and situation, communicate with PwAD or manage relationships with PwAD. In this current study, synchronicity appeared to be achieved when others adapted their own pacing and timing to match the person's tempo by observing the person's (in)actions and embodied communication. Examples include Susan's (family) efforts to self-monitor the speed at which she spoke, describing how she slowed her sentences and allowed space inbetween to give her dad time to process and respond. Similarly, I learnt to 'listen' and 'feel' Fraser's (PwAD) (re)actions and realised that I moved and spoke too quickly, hence I mindfully slowed myself down, which required insight and self-awareness (Jost, Neumann and Himmelmann, 2010; Hatton, 2019). Pacing 'the self' to match the PwAD was also observed between PwAD and staff, for example, when Morag (PwAD) and Katie (staff) looked at the photograph album

together and Morag hesitated when Katie attempted to turn the page, prompting Katie to slow down. This resonates with the literature review, particularly the work of Ellis and Astell (2017) and Wood (2019).

Literature about pacing in dementia practice recommends that activities and interactions are slowed down to synchronise with PwAD (Feil, 1993; Brooker and Kitwood, 2019; Jost, Neumann and Himmelmann, 2010; Hatton, 2019), a concept which is applied to 'slow nursing' with PwD (Lillekroken, Hauge and Slettebø, 2017; Lillekroken, 2020). Slow nursing is an evolving term that incorporates a caring approach to PwD focussing on one aspect at a time and on 'the moment' (Lillekroken, Hauge and Slettebø, 2017). Although three PwAD in this study seemed to require this type of approach, this was often not suited to Donald (PwAD). When Judy (staff) worked with Donald, she incorporated numerous activities into one session to satisfy his need for quick activities and stimulation. When Donald abruptly left the trainset activity to go for a walk, Judy was observed to speed up to catch up with him. Additionally, the pace was not always consistent. For example, Hamish (PwAD) sometimes required a slow approach but at other times, I needed to speed up my own thoughts or actions to correspond with his pace and mood, such as when he was quick-witted or performed a spontaneous comedic kick. This current study therefore broadens the literature by asserting that activities and interactions do not always need to be slow to co-create meaning since some people require the opposite. What seems important is to match and mirror the person's pace to reinforce their sense of (co)existence and create a connection.

As suggested in the literature review in Chapter Four, the meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD in this study did not seem to depend on their duration - momentary activities and interactions with PwAD could also be meaningful. Duration can be described as a concept which is continuously sensed, felt and changing as opposed to a construct which measures fractured time in units and risks veiling what lies between (Bergson, 1946). This is a helpful lens to explore the momentary activities in this current study which appeared to be fluid and dynamic as opposed to linear or static. This was clarified when staff described how meaning may appear to have been lost but could be recreated by using multisensory prompts such as photographs and accompanying spoken narratives. This finding is consistent with a synthesis of six qualitative studies by Keady *et al.* (2020) who identified a continuum of 'in the moment' interactions with people with varying stages of dementia. Keady *et al.* (2020) described 'being in the moment' as meaningful, sensory, relational or individual experiences embedded in the life histories of PwAD and the current context, which may be transient or extended. Similarly to this current study, Keady *et al.* (2020) identified how moments could be recreated, thereby linking the past to the present. This study aligns with and deepens the research by Keady *et*

al. (2020) by demonstrating how 'the moment' may be created through and with everyday activities and interactions with PwAD.

In the present study, there appeared to be tensions between situating PwAD in the past, present and future which appeared to impact upon synchronicity and the associated meaning. Examples include when family members and/or staff perceived PwAD to be in a different world or reality from them, and when PwAD were compared to their past or invited to do activities that were not adapted to their current skills and interests. Activities and interactions were often adapted by staff to match the person's life history and their present skills and interests which were 'banked' for future use. Techniques such as chaining and adapting the self/activity/environment seemed to enable the person to participate in activities and interactions in the present and enhance opportunities for synchronicity. The trainset activity with Donald (PwAD) provides a good illustration. Although collecting trains was a previously enjoyed activity for Donald, he was uninterested when this activity was static i.e. one of his trains being presented to him in its original box. However, when Judy (staff) introduced him to a working model railway which provided visual and auditory stimulation, Donald's curiosity and motivation were stimulated, enticing him to touch the train and pick it up, which provided an opportunity for Judy to interact with him. The animated train seemed to synchronise his previous interests of collecting model trains with his current skills, potentially creating a legacy for the future. A study by Isene *et al.* (2021b) also found meaning-making with people with severe dementia to be co-created through corporeal, sensory and social experiences, although they associated meaning with past, familiar experiences, not the present or future. This current study therefore initiates a rich and diverse discussion about temporality and reality, both in general terms and regarding PwAD, particularly since all people, whether they live with advanced dementia or not, experience time differently from one another (Deng, 2019).

The past, present and future self/selves of PwAD seemed iterative, therefore, if others were not synchronised with the temporal narrative of PwAD, momentary opportunities for meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD could be missed. For instance, when Hamish (PwAD) sang "*get off me barra*" during Lunch Club in the care home rather than at home with his children as he had done in the past, he did not receive the typical response of laughter. This may have been because others were not aware of this information and/or they did not hear him in the group setting. Even though I was aware of the importance of this narrative in Hamish's life, I only heard him sing this when watching and re-watching the audio-visual data. This highlights the importance of family members and staff sharing key information about PwAD in the past and present to continually update the narrative of PwAD (Jenkins, 2013) in a manner which feeds-forward and feeds-back. Keady *et al.* (2020) described a similar

situation which highlighted how moments such as the one described here require family members and care staff to be attentive and responsive to marry the present with the past, enhancing opportunities for the co-creation of momentary experiences. It is these easily missed aspects of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD which this current study managed to capture through the AR methodology, creative methods and audio-visual data, offering a further contribution to knowledge.

9.3.4.1 Visual representation

Figure 9.4 depicts a visual representation of this finding. Different colours of ink were dropped into water and photographs were taken as the colours dispersed to represent the fluidity and changeability of PwAD and meaning. The different colours represent PwAD and family members, staff or myself to communicate the merging of selves during co-occupations and synchronised activities/interactions. The reflections in the water are a reminder of the impact of the social and physical environment upon meaning-making opportunities. The reflections of the window in the images also signify how PwAD may be thought to live in a different reality from family members and staff. This is emphasised by the reflection changing as the inks merge.

Figure 9.4 Visual representation of key finding four

9.4 Original contribution to knowledge

This study has provided an understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD living in a care home that did not previously exist. It has done this by shifting the definition of meaning, activities and interactions in this context and has highlighted how PwAD and their participation in activities and interactions can be invisible and hidden amongst the everyday. Furthermore, it has altered the perspective of activities and interactions with PwAD by exploring what these may look like with PwAD, including micro-activities such as admiring paper and fire door stickers, looking behind doors and into baskets, and creating opportunities for PwAD to investigate the environment, for instance, by leaving therapy dolls for their discovery.

The AR methodology and flexible, creative, audio-visual methods enabled the active inclusion of PwAD in keeping with their everyday lives, which alongside the perspectives of family members and staff, created a richer, deeper understanding of the phenomenon at hand. Furthermore, AR provided opportunities for reciprocal learning, action and change with a population who are often perceived as being unable to directly contribute to research. Rather than excluding this group based on assumptions about their capabilities, using ill-fitting research designs (Webb *et al.*, 2020), or relying purely on observational data, this study has made a methodological contribution by actively including PwAD using multi-modal methods to match their everyday lives. As a result, this study has shown how research methodologies and methods can be adapted to suit PwAD, thus amplifying their voices. Additionally, the creative approach to reflexivity, learning and understanding throughout all stages of the research process has added a unique contribution to academia and demonstrated an alternative way to complete a doctoral degree that may inspire those who do not consider themselves to be intellectually aligned with higher education.

My own neurodiversity arguably enabled me to create a common understanding with PwAD. This seemed to add further depth to the findings, which could be experienced and felt. This experiential learning was invaluable and provided knowledge that other methods may not have generated. Neurodiversity also offered an alternative approach to all aspects of research, potentially showing other neurodiverse students a 'way into' and 'way through' academia.

By exploring 'meaning *in* activities' rather than 'meaningful activity', this study has contributed to how the *concept* of meaning can be understood and applied *with* a population often neglected in dementia studies. This study has developed the concept of meaning in relation to activities and interactions with PwAD, firstly through the literature review, secondly by exploring the conceptual literature, and lastly by developing this through direct study with PwAD, their family members and staff. Therefore, the concept of meaning has evolved from a

superficial, unclear understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD to a rich understanding which broadens opportunities in care home practice.

These original contributions to care home practice may benefit PwAD, family members and staff by providing insights into how meaning *in* activities and interactions can be enhanced and applied to everyday life rather than exploring 'meaningful activities', which may have offered more formal interventions. Examples include ensuring the person's physical, emotional and sensory needs are met, and using everyday creativity, authentic, mindful approaches, co-occupations and reflective practice. Additional learning suggests other people, activities, interactions and the social and physical environment can be adapted to (in)directly offer opportunities for PwAD to (co)create meaning. Moreover, possible links between meaning and context illuminates the care home as a potential space for everyday creativity where performance, humour and playfulness can form part of care home routines. Findings also highlight that immobile PwAD may be exposed to participation in unmeaningful activities and interactions and be more reliant on others to (co)create meaning. This knowledge may help family and staff to use mindful approaches when co-creating meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD who are immobile.

Furthermore, discovering that potentially meaningful activities for PwAD may be unseen or disregarded by others opens opportunities for family and staff to sensitise themselves to everyday aesthetics to enhance and/or share these experiences with PwAD. The finding that PwAD may need their (co)existence to be confirmed suggests they may feel unseen and invisible. This insight may enhance the awareness of this existential issue and emphasise how simple acts such as appropriate touch and saying 'hello' may co-create meaning by validating PwAD. Findings suggest that family and staff require opportunities for sensemaking and exploration of any tensions, for example, when activities and interactions may be (un)meaningful for PwAD. These opportunities may also create space for narratives about PwAD to be socially constructed, which may be meaningful for all involved. However these are likely to require regular updates to avoid information becoming static, for instance, to consider other possibilities for the (in)actions of PwAD rather than assuming a person is sleeping or bored if their eyes are closed, or that they are dissenting if they walk away.

9.5 Strengths and limitations

It is rare for PwAD to be actively included in research, particularly AR. Therefore, a major strength of this study was the active inclusion of PwAD, assisted by a flexible and creative methodology and methods, which became a meaningful process itself. Direct engagement

with PwAD was essential to feel and sense embodied communication and become closer to the voices of PwAD, which were re-lived and re-sensed through audio-visual methods. Through this experiential learning, PwAD taught me how to co-create meaning by listening and communicating through the body (Mittner, Dalby, and Gjørnum, 2021; Kemp *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, the perspectives of PwAD, their family members and staff added enabled meaning in activities and interactions to be considered from a variety of viewpoints, providing rich, diverse data.

Being both a researcher and participant in this study provided embodied and experiential learning opportunities, which added to the depth of the findings and revealed a felt and sensed insight into living with advanced dementia that would not have occurred with traditional methods. Through this experiential learning approach, I was able to reflect on how I felt about/perceived PwAD and how they received me, (co)creating meaning in activities and interactions as they unfolded. This required a self-aware and mindful approach to relinquish control. Surrendering control appeared to rely on improvisation, flexibility and releasing pre-planned ideas or assumptions. The literature review and conceptual meaning chapters provided the backdrop for this research design, which amplified the voices of PwAD.

Creative approaches to Doctoral study enabled academia to be adapted to my neurodiversity by acting as a tool for learning, reflection and documentation. Creative approaches enhanced personal meaning of this journey and reinforced my sense of self when I encountered challenges.

As explained in Section 4.19, a relativist approach to validity was selected for this study (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013; Smith and McGannon, 2018). This was a strength because it supported a flexible approach to assessing rigour, which was helpful given the changeability of activities and interactions with PwAD in a care home environment (Sparkes and Smith, 2009). This is strongest in the characterising trait, 'Localising research practices/methods', where research methods and analysis were personalised according to the everyday lives of PwAD (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). This approach enabled the research to 'fit' *all* participants, and particularly PwAD, because the flexibility and adaptability of the methodology, methods and myself as a research tool were able to shift according to the mood, interests and needs of PwAD (Webb *et al.*, 2020). This worked well with the fluidity required when seeking assent and dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010) as a form of process consent (Dewing, 2008). Combined, these approaches complemented one another and supported the evaluation of rigour throughout the whole research process, not just at completion (Gray and

Malins, 2004; Cypress, 2017). See the in-depth reflections of the methodology and methods in Chapter Five for further insights.

From another perspective, action, change and learning were demonstrated amongst some family members and staff, which is also suggestive of rigour in AR (Herr and Anderson, 2005; McNiff, 2013). This was mostly evident in Phase Three, which is reflective of skill-sharing, learning and legacy in the characterising trait, 'Community capacity building' (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013). Plans to improve and expand their practice described by some staff suggests the cycles of AR continued after the study ended. Furthermore, these plans were self-initiated by staff through the AR process and were an unexpected outcome, implying the research topic aligned with the values and interests of participants (Schinke, Smith and McGannon, 2013).

There are several limitations of this study. The pandemic greatly impacted and restricted this study, the lives of participants and care home practices, therefore it is likely that meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD was also affected. Furthermore, COVID-19 restrictions limited interaction between family members and staff, therefore, focus groups could only be facilitated between staff members as opposed to family members and staff. However, there were also some advantages to completing this research study during a pandemic. For example, the availability, type and range of activities were limited, and family members were unable to attend group activities. This may have reduced the potential for care home experiences to be embellished, potentially revealing fundamental meaning in everyday activities and interactions. By exploring the minutia of the everyday, unusual opportunities arose to explore the rich tapestry of the ordinary, which perhaps simultaneously revealed and (un)tangled its complexity (Neal and Murji, 2015). Through this lens, the pandemic may have provided a more genuine understanding of meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD.

Further limitations include ethical approval being sought for all three phases at once rather than the preferred staggered approach of applying for ethical approval before each phase to maximise co-creativity. The reasons for this were time restrictions in terms of PhD completion requirements combined with pandemic-related delays to the ethical approval process. Additionally, and sadly, the short life expectancy of PwAD was also a decision factor.

Although the methods of data collection and analysis were a strength of this study, creative approaches and audio-visual data was labour-intensive, making it difficult within the constraints of a funded PhD with one researcher. Furthermore, data was collected at one site during the hours of 10am and 4pm, therefore the findings may have been different if data had

been collected from other sites/at other times. While the days/times for data collection were purposely varied to accommodate family and staff member availability, data collection was further restricted by care home routines. Additionally, since Kitwood's (1993; 1997a) person-centred approach and theoretical framework has heavily influenced health and social care (Terkelsen, Petersen and Kristensen, 2020) and as this current study includes care home staff, it is reasonable to assume that their interpretation of meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD may closely align with Kitwood's (1993; 1997a) views. Moreover, the site for this study consistently received positive feedback from the care Inspectorate, hence the findings may vary in care homes with different profiles.

9.6 Implications and recommendations

These findings highlight learning for education, health and social care research, policy and care home practice, as follows:

9.6.1 Education

- Health and social care education programmes should include a focus on meaning *in* activities and interactions for PwAD where relevant. This should include space to explore assumptions towards/perceptions of PwAD, how PwAD may express meaning, and discussions about socially constructed narratives and the social and physical environment to explore how these may impact meaning-making opportunities. This should include experiential pedagogies where appropriate, for example, a sensory tour of the environment. PwD, their family members and care home staff should be included in the design and delivery of these modules to ensure they are embedded in and reflect the lived experience;
- Alternative approaches to learning to be offered to *all* students, even at Doctoral level. For example, using music and/or visual arts to reflect on learning or to use as a writing prompt. Universities will need to provide appropriate resources and spaces to enable 'messy' work, e.g. a room where work using different mediums can be created/displayed;
- Universities to expand their disability services to offer specific sessions about navigating academia in a way that makes sense to and celebrates the strengths and interests of individual students.

9.6.2 Research

- PwAD should be involved in research exploring their lived experiences using methods that can be adapted to their skills and interests;
- Researchers exploring the lived experiences of PwAD to be provided with appropriate support and training to explore and implement creative, flexible methods which suit post-verbal, embodied communication;
- Researchers to seek assent/dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010) from PwAD as part of recruitment processes and to continue this approach throughout data collection as a form of process consent (Dewing, 2008). This is likely to focus on assent/dissent for the researchers' presence rather than the person's participation in the study;
- Audio-visual methods to be used to analyse post-verbal, embodied communication. To sufficiently resource studies using these methods due to potentially large volumes of data. Research on the use of audio-visual methods with PwAD is also recommended.
- The following areas of further study are recommended:
 - Intended and implied meanings in activities and interactions to be explored with PwAD, family members and care home staff;
 - Visibility and (co)existence of PwAD to be examined in relation to meaning-making;
 - Social expectations/assumptions/rules to be investigated with people who use post-verbal, embodied communication, their family members and others who support the person;
 - To explore invisible participation in activities and interactions of interest to PwAD;
 - To study meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD who are immobile, potentially from a human rights perspective;
 - To examine flow and transcendence in PwAD.

9.6.3 Policy

- Guidelines such as the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN) to highlight meaning in activities and interactions as an important part of *everyday life* for PwAD, alongside suggestions and illustrations of how this can be achieved;
- To emphasise the importance of understanding meaning in activities and interactions when recommending meaningful activities for PwAD;

- When describing the changing needs of PwAD (Healthcare Improvement Scotland, 2023; Burton, Soiza and Quinn, 2024), to ensure meaningful activities are situated in past, present and future selves rather than only referring to previously enjoyed activities;
- To review the purpose, efficacy, usefulness and meaningfulness of care plans for PwAD to ensure they align with the person's current interests and abilities and are relevant for practice. For new guidelines to be issued accordingly.

9.6.4 Care home practice

The following recommendations acknowledge care home staff as skilled practitioners; they are intended as a response to the learning from this research to continue the legacy of AR.

- To provide the workforce with the skills required to enhance the everyday lives of PwAD (Hanson *et al.*, 2019). To maximise the interests, skills and participation of PwAD, managers should encourage all staff training in the following areas: everyday creativity; performance/improvisation skills and how these can be used in everyday activities/interactions; authentic approaches; and adapting the self, activities/interactions and the social and physical environment. Where appropriate, family members/friends of PwAD should be involved to nourish co-learning;
- Managers to facilitate supportive reflexive opportunities for care home staff to review meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, perhaps as part of group supervision and/or Action Learning Sets;
- Managers and staff to consider ways in which family members and care home staff can collaboratively create a 'tip sheet' for enhancing meaning in activities and interactions for PwAD and to share this with other care homes for legacy learning;
- Managers to offer family members and staff a sensory tour of the care home to help them make sense of the experience of living with advanced dementia;
- For managers and staff to assess the social and physical environment to identify how meaning in activities and interactions can be enhanced, either directly or indirectly, for example, by leaving appropriate items in areas for PwAD to discover. Other ideas include helping with household jobs such as folding washing and watering the garden (Jepson *et al.*, 2023);
- PwAD should be invited to participate in new activities alongside appropriately adapted previously enjoyed activities to provide opportunities for self-discovery and curiosity;
- Frequent opportunities should be provided for family members and staff to share learning and skills and to regularly review any assumptions about PwAD, for example

to explore other explanations for (in)action. This may broaden opportunities for activities and interactions with PwAD, their family members and staff;

- Staff to enhance choice and participation for all PwAD by ‘doing with’ rather than ‘doing to’ PwAD, including those who are immobile. This may be achieved by reimagining meaningful activities by focussing on meaning in everyday life, and by combining skills when attempting a task.
- For staff to be mindful of empowering PwAD who are immobile to make choices regarding their participation in activities and interactions and to consider this throughout the session, for example to attend to the person’s body for signs of (un)meaning and to act accordingly if the person expresses a wish to leave the activity through their body and/or words;
- For family members and staff to consider if one-to-one activities and interactions with PwAD are more appropriate than group sessions, where the PwAD assents.

9.7 Conclusion

This study explored the meaning *in* activities and interactions for PwAD, meeting the aims and objectives and answering the research question through four key findings. An original contribution to knowledge has been evidenced through these findings, including directly and actively researching with PwAD, their family members and care home staff rather than only relying on the latter perspectives. Furthermore, the creative, multi-modal methods enhanced the participation of PwAD, supporting an insight into the lived experience of meaning in activities and interactions. The creative methods used to document, reflect on and process learning has also offered an original contribution to academia by demonstrating a different way of navigating research.

The everyday is often described as mundane, but in this study, the everyday was rich with meaning. Meaning *in* activities and interactions with PwAD can be unseen or overlooked. The participation of PwAD can seem invisible, as can the person themselves. But PwAD are there and able to (co)create meaning given the opportunity to do so. PwAD in this study demonstrated a desire to know, a curiosity and a need for meaning. To reveal and see meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD, a different way of looking at the world using everyday creativity and an ability to *notice* is required to see its potential. PwAD seemed to have this ability and there is much to be learnt from observing their post-verbal, embodied communication and from ‘doing with’ them. Everyday creativity is all around us and this may be key to enhancing meaning in activities and interactions with PwAD.

My experience researching with PwAD, their family members and staff was invaluable and I will be forever grateful for the opportunities they provided. The PwAD taught me a great deal about meaning in activities and interactions and prompted me to reflect on my own approaches towards PwAD. PwAD have a fundamental human right to participate in research and I firmly believe that researchers need to adapt themselves and select appropriate methodologies and methods to authentically invite PwAD to collaborate in research.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Literature review data analysis techniques

A1.1 Data analysis stages of literature review: paperchains

A1.2 Data analysis stages of literature review: early mind-map

A1.3 Data analysis stages of literature review: movable collage

Appendix 2: Literature review series of mind maps

A2.1 Literature review: exploratory mind map of data

A2.2 Literature review: mindmap of early themes

A2.3 Literature review: mindmap of final themes

Appendix 3: Ethics approval letter

Scotland A Research Ethics Committee

Research Ethics Service
2nd Floor Waverley Gate
2-4 Waterloo Place
Edinburgh
EH1 3EG
www.hra.nhs.uk

Enquiries to: Manx Neill
Work Mobile: 07814609032
E-mail: [REDACTED]

28 September 2021

Dr Margaret Brown
Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice,
University of the West of Scotland
Lanarkshire Campus,
Stephenson Place
Hamilton International Technology Park,
South Lanarkshire
G72 0LH

Dear Dr Brown,

Study title:	Understanding meaning in activities and interactions when living with advanced dementia: A qualitative Participatory Action Research study
REC reference:	21/SS/0056
Protocol number:	N/A
IRAS project ID:	277401

Thank you for your letter of , responding to the Research Ethics Committee's (REC) request for further information on the above research and submitting revised documentation.

The further information has been considered on behalf of the Committee by the Chair and the Lead & Second Reviewers.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation as revised, subject to the conditions specified below.

Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000

I confirm that the Committee has approved this research project for the purposes of the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000. The Committee is satisfied that the requirements of section 51 of the Act will be met in relation to research carried out as part of this project on, or in relation to, a person who lacks capacity to consent to taking part in the project.

The [UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Research](#) sets out principles of good practice in the management and conduct of health and social care research. It also outlines the responsibilities of individuals and organisations, including those related to the four elements of [research transparency](#):

Chair-Dr Ian Zealley
Vice-Chair-Dr Mary-Joan MacLeod

1. [registering research studies](#)
2. [reporting results](#)
3. [informing participants](#)
4. [sharing study data and tissue](#)

Conditions of the favourable opinion

The REC favourable opinion is subject to the following conditions being met prior to the start of the study.

Confirmation of Capacity and Capability (in England, Northern Ireland and Wales) or NHS management permission (in Scotland) should be sought from all NHS organisations involved in the study in accordance with NHS research governance arrangements. Each NHS organisation must confirm through the signing of agreements and/or other documents that it has given permission for the research to proceed (except where explicitly specified otherwise).

Guidance on applying for HRA and HCRW Approval (England and Wales)/ NHS permission for research is available in the Integrated Research Application System.

For non-NHS sites, site management permission should be obtained in accordance with the procedures of the relevant host organisation.

Sponsors are not required to notify the Committee of management permissions from host organisations

Registration of Clinical Trials

All research should be registered in a publicly accessible database and we expect all researchers, research sponsors and others to meet this fundamental best practice standard.

It is a condition of the REC favourable opinion that **all clinical trials are registered** on a publicly accessible database within six weeks of recruiting the first research participant. For this purpose, 'clinical trials' are defined as the first four project categories in IRAS project filter question 2. Failure to register a clinical trial is a breach of these approval conditions, unless a deferral has been agreed by or on behalf of the Research Ethics Committee (see here for more information on requesting a deferral: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/research-planning/research-registration-research-project-identifiers/>)

If you have not already included registration details in your IRAS application form, you should notify the REC of the registration details as soon as possible.

Further guidance on registration is available at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/research-planning/transparency-responsibilities/>

Publication of Your Research Summary

We will publish your research summary for the above study on the research summaries section of our website, together with your contact details, no earlier than three months from the date of this favourable opinion letter.

Chair-Dr Ian Zealley
Vice-Chair-Dr Mary-Joan MacLeod

Should you wish to provide a substitute contact point, make a request to defer, or require further information, please visit: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/application-summaries/research-summaries/>

N.B. If your study is related to COVID-19 we will aim to publish your research summary within 3 days rather than three months.

During this public health emergency, it is vital that everyone can promptly identify all relevant research related to COVID-19 that is taking place globally. If you haven't already done so, please register your study on a public registry as soon as possible and provide the REC with the registration detail, which will be posted alongside other information relating to your project. We are also asking sponsors not to request deferral of publication of research summary for any projects relating to COVID-19. In addition, to facilitate finding and extracting studies related to COVID-19 from public databases, please enter the WHO official acronym for the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the full title of your study. Approved COVID-19 studies can be found at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/covid-19-research/approved-covid-19-research/>

It is the responsibility of the sponsor to ensure that all the conditions are complied with before the start of the study or its initiation at a particular site (as applicable).

After ethical review: Reporting requirements

The attached document "After ethical review – guidance for researchers" gives detailed guidance on reporting requirements for studies with a favourable opinion, including:

- Notifying substantial amendments
- Adding new sites and investigators
- Notification of serious breaches of the protocol
- Progress and safety reports
- Notifying the end of the study, including early termination of the study
- Final report
- Reporting results

The latest guidance on these topics can be found at <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/managing-your-approval/>.

Ethical review of research sites

Non-NHS/HSC sites

I am pleased to confirm that the favourable opinion applies to any non-NHS/HSC sites listed in the application, subject to site management permission being obtained prior to the start of the study at the site.

Approved documents

The final list of documents reviewed and approved by the Committee is as follows:

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Covering letter on headed paper [Cover Letter]		20 July 2021
Evidence of Sponsor insurance or indemnity (non NHS Sponsors only) [University Insurance Certificate]		26 June 2020
GP/consultant information sheets or letters [Letter to GP]	0.1	19 June 2021

Chair-Dr Ian Zealley
Vice-Chair-Dr Mary-Juan MacL.eod

Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Focus group guide]	0.1	19 June 2021
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Workshop schedule]	0.1	19 June 2021
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Observation guide]	0.1	19 June 2021
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants [Interview schedule]	0.1	19 June 2021
Letters of invitation to participant [TRACKED Aide Memoire]	0.2	14 September 2021
Letters of invitation to participant [CLEAN Aide Memoire]	0.2	14 September 2021
Other [Summary CV Supervisor 3]	0.1	19 June 2021
Other [Visuals to support introduction of study for people with advanced dementia]	0.1	19 June 2021
Other [Letter from care home]	N/A	28 May 2021
Other [Care Home's 'Adult Support and Protection' policy]	1	01 January 2020
Other [Risk assessment]	0.1	19 June 2021
Other [Data Management Plan]	0.1	19 June 2021
Other [Response Letter]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant consent form [Consent form – family/friends]	0.1	19 June 2021
Participant consent form [Consent form – care home staff]	0.1	19 June 2021
Participant consent form [Proxy consent form]	0.1	19 June 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS TRACKED_WG_WA_NR]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS CLEAN_WG_WA_NR]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS TRACKED_Families_friends]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS CLEAN_Families_friends]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS TRACKED_Staff]	0.2	14 September 2021
Participant information sheet (PIS) [PIS CLEAN_Staff]	0.2	14 September 2021
REC Application Form [REC_Form_20072021]		20 July 2021
Research protocol or project proposal [Study Protocol]	0.1	19 June 2021
Summary CV for Chief Investigator (CI) [Lead supervisor's CV]		19 June 2021
Summary CV for student [PhD student's CV]		19 June 2021
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) [Summary CV Supervisor 2]		19 July 2021

Statement of compliance

The Committee is fully compliant with the Regulations as they relate to ethics committees and the conditions and principles of good clinical practice.

Chair-Dr Ian Zealley
Vice-Chair-Dr Mary-Joan MacLeod

The Committee is constituted in accordance with the Governance Arrangements for Research Ethics Committees and complies fully with the Standard Operating Procedures for Research Ethics Committees in the UK.

User Feedback

The Health Research Authority is continually striving to provide a high quality service to all applicants and sponsors. You are invited to give your view of the service you have received and the application procedure. If you wish to make your views known please use the feedback form available on the HRA website: <http://www.hra.nhs.uk/about-the-hra/governance/quality-assurance/>

HRA Learning

We are pleased to welcome researchers and research staff to our HRA Learning Events and online learning opportunities– see details at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/learning/>

IRAS project ID: 277401 Please quote this number on all correspondence

With the Committee's best wishes for the success of this project.

Yours sincerely

Dr Ian Zealley
Chair

Email:

Enclosures: "After ethical review – guidance for researchers" [SL-AR2]

Copy to: Dr W Gordon Mackay
Lead Nation: Scotland:

Chair-Dr Ian Zealley
Vice-Chair-Dr Mary-Joan MacLeod

Appendix 4: Ethics approval and recruitment

A4.1 Data Management Plan

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Data Management Plan (dmponline)

Creator: Angela Gregory

Long title: Understanding meaning in activities and interactions when living with advanced dementia: A qualitative Participatory Action Research study

Affiliation: University of West of Scotland

ORCID iD: 0000-0003-1767-125X

DATA COLLECTION

What data will you collect or create?

The data collected/created will include:

- Audio and video files in an MP3 format
- Transcripts from audio and video interviews and focus groups in plain text
- Transcripts from audio and video interactive activities and workshops in plain text
- Pictorial data e.g. JPEG images, paper-based images produced in workshops

The volume of data will be as follows:

- Transcripts from up to 6 x interviews (n = up to 1 hour each; 6 hours total)
- Transcripts from up to 2 x focus groups (up to 1.5 hours each; 3 hours total)
- Transcripts from up to 12 x participant observations (up to 45 mins each; 9 hours total)
- Transcripts from up to 8 x participant/researcher interactions (up to 20 mins each; 2 hours and 40 mins total)
- Transcripts from up to 8 x participant interactions (person with advanced dementia, family member/friends/staff and researcher) (up to 45 mins each; 6 hours total)

- Transcripts from up to 2 x workshops (up to 1.5 hours each; 3 hours total)
- Pictorial data
- Field notes
- Reflexive diary

The PhD Student will transcribe the data and write analytic notes. NVivo software: <https://bit.ly/3bmXC1U> will be used to store and organise the data; the analysis will be carried out manually by the PhD Student.

An iPad and/or laptop will be used to collect all audio-visual data. The iPad will be password protected and encrypted using FileVault. The PhD Student's laptop is password protected and encrypted with Sophos. The PhD Student will upload data from the iPad/laptop to the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) OneDrive where it will be de-identified as much as possible e.g. blurring out any identifiable information where appropriate. It will then be imported into NVivo on the PhD Student's laptop. In the event of an outbreak of the pandemic, data will be collected digitally on the iPad/laptop where they will be transferred to the OneDrive and NVivo. The data on the iPad/laptop itself will then be permanently deleted.

All hardcopy pictorial data will be transported from the site in a locked carry case in the boot of the PhD Student's personal car and stored at the UWS in a staff only area in a locked cabinet. This data will then be photographed using the iPad and uploaded to the UWS OneDrive where it will be organised into NVivo. Hardcopy pictorial data and audio and video data will be de-identified e.g. blurring out any identifiable information.

Consent forms will also be stored at UWS in a staff only area in a locked cabinet. If sent digitally, consent forms will be placed on the UWS OneDrive then deleted from the PhD Student's email.

How will the data be collected or created?

A variety of data collection methods will be used according to the needs and abilities of participants, as described below. All data will be collected and managed by the PhD Student.

People living with advanced dementia

What:

- Participant observation of everyday activities with family members/friends/staff.

- Interactions with PhD Student, family member(s)/friend(s)/staff during everyday activities.
- Observations and interactions will be audio-visual recorded via an unobtrusive iPad/laptop.

Why?

- A mixture of observing and participating in everyday activities with the person with advanced dementia will enable an insider/outsider view of the meaning within.
- Using audio-visual data allows interactions to be thoroughly analysed by replaying the data to gain a deeper understanding (Schneider *et al.*, 2019).
- Video is able to catch subtleties in interactions with people with advanced dementia (Schneider *et al.*, 2019), as can be seen in Ellis and Astelle's (2017) study and a study by Kontos *et al.* (2017), both with people living with advanced dementia.

Family members/friends & care home staff

What:

- Observations & discussions (as described above)
- Interactions with person with advanced dementia and PhD Student (as described above)
- Interviews (family members only)
- Focus groups (staff only)
- Workshops (family and staff together)

Why?

- Visuals in research can offer reflective opportunities for participants (Li and Ho, 2019).
- Arts-based methods can help to create new knowledge (Burge *et al.*, 2016).
- The use of combined visual and textual methods provides opportunities for researchers to immerse themselves and connect with in the experience of participants and produce rich data (Culshaw, 2019).

In the event of another COVID-19 outbreak, interviews, focus groups, observations and workshops may be completed online using a Microsoft Teams platform, depending upon restriction levels. If participants do not have access to technology, interviews will be completed via telephone connection and will be audio recorded.

All data will be imported into NVivo. Once in NVivo, all data will be labelled and organised in a logical, hierarchical structure and grouped into folders according to the

date collected, the PAR cycles, type of data and participant group (where relevant). A consistent approach will be taken to increase rigour, for example:

"Name of Project>Cycle 1>Text>Interview group transcripts FAM OR STAFF"

As part of the Participatory Action Research (PAR) process, the analysed themes will be taken to family members and care home staff during collaborative workshops at the end of cycles two and three to establish their perspective of the findings.

DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

When the data is archived, a user guide will be created by the PhD Student to enable quick identification for re-use. The following documents are anticipated to be included in the user guide:

- Methodology
- Protocol
- Blank Participant Information Sheets
- Blank Consent form/proxy consent form
- Visuals to assist in explaining the research to person with advanced dementia
- Visual prompts for interviews, focus groups etc.
- Materials used during workshops
- Interview schedule
- Focus group guide
- Workshop schedule
- Observation guide
- Pseudo-anonymised interview and focus group transcripts
- Pseudo-anonymised excerpt of analysed data
- Field notes

A data list will accompany the user guide to provide an 'at a glance' overview of the study.

Data will be managed in accordance to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Information Commissioner's Office, 2018), the Data Protection Act 2018 (United Kingdom Act of Parliament, 2018), and the UWS Data Protection Code of Practice: <https://bit.ly/34Y3ACH> . The updated UK Government Data Protection Act (2018) Keeling Schedule: <https://bit.ly/3gw94uR> will also be referred to where necessary. The PhD Student completed training in GDPR and Information Security on 17th October 2019 and refreshed this learning on 13th November 2020. Resources from the UK Data Service: <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/> will also be utilised.

ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will you manage any ethical issues?

The Home Manager (or designated Depute) will identify all potential participants using the inclusion and exclusion criteria stated in the Protocol. Following a conversation to clarify the inclusion and exclusion criteria between the PhD Student and the House Manager (or designated Depute), the House Manager (or designated Depute) will identify the potential sample for the three different groups and the Welfare Guardian/Welfare Attorney/Nearest Relative WG/WA/NR (for potential participants with advanced dementia).

The House Manager (or designated Depute) will approach the Welfare Guardian/Welfare Attorney or Nearest Relative (WG/WA/NR) of the person with advanced dementia, family members/friends and care home staff to explain the study using an aide memoire containing the PhD Student's contact details. The WG/WA/NR, family member/friend or staff member can then either contact the PhD Student directly or ask the PhD Student to contact them. Please refer to the protocol for further details.

For family members/friends and care home staff interested in taking part, a Participant Information Sheet and a consent form will be provided by the PhD Student. For participants with advanced dementia, a Participant Information Sheet and a proxy consent form will be provided to the WG/WA/NR. The PhD Student will also attempt to gain the assent/dissent (Black *et al.*, 2010) and process consent (Dewing, 2008) of the person with advanced dementia.

Please see section '7.3.2. Consent' in the study Protocol for further information on the consent process.

Consent forms will ask for consent to:

- Participate in the research

- Use audio-visual recordings during data collection
- Share audio-visual data during workshops
- Use selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data in academic conferences (optional)
- Share de-identified, pseudo-anonymised data with the PhD Student's supervisors, during conferences, academic dissemination and for publications/reports/thesis

Store data

All data (except consent forms) will be pseudo-anonymised, including people and places and any potential identifying factor.

All hardcopy pictorial data will be transported in a locked carry case from the site in the boot of the PhD Student's personal car to UWS. It will be stored at the UWS in a staff only area in a locked cabinet. Hardcopy pictorial data will be photographed using the iPad and uploaded to the UWS OneDrive where it will be organised into NVivo. Data will be de-identified as much as possible e.g. blurring out any identifiable information.

Only the PhD Student will have access to raw data and the PhD Student and the PhD Student's supervisors will have access to de-identified data.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

As this is a PhD study, the data arising from the study will be owned by the UWS, in accordance to their Intellectual Property policy: <https://bit.ly/2SEveC2> .

Family members/friends will be encouraged to share what they feel is appropriate with the person with advanced dementia.

STORAGE AND BACKUP

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

All hardcopy pictorial data will be photographed on the iPad, uploaded to the UWS OneDrive and organised into NVivo onto the PhD Student's laptop. Digital data will also be kept on the OneDrive and organised into NVivo. The PhD Student's laptop requires a password to access and the documents will be password protected and kept on the UWS OneDrive. The OneDrive is supported by the Information Technology Helpdesk Team (ITDS) team at the university who are be responsible for recovery of the data if required.

All data will be backed up weekly on an external drive stored at the UWS in a staff only area in a locked cabinet.

All data that has not been anonymised e.g. consent forms will be kept in a separate password-protected document in the UWS OneDrive (if digital) or in kept at UWS in a staff only area in a locked cabinet (if hardcopy) to enable the PhD Student to refer back to them if required (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

How will you manage access and security?

Data will be managed in accordance to the GDPR (Information Commissioner's Office, 2018), the Data Protection Act 2018, and the UWS Data Protection Code of Practice, as previously stated.

The iPad will be password protected and encrypted using FileVault. The PhD Student's laptop is password protected and encrypted with Sophos. Any data initially created on the iPad will be digitally saved to the UWS OneDrive and imported into NVivo. Hardcopy pictorial data will be photographed, digitally saved to the UWS OneDrive and imported into NVivo. This will be completed weekly. Once the data on the iPad itself is no longer needed, it will be permanently deleted from the iPad.

The OneDrive requires a password comprising of a minimum of four forms of complexity. A multi-factor authentication is also required in order to access OneDrive files so if anyone else other than the PhD Student uses a different device to those the PhD Student has previously used, they would be asked for the 2nd factor, which is linked to the PhD Student's smartphone. Further information regarding Microsoft's management of the OneDrive can be found here: <https://bit.ly/2Shkcmd> .

Only the PhD Student will have access to the raw data. The PhD Student's supervisors will request access to the data through the PhD Student where necessary. Data shared with supervisors will be de-identified. Files will be shared using the UWS OneDrive.

Access to restricted pseudo-anonymised data (anonymised data that the PhD Student /the PhD Student's supervisors disseminate) will be publicly available through the PhD Student's thesis, potential published papers, conference events etc. Selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data may be used in academic conferences.

SELECTION AND PRESERVATION

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The data will be collected for the purpose of this PhD research study only; it will not be shared or reused for other studies or by other researchers.

Data will need to be retained to validate the research findings, for personal PhD development and learning purposes.

In accordance with the UWS Doctoral College Handbook (2019) and the UWS Record Retention Schedule for Research <https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv> the data generated from this study will be securely stored for ten years. After this date, the data will be securely destroyed – hardcopy pictorial data will be placed in the designated confidential document containers at UWS. Digital data will be permanently deleted from the OneDrive. If the PhD Student is no longer at UWS by this time, the PhD Student will arrange for the data to be destroyed and recorded with the ITDS.

In accordance with the UWS Record Retention Schedule for Research <https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv> , records which document active, potential and withdrawn participants need to be kept for 6 years and then destroyed. Records of the dissemination of research results need to be kept for 1 year and then destroyed and final versions of publications and presentations need to be kept for 3 years and then archived.

Regarding the sharing of data between the PhD Student and the PhD Student's supervisors, files will be shared using the UWS OneDrive.

In the unlikely event of a data security breach, the PhD Student will immediately report to their Lead Supervisor and the university's data breach procedure will be followed as per the university's Data Protection Code of Practice.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

In accordance with the UWS Doctoral College Handbook (2019) and the UWS Record Retention Schedule for Research <https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv> the data generated from this study will be securely stored for ten years. After this date, the data will be securely destroyed. The OneDrive is supported by the ITDS at the UWS.

DATA SHARING

How will you share the data?

The data will be collected for the purpose of this PhD research study only; it will not be shared or reused for other studies or by other researchers.

Only the PhD Student and the PhD Student's supervisors will have access to the data. The PhD Student's supervisors will request access to the de-identified data through the PhD Student where necessary; this will be completed using the UWS secure OneDrive.

Data may be shared with participants during the data collection cycles for reflective purposes as part of the Participatory Action Research process.

De-identified, pseudo-anonymised data will be used for reflective purposes and for conferences and publications/reports.

Selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data may be used in academic conferences.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Only the PhD Student and their supervisors will have access to the data as part of the PhD, therefore a data sharing agreement will not be required.

RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

Who will be responsible for data management?

The PhD Student is the data custodian responsible for the safe handling and management of the data collected. The data will be managed in accordance to the GDPR (Information Commissioner's Office, 2018), the Data Protection Act (2018), the UWS Data Protection Code of Practice.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

An iPad, a laptop and access to NVivo software is required for this study.

As this is a PhD study, all data will be transcribed, coded and analysed by the PhD Student. NVivo software will be used to organise the data; the analysis will be carried out manually by the PhD Student. NVivo is supported by the UWS and the PhD Student already has this software on a laptop. Money for NVivo training is allocated by the Doctoral College and the PhD Student will access this to learn the skills necessary to use the software effectively.

An iPad will be purchased from funding provided by the Scottish Dementia Research Consortium (already secured). The PhD Student has been provided with a laptop by the university which has the NVivo software installed.

References

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University of the West of Scotland (2019). Doctoral College Handbook. Available at: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/5320/doctoral-college-handbook-2019.pdf> (Accessed 18 June 2021).

A4.2 Risk assessment

Department/Unit Name: School of Health and Life Sciences				Department Risk Assessment No:			
Assessed by: Angela Gregory, PhD Student				Date of assessment: 19/06/2021			
Authorised by: Dr Margaret Brown				Date of reassessment:			
<p>Description of work activity or process <i>including any equipment/methods/procedures put in place to control risk.</i></p> <p>Participatory Action Research study situated in one Scottish care home using creative methods alongside observation, interviews, focus groups and workshops.</p>							
What are the individual hazards?	Who might be harmed and how?	What are you already doing?	Do you need to do anything else to manage this risk?	Risk Level? (see method)	Action by whom?	Action by when?	Done
Fire	Participants; PhD Student	Liaising with care home. Fire safety training completed at UWS	PhD Student will familiarise self with care home fire exits and procedures	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Confidentiality and data protection	Participants by being identifiable	Data Management Plan written	Follow Data Management Plan & UWS policies: https://bit.ly/3bDP0Uv	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	

COVID-19	Participants, staff, visitors, PhD Student by catching the virus	Vaccinations (x 2), good hand-washing technique, physical distancing, Person Protective Equipment	Follow Care Inspectorate's COVID-19 guidelines: https://bit.ly/2QVLRlw Follow government guidance: https://bit.ly/3fE5IWv Follow care home's infection control policy	Medium	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Use of video-audio data	Participants may not wish to be on video	Using technology which the care home already use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State in PIS and consent/proxy consent forms • Gain assent/dissent, process consent • PhD Student to place courtesy notices up in the area that filming will take place • PhD Student to position camera to focus on the required perspective 	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Use of audio-visual and sensory/creative methods	Participants may feel uncomfortable using certain methods	Offering a range of different activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure a range of materials from Post-it Notes to collage so that people can choose what they are most comfortable with • Offer breaks • Make the use of selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data in academic conferences optional in consent form 	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing	
Safety of others	PhD Student may observe concerns re. care of people with advanced dementia	Discussion with Lead supervisor & care home House Manager (or designated Depute)	Follow care home's Adult Support and Protection policy and also inform the House Manager and the PhD Student's Lead Supervisor	Medium	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	
Stress and distress (including health and wellbeing, burden, privacy and dignity)	People with advanced dementia may become stressed or distressed during data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion with supervisors & care home; • PhD Student is an HCPC registered occupational therapist and follows professional standards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD Student to become a familiar to residents through visits prior to collecting data; • Create a supportive, friendly welcoming space; • Gain assent/dissent/process consent; 	Low - Medium	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	

Stress and distress (including health and wellbeing, burden, privacy and dignity)	Families/ friends and staff may become upset or ill during data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion with supervisors & care home; • PhD Student is an HCPC registered occupational therapist and follows professional standards. Discussion with supervisors & care home management; • Management plan in place in study protocol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a supportive, friendly welcoming space; • Gain consent; • Extra sensitivity due to COVID-19; • Family member to use a pre-agreed sign if they want PhD Student to leave during family visit; • Ask participant if they are ok if they seem upset; pause/stop intervention if necessary; • Offer break(s); signpost if required e.g. support from care home staff/employer; • If participants become ill in care home, PhD Student to pause/stop recording and gain support from appropriate staff member; • If participant became ill in their own home, PhD Student to pause/stop recording and act accordingly and appropriately; • Refer to support listed on Participant Information Sheet • Use private room or private online App e.g. Teams • Time requested from participants will be as short as possible; • Routine meetings used where possible; • Research will be part of the everyday care home routine; • Options to postpone/withdraw will be discussed as required. 	Low - Medium	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	
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Health and wellbeing Lone working	PhD Student at slight risk of physical and/or psychological harm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion with supervisors; • Management plan in place in study protocol; • The PhD Student is an HCPC registered occupational therapist and is used to working in the community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care home: PhD Student to familiarise self with the layout of the care home and building exits prior to collecting data; PhD Student to inform House Manager (or designated Depute) of any incidents; • Family members/friends own home: the PhD Student and their supervisor will arrange safety procedures beforehand in accordance with the UWS fieldwork and lone working policy: https://bit.ly/3yD5qqq 	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	
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Protection from research involvement	Non-participants included in video data	Discussion with supervisors; management plan in place in study protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If non-participants are caught on camera, blur them out. • PhD Student to place courtesy notices up in the area that filming will take place • PhD Student to position camera to focus on the required perspective 	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	
Access to care home/permission	Management of care home will need to agree to research	Management of care home have provided a letter of support and permission to access	N/A	N/A	PhD Student	N/A	
Social media	Management of care home often post care home activities on social media	On no account will any data collected be posted on social media	PhD Student to converse with Home Manager (or designated Depute) and Lead supervisor. PhD Student to access UWS counselling service if needed.	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	

Reputation	University's and/or care home's reputation could be harmed if information were to be shared inappropriately	Discussion with supervisors	PhD Student will maintain the confidentiality of all participants, places and the university and care home during and after the research. All data will be pseudo-anonymised. Any concerns will be discussed with the PhD Student's Lead Supervisor in a timely manner.	Low	PhD Student	Ongoing, if required	
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As the COVID-19 pandemic is still active, there is a risk of the PhD Student either spreading the virus or catching it. The PhD Student will be very cautious and will follow guidance from the care home, the Care Inspectorate and the Scottish Government to protect others as much as possible. The PhD Student has already had COVID-19 and has been immunised, therefore it is unlikely the PhD Student will catch it again, however there is still a risk that the PhD Student may pass the virus onto others.

For further information and to view example risk assessments go to <http://www.hse.gov.uk/risk/casestudies/>

Risk Assessment Method

In order to assess a risk associated to a hazard, two factors need to be considered:-

The possible severity of the outcome

Realistically, what is the worst likely outcome? This method defines three categories of severity:-

- Slightly harmful
- Harmful
- Extremely harmful

The likelihood of the outcome to occur

How likely is it that the severe outcome will occur? Three categories are defined:-

- Highly unlikely
- Unlikely
- Likely

Once those two factors are assessed, the matrix below can be used to determine the level of risk. This information can then be used to prioritise any control measures necessary to eliminate or reduce the risk to an acceptable level.

	Slightly Harmful	Harmful	Extremely Harmful
Likely	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK	HIGH RISK
Unlikely	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK	HIGH RISK
Highly Unlikely	LOW RISK	LOW RISK	MEDIUM RISK

A4.2 Participant Information Sheet – family members

Participant Information Sheet – Family members/friends
Date: 14/09/2021 Version no. 0.2 Study ID (IRAS): 277401

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

- This is an invitation to take part in the above research study.
- Before you decide, it is important that you read this information. It may also be helpful for you to discuss it with friends or family.
- If you decide not to provide consent, this will not affect any care for your relative/friend.
- If anything in this sheet is unclear, please feel free to contact me and I will be happy to discuss it further.

The study at a glance

- The aim of the study is to explore the concept of meaning in activities and interactions in the everyday lives of people living with advanced dementia;
- The study is about people with advanced dementia, their family members and care home staff working together to make positive changes;
- I hope the study will improve the quality of everyday experiences of activities and interactions for all.

How to contact me

If you have any questions about this study, please feel free to contact me via email:

Alternatively, please leave your contact details with the House Manager of the care home and I will get back to you as soon as possible.

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Invitation

I would like to invite you to take part in the above research study. The House Manager here at the care home has identified you as a potential participant because you have a family member at the care home who lives with advanced dementia. Your decision is entirely voluntary and it is important that you fully understand what the research involves before making your decision.

I am happy to talk with you about the study and to go through this information sheet with you. This will take around 30 mins and will give you the opportunity to discuss any concerns and ask questions.

Who am I?

My name is Angela Gregory and I am completing a research study for my Doctor of Philosophy degree at the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice, University of the West of Scotland. The research will be carried out here in this care home to explore the concept of meaning in activities and interactions in the everyday lives of people living with advanced dementia.

What is the purpose of the research?

Little is known about what makes activities and interactions meaningful for people with advanced dementia. Consequently, the aim of this study is to explore how meaning is made in everyday activities and interactions between people living with advanced dementia and their carers. 'Meaning' in this study is defined as 'seeking a purpose or significance'. People living with advanced dementia are often inhibited

from experiencing meaning in everyday life, and as a result they are likely to feel alienated.

How will it work?

This research will involve up to four people with advanced dementia, up to six family members and up to six care home staff from one Scottish care home. An approach called 'Participatory Action Research' (PAR) will be used, consisting of repetitive cycles of planning, doing, observing and reflecting to encourage learning and make positive changes within the community of the care home. The study will include up to three cycles of PAR, as shown in the image below.

The cycles of the study

What would taking part involve?

If you took part in the study, it would involve the following:

- **An interview** lasting up to one hour. During the interview, I would like to find out about your relative/friend and ask you some questions about meaning. I would ask you to bring a significant object, item and/or image to the interview.
- **Observations** of you sharing up to five activities with your relative/friend that happen routinely in everyday life. These will be a mixture of care activities such as eating/drinking, brushing teeth/hair and leisure activities such as family visits, folding/touching/looking at items/objects. Please note that intimate/personal care will not be observed. The observations will take place wherever they naturally occur, including in social areas and your relative's/friend's bedroom to fit with their usual, familiar routine. During/after the observations, I will be capturing short discussions to understand the meaning in the activities and interactions. The combined activities and discussions will last no longer than 45 mins each. These observations can happen within a period of 12 weeks, when suitable.
- **Up to 2 x activities/interactions** with myself, your relative/friend and possibly a care home staff member to revisit some of the activities above to apply our learning 'in the moment'.
- **2 x Workshops** lasting up to 1.5 hours each with care home staff and myself to look at what we have found at the end of Cycles 2 and 3. This will involve discussion and doing activities such as writing on Post-it Notes and creating images.
- The **total commitment time** would be up to 7 hours and 45 mins over a period of up to six months.

All of these methods will be video-audio recorded. Using video will allow me to revisit the data to look at how you and your relative/friend use body language, gestures and expressions to interact.

If you decide not to provide consent, this will not affect any care for your relative/friend.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There is no direct benefit to you but I hope that the knowledge gained from this study will increase the quality of life and wellbeing of people living with advanced dementia.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

I understand that seeing your relative/friend in a care home may be an upsetting experience, therefore there is the possibility that you may become upset at some point during data collection. I also acknowledge that COVID-19 will have affected visits to your relative/friend. If you become upset during data collection, I would pause/stop the recording and ask you if you were ok. We would then either pause/take a break or rearrange. We could also agree a signal so that you could communicate to me if you wanted me to leave at any point during the observations with your relative/friend. If I saw you use the agreed signal, I would quietly leave the room and give you privacy. I would call you afterwards to check you were ok. Care Home staff are also around to talk to should you need their support. It may also be helpful for you to have the following contacts:

Alzheimer Scotland's 24 hour Freephone Dementia Helpline:

0808 808 3000. Email: helpline@alzscot.org

Age Scotland helpline: 0800 12 44 222, Monday – Friday, 9am – 5pm.

Email: helpline@agescotland.org.uk

Care Inspectorate enquiries: 0345 600 9527. Email:

enquiries@careinspectorate.gov.scot

How will you help to protect me from COVID-19?

The following measures are being taken to protect all participants:

- I will have received 2 x COVID-19 vaccinations before the study begins;
- I will be completing lateral flow tests before each visit;
- I will be observing and following the current guidelines and restrictions;
- I will wear Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) where required;
- I will be using good hand hygiene procedures;
- I will only be working in one house to reduce the risk of spreading infection.

What if you are unhappy with any aspect of the research?

I will keep you fully informed throughout this study and I would be grateful if you could let me know of any concerns you may have as they arise. You are also welcome to raise any concerns with Dr James Taylor, Head of Division: Mental Health Nursing & Integrated Practice, University of the West of Scotland: Email: james.taylor@uws.ac.uk
Tel: 01698 283100 Ext 8246.

What will happen if you wish to withdraw from the study?

You are free to withdraw from the study at any point without providing a reason. You relative's/friend's care would not be affected by this in any way. The anonymous data collected up to that point would be included in the study.

What will happen to the information collected about me?

The information collected will be used to improve the quality of everyday experiences of people living with advanced dementia and their relationships with family members/friends and care home staff.

All the data collected will be anonymised and names will be changed. The purpose of a PAR study is to work together with all involved to create learning opportunities and promote positive change, therefore some of the videos and other material may be shown to the other participants.

All videos, written material and items created by the people involved in this study will be anonymised and stored safely and securely in the University of the West of Scotland for 10 years, after which they will be disposed of securely.

What will happen to the results of the research?

This study is for my Doctor of Philosophy degree at the University of the West of Scotland, for which I will write a thesis and a report explaining what I found during the study. Academic papers and presentations may also be published from this research. These will be shared with people with dementia and their family members, carers, health and social care professionals, researchers and students. Selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data may be used in academic conferences. I will also share the findings of the research with you. You are welcome to share what you feel is appropriate with your relative/friend.

How have people with dementia and their carers been involved in this study?

The opinions of people living with dementia, their families/friends and those who work with them have informed the research topic, how the research is carried out, and this information sheet.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland. The Scotland A Research Ethics Committee have looked in depth at the

content of this study and have given permission for it to be carried out. The managers of the care home have also authorised this study.

Background information

I am supported in my studies by my supervisors Dr Margaret Brown, Dr Rhoda Macrae and Dr Angela Beggan, who all work at the university. The study is funded by the University of the West of Scotland, Erskine and Alzheimer Scotland.

What if you need further information?

If you would like to discuss any aspect of the study, please contact me and I will be happy to discuss it with you.

Email:

[REDACTED]

Alternatively, please leave your contact details with the House Manager of the care home and I will get back to you as soon as possible.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet

Privacy Notice

University of the West of Scotland

The University of the West of Scotland (the "University" or "we") is the sponsor for this study based in the United Kingdom. The University is committed to looking after any information that you make available to us and we aim to be clear about what we will do with your data. This privacy notice explains when and why we collect personal information about you and how we will use this information.

We will use the information you have provided to us in order to carry out the research study and our basis for doing this is that it is in the public interest for us to do so. We will act as the data controller in relation to the information you provide. We will not share your information with any third parties that are not part of the research group mentioned in this Participant Information Notice. We will keep identifiable information about you for 10 years after the study has finished.

The information you have provided to us will not be transferred out of the EEA.

You can find information about:-

- The details of our data protection officer
- How we will keep your information safe
- What choices you have in relation to your information
- How you can complain about the use of your information

in our privacy notice which you can read here -

<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-our-website/privacy/>

Some of the rights you have in relation to your information that are set out in the privacy notice are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we will delete the information about you that we have already obtained, where it is possible for us to do so. To safeguard, your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible.

A4.3 Participant Information Sheet - staff

Participant Information Sheet – Care Home Staff

Date: 14/09/2021

Version no. 0.2

Study ID (IRAS): 277401

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

- This is an invitation to take part in the above research study.
- Before you decide, it is important that you read this information. It may also be helpful for you to discuss it with colleagues.
- If you decide not to provide consent, this will not affect any aspect of your employment.
- If anything in this sheet is unclear, please feel free to contact me and I will be happy to discuss it further.

The study at a glance

- The aim of the study is to explore the concept of meaning in activities and interactions in the everyday lives of people living with advanced dementia;
- The study is about people with advanced dementia, their family members and care home staff working together to make positive changes;
- I hope the study will improve the quality of everyday experiences of activities and interactions for all.

How to contact me

If you have any questions about this study, please feel free to contact me via email:

Alternatively, please leave your contact details with the House Manager of the care home and I will get back to you as soon as possible.

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Invitation

I would like to invite you to take part in the above research study. The House Manager has identified you as a potential participant because you have stated an interest in being a participant. Your decision is entirely voluntary and it is important that you fully understand what the research involves before making your decision.

I am happy to talk with you about the study and to go through this information sheet with you. This will take around 30 mins and will give you the opportunity to discuss any concerns and ask questions.

Who am I?

My name is Angela Gregory and I am completing a research study for my Doctor of Philosophy degree at the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice, University of the West of Scotland. The research will be carried out here in the House to explore the concept of meaning in activities and interactions in the everyday lives of people living with advanced dementia.

What is the purpose of the research?

Little is known about what makes activities and interactions meaningful for people with advanced dementia. Consequently, the aim of this study is to explore how meaning is made in everyday activities and interactions between people living with advanced dementia and their carers. 'Meaning' in this study is defined as 'seeking a purpose or significance'. People living with advanced dementia are often inhibited from experiencing meaning in everyday life, and as a result, they are likely to feel alienated.

How will it work?

This research will involve up to four people with advanced dementia, up to six family members and up to six care home staff from one Scottish care home. An approach called 'Participatory Action Research' (PAR) will be used, consisting of repetitive cycles of planning, doing, observing and reflecting to encourage learning and make positive changes within the community of the care home. The study will include up to three cycles of PAR, as shown in the image below.

The cycles of the study

What would taking part involve?

If you took part in the study, it would involve the following:

- **1 x focus group** with a small group of your colleagues, lasting up to 1.5 hours. During the focus group, I would like to find out about your understanding of meaning in activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia. This will involve discussion and doing activities such as writing on Post-it Notes and creating images.
- **Observations** of you sharing up to five activities with the person with advanced dementia that happen routinely in daily care. These will be a mixture of care activities such as eating/drinking, brushing teeth/hair and leisure activities such as family visits, folding/touching/looking at items/objects. Please note that intimate/personal care will not be observed. The observations will take place wherever they naturally occur, including in social areas and the person's bedroom to fit with their usual, familiar routine. During/after the observations, I will be capturing short discussions to understand the meaning in the activities and interactions. The combined activities and discussions will last no longer than 45 mins each. These observations can happen within a period of 12 weeks, when suitable.
- **Up to 2 x activities/interactions** with myself, the resident and possibly their family member/friend to revisit some of the activities to apply our learning 'in the moment'.
- **2 x Workshops** lasting up to 1.5 hours each with family members and myself to look at what we have found at the end of Cycles 2 and 3. These will use similar media/techniques to those described in the focus groups.

All of these methods will be video-audio recorded and the study will last up to six months.

If you decide not to provide consent, this will not affect your work in any way.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There is no direct benefit to you but I hope that the knowledge gained from this study will increase the quality of life and wellbeing of people living with advanced dementia.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

I understand that caring for residents may sometimes be an emotional experience, I also acknowledge that COVID-19 will have affected your interactions with the person. If you wish to stop at any time, I will pause/stop take a break or rearrange. Your employer will also provide wraparound support, including support from your supervisor/manager and colleagues as necessary.

How will you help to protect me/the residents from COVID-19?

The following measures are being taken to protect all participants:

- I will have received 2 x COVID-19 vaccinations before the study begins;
- I will be completing lateral flow tests before each visit;
- I will be observing and following the current guidelines and restrictions;
- I will wear Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) where required;
- I will be using good hand hygiene procedures;
- I will only be working in one house to reduce the risk of spreading infection.

What if you are unhappy with any aspect of the research?

I will keep you fully informed throughout this study and I would be grateful if you could let me know of any concerns you may have as they arise. You are also welcome to raise any concerns with Dr James Taylor, Head of Division: Mental Health Nursing & Integrated Practice,

University of the West of Scotland: Email: [REDACTED]

Tel: 01698 283100 Ext 8246.

What will happen if you wish to withdraw from the study?

You are free to withdraw from the study at any point without providing a reason. Your work will not be affected by this in any way. The anonymous data collected up to that point would be included in the study.

What will happen to the information collected about me?

The information collected will be used to improve the quality of everyday experiences of people living with advanced dementia and their relationships with family members/friends and care home staff.

All the data collected will be anonymised and names will be changed.

The purpose of a PAR study is to work together with all involved to create learning opportunities and promote positive change, therefore some of the videos and other material may be shown to the other participants.

All videos, written material and items created by the people involved in this study will be anonymised and stored safely and securely in the University of the West of Scotland for 10 years, after which they will be disposed of securely.

What will happen to the results of the research?

This study is for my Doctor of Philosophy degree at the University of the West of Scotland, for which I will write a thesis and a report explaining what I found during the study. Academic papers and presentations may also be published from this research. These will be shared with people with dementia and their family members, carers, health and social care professionals, researchers and students. Selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data may be used in academic conferences. I will also share the findings of the research with you.

How have people with dementia and their carers been involved in this study?

The opinions of people living with dementia, their families/friends and those who work with them have informed the research topic, how the research is carried out, and this information sheet.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been approved by the University of the West of Scotland. The Scotland A Research Ethics Committee have looked in depth at the content of this study and have given permission for it to be carried out. The managers of the care home have also authorised this study.

Background information

I am supported in my studies by my supervisors Dr Margaret Brown, Dr Rhoda Macrae and Dr Angela Beggan, who all work at the university. The study is funded by the University of the West of Scotland, Erskine and Alzheimer Scotland.

What if you need further information?

If you would like to discuss any aspect of the study, please contact me and I will be happy to discuss it with you.

Email: [REDACTED]

Alternatively, please leave your contact details with the House Manager of the care home and I will get back to you as soon as possible.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet

Privacy Notice
University of the West of Scotland

The University of the West of Scotland (the "University" or "we") is the sponsor for this study based in the United Kingdom. The University is committed to looking after any information that you make available to us and we aim to be clear about what we will do with your data. This privacy notice explains when and why we collect personal information about you and how we will use this information.

We will use the information you have provided to us in order to carry out the research study and our basis for doing this is that it is in the public interest for us to do so. We will act as the data controller in relation to the information you provide. We will not share your information with any third parties that are not part of the research group mentioned in this Participant Information Notice. We will keep identifiable information about you for 10 years after the study has finished.

The information you have provided to us will not be transferred out of the EEA.

You can find information about:-

- The details of our data protection officer
- How we will keep your information safe
- What choices you have in relation to your information
- How you can complain about the use of your information

in our privacy notice which you can read here -

<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-our-website/privacy/>

Some of the rights you have in relation to your information that are set out in the privacy notice are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we will delete the information about you that we have already obtained, where it is possible for us to do so. To safeguard, your rights, we will use the minimum personally-identifiable information possible.

A4.4 Proxy Consent Form

Proxy Consent Form

Title of Project Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Name of Researcher: Angela Gregory, PhD Student

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated.....
(version.....) for the above study
2. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask
questions, and that these have been answered satisfactorily
3. To the best of my knowledge, my relative/person I am consenting on
behalf of has not expressed a wish to be excluded from participating
in research
4. I agree for the researcher to contact my relative's/person I am
consenting on behalf of's General Practitioner (GP) for the purposes
of this study
5. I agree for my relative/person I am consenting on behalf of to be
filmed and audio recorded for this study
6. I agree for relevant data collected during the study to be shared with
study participants during discussion and workshops
7. I agree to selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data being
used in academic conferences*

1. I agree to my relative's/person I am consenting on behalf of's data to be transcribed anonymised and stored, and for anonymous quotes to be used in academic conferences and publications, including the researcher's thesis

2. I understand that my relative's/person I am consenting on behalf of's participation is voluntary and that they may withdraw at any time without giving reason and without their care being affected

3. I understand that anonymised data already collected will be used if my relative/ person I am consenting on behalf of withdraws from the study

4. I agree to the person for whom I am providing consent to take part in the above study

5. I confirm that I have Welfare Guardianship/Welfare Attorney/I am the Nearest Relative for the person for whom I am providing consent (please underline the relationship)

Name of person for whom I am providing consent: _____

Signs that my relative/person I am consenting on behalf of may be stressed/distressed: _____

Name of Welfare Guardian/ Welfare Attorney/Nearest Relative	Date	Signature
<u>ANGELA GREGORY</u>		
Name of Person seeking consent	Date	Signature

A4.5 Consent Form – family members

Consent Form - Family members/friends

Title of Project: Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Name of Researcher: Angela Gregory, PhD Student

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated.....
(version.....) for the above study
2. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask
questions, and that these have been answered satisfactorily
3. I agree to be filmed and audio recorded for this study
4. I agree for relevant data collected during the study to be shared with
study participants during discussion and workshops
5. I agree to selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data being
used in academic conferences*
6. I agree for any data collected during the study to be transcribed
anonymised and stored, and for anonymous quotes to be used in
academic conferences and publications, including the researcher's
thesis
7. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can
withdraw at any time without giving any reason

1. I understand that anonymised data already collected will be used if I withdraw from the study

2. I agree to take part in the above study

Name of participant

Date

Signature

ANGELA GREGORY

Name of Person
seeking consent

Date

Signature

A4.6 Consent form - staff

Consent Form - Care Home Staff

Title of Project: Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Name of Researcher: Angela Gregory, PhD Student

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated.....
(version.....) for the above study
2. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask
questions, and that these have been answered satisfactorily
3. I agree to be filmed and audio recorded for this study
4. I agree for relevant data collected during the study to be shared with
study participants during discussion and workshops
5. I agree to selected, anonymised, illustrative, audio-visual data being
used in academic conferences*
6. I agree for any data collected during the study to be transcribed
anonymised and stored, and for anonymous quotes to be used in
academic conferences and publications, including the researcher's
thesis
7. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can
withdraw at any time without giving any reason

1. I understand that anonymised data already collected will be used if I withdraw from the study

2. I agree to take part in the above study

Name of participant

Date

Signature

ANGELA GREGORY

Name of Person
seeking consent

Date

Signature

A4.7 Aide Memoire

Angela Gregory – Aide Memoire; Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia; Version 0.2 14/09/2021; IRAS No. 277401

Meaning in activities and interactions when living with advanced dementia

Hello my name is Angela Gregory and I am completing a research study for my Doctor of Philosophy degree at the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice, University of the West of Scotland.

The aim of the study is to explore the idea of meaning in everyday activities and interactions for people living with advanced dementia in this care home, with the hope of improving the quality of these experiences for all involved.

I am looking to work together with people living with advanced dementia, their family members/friends and care home staff to learn from each other and make positive changes.

Photo by Bruno Aguirre on Unsplash

Do you think that you and/or your relative/friend would like to participate in this study?

If so, you are welcome to contact me for a chat and to find out more about the study by emailing: Angela.Gregory@uws.ac.uk

Alternatively, please leave your contact details with the House Manager of the care home and I will get back to you as soon as possible

Appendix 5: Permission to access care home from Director of Care

Director of Care:

Our Ref: [REDACTED]

28 May 2021

Dear Ethics Committee

Angela Gregory application for ethic approval

We are delighted to support Angela's research field work being carried out here at [REDACTED] specifically in [REDACTED] Home. [REDACTED] Home cares for up to 40 residents all living with dementia.

At [REDACTED] we have experience of participation in research with a number of universities including the University of the West of Scotland where we jointly undertook the Food for Thought project. More recently we supported a Queen Margaret University PhD student who was researching sexual expression in people living with dementia. Residents, relatives and staff have all taken part in various research projects over the past few years, including a CSO funded project last year looking at the impact of COVID on relatives.

[REDACTED]

We understand the methodology will be Participatory Action Research using everyday creative methods. We understand this will include, observations/discussions of activities/interactions between residents with advanced dementia and their family members/friends and staff; interviews with family members; focus groups with staff; and workshops with families and staff. We also understand that Angela will be video recording using an iPad as part of data collection and that this will be kept securely.

[REDACTED] carries public liability insurance which allows us to support this research.

Please let me know if you require any further information.

Yours sincerely

[REDACTED]
Director of Care

What is the study about?

- What doing the things you like to do means to you
- What being with others means to you

Which activities will we do?

Everyday activities like brushing your teeth
and seeing your family and friends

How will we do it?

If you would like to, we will film the activities

Would you like to be part of this?

Yes

Not sure

No

Appendix 7: Interview Schedule

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Interview Schedule – family members/friends

Aims:

- To understand what the family members/friends know of the person with advanced dementia
- To understand signs of stress/distress and happiness/enjoyment
- To explore how family members/friends understand meaning in activities and interactions

General preparation:

- Consent form will have been signed by participants after reading Participant Information Sheet and having any questions answered satisfactorily.
- Convenient time prearranged with House Manager & participant.
- Current COVID-19 guidelines followed.

Venue

Confidential, private space in care home or family member/friend's own home (see the University of the West of Scotland's fieldwork and lone working policy: <https://bit.ly/3yD5gqq>). Online (Microsoft Teams) if COVID-19 restrictions in place.

Format

There will be one interview per person in Cycle 1 family members/friends (n = up to 4), lasting up to one hour.

Contingency

If current restrictions/regulations do not allow the Chief Investigator (CI) to enter the care home/family member/friend's own home, an online interview will be completed using a Microsoft Teams App. Visuals will be facilitated using an online platform e.g. Padlet: <https://padlet.com/> . If participants do not have access to technology, interviews will be completed via telephone and will be audio recorded.

If the CI is not able to run the session e.g. illness, then participants will be informed that the interview is cancelled by the CI (if able) or the House Manager. When able, the CI will re-arrange the interview.

Resources

- iPad
- Images
- Object/item/image brought in by family member/friend

Process:

1. CI to briefly introduce self and study
2. CI to check for verbal consent to complete interview and record
3. CI to check comfort level of participant(s)
4. CI to ask participant(s) questions using visual prompts
5. CI to check if the participant(s) have any questions about the interview/study
6. CI to close interview and thank participant.

Please see interview questions overleaf.

Person with advanced dementia = PwAD

Interview questions (informed by Braun & Clarke, 2013)

State: Thank you for agreeing to be part of this study. This interview will help me to understand more about [name of PwAD] and get to know them better. My research is about exploring the concept of meaning when doing activities with people with advanced dementia. I'm interested in hearing your thoughts and ideas – there is no wrong or right! If you need to pause or stop at any point, just let me know. Are you happy to continue?

Opening questions

1. To begin with, I'd love to hear about [name of PwAD], please could you tell me about them as a person? *Prompts if needed: life history, personal attributes & interests, preferences, routines.*
2. How often are you able to visit?
3. How do you spend your time together when you visit?

Specific questions related to activities and interactions

4. I'd love to hear more about what activities [name of PwAD] likes to do, can you share this with me?
5. What does [name of PwAD] like about these activities?
6. What do you think [name of PwAD] would like to do more of in the care home?

Questions regarding signs of stress, distress and enjoyment

7. How do you know when [name of PwAD] is happy?
8. If [name of PwAD] were distressed, what would this look like?

Specific questions related to meaning

9. When you hear the word 'meaning/meaningful' what does this mean to you? [Use their object/item/image as prompt]
10. Can you share times when you visited [name of PwAD] and felt that that it was meaningful?
11. What do you think made it meaningful for [name of PwAD]? Why?
12. Have you noticed any times when your visits seem to have **less** meaning?
13. What do these visits look like? *Prompts if needed: activity/who was present/context/environment*

Appendix 8: Focus group schedule

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Focus group Guide

Aims:

- To explore how staff understand meaning in activities and interactions
- To identify priorities for change

General preparation

- Consent form will have been signed by participants after reading Participant Information Sheet and having any questions answered satisfactorily.
- Convenient time prearranged with House Manager.
- Current COVID-19 guidelines followed.

Venue

Either in the care home in a confidential, private space or online via Microsoft Teams if COVID-19 restrictions in place.

Contingency

Should the session require to be cancelled due to lack of participants or exigencies of the care service, all will be contacted as soon as possible and another date set. If staff members arrive but are then sent back, the focus group will be rearranged if it cannot continue that day.

If the CI is not able to run the session e.g. illness, then participants will be informed that the focus group is cancelled by the CI (if able) or the House Manager. When able, the CI will re-arrange the focus group.

Format: There will be two separate focus groups in Cycle 1 with staff members (n = 3 per group). Each group will last for up to 1.5 hours, with a 10-15 minute tea/coffee break if needed.

Process:

1. CI to briefly introduce self and remind participants of study aims and purpose of focus group
2. CI to check for verbal consent to participate in focus group and video-audio record session
3. Collaborative ground rules to be set e.g. confidentiality before & after group; parameters, mutual respect etc.

Resources needed:

- A room
- iPad
- Prompts:
 - Objects/images e.g. pebble; feather; toothbrush; family photo; picture of someone laughing; telephone; coloured fabric; soft fabric (if this is online, the objects will be replaced by images of objects/participants could bring an object).
 - Images/objects of everyday activities e.g. tea cup, clothes, people, combs
 - 'Meaningful activity' card;
 - 'Meaning IN activity' card.

Focus group questions/prompts (informed by Braun & Clarke, 2013)

State: We are here to discuss the concept of meaning when doing activities with people with advanced dementia. You will be invited to participate in different ways e.g. using words, objects, images etc. – only do what feels comfortable for you. I'm interested in hearing your thoughts and ideas – there is no wrong or right!

Opening questions

1. What comes to mind when I say the word 'meaning'? You may wish to choose one of the objects/images/words on the table which best represents the word to you?
2. What gives us meaning in life?

Questions to elicit shared understanding of meaning

3. What do you think of/feel when you hear the term 'meaningful activities'? [Props]
4. What do you think of/feel when you hear the term 'meaning in activities'? [Props]
5. What might meaning look like for people with advanced dementia?
6. How might we know if something is meaningful to a person with advanced dementia?

Questions about meaning-making

7. How do we create meaning with a person with advanced dementia?
8. When doing activities with a person with advanced dementia, what do we need to do in order to create meaning?
9. Can you give me an example of when you feel a person with advanced dementia has experienced meaning? Use the prompts on the table if needed
10. Can you give me an example of when you feel meaning has been NOT been created with a person with advanced dementia?

Closing question

11. Is there anything else you'd like to share?

References

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful qualitative research : a practical guide for beginners / Virginia Braun & Victoria Clarke*. London: London : SAGE, 2013.

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Observation/interaction Researcher Guide

What

Observations, discussions and researcher interactions during activities will involve the person with advanced dementia and their family member/friend or care home staff. They will take place during care activities such as eating/drinking, teeth cleaning, hair brushing and leisure activities such as family visits, folding/touching/feeling/looking at items, watching occurrences in the care home; these activities/interactions may be scheduled or spontaneous. Discussions with family, friends and staff may be woven into the observations or may happen at the end of the activity/interaction. This will involve the person with advanced dementia if that is possible.

Aims:

- To gain the perspective of the person with advanced dementia
- To examine how family members/friends and staff use meaning in everyday activities and interactions with people with advanced dementia
- To review how meaning in activities and interactions can be enhanced in the everyday lives of people with advanced dementia (Cycle 3 only)

Preparation:

- Consent form/proxy consent form will have been signed by participants/representatives after reading the Participant Information Sheet and having any questions answered satisfactorily.
- Convenient time prearranged with House Manager & participants, or for spontaneous activities/interactions, the researcher will ask consent in the moment.
- Current COVID-19 guidelines followed.

Venue

Care Home. The activities/interactions will mainly be observed in social, public spaces, however if an activity normally happens in the bedroom of a person with advanced dementia, the observation/activity will happen there to ensure consistency and familiarity for the person with advanced dementia. Intimate care activities are excluded.

Format

Cycle 2: Audio-visual participant observation periods with person with advanced dementia will happen during different activities/interactions with either family member/friend or care home staff. Discussions will be woven into observations to capture meaning in activity and interaction as it arises. This will involve the person with advanced dementia if that is possible.

(n= up to 3 observations/discussions per person, up to 45 mins each).

Cycle 2: Audio-visual participant interaction periods with person with advanced dementia.

(n = up to 2 interactions per person, up to 20 mins per activity/intervention).

Cycle 3: Audio-visual participant interaction with the person with advanced dementia during different activities/interactions with family member/friend or care home staff. The purpose of this is to apply learning together to enhance meaning in activity and interaction in the moment.

(n = up to 2 x interactions per person, up to 45 mins each).

Contingency

If current restrictions/regulations do not allow the Chief Investigator (CI) to enter the care home an online alternative will be completed using Microsoft Teams.

If the CI is not able to attend e.g. illness, the CI will inform the House Manager and other participants. When able, the CI will re-arrange.

Resources

- The room/space usually used during specific activities
- iPad
- Items needed for specific activities e.g. comb/brush if grooming hair

PwAD = Person with advanced dementia

Example discussion questions

- How do you think that went in terms of a meaningful experience?
[to PwAD] Did you like that? Can you show me why you liked it /why not?
- What helped to create meaning?
[to PwAD] Can you show me how you feel?
- Do you think [name of PwAD] found it meaningful? Why/why not?
- Did anything get in the way?

Meaning in activities and interactions in advanced dementia

Workshop Schedule – Family members/friends & staff

Rationale

Using the principles of Participatory Action Research (PAR), the purpose of the workshop is to work creatively with family members/friends and staff to respond to the interim research findings and identify learning and change (Stringer, 2014). A workshop was chosen because it can be delivered in an informal way using a variety of materials to elicit different types of information, potentially adding depth to the data. The Chief Investigator (CI) is experienced in leading workshops as a Freelance Artist and clinical groups as an occupational therapist.

Aims

- To explore findings from research so far with participants
- For participants to respond to and develop findings to gain a deeper understanding
- To provide a critical reflective opportunity to facilitate and embed learning
- To collaboratively discuss the dissemination of the findings

Preparation:

- Consent form will have been signed by participants after reading Participant Information Sheet and having any questions answered satisfactorily.
- Convenient time prearranged with House Manager.
- Current COVID-19 guidelines followed.

Venue

The workshop will take place either at the care home or online (Teams), depending upon COVID-19 restrictions.

Contingency:

If current restrictions/regulations do not allow family members/friends and staff to meet together in the care home, an online version will be completed using a Teams App. Activities will be adapted e.g. using Padlet <https://padlet.com/> and Miro online whiteboard: <https://www.miro.com/> . Depending on the situation, family members/friends and staff may need to do the workshop separately and/or the workshop may need to be shorter/more breaks added due to online fatigue.

If the CI is not able to run the session e.g. illness, then participants will be informed that the workshop is cancelled by the CI (if able) of the House Manager. When able, the CI will re-arrange the workshop.

Format:

There will be two separate workshops with family members/friends (n = 3 per workshop) and staff (n = 3 per workshop) (together), one at the end of Cycle 2 and one at the end of Cycle 3. Each will last for up to 1.5 hours, with a 10-15 minute tea/coffee break if needed.

Resources

- Confidential, quiet room in care home or Teams App on laptop
- Table, chairs
- Whiteboard
- iPad
- Creative Toolkit (e.g. paper, scissors, magazines, words, disposable camera, pens/pencils, Smencils (pencils with a scent), sounds/music, Post-it notes, objects etc.)
- Refreshments
- Name badges

Process:

1. CI to welcome participants and check they are happy to continue
2. Participants to introduce themselves (name and favourite hobby)
3. CI to report study findings so far – examples of data to be shared
4. Participants to respond to initial findings using Creative Toolkit e.g. recordings, mind-maps, drawings (in twos/threes).
5. Participants to work as a team to map out findings and responses using items from Creative Toolkit e.g. collage, montage, objects etc.
6. Participants to verbally describe visual map
7. Workshop feedback
8. Participants to report what they discussed back to other groups
9. Participants to work as a team with CI to map out learning so far and
10. Discuss dissemination of findings (final workshop only)
11. CI to check if the participant(s) have any questions about the interview/study
12. CI to close workshop and thank participants.

Feedback plan

Feedback will be gathered from participants using post-it notes. They can add their thoughts to the following themes onto a wall:

1. What worked well?
2. Could anything be improved?
3. Ideas for next workshop

Anticipated outcomes:

- Participant feedback on findings so far
- Findings and thoughts mapped out visually
- Learning established + next steps
- Feedback on workshop gained

Post-workshop activity

After the workshop, the CI will take photographs of the hardcopy pictorial data (if in person) or download it from Miro/Padlet (if online) and write field notes. The hardcopy pictorial data will then be taken back to the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) and stored in a in a staff only area in a locked cabinet. Digital data will be transferred to the UWS OneDrive and catalogues in NVivo.

Appendix 11: Phase One data analysis mind-maps

A11.1 Phase One data analysis: mind-map of early codes

A11.2 Phase One data analysis: mind-map of refined codes

A11.3 Phase One data analysis: mind-map of developing themes

Appendix 12: Phase Two data analysis and mind-map images

A12.1 Phase Two analysis: mind-map of developing themes

A12.2 Phase Two analysis: developing theme: Curiosity, Emovere, Sentience

A12.3 Phase Two analysis: developing theme: Resonating and Symbiosis

A12.4 Phase Two analysis: developing theme: Virtuosity

A12.5 Phase Two analysis: example of grouped features and elements within developing theme

Appendix 13: Phase Three data analysis moveable collages

A13.1 Phase Three data analysis: development of Theme One

A13.3 Phase Three data analysis: development of Theme Three

staff (barriers / restrictions) exclusion

Understanding what meaning in activity might look like

Wants to know / not knowing

What person does what home does How person is

Reframing meaning (T3)

staff (and what PwPD get from meaningful activity)

staff (meaning can be regained)

staff - co-creating

PwPD (demonstrating interest) co-creating

Wants linking / picking up the thread (clarifying)

P3

T3

PwPD

The Thing

So what do you mean by the meaning of meaning?

Well that's what I mean by the thing.

So what is this thing of which you are speaking?

The meaning of meaningful things.

So how will you find the meaning of meaning?

Well that's a good question, you see!

*Through diaries and pictures and interview data,
collected artistically.*

So what will the data tell you about meaning?

Well frankly I can't really say.

For the thing I am seeking's the meaning of meaning,

I'll work out my thing on the way.

Poem by Dr Michael Smith, created during Creative Seminar Series (2021) in response to this study